

In-depth investigation on the connection between climate change and NCDs

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Acronym	Full Name of Organisation
HWWI	Hamburgisches Weltwirtschaftsinstitut
UPO	Università degli Studi del Piemonte Orientale Amedeo Avogadro
CTP	Consortio de la Comunidad de Trabajo de los Pirineos
SCJUT	Spitalul Clinic Județean de Urgență Pius Brînzeu Timișoara
NCSR	National Center for Scientific Research "Demokritos"
EQY	Euroquality SAS

List of abbreviations

Acronym Full Term

ADO	African Dust Outbreak
ARI	Acute respiratory infection
CC	Climate Change
CHD	Congenital heart defect
CMD	Common mental disorders
CO ₂	Carbon dioxide
COPD	Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease
COP	Conference of the Parties
CVD	Cardiovascular disease
DRM	Disaster risk management
DRR	Disaster risk reduction
ECDC	European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control
ED	Emergency department
ESS	European Social Survey
EWE	Extreme weather event
GHG	Greenhouse gases
ICU	Intensive care unit
IHD	Ischemic heart disease
MCI	Mass Casualty Incidents
MI	Myocardial infarction
MMT	Minimum Mortality Temperature
NCD	Non-communicable disease
NO ₂	Nitrogen dioxide
OP	Oxidative potential
PM	Particulate matter

PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
PTSD	Post-traumatic stress disorder
RT	Respiratory tract
SABA	Short-acting beta-2-agonist
SPT	Skin prick testing
TB	Tuberculosis
TBE	Tick-borne encephalitis
TEOM	Tapered Element Oscillating Microbalance
WNV	West Nile virus
WHO	World Health Organization

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Executive Summary

This report presents a comprehensive picture of how climate change influences human well-being and the urgent need for mitigation and adaptation strategies. It comprises of five chapters that collectively examine the relationship between extreme weather events (EWEs), health risks, and the broader implications for health systems, public health strategies, and disease patterns. Chapter 1 performs a systematic literature review on studies that analyse health risks like NCDs, including cardiovascular, respiratory, and mental health disorders from EWEs such as heatwaves, wildfires, floods, storms, and droughts. It suggests that elderly and socioeconomically disadvantaged groups are the most vulnerable. It also finds the need for improved research methods and data to capture the specific health effects of climate change more accurately.

Building on Chapter 1, Chapter 2 shifts the focus to how EWEs disrupt health systems. The chapter examines how disasters—such as the 2021 floods in Germany—damage healthcare infrastructure, limit resource availability, and disproportionately affect mountain regions like the European Alps. It underscores the lack of tailored disaster risk reduction (DRR) strategies for such vulnerable areas. Expanding on the regional vulnerabilities discussed in Chapter 2, Chapter 3, focusses on the Pyrenees, a transboundary mountain region severely affected by climate change. Rising temperatures, changing precipitation patterns, and more frequent EWEs threaten both ecosystems and human health. Direct impacts include heat-related illnesses and increased mortality, while indirect effects range from altered disease transmission patterns to degraded air and water quality. The chapter highlights the challenge of obtaining region-specific data, as most research focuses on broader Mediterranean or European scales.

Chapter 4 builds on the findings of Chapter 1 by systematically analyzing the relationship between EWEs and NCDs using European-wide health and climate data. Statistical models show that high temperatures significantly increase the prevalence of high blood pressure and respiratory issues. While precipitation has minimal impact on health, heatwaves pose a major risk, particularly for cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. Extending the discussion on climate-related health risks, Chapter 5 focuses on the impact of climate change on allergic diseases. Rising CO₂ levels, temperature increases, and air pollution intensify pollen allergenicity and extend allergy seasons. The spread of invasive species like ragweed exacerbates respiratory conditions, especially in countries like Romania.

Chapter 1: Empirical evidence of the effects of climate change on NCDs

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1. Introduction

Earth's climate has been gradually yet persistently changing due to various geological and atmospheric processes. Over the past 65 million years, alternating warm and cool periods, along with occasional abrupt shifts, have been identified through deep-sea sediment analysis ¹. However, since the 20th century, these natural changes have accelerated. Global warming, characterized by the gradual rise in Earth's surface temperature, is considered the primary driver of contemporary climate change ². This warming trend is evident from indicators such as rising sea levels and increasing global land, air, and sea temperatures ³. The resulting temperature increase has contributed to more frequent extreme weather events (EWEs), such as heatwaves, wildfires, air pollution, floods, droughts, and storms ⁴. For instance, a recent study reports that the frequency of extreme wildfires has more than doubled from 2003 to 2023, with six of the most intense events occurring in the past seven years ⁵.

These EWEs impact human health in both direct and indirect ways ⁶. Indirect effects lead to changes in socio-economic characteristics of the population. For example, a possibility of the occurrence of a future EWE could influence individual well being or mental health, which in turn affects expectations of individuals⁷. Direct effects are due to actual exposure of the population by virtue of spatial proximity to the EWEs resulting in natural disasters. These direct effects are identified through devastation of human habitation and infrastructure, along with morbidity (aggravation of existing diseases) and mortality (death). Moreover, these disasters create environmental conditions that can affect even healthy populations, exposing them to unfamiliar diseases and exacerbating pre-existing health issues.

¹ James Zachos et al., "Trends, Rhythms, and Aberrations in Global Climate 65 Ma to Present," *Science* 292, no. 5517 (April 27, 2001): 686–93, <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1059412>.

² J. Hansen et al., "GLOBAL SURFACE TEMPERATURE CHANGE," *Reviews of Geophysics* 48, no. 4 (December 14, 2010): RG4004, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2010RG000345>.

³ NASA, "Global Surface Temperature | NASA Global Climate Change," *Climate Change: Vital Signs of the Planet*, 2024, <https://climate.nasa.gov/vital-signs/global-temperature?intent=121>.

⁴ Michael Berlemann and Max Friedrich Steinhardt, "Climate Change, Natural Disasters, and Migration—a Survey of the Empirical Evidence," *CESifo Economic Studies* 63, no. 4 (December 1, 2017): 353–85, <https://doi.org/10.1093/cesifo/ifx019>.

⁵ Calum X. Cunningham, Grant J. Williamson, and David M. J. S. Bowman, "Increasing Frequency and Intensity of the Most Extreme Wildfires on Earth," *Nature Ecology & Evolution* 8, no. 8 (June 24, 2024): 1420–25, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41559-024-02452-2>.

⁶ Michael Berlemann and Marina Eurich, "Chapter 12: Natural Disasters and Self-Reported Well-Being: A Review of the Literature," in *Handbook on the Economics of Disasters*, 2022, <https://www.elgaronline.com/edcollchap/book/9781839103735/book-part-9781839103735-21.xml>.

⁷ Michael Berlemann, "Does Hurricane Risk Affect Individual Well-Being? Empirical Evidence on the Indirect Effects of Natural Disasters," *Ecological Economics* 124 (April 1, 2016): 99–113, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2016.01.020>.

These diseases are commonly known as non-communicable diseases (NCD) such as cardiovascular diseases, respiratory disorders, diabetes, and mental health issues ⁸. Unlike communicable diseases such as AIDS, malaria, and COVID-19, NCDs are chronic and non-infectious. Their development is often linked to a combination of physiological, behavioural, genetic, and environmental factors, the latter being the focus of this chapter. Cardiovascular diseases include coronary artery disease, hypertension, heart failure, and stroke, while common respiratory conditions are chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma. Mental health disorders range from depression and anxiety to bipolar disorder and schizophrenia. NCDs are highly relevant to this study, as the increasing frequency and intensity of EWEs driven by climate change significantly impacts their prevalence and severity ⁹.

The growing impact of EWEs on the prevalence and severity of NCDs is particularly evident in the case of heatwaves. As one of the most direct manifestations of climate change, heatwaves are known to increase the risk of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases. Understanding how heatwaves are defined and measured is crucial to assessing their health impacts. Heatwaves are identified using various metrics depending on the research question. One common approach is percentile-based definitions, which set thresholds relative to historical temperature distributions, taking local climate variations into account. Another method involves absolute temperature thresholds, which use fixed temperature limits that allow for consistent criteria across different regions. Some studies define heatwaves using a heat index and apparent temperature, which account for perceived temperatures, including both heat and humidity, providing a more accurate representation of human exposure. Additionally, some approaches use climatological periods and variability, identifying specific periods based on climatological analysis or considering temperature variability to account for prolonged heat exposure (for more details, see section 4.1). These indicators have been

⁸ World Health Organization, “Noncommunicable Diseases,” World Health Organization, September 16, 2023, <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/noncommunicable-diseases>.

⁹ Liu, Yongqiang, Stanturf, John, and Goodrick, Scott, “Trends in Global Wildfire Potential in a Changing Climate,” *Forest Ecology and Management* 259, no. 4 (2010), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foreco.2009.09.002>; P. Peduzzi et al., “Global Trends in Tropical Cyclone Risk,” *Nature Climate Change* 2, no. 4 (April 2012): 289–94, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate1410>; S. E. Perkins-Kirkpatrick and S. C. Lewis, “Increasing Trends in Regional Heatwaves,” *Nature Communications* 11, no. 1 (July 3, 2020): 3357, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-020-16970-7>; B. Tellman et al., “Satellite Imaging Reveals Increased Proportion of Population Exposed to Floods,” *Nature* 596, no. 7870 (August 5, 2021): 80–86, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-021-03695-w>; Kevin E. Trenberth et al., “Global Warming and Changes in Drought,” *Nature Climate Change* 4, no. 1 (January 2014): 17–22, <https://doi.org/10.1038/nclimate2067>; Veronika Weilhhammer et al., “Extreme Weather Events in Europe and Their Health Consequences – A Systematic Review,” *International Journal of Hygiene and Environmental Health* 233 (April 1, 2021): 113688, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijheh.2021.113688>.

linked to higher mortality rates and increased hospital admissions for cardiovascular and respiratory conditions ¹⁰.

Wildfires release air pollutants comprising particulate matter and other toxic gases that aggravate respiratory issues and trigger cardiovascular events ¹¹. Socioeconomically disadvantaged populations are more vulnerable to these effects than other segments of the population. Air pollution from wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses and the impact varies depending on the topography and inhabitation. Additionally, anthropogenic intervention such as deforestation aggravates the severity of wildfires.

Floods disrupt healthcare access and food security, leading to worsened chronic health conditions and mental health issues ¹². These events often lead to increased rates of common mental disorders such as anxiety and depression ¹³. The stress associated with floods may stem from property damage, displacement, and the subsequent recovery process that in turn aggravate existing health conditions and hinders effective management of NCDs ¹⁴.

Similarly, storms and droughts pose significant health risks by exacerbating health problems. Storms primarily limit access to essential healthcare services during peak treatment periods due to inadequate treatment capacity or unavailable healthcare infrastructure in locality caused by devastation of existing infrastructures and a lack of adequate transport facilities. Droughts lead to a slow and gradual degradation of socioeconomic status due to income loss, leading to mental health problems, especially in rural regions and for those directly or indirectly dependent on agricultural production

¹⁰ A.G Barnett et al., “Cold and Heat Waves in the United States,” *Environmental Research* 112 (2012): 218–24, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2011.12.010>; Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.,” 2015, <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0048969714015538>; Scott C. Sheridan and Shao Lin, “Assessing Variability in the Impacts of Heat on Health Outcomes in New York City Over Time, Season, and Heat-Wave Duration,” *EcoHealth* 11 (2014): 512–25, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10393-014-0970-7>; Lyle R. Turner, Des Connell, and Shilu Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia,” *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 28, no. 5 (October 2013): 482–87, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X13008789>; Weilin Zeng et al., “The Effect of Heat Waves on Mortality and Effect Modifiers in Four Communities of Guangdong Province, China,” *Science of The Total Environment* 482–483 (2014): 214–21, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2014.02.049>.

¹¹ Francisco Caamano-Isorna et al., “Respiratory and Mental Health Effects of Wildfires: An Ecological Study in Galician Municipalities (North-West Spain),” *Environmental Health* 10, no. 1 (May 21, 2011): 48, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-10-48>.

¹² Ioana Agache et al., “Climate Change and Global Health: A Call to More Research and More Action,” *Allergy* 77, no. 5 (2022): 1389–1407, <https://doi.org/10.1111/all.15229>.

¹³ Hilary Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health: An Analysis Using England’s Mental Health Survey,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 16, no. 18 (January 2019): 3256, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16183256>.

¹⁴ Jessica Elizabeth Lamond, Rotimi D. Joseph, and David G. Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households,” *Environmental Research* 140 (July 1, 2015): 325–34, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2015.04.008>.

for their livelihood¹⁵. In turn, such EWEs limit access to healthcare systems for the financially deprived populations, making them more vulnerable to such health risks. For detailed discussion, see section 4.4 for droughts and section 4.5 for storms.

This chapter aims to systematically review and analyse the empirical evidence regarding the effects of climate change on NCDs. By examining studies from various geographical regions and climate contexts, it seeks to provide a comprehensive understanding of how climate change leads to EWEs which in turn influence NCDs to offer insights that can inform effective public health strategies and interventions. We find that the impact of climate-related disasters on NCDs is increasingly discussed in the scientific literature. The growing body of research on this topic highlights the need to explore its heterogeneity across different EWEs, NCDs, and affected populations.

The chapter is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses the method used for gathering literature from various online sources and explains how the most relevant literature is selected for further analysis. Various aspects of this retained literature are discussed in section 3. Section 4 performs a systematic review of this retained literature to understand how climate change leads to EWEs which in turn influence NCDs. Section 5 provides a conclusion.

2. Method

We conduct a systematic review synthesizing scientific and empirical evidence regarding the effects of climate change on NCDs. Our methodology follows the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) 2020 framework, which provides a structured approach to identifying, screening, and including relevant studies¹⁶. This method ensures transparency and reproducibility in our review process. It involves the identification of relevant studies via databases, registers, and sources, the screening of the collected studies, and the assessment of their eligibility. In the following chapter, we describe the application of the PRISMA method in more detail.

2.1. Search strategy

To gather relevant studies, we systematically search three databases: Web of Science, PubMed, and Scopus. We chose these three databases for our literature review as these

¹⁵ E. Moyo et al., “Health Effects of Climate Change in Africa: A Call for an Improved Implementation of Prevention Measures,” *Eco-Environment and Health* 2, no. 2 (2023): 74–78, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eehl.2023.04.004>.

¹⁶ Matthew J Page et al., “The PRISMA 2020 Statement: An Updated Guideline for Reporting Systematic Reviews,” *BMJ*, March 29, 2021, n71, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.

collectively provide extensive coverage of scholarly literature in the field, including peer-reviewed articles, conference proceedings, and other academic publications.

The search terms used encompass a broad range of climate phenomena and terms implicating potential impacts on various NCDs, including mental health issues, cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, and other non-communicable diseases.

The search string used is:

```
("climate change" OR "global warming" OR "pollution" ) AND ( "human" OR "anthropogenic" ) AND ( "disaster" OR "heat wave" OR "heatwave" OR "hurricane" OR "wildfire" OR "flood" OR "drought" OR "storm" OR "heavy rain" OR "catastrophe" OR "cyclone" ) AND ( "dissatisfaction" OR "hospitalization" OR "cardiovascular" OR "respiratory" OR "mental health" OR "ncd" OR "non-communicable" OR "psychological" OR "depression" OR "stress" OR "anxiety")
```

We included the terms "human" and "anthropogenic" to focus specifically on human health outcomes and exclude results primarily related to agricultural or livestock studies. To encompass the mental health aspect of NCDs, we incorporated terms such as "psychological", "depression", "stress", "anxiety", "dissatisfaction", and the bigram "mental health". For climate change indicators, we employed a range of terms including "climate change", "global warming", and "pollution", as well as specific extreme weather events often associated with climate change: "disaster", "heat wave", "heatwave", "hurricane", "wildfire", "flood", "drought", "storm", "heavy rain", "catastrophe", and "cyclone".

2.2. Data extraction and synthesis

Based on the search results from all three databases, we initially retrieved 2,944 studies. We developed a custom script using the software tool R to consolidate the results into a structured, merged database, extract relevant details, and systematically screen for duplicates. After this process, we identified 1,906 unique studies. For each entry, we extracted key information such as bibliographic details (title, authors, year, source, volume, issue), abstract, identifiers (DOI, PubMed ID), and metadata (affiliations, keywords, document type, open access status). Additionally, we included 46 more references identified through citations in other papers.

Three researchers independently reviewed and analysed the collected studies, screening them for relevance and excluding those that did not meet the following criteria:

Reason 1: The article is not directly related to the topic.

Reason 2: The article is not in English.

In case where reports were not retrievable due to reasons such as broken links, retraction, or incorrect citations, or were not eligible according to our criteria, we removed them from our sample.

Finally, we include 152 articles in our review. The detailed steps of our literature search and screening process are illustrated in the PRISMA flow diagram shown below (Figure 1).

Figure 1. The PRISMA flow diagram.

3. Search Results

3.1. Number of publications and natural disasters

The body of empirical evidence on the effects of climate change on NCDs is extensive and diverse, encompassing studies from various countries and examining a wide range of outcomes. Figure 2 illustrates the number of natural disasters and related academic publications from 1980 until 2023.¹⁷ The publication count (red line) reflects the number of search results from the three searched databases: PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science. The first search result appears in the year 1981. Afterwards, the number of publications grows slowly at first but then accelerates sharply after 2000, reflecting a surge in academic interest likely driven by the growing recognition of climate change impacts and the increasing frequency of natural disasters.

Figure 2. Annual number of publications (red), number of natural disasters (grey) and the five-year moving average of the disasters (blue) from 1980 until 2023.

¹⁷ For 2024, Scopus has recorded 145 results, PubMed 18 results, and Web of Science 3 results. The relatively lower counts for 2024 are likely due to the ongoing year and the fact that not all publications have been released or indexed yet (as of July 2024).

3.2. Measurements and types of NCDs

In the screened literature, non-communicable diseases are medical conditions or diseases that are not infectious and cannot be transmitted from person to person. They are typically long-lasting and progress slowly ¹⁸. NCDs cover a wide spectrum of chronic conditions, such as cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, diabetes, and mental health disorders, as well as neurologic, endocrine, gastrointestinal, renal, allergic, and autoimmune disorders.

According to the World Health Organization (WHO), NCDs are responsible for 41 million deaths annually, representing 74% of all deaths worldwide ¹⁹. **Cardiovascular diseases** (CVDs), the leading cause of NCD deaths, account for 17.9 million fatalities each year. These diseases include coronary artery disease, hypertension (high blood pressure), arrhythmia (irregular heartbeats), heart failure, and stroke. They often result from genetic predisposition and lifestyle factors such as poor diet, lack of physical activity, and smoking ²⁰.

Cancers are the second leading cause of NCD deaths, claiming 9.3 million lives annually. They can affect any part of the body and are characterized by the uncontrolled growth of abnormal cells, with risk factors including genetics, lifestyle choices, and environmental exposures. For example, following an earthquake and tsunami, higher hospitalization rates were observed for the progression of lung cancer, among other respiratory diseases ²¹.

Chronic respiratory diseases, responsible for 4.1 million deaths each year, include conditions like chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) and asthma. These diseases can be exacerbated by environmental factors such as air pollution, smoking, and exposure to occupational hazards.

Diabetes results in 2.0 million deaths annually, including those from kidney disease caused by diabetes. This metabolic disorder, particularly type 2 diabetes, is characterized by high blood sugar levels due to insulin resistance or deficiency and is heavily influenced by diet, physical activity, and obesity. Natural disasters can exacerbate diabetes management due to increased stress levels, food insecurity, and malnutrition, all of which are associated with a higher incidence of diabetes and impaired glucose tolerance ²².

¹⁸ World Health Organization, “Noncommunicable Diseases.”

¹⁹ World Health Organization.

²⁰ World Health Organization.

²¹ Shinsuke Yamanda et al., “The Impact of the 2011 Great East Japan Earthquake on Hospitalisation for Respiratory Disease in a Rapidly Aging Society: A Retrospective Descriptive and Cross-Sectional Study at the Disaster Base Hospital in Ishinomaki,” *BMJ Open* 3, no. 1 (January 1, 2013): e000865, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2012-000865>.

²² Christine Ngaruiya et al., “Systematic Review on Chronic Non-Communicable Disease in Disaster Settings,” *BMC Public Health* 22, no. 1 (June 21, 2022): 1234, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-022-13399-z>.

Mental health disorders encompass a wide range of conditions that affect mood, thinking, and behaviour, including depression, anxiety, bipolar disorder, and schizophrenia. These disorders are influenced by genetics, environmental factors, trauma, and significant life changes. A subset of these conditions, referred to as Common Mental Disorders (CMD), includes non-psychotic disorders such as depression, anxiety disorders, phobias, and obsessive-compulsive disorder ²³.

Collectively, these four major NCDs—cardiovascular diseases, cancers, chronic respiratory diseases, and diabetes—are responsible for over 80% of all premature NCD deaths ²⁴.

The **measurement** of NCDs is broadly categorized into mortality and hospital admissions. Mortality indicators include general mortality (total and all-cause mortality), age-specific mortality, and cause-specific mortality. Hospital admissions indicators encompass all-cause hospitalizations, emergency department visits, excess hospital admissions, ambulance attendances, age-specific admissions, and cause-specific admissions (e.g. cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, including asthma and allergic diseases, as well as renal diseases and mental health conditions).

3.3. Inclusion of socio-economic control variables

In analysing the impact of climate change on NCDs, it is crucial to include socio-economic control variables, as these factors can significantly influence health outcomes and help account for confounding effects ²⁵. These control variables help to isolate the specific effects of extreme weather events on health outcomes. Studies find evidence that older people or socioeconomically deprived people are more vulnerable due to either existing health problems or inability to afford medical treatment (see section 4.2).

Commonly used socio-economic control variables in these studies include **age**, as different age groups can have varying susceptibility to the health impacts of extreme weather events, and **gender**, since health impacts may differ between males and females, necessitating gender-specific analysis ²⁶. Some studies use different age groups, some use the pension status of individuals ²⁷.

²³ Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health.”

²⁴ World Health Organization, “Noncommunicable Diseases.”

²⁵ Weilhhammer et al., “Extreme Weather Events in Europe and Their Health Consequences – A Systematic Review.”

²⁶ Anne Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France,” *International Archives of Occupational and Environmental Health* 80, no. 1 (2006): 16–24, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00420-006-0089-4>.

²⁷ Caamano-Isorna et al., “Respiratory and Mental Health Effects of Wildfires.”

Income level is another crucial variable, as socio-economic status often influences access to healthcare and overall vulnerability to health impacts ²⁸. **Education** level is also commonly controlled for, given that higher education levels are generally associated with better health outcomes and greater awareness of health risks. **Employment** status can affect stress levels, access to healthcare, and overall health, making it an important variable. In some studies, the employment status is classified as either employed, unemployed or inactive ²⁹. This approach can, however, contradict the Clean Control Condition, as EWEs often impact both income and employment levels. For instance, a flood may destroy income sources, which in turn affects NCDs through changes in socio-economic status. Thus, when including these variables, the direct impact of EWEs on NCDs might be underestimated, as the control variables themselves can obscure the full effect of the disasters ³⁰.

Additionally, the distinction between urban and rural **residence** is significant because the location of residence can influence exposure to extreme weather events and access to healthcare services.

Housing tenure can affect the extent of damage experienced and the capacity for recovery, which in turn impacts health. For instance, ³¹ utilized housing tenure as a control variable in their study on the effects of storms, categorizing participants as owner-occupiers (reference group), social renters, and private renters.

Alcohol consumption is a known risk factor for various NCDs, including cardiovascular diseases, liver disease, and certain cancers. Some studies therefore categorize participants into low/no risk (reference group), hazardous, and harmful drinkers ³². This categorization helps isolate the specific effects of alcohol consumption, ensuring that varying health risks associated with alcohol are adequately accounted for.

4. Indicators of climate change and their impact on NCDs

In most studies, extreme weather events serve as critical indicators of climate change and are essential in analysing its impacts on non-communicable diseases. Existing literature extensively examines the effects of individual extreme weather events or changes in specific climate variables on NCDs. In this review, we focus on heatwaves, wildfires and air pollution, floods, droughts as well as storms.

²⁸ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households.”

²⁹ Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health.”

³⁰ Berlemann and Eurich, “Chapter 12.”

³¹ Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health.”

³² Graham et al.

4.1. Heatwaves

Heatwaves are mostly defined as prolonged periods of excessively high temperatures. Various studies have employed different criteria to define heatwaves, often depending on the specific climate and population characteristics of the study regions. The definitions of heatwaves in the literature vary significantly, reflecting different criteria and thresholds used across studies. These can be grouped and classified into several main categories based on their defining characteristics (Table 1).

Percentile-based approaches, like using the 90th percentile of local temperatures, account for regional climate variability but may lack consistency across different areas. Absolute thresholds, such as defining heatwaves as temperatures above 35°C, provide clear and comparable criteria but ignore local climate differences. Heat index methods, which factor in humidity, are more complex to calculate. Impact-based definitions, such as hospital admissions during heatwaves, directly link heat to health outcomes but may not capture the full range of effects on non-communicable diseases like cardiovascular or respiratory conditions. Table 1 provides an overview of the different definitions of heatwaves, their characteristics, and some associated references.

Definition	Description	References
Percentile-Based	Thresholds set relative to historical temperature distributions, considering local climate variations.	Chen et al., 2015; Ma et al., 2015; Revich & Shaposhnikov, 2008; Son et al., 2014; Zeng et al., 2014
Absolute Temperature Thresholds	Definitions based on fixed temperature thresholds, enabling consistent criteria across different regions.	Hertel et al., 2009; Huang et al., 2010; Huynen et al., 2001; Sun et al., 2014; Turner et al., 2013; Yang et al., 2013
Heat Index and Apparent Temperature	Consideration of perceived temperatures, including both heat and humidity, for a more accurate representation of human exposure.	D'Ippoliti et al., 2010; Gronlund et al., 2014; Mastrangelo et al., 2007; Monteiro et al., 2013
Climatological Periods and Variability	Use of specific periods identified through climatological analysis or temperature variability to account for prolonged heat exposure.	Conti et al., 2007; Fouillet et al., 2006; Knowlton et al., 2008; Rocklöv & Forsberg, 2009
Impact-Based	Definitions based on observed health outcomes, focusing on real-world effects rather than temperature alone.	Anderson et al., 2013; Kovats et al., 2004; Lin et al., 2013; Stafoggia et al., 2006

Table 1. Definitions of heatwaves in the literature.

Overall, we identify 37 papers which examine the impact of heat and rising temperatures on both mortality and morbidity related to NCDs. 25 of them report results on mortality, 16 on morbidity and 4 analyse both outcomes.

4.1.1. Impact on mortality

Heatwaves appear to have a significant impact on NCDs, as suggested by numerous studies conducted in various regions and among different populations (see Table 2). Results from the reviewed studies were classified as significant or insignificant based on whether the authors explicitly stated the level of significance in their papers or if the results were marked as significant in the tables provided (see note below Table 2). for an explanation of the effect size symbols). In cases where outcomes across multiple locations (e.g., cities) were investigated and (1) not all or the majority of results were significant, (2) significant results showed conflicting directions (e.g., increase or decrease), or (3) different statistical methods led to varying results, the findings were classified as inconclusive.

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference
Mortality			
All-cause	Increase	Significant	+++ Fouillet et al., 2006; +++ Monteiro et al., 2013; ++ Baccini et al., 2008; ++ Conti et al., 2007**; ++ Hertel et al., 2009; ++ Royé et al., 2020; ++ Stafoggia et al., 2006; + Analitis et al., 2014; + Bi et al., 2022; + Chen et al., 2015; + D'Ippoliti et al., 2010*; + Huynen et al., 2001; + Huang et al., 2010; + Kovats et al., 2004; + Lin et al., 2013; + Revich & Shaposhnikov, 2008; + Schulte et al., 2021; + Sun et al., 2014; + Yang et al., 2013; Barnett et al., 2012; Cheng et al., 2024; Cvetinov et al., 2019; Ma et al., 2015; Sheridan & Lin, 2014; Zeng et al., 2014
Cardiovascular	Increase	Significant	++ Baccini et al., 2008; ++ Chen et al., 2015; ++ Fouillet et al., 2006; ++ Miron et al., 2015; ++ Royé et al., 2020; ++ Schulte et al., 2021; ++ Yang et al., 2013; + Analitis et al., 2014; + Bi et al., 2022; + D'Ippoliti et al., 2010; + Huang et al., 2010; + Lin et al., 2013; + Sun et al., 2014; Arisco et al., 2023; Cheng et al., 2024; Huynen et al., 2001; Khatana et al., 2022; Ma et al., 2015; Sheridan & Lin, 2014
		Insignificant	Hertel et al., 2009
- Stroke	Increase	Significant	+++ Chen et al., 2015; + Huang et al., 2010; ++ Schulte et al., 2021
- IHD	Increase	Significant	+++ Chen et al., 2015; + Revich & Shaposhnikov, 2008
- MI	Increase	Significant	Schulte et al., 2021; Zanobetti et al., 2012
- Heart failure	Increase	Significant	+ Schulte et al., 2021; Zanobetti et al., 2012
- CHD	Increase	Significant	Huang et al., 2010
- Arrhythmia	Increase	Significant	++ Schulte et al., 2021

- Hypertension	Increase	Significant	++ Schulte et al., 2021
Respiratory	Increase	Significant	+++ Baccini et al., 2008; +++ Fouillet et al., 2006; +++ Hertel et al., 2009; +++ Revich & Shaposhnikov, 2008; ++ Analitis et al., 2014; ++ Chen et al., 2015; ++ D'Ippoliti et al., 2010*; ++ Royé et al., 2020; ++ Yang et al., 2013; + Bi et al., 2022; + Cheng et al., 2024; + Huang et al., 2010; + Huynen et al., 2001; + Miron et al., 2015; + Sun et al., 2014; Ma et al., 2015; Sheridan & Lin, 2014
		Insignificant	Arisco et al., 2023
		Inconclusive	Lin et al., 2013
- COPD	Increase	Significant	++ Chen et al., 2015; Zanobetti et al., 2012
		Insignificant	Huang et al., 2010
- ARI		Insignificant	Huang et al., 2010
Cerebrovascular	Increase	Significant	++ D'Ippoliti et al., 2010*; + Revich & Shaposhnikov, 2008; Ma et al., 2015
		Insignificant	Analitis et al., 2014
Neoplasm	Increase	Significant	Fouillet et al., 2006; Huynen et al., 2001
		Insignificant	Hertel et al., 2009

Table 2. Impact of heat on mortality.

Note: IHD = Ischemic Heart Disease; MI = Myocardial Infarction; CHD = Congenital Heart Defect; COPD = Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; ARI = Acute Respiratory Infection. Statistical significance is defined by a 95% confidence interval (CI). + An increase of 10 – 25%; ++ An increase of 25 – 50%; +++ An increase of ≥ 50%. * For individuals ≥ 65 years; ** For individuals ≥ 75 years.

Out of 29 studies analysed, 25 found significant increases in all-cause mortality associated with heatwaves (³³, among others). Cardiovascular mortality was also substantially affected, with 19 studies reporting significant increases (e.g., ³⁴) and respiratory outcomes were significantly impacted in 17 studies (e.g., ³⁵). In addition, heatwaves were found to have varying effects on specific diseases within these two categories. For instance, **stroke**-related

³³ Michela Baccini et al., “Heat Effects on Mortality in 15 European Cities,” *Epidemiology* 19, no. 5 (2008): 711–19, <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0b013e318176bfcd>; Susanna Conti et al., “General and Specific Mortality among the Elderly during the 2003 Heat Wave in Genoa (Italy),” *Environmental Research* 103, no. 2 (2007): 267–74, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2006.06.003>; Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France”; Ana Monteiro et al., “Excess Mortality and Morbidity during the July 2006 Heat Wave in Porto, Portugal,” *International Journal of Biometeorology* 57 (2013): 155–67, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-012-0543-9>.

³⁴ Baccini et al., “Heat Effects on Mortality in 15 European Cities”; Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.”; Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France”; F. Schulte, M. Rössli, and M. S. Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland: A Clinical Perspective,” *Swiss Medical Weekly* 151 (2021): w30013, <https://doi.org/10.4414/SMW.2021.w30013>.

³⁵ Baccini et al., “Heat Effects on Mortality in 15 European Cities”; Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France”; B Revich and Dmitry Shaposhnikov, “Excess Mortality during Heat Waves and Cold Spells in Moscow, Russia,” *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 65, no. 10 (2008): 691–96, <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2007.033944>.

mortality showed significant increases in three studies ³⁶, while mortality due to **ischemic heart disease (IHD)** was also elevated ³⁷.

Similarly, **respiratory** diseases such as **COPD** were particularly vulnerable to heat, with multiple studies reporting significant increases in mortality ³⁸. While evidence on cardiovascular mortality is mostly conclusive, some studies report inconclusive or insignificant results for respiratory, cerebrovascular disease and neoplasm (e.g., ³⁹).

In summary, the reviewed studies overwhelmingly show that extreme heat and rising temperatures are associated with increased mortality, particularly from cardiovascular, respiratory, and all-cause outcomes. The evidence emphasizes the heightened vulnerability of certain groups, including the elderly and those with existing NCDs, to the impacts of extreme temperatures.

4.1.2. Impact on morbidity

When examining the impact of heat, heatwaves, and higher temperatures on NCDs, most studies found significant increases in morbidity, as measured by hospitalizations, emergency department visits or need for medical assistance (Table 3). For instance, **morbidity** (measured as hospital admissions) was reported to significantly increase due to heat exposure in studies by ⁴⁰ with some showing strong effects ⁴¹. However, studies like ⁴² noted decreases in

³⁶ Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.”; Wei Huang, Haidong Kan, and Sari Kovats, “The Impact of the 2003 Heat Wave on Mortality in Shanghai, China,” *Science of The Total Environment* 408, no. 11 (2010): 2418–20, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2010.02.009>; Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland.”

³⁷ Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.”; Revich and Shaposhnikov, “Excess Mortality during Heat Waves and Cold Spells in Moscow, Russia.”

³⁸ Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.”; Antonella Zanobetti et al., “Summer Temperature Variability and Long-Term Survival among Elderly People with Chronic Disease” 109, no. 17 (2012): 6608–13, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1113070109>.

³⁹ Antonis Analitis et al., “Effects of Heat Waves on Mortality Effect Modification and Confounding by Air Pollutants,” *Epidemiology* 25, no. 1 (2014): 15–22, <https://doi.org/10.1097/EDE.0b013e31828ac01b>; Sabine Hertel et al., “Quantification of the Heat Wave Effect on Cause-Specific Mortality in Essen, Germany,” *European Journal of Epidemiology* 24 (2009): 407–14, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10654-009-9359-2>; Huang, Kan, and Kovats, “The Impact of the 2003 Heat Wave on Mortality in Shanghai, China.”

⁴⁰ Carina J. Gronlund et al., “Heat, Heat Waves, and Hospital Admissions among the Elderly in the United States, 1992–2006,” *Environmental Health Perspectives* 122, no. 11 (November 2014): 1187–92, <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.1206132>; Kim Knowlton et al., “The 2006 California Heat Wave: Impacts on Hospitalizations and Emergency Department Visits,” *Environmental Health Perspectives* 117, no. 1 (2008): 61–67, <https://doi.org/10.1289/ehp.11594>.

⁴¹ Turner, Connell, and Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia.”

⁴² Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland.”

morbidity, and others like ⁴³ found insignificant changes in all-cause hospital admissions but significant increase in respiratory morbidity. ⁴⁴ categorized morbidity outcomes as inconclusive, indicating that varying methods yield different results.

In total, 20 papers are included in our review focusing on the impact of heat and rising temperatures on morbidity. 4 of them show a significant increase in all-cause morbidity, 7 report a significant increase in cardiovascular diseases while 8 provide insignificant results. For respiratory disease, we find 12 significant results in the screened literature.

Outcome	Direction	Significance	Reference
Morbidity			
All-cause	Increase	Significant	+++ Turner et al., 2013; Gronlund et al., 2014; Knowlton et al., 2008; Ma et al., 2011
	Decrease	Significant	Schulte et al., 2021
		Insignificant	Kovats et al., 2004; Schneider et al., 2023
		Inconclusive	Guirguis et al., 2018; Rocklöv & Forsberg, 2009
Cardiovascular	Increase	Significant	++ Turner et al., 2013; + Mastrangelo et al., 2007**; + Schneider et al., 2023; Knowlton et al., 2008; Ma et al., 2011; Monteiro et al., 2013; Son et al., 2014
	Decrease	Significant	- Schulte et al., 2021
		Insignificant	Giang et al., 2014; Gronlund et al., 2014*; Guirguis et al., 2018; Kovats et al., 2004; Lim et al., 2012; Michelozzi et al., 2009; Ponjoan et al., 2017; Sheridan & Lin, 2014
		Inconclusive	Rocklöv & Forsberg, 2009
- Stroke		Insignificant	Lim et al., 2012; Schulte et al., 2021
- IHD		Inconclusive	Lim et al., 2012
- MI	Decrease	Significant	- Schulte et al., 2021; Knowlton et al., 2008
		Insignificant	Lim et al., 2012
- Cardiac failure	Increase	Significant	+ Lim et al., 2012
	Decrease	Significant	-- Monteiro et al., 2013; - Schulte et al., 2021; Hopp et al., 2018*
- Cardiac disease		Inconclusive	Lim et al., 2012
- Arrhythmia		Insignificant	Schulte et al., 2021
		Inconclusive	Lim et al., 2012
- Hypertension	Decrease	Significant	-- Schulte et al., 2021
Respiratory	Increase	Significant	+++ Turner et al., 2013; ++ Michelozzi et al., 2009; ++ Monteiro et al., 2013; + Lim et

⁴³ Sari Kovats, Shakoor Hajat, and P Wilkinson, “Contrasting Patterns of Mortality and Hospital Admissions during Hot Weather and Heat Waves in Greater London, UK,” *Occupational and Environmental Medicine* 61, no. 11 (2004): 893–98, <https://doi.org/10.1136/oem.2003.012047>.

⁴⁴ Joacim Rocklöv and Bertil Forsberg, “Comparing Approaches for Studying the Effects of Climate Extremes – a Case Study of Hospital Admissions in Sweden during an Extremely Warm Summer,” *Global Health Action* 2, no. 1 (2009), <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v2i0.2034>.

			al., 2012; + Mastrangelo et al., 2007**; Anderson et al., 2013; Gronlund et al., 2014*; Knowlton et al., 2008; Kovats et al., 2004; Ma et al., 2011; Sheridan & Lin, 2014; Son et al., 2014
		Insignificant	Schneider et al., 2023
		Inconclusive	Guirguis et al., 2018; Rocklöv & Forsberg, 2009
- COPD	Increase	Significant	++ Monteiro et al., 2013; Anderson et al., 2013
		Inconclusive	Lim et al., 2012
- ARI		Insignificant	Anderson et al., 2013
- Asthma	Increase	Significant	+ Lim et al., 2012; Son et al., 2014
- Allergic disease	Increase	Significant	Son et al., 2014
Cerebrovascular	Decrease	Significant	Knowlton et al., 2008
		Insignificant	Michelozzi et al., 2009; Monteiro et al., 2013
Renal disease	Increase	Significant	+ Gronlund et al., 2014*; + Hopp et al., 2018*; + Knowlton et al., 2008; Guirguis et al., 2018; Kovats et al., 2004
Mental health	Increase	Significant	Bundo et al., 2021
		Insignificant	Guirguis et al., 2018
Heat-related disease ⁵	Increase	Significant	+++ Guirguis et al., 2018; +++ Hopp et al., 2018*; +++ Knowlton et al., 2008

Table 3. Impact of heat on morbidity (hospitalizations, emergency department visits).

Note: MI = Myocardial Infarction; COPD = Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease; ARI = Acute Respiratory Infection. Statistical significance is defined by a 95% confidence interval (CI). +/- An increase of 10 – 25%; +/- An increase of 25 – 50%; +++/--- An increase of ≥ 50%. * For individuals ≥ 65 years; ** For individuals ≥ 75 years. ^a Illnesses related to ICD-9-CM Code 992 (e.g., heat exhaustion, heat fatigue, heat edema, etc.)

Heat-related diseases, such as heat exhaustion or heat fatigue, were shown to strongly increase NCDs (+++) across multiple studies, with various authors finding severe effects.

Significant increases in **cardiovascular** morbidity were found in studies such as ⁴⁵ and ⁴⁶, with strong effects (++) across multiple populations. Nevertheless, ⁴⁷ reported decreases in cardiovascular emergency hospital admissions, while research by ⁴⁸ and ⁴⁹ found no significant effects. The decrease in cardiovascular emergency hospital admissions may be

⁴⁵ Turner, Connell, and Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia.”

⁴⁶ Mastrangelo et al., “Pattern and Determinants of Hospitalization during Heat Waves: An Ecologic Study,” *BMC Public Health* 7, no. 200 (2007), <https://doi.org/10.1186/1471-2458-7-200>.

⁴⁷ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland.”

⁴⁸ Gronlund et al., “Heat, Heat Waves, and Hospital Admissions among the Elderly in the United States, 1992–2006.”

⁴⁹ Paola Michelozzi et al., “High Temperature and Hospitalizations for Cardiovascular and Respiratory Causes in 12 European Cities,” *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine* 179, no. 5 (March 2009): 383–89, <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.200802-217OC>.

due to heat causing people to sweat more and their blood vessels to widen, which reduces the strain on the heart ⁵⁰. This lowers blood pressure and improves the condition of patients with heart failure, similar to the effects of medications that specifically target heart function. Moreover,⁵¹ again classified their results as inconclusive due to conflicting results in the data.

Respiratory outcomes, on the other hand, exhibited a more consistent pattern of deterioration, particularly in relation to heat exposure. Strong effects (+++) were found in studies like ⁵² and ⁵³ for conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD). Studies by ⁵⁴ and ⁵⁵ further confirmed these findings, although some studies reported inconclusive outcomes for specific respiratory conditions like acute respiratory infections (ARI) ⁵⁶.

The impact of high temperatures and heat on **mental health** appears rather inconclusive. Studies like ⁵⁷ report increases in mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and stress during heat events. In contrast, ⁵⁸ report insignificant results in their study focusing on different climate regions of San Diego County in the United States.

In conclusion, most findings consistently point toward a significant increase in morbidity—especially for respiratory conditions and heat-related diseases—as a result of heat exposure.

4.2. Wildfires and air pollution

Wildfires, which are often intensified by extreme heat, not only further raise temperatures but also release harmful pollutants into the air, compounding the health risks associated with heatwaves. The channels through which they affect human health also include air, water, and land pollution. This section highlights the literature on the relationship between air pollution due to wildfires and human health based on their corresponding focus-areas:

- Wildfire smoke affects human health significantly through air pollution.

⁵⁰ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland.”

⁵¹ Rocklöv and Forsberg, “Comparing Approaches for Studying the Effects of Climate Extremes – a Case Study of Hospital Admissions in Sweden during an Extremely Warm Summer.”

⁵² Turner, Connell, and Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia.”

⁵³ Monteiro et al., “Excess Mortality and Morbidity during the July 2006 Heat Wave in Porto, Portugal.”

⁵⁴ Mastrangelo et al., “Pattern and Determinants of Hospitalization during Heat Waves: An Ecologic Study.”

⁵⁵ Brooke Anderson et al., “Heat-Related Emergency Hospitalizations for Respiratory Diseases in the Medicare Population,” *American Journal of Respiratory and Critical Care Medicine* 187, no. 10 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1164/rccm.201211-1969OC>.

⁵⁶ Anderson et al.

⁵⁷ Marvin Bundo et al., “Ambient Temperature and Mental Health Hospitalizations in Bern, Switzerland: A 45-Year Time-Series Study,” *PLOS ONE* 16, no. 10 (October 12, 2021): e0258302, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0258302>.

⁵⁸ Kristen Guirguis et al., “Heat, Disparities, and Health Outcomes in San Diego County’s Diverse Climate Zones,” *GeoHealth* 2, no. 7 (July 2018): 212–23, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2017GH000127>.

- Socioeconomically deprived populations are more vulnerable than other segments of the population.
- Air pollution due to wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses.
- Impact depends on the topography and inhabitation.
- Anthropogenic intervention like deforestation aggravates wildfires.

Wildfire smoke affects human health significantly through air pollution. This smoke contains particulate matter and poisonous substances causing respiratory, cardiovascular, ophthalmologic and mental health problems⁵⁹. The main cause can be attributed to high blood pressure that distorts heart rhythm resulting in increased hypertension, heart attacks, or ischemic heart issues. Additionally, wildfire smoke can exacerbate gastrointestinal diseases, allergies, asthma or related issues, as well as cancers such as breast and lung cancer. These effects are heterogenous amongst the population based on sociodemographic characteristics given similar levels of exposure to the events⁶⁰. Numerous studies show that the most significant channel of impact is through air pollution, with respiratory morbidity and mental illnesses being the most prominent NCDs⁶¹. Wildfire smoke also leads to increased cognitive impairment like Dementia and Alzheimer as well as mental health issues like anxiety⁶². These effects are more pronounced for people with existing cognitive issues, people under psychiatric medications as well as for people who are highly concerned about mental well-being.

Furthermore, people exposed to a wildfire in Californian region were found to be using increased psychotropic medication, suggesting a higher level of mental health problems⁶³. Evidence suggests that health issues related to air pollution constitute a significant proportion of total health issues. This is supported by the notable proportion of literature related to air pollution compared to the total literature in our sample literature collection (see Figure 3). For example, due to wildfire smoke, chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases account for 50% and ischemic heart diseases account for 25% of the total disease burden⁶⁴. These effects are predicted to increase significantly in the future. A study based on the

⁵⁹ Sara Wollschlaeger et al., “Investigation of Climate Change Impacts on Long-Term Care Facility Occupants,” *City and Environment Interactions* 13 (January 2022): 100077, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cacint.2021.100077>.

⁶⁰ Sarah Elise Finlay et al., “Health Impacts of Wildfires,” *PLoS Currents* 4 (November 2, 2012): e4f959951cce2c, <https://doi.org/10.1371/4f959951cce2c>.

⁶¹ Jia C. Liu et al., “A Systematic Review of the Physical Health Impacts from Non-Occupational Exposure to Wildfire Smoke,” *Environmental Research* 136 (January 2015): 120–32, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2014.10.015>; M.C. Sheehan, “2021 Climate and Health Review – Uncharted Territory: Extreme Weather Events and Morbidity,” *International Journal of Health Services* 52, no. 2 (2022): 189–200, <https://doi.org/10.1177/00207314221082452>.

⁶² Wollschlaeger et al., “Investigation of Climate Change Impacts on Long-Term Care Facility Occupants.”

⁶³ Z.S. Wettstein and A. Vaidyanathan, “Psychotropic Medication Prescriptions and Large California Wildfires,” *JAMA Network Open* 7, no. 2 (2024): E2356466, <https://doi.org/10.1001/jamanetworkopen.2023.56466>.

⁶⁴ Howard Frumkin and Andy Haines, “Global Environmental Change and Noncommunicable Disease Risks,” *Annual Review of Public Health* 40, no. Volume 40, 2019 (April 1, 2019): 261–82, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-040218-043706>.

wildfire smoke exposure and either hospitalisation or emergency visits during the period 2003-2010 in the western USA, estimated the impact of future increases in wildfires on potential health outcomes in the year 2050 ⁶⁵. Some studies find evidence that decrease in air pollution levels to a reduction in respiratory and cardiovascular diseases ⁶⁶. This evidence is crucial for understanding the counterfactual and causal links when it comes to wildfire smoke exposure and health outcomes: it shows not only that an increase in air pollution is associated with an increase in NCDs but also demonstrates that a decrease in air pollution is linked to a reduction in NCDs.

Studies find that socioeconomically deprived populations are more vulnerable than other segments of the population. For example, a study on the October 2007 wildfires in Southern California as a natural experiment explores the heterogenous impact of wildfire smoke on both sides of the San Diego-Tijuana border based on corresponding cardio-respiratory hospitalizations ⁶⁷. It finds that Tijuana has lesser hospitalization rates than San Diego and attributes this difference in rate across the border to socioeconomic characteristics, such as the poverty rate, which in Tijuana is three times more than that of San Diego.

Another study finds that the effects are heterogenous across age groups, where the greatest share of affected are children younger than 5 years and individuals older than 65 years ⁶⁸. It also finds that that smoke increases respiratory diseases by 3%, where 10% of the 3% increase is due to asthma. Not only across age groups but also across gender is the effect heterogenous due to the extent of exposure to the smoke. For example, a study on the August 2006 wildfires in Galicia, Spain, finds increased drug use for obstructive airway diseases among pensioners and a significant rise in anxiolytic-hypnotic use among men in fire-affected areas ⁶⁹.

Air pollution due to wildfires also causes diseases healthy population. A study on the wave of fires in November 2016 in Israel finds that individuals of low socio-economic status without existing illnesses were at greater risk of experiencing long-term effects following fires, that was evident from persistently higher hospitalization rates for two years post event

⁶⁵ Jennifer D Stowell et al., “Asthma Exacerbation Due to Climate Change-Induced Wildfire Smoke in the Western US,” *Environmental Research Letters* 17, no. 1 (January 1, 2022): 014023, <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ac4138>.

⁶⁶ Susanne Breiter-Busch et al., “Impact of Climate Change on Non-Communicable Diseases Due to Increased Ambient Air Pollution,” *Journal of Health Monitoring* 8, no. Suppl 4 (September 6, 2023): 103–21, <https://doi.org/10.25646/11655.2>; J. Hwang et al., “Face-to-Face with Scorching Wildfire: Potential Toxicant Exposure and the Health Risks of Smoke for Wildland Firefighters at the Wildland-Urban Interface,” *The Lancet Regional Health - Americas* 21 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lana.2023.100482>.

⁶⁷ L. Schwarz et al., “Wildfire Smoke Knows No Borders: Differential Vulnerability to Smoke Effects on Cardio-Respiratory Health in the San Diego-Tijuana Region,” *PLOS Global Public Health* 3, no. 6 (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgph.0001886>.

⁶⁸ Alexandra Heaney et al., “Impacts of Fine Particulate Matter From Wildfire Smoke on Respiratory and Cardiovascular Health in California,” *GeoHealth* 6, no. 6 (June 2022): e2021GH000578, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2021GH000578>.

⁶⁹ Caamano-Isorna et al., “Respiratory and Mental Health Effects of Wildfires.”

⁷⁰. These effects could be categorized into two effects viz. short-term and long-term ⁷¹. It shows that the short-term manifests from short duration exposure to increase in fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) that leads to increase in the risk of acute cardiovascular events by 1 to 3%. The long-term effect from prolonged exposure over time that increases the risk of acute cardiovascular events by 10% due to the onset or aggravation of hypertension and diabetes.

Some studies find that air pollution due to wildfires exacerbates existing illnesses. Its exposure increases oxidative stress and inflammation, individuals with pre-existing cardiovascular conditions may experience increased illness during and after wildfire events ⁷². Similar effects are found by another study on the wave of fires in November 2016 in Israel already discussed earlier. It finds that people with underlying morbidity are at greater risk of experiencing long-term effects following fires ⁷³. The reason of these effects could be that beyond a certain threshold of pollutants is exceeded during wildfires, respiratory hospitalizations and emergency visits (ED) due to asthma and chronic obstructive pulmonary disease increase ⁷⁴. One study explains this threshold effect by exploring various wildfires in Greece to estimate differences in particle toxicity or deposition location in the human respiratory tract (RT) on the oxidative potential (OP) exposure ⁷⁵. It finds that air pollutants have significant OP, which implies reduction in level of antioxidants in body, resulting in exacerbation of cardiovascular and respiratory illnesses.

The effects of air pollution from wildfire are also heterogenous based on the topography and inhabitation around the wildfire events. For example, emissions like poisonous gases and harmful particulate matter from wildfires that impact human health are influenced by factors like the type of vegetation, fire characteristics, landscape and weather conditions ⁷⁶. A study finds no relationship for the overall sample between PM_{2.5} content and respiratory or circulatory disease-related hospital emergency visits or mortality between 2013 and 2018 in

⁷⁰ Odeya Cohen, Stav Shapira, and Eyal Furman, “Long-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Exposure: A Retrospective Study Exploring Hospitalization Dynamics Following the 2016 Wave of Fires in Israel,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 9 (April 20, 2022): 5012, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19095012>.

⁷¹ Breitner-Busch et al., “Impact of Climate Change on Non-Communicable Diseases Due to Increased Ambient Air Pollution.”

⁷² Wayne E. Cascio, “Wildland Fire Smoke and Human Health,” *Science of The Total Environment* 624 (May 15, 2018): 586–95, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.086>.

⁷³ Cohen, Shapira, and Furman, “Long-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Exposure.”

⁷⁴ Colleen E. Reid et al., “Associations between Respiratory Health and Ozone and Fine Particulate Matter during a Wildfire Event,” *Environment International* 129 (August 2019): 291–98, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2019.04.033>.

⁷⁵ M. Mylonaki et al., “Wildfire and African Dust Aerosol Oxidative Potential, Exposure and Dose in the Human Respiratory Tract,” *Science of the Total Environment* 913 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169683>.

⁷⁶ Cascio, “Wildland Fire Smoke and Human Health.”

California's Shasta county ⁷⁷. However, it finds that in sub-local regions with lower elevation, dense population, generally poor air quality areas, PM2.5 is associated with 15% increase in respiratory disease-related hospital visits in the same week.

The final type of literature delves into wildfires caused by anthropogenic intervention and its effects on human health. Our search result found only one literature that examines the association between deforestation-induced fires and respiratory health issues ⁷⁸. It finds that deforestation leads to arid conditions, higher temperatures, and lower precipitation that leads to wildfires and shows higher hospitalisation rates in Brazil's Amazon region during the forest fire season between 2009–2019. Another study on exceptionally intense global wildfire events using 21 years of satellite data shows that the frequency of extreme wildfires has increased 2.2 times from 2003 to 2023, with 6 of the most extreme events occurring in the past 7 years ⁷⁹. Studies like above are very few and need to be extended to other EWEs to examine the causal linkage between climate change, EWEs and their impact on NCDs.

In conclusion, although some studies find mixed effects which could be attributed either to their research design or data, most of the studies find significant effects of wildfires through air pollution on human respiratory, cardiovascular and mental health. Most of the studies report significant impacts on physiological illnesses and very few of them focus on mental illnesses. Morbidity and mortality due to asthma, hypertension, diabetes increase, which is identified through increased hospitalisation rates, increase in medicinal drugs consumption as well as reporting of aggravation of existing diseases. Similar effects are also found for mental illnesses which provides evidence of wildfire fires and air pollution on mental health. The effects are also heterogenous across different ages, sociodemographic factors, and topographies. For example, older and younger people are more vulnerable, financially weak people are unable to avail treatment due to higher treatment costs. This bolsters the deployment of socioeconomic variables like age, education, employment, gender etc in the empirical analysis.

Finally, deforestation is shown to lead towards drier weather, lesser rainfall, higher temperatures and increased wildfires. Few studies focus on establishing linkage between either climate change or anthropogenic activities and wildfire or air pollution. Most of them consider climate change as a premise to wildfires without providing adequate empirical evidence. However, there are also studies which show the effects of wildfires without positing climate change as given. This is a substantial gap which would serve as a significant

⁷⁷ Joan A. Casey et al., "Wildfire Particulate Matter in Shasta County, California and Respiratory and Circulatory Disease-Related Emergency Department Visits and Mortality, 2013–2018," *Environmental Epidemiology* 5, no. 1 (February 2021): e124, <https://doi.org/10.1097/EE9.0000000000000124>.

⁷⁸ M.R. Ribeiro et al., "Amazon Wildfires and Respiratory Health: Impacts during the Forest Fire Season from 2009 to 2019," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 21, no. 6 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21060675>.

⁷⁹ Cunningham, Williamson, and Bowman, "Increasing Frequency and Intensity of the Most Extreme Wildfires on Earth."

contribution to existing literature by linking climate change and human health (non-communicable diseases, mental health) through extreme weather events like wildfires. The next section 4.3 discusses the effect of floods on human health.

4.3. Floods

4.3.1 Anxiety and trauma

Flooding can have significant long-term psychological effects, particularly in communities that experience repeated flooding. The distress and trauma associated with flood damage and losses can lead to lasting mental health disorders, which can undermine the community's resilience to future flooding events.

A review study by ⁸⁰ illustrates the wide range of measured impacts of flooding on mental health, showing that between 8.6% and 53% of the population in countries such as Korea, England, China, and Thailand exhibit symptoms of psychological nature such as Post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, or depression. In Table 4, the effect sizes of various outcomes are displayed, indicating that anxiety has a very strong effect, with over 60% of respondents reporting frequent anxiety during rainfall, even long after the flood event.

Frequent flashbacks were reported by 23% of households as occurring “always” or “very often”, while nearly two-thirds experienced them, albeit rarely. Nightmares were less prevalent, with 60% of respondents never experiencing them and fewer than 10% reporting them as occurring “always” or “very often”. Sleeplessness and depression showed similar patterns, with 18% of respondents experiencing these issues “always” or “very often”. Consequently, flashbacks, sleeplessness, and depression are associated with a moderate effect size, while nightmares are categorized as having a weak effect size. Additionally, stress, anger, relationship tension, loss of concentration, increased need to visit the doctor, and alcohol use are identified as having a moderate effect size. Notably, studies conducted shortly after a flood event tend to report higher rates of mental health disorders compared to those conducted later, although symptoms can persist in some individuals for many years. Additionally, the study reveals that minor psychosocial impacts are less frequently measured or reported compared to more severe disorders.

Moreover, the study by ⁸¹ empirically investigates the long-term psychological effects of the 2007 flood event in England using a postal survey of affected households. The authors found that household income, the depth of flooding, the need to relocate during restoration, as well as mitigation actions were related to the prevalence of stress, anxiety, depression, and mental

⁸⁰ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households.”

⁸¹ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs.

health deterioration. Relocation and household income were the most predictive factors for psychological distress.

Outcome	Effect Size
Anxiety	Very strong
Flashbacks	Moderate
Nightmares	Weak
Sleeplessness, Depression	Moderate
Stress, Anger, Relationship tension, Loss of concentration, Need to visit the doctor, Alcohol use	Moderate

Table 4. Effect of floods on mental health in Lamond et al. (2015).

In addition, these mental health effects of flooding extend beyond immediate trauma and can persist for years⁸². In line with the findings from⁸³, a study by⁸⁴ shows that the threat of flooding significantly contributes to a decline in well-being. This decline is particularly pronounced in rural communities, where the interplay between these climatic stressors exacerbates mental health challenges. Moreover, their research indicates that psychological morbidity, such as symptoms of depression and anxiety, can continue for at least three years after a flooding event. Additionally, the study points out that perceived risks associated with climate change further contribute to psychological distress, as individuals grapple with the anticipation and uncertainty of future climate-related threats.

Consistent with previous findings,⁸⁵ observe that PTSD and anxiety were prevalent among survivors of the 1998 Dongting Lake flood in China, with rates of 9.5% and 9.2%, respectively. Although these figures align with the general pattern of persistent mental health issues observed in flood survivors, they are notably lower compared to the higher prevalence rates reported in studies examining the immediate aftermath of other major flooding events.

⁸² Fiona Charlson et al., “Climate Change and Mental Health: A Scoping Review,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, no. 9 (January 2021): 4486, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18094486>.

⁸³ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households.”

⁸⁴ Charlson et al., “Climate Change and Mental Health.”

⁸⁵ Wenjie Dai et al., “Long-Term Psychological Outcomes of Flood Survivors of Hard-Hit Areas of the 1998 Dongting Lake Flood in China: Prevalence and Risk Factors,” *PLOS ONE* 12, no. 2 (February 7, 2017): e0171557, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0171557>.

On the contrary, ⁸⁶ report a decrease in the prevalence of depression, anxiety, and PTSD following a flood. Their study found that depression rates dropped from 20.8% in the first year to 7.8% by the third year, anxiety from 27.6% to 11.8%, and PTSD from 33.2% to 17.1%. However, mental illness rates remained higher compared to the period before the flood, which is in line with previous findings.

4.3.2 Risk factors

Different studies yield varying findings on the risk factors for developing mental illness following disasters. These risk factors encompass several variables, including: the severity of the traumatic event, exposure to the injury or death of a loved one, gender, age, socioeconomic status, educational level, minority or ethnic background, psychiatric history, family instability, and insufficient social support ⁸⁷. For instance, ⁸⁸ identified that low social support and traits of emotional instability were significant risk factors for PTSD among disaster survivors, with females being particularly vulnerable to such psychiatric disorders. However, their study did not identify significant associations between PTSD or anxiety and other factors such as age, educational level, or marital status, which have been reported as risk factors in other research. Individuals in low- and middle-income countries are especially susceptible due to their heightened exposure to extreme weather events, greater levels of poverty, and limited access to essential services ⁸⁹.

4.3.3 Drowning, Physical Injuries, and Contamination

Expanding on these insights, a review by ⁹⁰ identifies drowning as the leading cause of death during floods, with flash floods exacerbating this risk. Immediate health threats also include trauma, musculoskeletal injuries, wounds, and carbon monoxide poisoning from unventilated generators. Additionally, floods contribute to indirect health issues through damage to healthcare infrastructure and exposure to contaminants.

⁸⁶ Ranya Mulchandani et al., “The English National Cohort Study of Flooding & Health: Psychological Morbidity at Three Years of Follow Up,” *BMC Public Health* 20, no. 1 (March 30, 2020): 321, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-8424-3>.

⁸⁷ Lawrence A Palinkas and Marleen Wong, “Global Climate Change and Mental Health,” *Current Opinion in Psychology, Socio-Ecological Psychology*, 32 (April 1, 2020): 12–16, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.copsyc.2019.06.023>.

⁸⁸ Dai et al., “Long-Term Psychological Outcomes of Flood Survivors of Hard-Hit Areas of the 1998 Dongting Lake Flood in China.”

⁸⁹ Paolo Cianconi, Sophia Betrò, and Luigi Janiri, “The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review,” *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 11 (2020), <https://www.frontiersin.org/journals/psychiatry/articles/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00074>.

⁹⁰ Agache et al., “Climate Change and Global Health.”

The review highlights the risks of water contamination, which can lead to increased mortality, loss of potable water, and increased spread of vector-borne and waterborne diseases. The aftermath of Hurricane Katrina is cited as an example, with residents exposed to pollutants and pathogens such as hydrocarbon fuels and heavy metals ⁹¹.

Similarly, ⁹² emphasize the increased risks of disease outbreaks related to flooding. Their review highlights the increased risks of waterborne and foodborne diseases, including gastrointestinal illnesses. While these infectious conditions are important health concerns, they fall outside the primary scope of NCDs.

In conclusion, the impact of flooding on NCDs is significant, encompassing both psychological and physical health dimensions. The long-term psychological effects of flooding, particularly in areas with recurrent events, manifest as persistent mental health disorders such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression. While some studies indicate a decrease in these conditions over time, mental health issues often remain elevated compared to pre-flood levels.

4.4. Droughts

Documenting the impacts of drought is challenging due to the slow onset of the phenomenon and the complex nature of its effects. The difficulty lies in measuring and defining drought due to its gradual development, lack of highly visible impacts, and ability to affect large areas across geopolitical boundaries. Various indicators are used to measure the onset, duration, and extent, which leads to diverse definitions and a lack of standardization. Generally, drought is defined as a prolonged period of abnormally dry weather, resulting in a significant water deficit compared to a regional norm ⁹³. It can lead to serious hydrological imbalances and is characterized by a deficiency in water supply due to consistently below-average precipitation.

Standard quantitative indices of drought measurements are deployed to monitor and evaluate droughts ⁹⁴. One study considered a variety of such indices to analyse effects of drought in USA ⁹⁵. It finds that 6-month exposure duration witnessed higher risk of

⁹¹ Agache et al.

⁹² Weinhhammer et al., “Extreme Weather Events in Europe and Their Health Consequences – A Systematic Review.”

⁹³ Carla Stanke et al., “Health Effects of Drought: A Systematic Review of the Evidence,” *PLoS Currents* 5 (June 5, 2013): ecurrents.dis.7a2cee9e980f91ad7697b570bcc4b004, <https://doi.org/10.1371/currents.dis.7a2cee9e980f91ad7697b570bcc4b004>.

⁹⁴ Drought NCEI, “Did You Know? | Measuring Drought | National Centers for Environmental Information (NCEI),” September 10, 2024, <https://www.ncei.noaa.gov/access/monitoring/dyk/measuring-drought>.

⁹⁵ Y. Gwon et al., “The Effect of Heterogeneous Severe Drought on All-Cause and Cardiovascular Mortality in the Northern Rockies and Plains of the United States,” *Science of the Total Environment* 912 (2024), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.169033>.

cardiovascular mortality as compared to 12-month exposure duration. We consider one potential cause as the timing and intensity of accompanying heatwave and air pollution in the short term as well as the duration for which the drought persisted with highest intensity. These factors are not well explained in this study. Furthermore, they are not well researched using adequate research designs. They also find the higher levels of mortality for both older male and female population. Furthermore, white populations show statistically significant effect on general mortality, however other race population showed statistically insignificant effects. Studies have found that Australian women's mental health appears less affected by droughts compared to men. This difference is attributed to the lack of consideration for occupational differences between genders in the research ⁹⁶. This encourages to delve more into sociodemographic heterogeneity effects due to race as well as exposure duration.

A systematic literature review highlights the mechanisms through which droughts contribute to NCDs ⁹⁷. It posits that droughts lead to arid and drier environment that causes dust air pollution and wildfires. Similar to the effects of heatwaves and air pollution as discussed in section 4.1 and section 4.2, respectively, droughts lead to mental stress due to food scarcity. One systematic literature review finds an increase of 3.1% in the level of distress or occupational stress in farmers due to a higher need for psychological resilience during drought affecting their production in USA as compared to non-drought conditions ⁹⁸. These effects are more pronounced in rural regions than urban regions due to higher prevalence of farming activities and greater reliance of the rural populations on agricultural output for their livelihood or income ⁹⁹. It is also found that affluent counties in Australia have better mental health conditions during drought as compared to less affluent counties due to better resilience ¹⁰⁰. Furthermore, cultivation in drought prone areas is sustained by increased deployment of chemical fertilisers, which may have potential effects on mental health disorders, though this aspect is not covered in the literature.

Another systematic literature review on droughts in Australia finds that on average, the overall population is 26% more likely to experience psychological problems during a drought compared to a non-drought situation ¹⁰¹. Furthermore, the review finds studies that show that although children and adolescents in drought-affected areas report higher levels of

⁹⁶ Holly Vins et al., “The Mental Health Outcomes of Drought: A Systematic Review and Causal Process Diagram,” *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 12, no. 10 (October 22, 2015): 13251–75, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph121013251>.

⁹⁷ Coral Salvador et al., “Public Health Implications of Drought in a Climate Change Context: A Critical Review,” *Annual Review of Public Health* 44, no. 1 (April 3, 2023): 213–32, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-publhealth-071421-051636>.

⁹⁸ Sheehan, “2021 Climate and Health Review – Uncharted Territory: Extreme Weather Events and Morbidity.”

⁹⁹ J. Sullenbarger, E. Schutzenhofer, and E. Haase, “Climate Change: Implications for Community Mental Health,” in *Textbook of Community Psychiatry: American Association for Community Psychiatry, Second Edition* (Springer International Publishing, 2022), 427–42, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-10239-4_31.

¹⁰⁰ Vins et al., “The Mental Health Outcomes of Drought.”

¹⁰¹ A. Walinski et al., “The Effects of Climate Change on Mental Health,” *Deutsches Arzteblatt International* 120, no. 8 (2023): 117–24, <https://doi.org/10.3238/arztebl.m2022.0403>.

emotional distress compared to a normal sample, the difference is not statistically significant. Similarly, there is no significant difference in emotional distress between children living on farms and those in rural regions. This could either due to the type of research design or absorption of stress by adults and having no spillovers to children and adolescents, which demands further exploration of the results based on heterogeneity in age as well as occupation classes.

When a drought is followed by a heatwave or increased air pollution, cardiovascular or respiratory diseases are reported. Urban areas are at higher risk of such diseases during drought periods due to pre-existing higher traffic-related air pollution and trapped urban heat ¹⁰². A systematic literature review in Spain finds two related studies ¹⁰³. The first study conducted in Galicia, Spain finds higher levels of cardiovascular and respiratory mortality rates in interior regions compared to coastal regions, attributed to a relative cooling effect and moisture from sea proximity ¹⁰⁴. This shows that drier and arid regions exhibit higher mortality levels during drought periods. The study finds worsening drought increases the risk of respiratory mortality (11%) more than that of cardiovascular mortality (6.4%). The second study that covers the entire Spanish region found no overall effect between either respiratory or cardiovascular mortality and droughts ¹⁰⁵. However, it finds that urban provinces such as Madrid and Barcelona experience significantly higher mortality rates during drought periods due to cardiovascular and respiratory issues compared to rural provinces, which can be attributed to factors like population density, environmental pollution, and healthcare disparities.

Another study examining children under 5 years of age in the municipalities in Brazil's Amazon region affected by drought during the year 2005 finds a significant increase in hospitalisation rates due to respiratory diseases from aerosol exposure ¹⁰⁶. During the 2005 drought, 31.3% (77) of the affected municipalities saw hospitalizations increase from 1.3% to 180% compared to the 10-year mean. In another drought in 2010, 43.0% (197) of municipalities experienced hospitalization increases ranging from 1.2% to 267%. The increase in hospitalizations during the 2010 drought was both more widespread and severe compared to 2005. Aerosols were a more significant factor in the 2005 drought than in 2010, despite the latter's larger spatial extent. This indicates that the concentration and distribution of aerosols, rather than the total drought area, may have a more pronounced impact on

¹⁰² Salvador et al., "Public Health Implications of Drought in a Climate Change Context."

¹⁰³ Weilhhammer et al., "Extreme Weather Events in Europe and Their Health Consequences – A Systematic Review."

¹⁰⁴ C. Salvador et al., "Effects on Daily Mortality of Droughts in Galicia (NW Spain) from 1983 to 2013," *Science of The Total Environment* 662 (April 20, 2019): 121–33, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.01.217>.

¹⁰⁵ C. Salvador et al., "Short-Term Effects of Drought on Daily Mortality in Spain from 2000 to 2009," *Environmental Research* 183 (April 1, 2020): 109200, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2020.109200>.

¹⁰⁶ Lauren T. Smith et al., "Drought Impacts on Children's Respiratory Health in the Brazilian Amazon," *Scientific Reports* 4, no. 1 (January 16, 2014): 3726, <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep03726>.

respiratory diseases. In areas severely affected by rainfall shortages, aerosol remained the key driver of respiratory diseases.

Not only do arid regions suffer from drought, but also water abundant countries like Canada can face them with dire consequences alike other drought prone countries ¹⁰⁷. One reason is that 98% of the Canadian population lives in regions holding 38% of the volume of Canada's freshwater resources. Additionally, general warming trends are leading to changes in freshwater volume throughout the year, including intermittent dry periods with little to no rainfall. While the extent of drought-induced NCDs in Canada is not yet as critical as in more drought-prone countries, the potential for future health impacts should be a reason for concern.

In conclusion, due to the slow and pervasive nature of droughts, mental stress persists for a longer duration as compared to other forms of extreme weather events. As a major aspect of drought deals with water scarcity, rural regions are the forefront and worst to get affected. Correspondingly, in terms of occupation, farmers and the allied supply chain related to food and nutrition incurs market failure. This is a good avenue for economists to develop adequate incentives and correct inadequacies during times of drought for a more resilient society. Furthermore, some studies show no evidence for effect on women due to less focus on heterogeneity in gender-based occupation. This encourages detailed evaluation of the role of causal channels due to occupation. The studies have a global coverage from USA and Canada to Africa, from affluent to underdeveloped countries, which in purview of the present trend of growing drought cases would provide ample number of good comparison regions. Finally, drought leads to wildfires, which in turn leads to other events like heatwaves and air pollution and demands exploration of the effects on health through detailed integrated assessment models.

4.5. Storms

The occurrence of storms, especially in the form of cyclones with massive destructive power, is closely connected to climatic factors ¹⁰⁸. The impact of these storms on humans depends significantly on factors such as cyclone intensity, local population density, socioeconomic status and governance. Although the frequency of tropical cyclones is expected to decrease, the anticipated rise in both population density and cyclone intensity over the next two

¹⁰⁷ Anna Yusa et al., "Climate Change, Drought and Human Health in Canada," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 12, no. 7 (July 2015): 8359–8412, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph120708359>.

¹⁰⁸ Edward A. Keller, Duane E. DeVecchio, and Robert H. Blodgett, *Natural Hazards: Earth's Processes as Hazards, Disasters, and Catastrophes*, 5th ed. (Fifth edition. | New York: Routledge, 2019. | "Fourth edition published by Pearson Education, Inc. 2015"—T.p. verso. |: Routledge, 2019), <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315164298>.

decades will likely lead to a significant increase in the number of people exposed annually, intensifying disaster risk, even with potential improvements in development and governance ¹⁰⁹.

While the relationship between climatic factors and the occurrence of storms is complex, there is evidence that both tropical and extratropical storm severity (wind speed, rainfall rates, etc.) may increase due to climate change (Bender et al. 2010). Additionally, global warming is likely to impact the regions where storms occur, potentially shifting their geographical distribution ¹¹⁰. Understanding these shifts is crucial, as changes in storm patterns have significant implications for non-communicable diseases. The disruption caused by storms can lead to exacerbations of cardiovascular and respiratory conditions due to physical stress, displacement, and exposure to pollutants, which are discussed in detail hereafter.

Effect of storms depends on its type and the mechanism through which it affects NCDs. ¹¹¹ focus on hurricane studies in USA on psychological disorders. They find that hurricanes not only increase anxiety in mentally healthy individuals but are also persistent for up to 12 years post exposure to hurricanes. They also find that due to destruction of healthcare infrastructure during hurricanes, mental health treatment completion rates dropped to half, leading to higher mental health patients. This phenomenon is more prevalent in adolescent and young adults with more traumatic exposures during hurricanes. All the above effects are attributed by the authors to presence of injuries or death within family or disruption of income and socioeconomic ties.

Moreover, not only actual storm events, but also repeated storm threats and recovery efforts lead to stress and anxiety and can negatively impact mental health, increasing the prevalence of depression and anxiety disorders. An analysis of the Adult Psychiatric Morbidity Survey in England, individuals whose homes were damaged from storms have a 50% higher likelihood of experiencing CMD compared to those whose homes were not damaged ¹¹². This analysis also shows that these effects are heterogenous based on age, gender and other socioeconomic features. For example, females have a 105% higher likelihood of experiencing CMD compared to males. 25–34 years age group has an 8% lower likelihood of CMD compared to the 16–24 years group. Private renters have a 4% higher likelihood of CMD, but this is not statistically significant. Inactive individuals have a 31% higher likelihood of CMD compared to employed individuals. Those in the most deprived areas have a 42% higher likelihood of CMD compared to those in the least deprived areas. Individuals in poor health have a 2794% higher likelihood of CMD compared to those with excellent health.

¹⁰⁹ Peduzzi et al., “Global Trends in Tropical Cyclone Risk.”

¹¹⁰ Markku Rummukainen, “Changes in Climate and Weather Extremes in the 21st Century,” *WIREs Climate Change* 3, no. 2 (March 2012): 115–29, <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.160>.

¹¹¹ Walinski et al., “The Effects of Climate Change on Mental Health.”

¹¹² Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health.”

A study finds that thunderstorms aggravate respiratory issues like asthma and pollen allergy by virtue of osmotic shock from thunder that ruptures pollens releasing allergens, or due to accompanying precipitation that hydrates pollens releasing allergens¹¹³. It also cites a study in New South Wales, Australia which finds that thunderstorm outflows occurred on 33% of days when epidemics took place, in contrast to only 3% of days without epidemics. This suggests that thunderstorm outflows are significantly more frequent on days when epidemics are occurring. Epidemic days refer to specific days on which an outbreak of a disease or illness is happening in a particular population. In this study, these are the days when the incidence of the disease is higher than usual, indicating an epidemic event. The data shows a notable association between the presence of thunderstorm outflows and these epidemic days. This suggests that on those days when asthma epidemics are reported, thunderstorm outflows are significantly more frequent.

Various studies find not only occurrence but also an increase in frequency of thunderstorms due to climate change linked to exacerbation of asthma cases, based on higher observed morbidity levels¹¹⁴. Furthermore, some of these studies consider climate change as given and consider higher frequency of thunderstorms as the effect without providing adequate quantitative information. Additionally, these studies find people with existing respiratory ailments to have increased morbidity during thunderstorms. However, there is not enough evidence to establish the causal link due to the complex interactions between thunderstorms, atmosphere and spatiotemporal heterogeneity amongst humans¹¹⁵. This is a substantial gap in the literature, where the causal link from climate change to storms to NCDs could be explored.

Another type of storm, the dust storm, has more severe and persistent impact on respiratory diseases like asthma, allergy than thunderstorms due to presence of toxic minerals and particulate matter¹¹⁶. The main mechanism of impact from dust storms is like air pollution either from heatwaves (see section 4.1) or from wildfires (see section 4.2) or from droughts (see section 4.4). However, due to the accompanying high-speed winds and volume of toxic minerals and particulate matter, the effects are different. For example, dust storms in USA between 2000-2015 have led to 9.2% increase in respiratory issues related hospital admissions on the day of dust storm and 7.5% increase on fifth day after dust storm¹¹⁷. However, the study in previous example could not find significant results for cardiovascular issues although the proportion of hospital admissions for cardiovascular issues is more than

¹¹³ Gennaro D'Amato et al., "Meteorological Conditions, Climate Change, New Emerging Factors, and Asthma and Related Allergic Disorders. A Statement of the World Allergy Organization," *World Allergy Organization Journal* 8 (January 1, 2015): 25, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40413-015-0073-0>.

¹¹⁴ D'Amato et al.

¹¹⁵ D'Amato et al.

¹¹⁶ C.E. Ramirez et al., "Elemental Composition of Airborne Particulate Matter from Coastal South Florida Area Influenced by African Dust Events," *Aeolian Research* 54 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aeolia.2022.100774>.

¹¹⁷ C. S. Rublee et al., "Associations Between Dust Storms and Intensive Care Unit Admissions in the United States, 2000–2015," *GeoHealth* 4, no. 8 (2020): e2020GH000260, <https://doi.org/10.1029/2020GH000260>.

double that for respiratory issues. This deviation is not thoroughly explained by the authors. We posit that this could be due to lower level of associated variation between the timing of dust event and cardiovascular issues, which is far lower than that for respiratory issues. As the most prominent and early effect of dust storm leads to respiratory issues. This is a substantial gap that could be addressed with adequate data and research design.

Similar mixed and inadequate evidence is also found in existing systematic literature review on dust storm and its effects on human health¹¹⁸. On one hand, it finds some studies conclude that dust storms do not have statistically significant effect on mortality due to respiratory or cardiovascular issues. On the other hand, it also finds studies conclude that dust storms have statistically significant effect on mortality due to respiratory or cardiovascular issues. One reason cited by the authors is due to different consideration of dust type in the dust storm like pm2.5, pm10 etc. Another reason is lack of clarity in explaining the data for type of hospitalisation or mortality cases reported as well as the research design. Furthermore, these studies are quite inconclusive from the aspect of exposure duration, in the sense that some studies find greater effect in short term exposure, some find no effect in short term.

A better understanding is provided by another systematic literature review on effect of storms, super-cyclones, hurricanes and snowstorms on mental health disorders in Asian and South American regions¹¹⁹. They find around 40% increase in psychological morbidity due to these types of storms in the first year of exposure. This trend gradually decreases but persists up to a certain level that varies across countries based on the nature of storm, degree of impact, measurement timing, affected population type etc. Anxiety accounts for the highest incidence followed by depression, especially because the studies that focussed on anxiety included storms that were more devastative in nature. Furthermore, the extent of anxiety and depression observed across the studies are in general lower for less developing countries, due to lower reporting and less mental health awareness.

In conclusion, the findings from the studies is quite conclusive that storms lead to increased health issues due to respiratory, cardiovascular, mental health problems. There are generally higher levels of morbidity, but mortality increases when the duration and intensity of storms increase. Nevertheless, only one systematic review by¹²⁰ find that mortality due to cardiovascular issues were highest on first day and that trend decreases day two onwards. These incidents happen only where unpreparedness due to sudden occurrence of event or

¹¹⁸ Ali Sadeghimoghaddam et al., "Investigating the Effects of Dust Storms on Morbidity and Mortality Due to Cardiovascular and Respiratory Diseases: A Systematic Review," *Journal of Education and Health Promotion* 10, no. 1 (2021): 191, https://doi.org/10.4103/jehp.jehp_1272_20.

¹¹⁹ Elisabeth Rataj, Katharina Kunzweiler, and Susan Garthus-Niegel, "Extreme Weather Events in Developing Countries and Related Injuries and Mental Health Disorders - a Systematic Review," *BMC Public Health* 16, no. 1 (September 29, 2016): 1020, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-016-3692-7>.

¹²⁰ Sadeghimoghaddam et al., "Investigating the Effects of Dust Storms on Morbidity and Mortality Due to Cardiovascular and Respiratory Diseases."

lack of preparedness due to economic conditions prevail. Additionally, there are studies which do not detail the air pollutants from dust storm as well as specific illnesses pertaining to cardiovascular diseases to ascertain the correct linkage. Even though, the statistical analysis direct towards similar inconclusive findings, as the quality of empirical evidence is still challengeable due to the methods deployed in the studies.

5. Conclusion

Climate change is driving an increase in the frequency and severity of extreme weather events which has heightened their impact on non-communicable diseases. In recent years, a lot of research has emerged on the topic of climate change and its effects on NCDs, highlighting the growing relevance and urgency of this issue. As climate-related disasters become more frequent and severe, their impact on NCDs has become increasingly evident. The screened literature reveals that EWEs, including heatwaves, wildfires, flooding, droughts, and storms, exacerbate existing NCDs and contribute to the emergence of new health risks. This evidence underscores the effects of climate-induced changes on the incidence and severity of NCDs, demonstrating how these events can worsen health outcomes and increase the overall burden of disease.

Heatwaves or increased temperatures greatly affect both mortality as well as morbidity. Most studies report intensified chronic conditions such as cardiovascular diseases or respiratory disorders. The elevated temperatures associated with heatwaves not only increase the risk of heat-related illnesses but also aggravate existing health problems, further straining vulnerable populations. Based on the current literature, the evidence regarding the impact of heatwaves on mental health remains inconclusive, with studies showing mixed results on whether there is a significant increase in mental health problems following such events.

Wildfires significantly impact NCDs by exacerbating respiratory conditions and inducing mental health issues. The air pollution resulting from wildfires, including harmful particulates and gases, deteriorates air quality and worsens conditions such as chronic obstructive pulmonary disease and ischemic heart disease. The associated oxidative stress and inflammation from wildfire emissions further heighten cardiovascular risks. Additionally, the psychological stress from wildfires contributes to mental health issues like anxiety and depression.

Flooding has notable long-term psychological effects, particularly in communities that experience repeated events. The trauma and distress caused by flood damage can lead to persistent mental health disorders such as PTSD, anxiety, and depression. While some research indicates that the prevalence of these conditions may decrease over time, mental illness rates often remain higher compared to the period before the flood. The prevalence of

these conditions is influenced by factors such as household income, flood depth, and the necessity of relocation.

Droughts present challenges in assessing their health impacts due to their gradual onset and complex nature. Droughts result in water deficits and hydrological imbalances that affect water supply and agriculture, leading to health issues like heat-related illnesses and mental health problems like stress and anxiety due to economic distress for stakeholders across the food supply chain. Furthermore, the slow development and varying definitions of drought complicate precise measurement of its health effects. Furthermore, the bidirectional linkages of drought with other extreme weather events like heatwaves and wildfires. These linkages are not studied in the literature and results from existing studies are highly biased due to the confounding nature of these conditions.

Storms, including cyclones, impact health through physical stress, displacement, and exposure to pollutants. Increased storm intensity and frequency, driven by climate change, exacerbate cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. The stress and anxiety associated with storms and recovery efforts also contribute to heightened mental health issues, such as depression and anxiety disorders. Additionally, effects of the type of storms like dust storms, thunderstorms, super-cyclones etc on health are not separately studied in general. Furthermore, the types of diseases in many studies are not explicitly highlighted, like asthma or bronchitis in respiratory disease, ischemic heart problem or heart attack in cardiovascular disease. These drawbacks deter from drawing empirically correct conclusions.

Overall, the evidence underscores the significant health impacts of climate-related disasters on NCDs. Understanding these interactions is crucial for developing effective strategies to address and mitigate the adverse effects of climate change on health.

Chapter 2: The Impacts of Extreme Weather Events on Health Systems and the Implications for Mountain Areas: An Overview of Reviews

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1. Introduction

As the global community confronts the intensifying consequences of climate change, the 28th Conference of the Parties (COP 28) held in late 2023 underscored the urgent need for action, setting new records for attendance and introducing its first-ever Health Day. This event aimed to enhance the integration of health considerations into climate action, as reflected in the COP 28 UAE Declaration on Climate and Health ¹²¹. One of its primary objectives is to strengthen health systems' capacity to anticipate and implement adaptive strategies for climate-sensitive health threats. This goal has become increasingly pressing given that the occurrence of Extreme Weather Events (EWEs) has surged fivefold over the past 50 years ¹²².

The influence of climate change on EWEs—ranging from floods and storms to heatwaves and wildfires—is profound, as these events are intensifying in both frequency and severity ¹²³. Often, such phenomena escalate into disasters that significantly impact public health, health systems, ecosystems, and the economy. However, while extensive research has explored the effects of EWEs on population health, comparatively less focus has been directed to understanding their implications for health systems.

Investigating the impacts of EWEs on health systems is complex, as the latter consists of intricate networks of interdependent components that vary considerably across countries. Generally, health systems include critical subcomponents such as pre-hospital care, hospital infrastructure, primary care services, pharmacies, and public health departments. EWEs may disrupt these components, affecting infrastructure, service delivery, medication quality, and resource availability. For instance, the floods in Germany in 2021 resulted in power outages, damage to the water supply system, and patient record losses, leading to a marked decline in patient visits at clinics that were forced to relocate ¹²⁴. Similarly, heatwaves in Australia

¹²¹ COP28 UAE, 'COP28 UAE Declaration On Climate And Health', accessed 16 October 2024, <https://www.cop28.com/en/cop28-uae-declaration-on-climate-and-health>.

¹²² WMO, 'WMO Atlas of Mortality and Economic Losses from Weather, Climate and Water Extremes (1970–2019)', World Meteorological Organization, 30 October 2023, <https://wmo.int/publication-series/wmo-atlas-of-mortality-and-economic-losses-from-weather-climate-and-water-extremes-1970-2019>.

¹²³ UNDRR, 'Hazard Definition and Classification Review: Technical Report | UNDRR', 28 July 2020, <https://www.undrr.org/publication/hazard-definition-and-classification-review-technical-report>.

¹²⁴ Luca Theresa Wieseahn and Andrea Kaifie, 'The Impact of the 2021 Flood on the Outpatient Care in the North Rhine Region, Germany: A Cross-Sectional Study', *BMC Public Health* 24, no. 1 (22 January 2024): 250, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-023-17279-y>.

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and the United Kingdom have been linked to increased demand for health services, such as hospital admissions, emergency room visits, and ambulance calls ¹²⁵.

The knowledge gap widens further when considering vulnerable regions, such as mountain areas, encompassing over 900,000 km² of terrestrial ecosystems across Europe ¹²⁶. These regions are at heightened risk due to their remoteness and the complex interdependence between high-altitude areas and the surrounding valleys ¹²⁷. Due to climate change, mountain regions have experienced above-average warming and increased precipitation levels—trends projected to persist and elevate disaster risk. Additionally, the significant thermal gradient in mountain ecosystems makes them particularly susceptible to temperature fluctuations, resulting in the loss of snow cover and glaciers that reflect solar radiation ¹²⁸.

Mountain areas' vulnerability is particularly evident in the context of hydro-meteorological events, whose frequency and intensity are strongly influenced by the projected global temperature increase ¹²⁹. For instance, in the European Alps, the number of disasters has risen by approximately 26% over the past four decades, increasing from more than 60 events between 1981 and 1990 to more than 85 between 2011 and 2020. According to the EM-DAT database ¹³⁰, floods (44.7%), mass movements (28.9%) and storms (21.1%) occur most frequently in the European Alps ¹³¹. It is also important to highlight the potential interaction between hydro-meteorological and geological hazards, which can lead to cascading and compounding effects and can generate an overall impact that is greater than the sum of the individual events ¹³².

¹²⁵ Katya Brooks et al., 'Heatwaves, Hospitals and Health System Resilience in England: A Qualitative Assessment of Frontline Perspectives from the Hot Summer of 2019', *BMJ Open* 13, no. 3 (March 2023): e068298, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2022-068298>; Hannah Mason et al., 'Systematic Review of the Impact of Heatwaves on Health Service Demand in Australia', *BMC Health Services Research* 22, no. 1 (28 July 2022): 960, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-022-08341-3>.

¹²⁶ Marco Cervellini et al., 'A Grid-Based Map for the Biogeographical Regions of Europe', *Biodiversity Data Journal* 8 (30 June 2020): e53720, <https://doi.org/10.3897/BDJ.8.e53720>.

¹²⁷ GLOMOS, 'Towards Systemic Disaster Risk Reduction in Mountains | PreventionWeb', 12 October 2023, <https://www.preventionweb.net/publication/towards-systemic-disaster-risk-reduction-mountains>.

¹²⁸ Irasema Alcántara-Ayala, Peng Cui, and Alessandro Pasuto, 'Disaster Risk Reduction in Mountain Areas: A Research Overview', *Journal of Mountain Science* 19, no. 6 (1 June 2022): 1487–94, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11629-022-7487-2>.

¹²⁹ Anina Stäubli et al., 'Analysis of Weather- and Climate-Related Disasters in Mountain Regions Using Different Disaster Databases', in *Climate Change, Extreme Events and Disaster Risk Reduction: Towards Sustainable Development Goals*, ed. Suraj Mal, R.B. Singh, and Christian Huggel (Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2018), 17–41, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-56469-2_2.

¹³⁰ 'EM-DAT: The International Disaster Database.', accessed 16 October 2024, <https://public.emdat.be/>.

¹³¹ Kamar Naser, Zaeem Haq, and Bernard D. Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries: A Systematised Review and Thematic Analysis', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 21, no. 4 (3 April 2024): 434, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21040434>; Stäubli et al., 'Analysis of Weather- and Climate-Related Disasters in Mountain Regions Using Different Disaster Databases'.

¹³² GLOMOS, 'Towards Systemic Disaster Risk Reduction in Mountains | PreventionWeb'.

Despite the growing threats posed by EWEs on health systems in mountain areas, the Midterm Review of the Implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015–2030 ¹³³ highlights how disaster risk reduction (DRR) strategies tailored for mountain areas are still scarce ¹³⁴. This knowledge gap is also evident when it comes to health systems resilience and adaptation to climate change in mountain regions.

To fill the gap in knowledge on the implications of EWEs on health systems in mountain areas, and to support the preparatory phases of the Mountadapt project, this systematic review of reviews details the various impacts of EWEs on the health system, and its subcomponents, offering a critical analysis of findings and tailored implications for mountain areas. The results of this review will provide essential information to enhance health system preparedness for EWEs, a critical element for effective public health planning.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study design

Given the existing literature on the effects of selected EWEs on some health system components, a systematic review of reviews was considered the most suitable method for mapping current knowledge on the impacts of EWEs on the health system ¹³⁵. The Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) guidelines ¹³⁶ were followed for conducting and reporting this review.

In parallel to the review of reviews, a non-systematic review of scientific and grey literature was conducted to explore the unique characteristics of disaster risk management (DRM) in mountain areas. The information gathered in this phase was analysed and used to critically interpret the review of reviews' findings, with a focus on mountain areas. The results were then submitted to a healthcare professional with expertise in DRM in a mountain area of Italy, who provided feedback and suggestions through two rounds of feedback, helping to refine the interpretation of the findings in relation to mountain environments.

¹³³ UNDRR, 'The Report of the Midterm Review of the Implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030 | Midterm Review of the Sendai Framework', 5 April 2023, <https://sendaiframework-mtr.undrr.org/publication/report-midterm-review-implementation-sendai-framework-disaster-risk-reduction-2015-2030>.

¹³⁴ GLOMOS, 'Towards Systemic Disaster Risk Reduction in Mountains | PreventionWeb'.

¹³⁵ Michele Pollock et al., 'Chapter V: Overviews of Reviews [Last Updated August 2023]', in Higgins JPT, Thomas J, Chandler J, Cumpston M, Li T, Page MJ, Welch VA (Editors). *Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions Version 6.5*. Cochrane, 2024, 2023, <https://training.cochrane.org/handbook/current/chapter-v>.

¹³⁶ Matthew J. Page et al., 'The PRISMA 2020 Statement: An Updated Guideline for Reporting Systematic Reviews', *BMJ* 372 (29 March 2021): n71, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71>.

2.2. Search strategy

Review of reviews: the impact of EWEs on the health system

A comprehensive literature search was conducted across the PubMed, Scopus, and Web of Science databases. The search strategy employed a combination of two distinct term clusters: one related to health systems and the other to EWEs (Table 1), utilising Boolean operators and truncation symbols tailored to each database's requirements. The search was designed to capture studies featuring these words in titles and abstracts, or, when applicable, through the use of MeSH terms. Filters were applied to restrict the results to review articles, including narrative reviews, systematic reviews, and meta-analyses.

Table 1. Health system- and EWEs-related search terms

Health system-related search terms	EWEs-related search terms
"health services accessibility", "delivery of health care", "health system*", "health service*", "health care", "healthcare", "primary care", "primary health care", "primary healthcare", "general practi*", "pharmac*", "psychology*", "psychiatry*", "pre-hospital", "emergency department*", "emergency room*", "emergency service*", "emergency care", "emergency visit*", "outpatient", "A&E", "ambulance*", "emergency ward*", "hospital*", "clinic*", "health facility*", "ambulator*", "public health", "vaccin*", "nursing home*", "hospice", "health worker*", "health professional*", "doctor*", "nurse*", "physician*"	"extreme weather", "extreme event", "extreme climate", "flood*", "inundation*", "cold wave*", "extreme cold", "heat wave*", "heatwave*", "extreme heat", "hot weather", "hot temperature", "extreme temperature", "temperature-related", "wildfire*", "bushfire*"

The search, performed in June 2024, was limited to articles published in the past 10 years and was restricted to literature reviews only. The study selection process relied on the following inclusion criteria: (a) the study is a review (systematic review with meta-analysis, systematic review without meta-analysis, narrative review); (b) the study addresses the direct or indirect impacts of either floods/storms, landslides, heatwaves, cold spells, or wildfires on any component of the health system. Exclusion criteria were: (a) the study focuses on the health impacts, without clear identification of the impacts on the health system; (b) the study is published before the chosen timeframe; (c) the study's full text is not available online nor obtained after contacting the corresponding author.

Narrative review: peculiarities of DRM in mountain areas

In July 2024, both scientific and grey literature on DRM in mountain areas, with a specific emphasis on health-related DRM in European Alpine regions, was collected. This literature included a compilation of case studies on EWEs that have historically impacted the demonstration sites involved in the Mountadapt project (e.g., Austria, France, Romania, Slovenia). Additionally, grey literature related to DRM in mountain areas was gathered, including reports from previous European projects focused on Alpine or mountainous regions. Scientific literature was also sourced through comprehensive searches across multiple databases, including PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, and Google Scholar.

2.3. Operational definition

The following operational definitions were considered in this study:

Health system: the entirety of different levels of care, namely the pre-hospital care system, the hospital system, the primary care and elderly care systems, pharmacies and public health. For the hospital system, different productive pipelines were further distinguished: emergency pathway, medical and surgical pathway, and outpatient and Day Hospital pathways¹³⁷. When the specific level of care was unclear from the article, linguistic criteria were systematically applied to classify the impacts. For instance, when authors referred to “outpatient visits”, these were classified within the hospital system, specifically in the outpatient pathway; references to “mental health services” without further specifications were similarly included in the hospital system within the outpatient pathway; “physician visits” were instead included in the primary care system.

Extreme weather event: a rare event for a given location and time of year. Typically, an EWE is as rare as, or rarer than, the 10th or 90th percentile of a probability distribution based on observations. Extreme weather characteristics can vary significantly by region¹³⁸; the ones considered in this study are those typically occurring in the selected European Alpine regions in the Mountadapt: floods/storms, landslides, heatwaves, cold spells and wildfires. Given the heterogeneity in definitions of EWEs, and sometimes the lack of indicators defining such events in the included studies, a degree of flexibility was maintained in classifying certain conditions as EWEs. For example, if “days of extreme heat” were reported as having impacts akin to those expected from heatwaves, such information was extracted and categorised under heatwave impacts.

¹³⁷ G. Bensa, Anna Prenestini, and Stefano Villa, ‘La logistica del paziente in ospedale: aspetti concettuali, strumenti di analisi e leve di cambiamento’ (Egea, 2008), <https://iris.unibocconi.it/handle/11565/1898991>.

¹³⁸ ‘IPCC Glossary Search’, accessed 16 October 2024, <https://apps.ipcc.ch/glossary/>.

Impact on the health system: effect observed across various areas and functions of the health system, including impacts on infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, utilisation of healthcare services and patient flow, surge capacity, and resources, including equipment and human resources ¹³⁹.

2.4. Data extraction and analysis

Review of reviews: the impact of EWEs on the health system

Selected information on the records was inserted in a Google Sheet database and duplicates were removed. Three authors screened the articles' eligibility for inclusion by first looking at titles and abstracts and then the articles' full texts. Data was extracted from the reviews following a deductive approach. Precisely, the subjects covered by each review were systematically mapped into different topics that aligned with the study objective and operational definitions. In particular, information was extracted about the type of EWE, the characteristics of the study (e.g., whether a review performed a meta-analysis, was systematic or narrative) and the type of impacts on the health system. Each impact was thematically assigned to both a health system's level of care (e.g., pre-hospital system, primary care system) and a specific area (e.g., infrastructure, quality of care).

Narrative review: peculiarities of DRM in mountain areas

Selected articles from scientific and grey literature were collected and uploaded in a Google Drive folder. Information on the peculiarities of DRM in mountain areas was extracted and classified according to the pertinent health system area (i.e., infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, utilisation of healthcare services and patient flow, surge capacity, and resources, including equipment and human resources).

2.5. Data synthesis and reporting

Review of reviews: the impact of EWEs on the health system

Demographic information on the reviews included in this study was summarised in a table detailing all included records, the type of review, the percentage of European studies included in each review, the types of hazards addressed, and the level of care for which impacts were reported. Specific impact information was summarised in text for each level of

¹³⁹ R.K. Phalkey and V.R. Louis, 'Two Hot to Handle: How Do We Manage the Simultaneous Impacts of Climate Change and Natural Disasters on Human Health?', *The European Physical Journal Special Topics* 225, no. 3 (1 May 2016): 443–57, <https://doi.org/10.1140/epjst/e2016-60071-y>.

care and production pipeline, distinguishing between different hazards and areas/functions affected. A graphical representation of the most significant results is presented following the text for each level of care, to enhance the understanding of key results.

Narrative review: peculiarities of DRM in mountain areas

The information gathered from the narrative review on mountain areas was used to supplement the findings of the systematic review of reviews. Specific considerations were added in a text box under the relevant level of care and production pipeline, and subsequently enriched by a DRM expert with extensive experience in a mountain area of Italy. This expert provided a critical interpretation of some review of reviews' findings, rendering them applicable to European Alpine regions as per the Mountadapt requirements.

3. Impact of Extreme Weather Events on the Health System

A total of 2108 reviews were identified, with 668 duplicates removed, leaving 1440 reviews for screening. Following the screening of titles and abstracts, 1286 reviews were excluded. A full-text evaluation of the remaining 154 reviews resulted in the exclusion of an additional 40, leaving 114 reviews for inclusion (Figure 1). Out of 114 reviews, 19 performed a meta-analysis, 48 adopted a systematic process, and 47 were narrative, non-systematic reviews.

The majority of the reviews included in this study addressed the impacts of heatwaves and cold spells (74% of meta-analyses, 60% of systematic reviews, 68% of narrative reviews), whereas the impacts most frequently mentioned were on hospitals (84% of meta-analyses, 81% of systematic reviews, 96% of narrative reviews) (Table 2).

Figure 1. Prisma flowchart detailing the screening process and selection of records

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Table 2. Characteristics of included reviews

1st author, date	Type of review	% of European studies	Hazard				Level of care					
			Floods	Heatwaves and cold spells	Wildfires	Not specified	Hospital	Pre-hospital	Primary care	Public health	Pharmacies	Elderly care
Barros B, 2023	Metanalysis	11.5%			x		x	x	x		x	
Borchers Arriagada N, 2019	Metanalysis	0%			x		x		x		x	
Cheng J, 2019	Metanalysis	32.7%		x			x	x				
Cruz J, 2020	Metanalysis	100.0%	x	x					x			
Faurie C, 2022	Metanalysis	9.7%		x			x					
Gao D, 2022	Metanalysis	0%		x			x					
Gould CF, 2024	Metanalysis	0%			x		x					
Liu J, 2021a	Metanalysis	18.9%		x			x					
Liu J, 2021b	Metanalysis	17.1%		x			x	x				
Liu J, 2022	Metanalysis	24.1%		x			x	x				
Makrufardi F, 2023	Metanalysis	16.1%				x	x					
Makrufardi F, 2024	Metanalysis	6.3%		x			x					
Moon J, 2021	Metanalysis	22.2%		x			x		x			
Oberai M, 2024	Metanalysis	0%		x				x				
Phung D, 2016	Metanalysis	40.6%		x			x					
Thompson R, 2023	Metanalysis	34.7%		x			x					
Weeda LZ, 2024	Metanalysis	N/A		x			x					
Xu Z, 2023	Metanalysis	14.6%		x				x				
Zhang Y, 2024	Metanalysis	10.2%			x		x					
Adetona O, 2016	Syst. review	10.0%			x		x		x		x	
Ahmer Raza M, 2021	Syst. review	0%	x		x						x	
Arsad FS, 2022	Syst. review	15.6%		x			x	x				
Babaie J, 2021	Syst. review	7.7%	x						x		x	

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1st author, date	Type of review	% of European studies	Hazard				Level of care						
			Floods	Heatwaves and cold spells	Wildfires	Not specified	Hospital	Pre-hospital	Primary care	Public health	Pharmacies	Elderly care	
Bell SA, 2020	Syst. review	0%			x		x						
Berberian AG, 2022	Syst. review	0%	x	x	x		x						
Bhatta M, 2023	Syst. review	0%		x			x	x	x				
Burhan E, 2020	Syst. review	16.7%			x		x						
Charlson F, 2021	Syst. review	9.2%	x	x	x		x						
Cicci KR, 2022	Syst. review	50.0%		x			x						
Conti A, 2022	Syst. review	N/A		x			x	x	x				
Feriato Corvetto J, 2023	Syst. review	26.7%	x	x	x		x	x					
Gosh AK, 2022	Syst. review	2.1%				x	x		x				
Harvey G, 2024	Syst. review	0%		x			x	x					
Henry S, 2021	Syst. review	6.3%			x		x						
Hindle EM, 2013	Syst. review	N/A		x				x					
Jiao A, 2023	Syst. review	5.7%			x		x				x		
Klinger C, 2014	Syst. review	5.0%	x	x	x		x		x				
Lee GW, 2023	Syst. review	0%	x	x	x		x	x	x				
Li M, 2015	Syst. review	15.2%		x			x	x					
Lindsey S, 2022	Syst. review	11.1%	x	x	x		x						
Linh Tran NQ, 2023	Syst. review	0%	x	x			x		x				
Lo YTE, 2024	Syst. review	N/A		x			x	x					
Louis S, 2023	Syst. review	25.6%				x	x						
Man RX, 2018	Syst. review	5.9%	x				x			x	x		
Massazza A, 2022	Syst. review	100%	x					x					
Naser K, 2024	Syst. review	4.4%	x	x			x	x	x	x			
O'Donnell E, 2021	Syst. review	0%		x				x					
Ochi S, 2014	Syst. review	4.3%	x		x				x		x	x	

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1st author, date	Type of review	% of European studies	Hazard				Level of care					
			Floods	Heatwaves and cold spells	Wildfires	Not specified	Hospital	Pre-hospital	Primary care	Public health	Pharmacies	Elderly care
Ospelt E, 2023	Syst. review	4.8%		x	x		x		x			
Parish GH, 2016	Syst. review	N/A		x				x				
Rocque RJ, 2021	Syst. review	31.9%	x	x	x		x	x		x		
Sahota H, 2023	Syst. review	0%	x		x		x				x	
Saulnier DD, 2017	Syst. review	0.9%	x				x		x			
Schmitt LHM, 2016	Syst. review	5.0%	x	x						x		
Skinner R, 2022	Syst. review	0%			x		x					
Strathearn M, 2022	Syst. review	0%		x			x					
Thompson R, 2018	Syst. review	34.3%		x			x					
Veenema TG, 2017	Syst. review	19.2%	x				x					
Wondmagegn BY, 2018	Syst. review	20.0%		x						x		
Woodland L, 2023	Syst. review	16.1%	x	x	x		x					
Wu WJ, 2023	Syst. review	16.1%		x			x		x		x	
Xu Z, 2014	Syst. review	41.7%		x			x	x				
Yates EF, 2023	Syst. review	6.3%	x				x					
Youssef H, 2014	Syst. review	11.7%			x		x		x		x	
Zurynski Y, 2024	Syst. review	8.3%	x		x		x					
Apisarnthanara KA, 2013	Narr. review	N/A	x							x		
Arbuthnott KA, 2017	Narr. review	100% (UK)		x			x		x			
Aune KT, 2021	Narr. review	N/A	x				x					
Bainbridge A, 2022	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x	x				
Barten DG, 2021	Narr. review	N/A	x		x		x					
Bayram H, 2023	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x					
Bein T, 2020	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					
Bekkar B, 2023	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					

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1st author, date	Type of review	% of European studies	Hazard				Level of care					
			Floods	Heatwaves and cold spells	Wildfires	Not specified	Hospital	Pre-hospital	Primary care	Public health	Pharmacies	Elderly care
Bell JE, 2018	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x
Belzer A, 2023	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x	x			x	
Black C, 2017	Narr. review	N/A			x		x		x			
Brennan M, 2020	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					
Cascio EW, 2018	Narr. review	N/A			x		x					
Casey JA, 2020	Narr. review	N/A				x	x			x	x	
Chang A, 2022	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x					
Chaseling GK, 2023	Narr. review	0% (New Zealand)		x			x					
Chersich MF, 2023	Narr. review	0% (Africa)		x			x					
Cianconi P, 2020	Narr. review	N/A		x	x		x					
Curtis S, 2017	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x	x	x			
Dhimal M, 2021	Narr. review	0% (Himalaya)	x	x			x					
Ghazal DA, 2018	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x					
Gronlund CJ, 2018	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					
Ha S, 2022	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x					
Hadley MB, 2022	Narr. review	N/A			x		x		x			
Holm SM, 2021	Narr. review	N/A			x		x					
Kam S, 2023	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x					
Kelly G, 2023	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x	x				
Lane K, 2013	Narr. review	0% (US coasts)	x				x	x			x	x
Leyva EWA, 2017	Narr. review	N/A	x	x			x					x
Liang SY, 2018	Narr. review	N/A	x							x		
Linares C, 2020	Narr. review	N/A	x	x	x		x	x				
Liu C, 2015	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					
Naserinejad N, 2023	Narr. review	N/A			x		x		x			

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1st author, date	Type of review	% of European studies	Hazard				Level of care						
			Floods	Heatwaves and cold spells	Wildfires	Not specified	Hospital	Pre-hospital	Primary care	Public health	Pharmacies	Elderly care	
Nidens N, 2023	Narr. review	N/A		x			x					x	
Orimoloye IR, 2019	Narr. review	0% (South Africa)	x	x			x						

3.1. Pre-hospital care system

Floods and storms

All aspects of the pre-hospital care system, except for infrastructure and quality of care, are reportedly affected by floods and storms.

Access to care - Floods and storms impact the ability to reach care. In particular, the ability of rescuers and ambulances to reach victims is hindered by blocked and collapsed roads¹⁴⁰. When air rescue is activated, it becomes restricted during nighttime¹⁴¹; similarly, when boats are used to reach and transport patients, trips are often difficult, time-consuming and expensive¹⁴².

Service utilisation - Evidence shows that the demand for ambulance services increases during floods and storms, both in terms of callouts and dispatches¹⁴³, specifically to assist those who rely on electrically powered medical equipment (e.g., ventilators, oxygen), which stop functioning in case of power outages¹⁴⁴, and to rescue those bitten by arthropods¹⁴⁵.

Surge capacity - The impacts on surge capacity concern *Staff* and *Stuff* – as per the 4s Surge Capacity framework¹⁴⁶. In particular, it has been reported that the air transport of supplies and staff in affected areas is often hampered by fog and adverse weather conditions¹⁴⁷.

¹⁴⁰ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease: A Guide for the Dermatologist', *American Journal of Clinical Dermatology* 24, no. 4 (July 2023), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40257-023-00770-y>; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas: A Review and Vulnerability Assessment', *Journal of Environmental and Public Health* 2013 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1155/2013/913064>; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Kazuo Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 3 (19 January 2022): 1098, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19031098>; Jouni Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK', *Environmental Health: A Global Access Science Source* 16, no. Suppl 1 (5 December 2017): 113, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-017-0328-z>.

¹⁴¹ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

¹⁴² Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'.

¹⁴³ Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

¹⁴⁴ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

¹⁴⁵ Sarah Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems', *Environmental Health* 16, no. 1 (5 December 2017): 128, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-017-0324-3>.

¹⁴⁶ Samantha K. Watson, James W. Rudge, and Richard Coker, 'Health Systems' "Surge Capacity": State of the Art and Priorities for Future Research', *The Milbank Quarterly* 91, no. 1 (14 March 2013): 78, <https://doi.org/10.1111/milq.12003>.

¹⁴⁷ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

Resources - Considering the resources, the main impact is reported for rescuers and ambulance personnel, who may suffer from Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD) after rescue operations ¹⁴⁸. A study included in the review from Massazza et al. (2022) noted that 11.8% of the rescue squad personnel suffered from PTSD up to 7 years after responding to a flood in Italy ¹⁴⁹.

Heatwaves and cold spells

All aspects of the pre-hospital care system, except for infrastructure, are reportedly affected by heatwaves and cold spells.

Access to care - Heatwaves impact the ability to reach care. Specifically, it has been reported that the ability of ambulances to reach those in need during heatwaves is challenged by pavement failure, cracking railway lines, and power losses ¹⁵⁰. During cold spells, a longer ambulance response time has been reported ¹⁵¹.

Quality of care - Impacts on the quality of pre-hospital care predominantly concern drug deterioration in extreme heat (e.g., piritramid, midazolam, succinylcholine, atropine, nifedipine, insulin, inhaled asthma medications), especially those transported by ambulance ¹⁵². Also, the vaporisers' output for field anaesthesia fluctuates in extreme heat ¹⁵³, posing serious risks to the patients. Similarly, drug deterioration happens in extreme cold conditions (e.g., piritramid, etomidate, propofol, furosemide, insulin, rTPA, alteplase) ¹⁵⁴.

¹⁴⁸ Alessandro Massazza, Vittoria Ardino, and Rita Erica Fioravanzo, 'Climate Change, Trauma and Mental Health in Italy: A Scoping Review', *European Journal of Psychotraumatology* 13, no. 1 (2022): 1–16, <https://doi.org/10.1080/20008198.2022.2046374>.

¹⁴⁹ Mario Di Fiorino et al., 'Forma Piena e Sottosoglia Del Disturbo Post-Traumatico Da Stress Nelle Squadre Di Soccorso Sette Anni Dopo Un'alluvione', *Psichiatria e Territorio*, 1 January 2004.

¹⁵⁰ Mason et al., 'Systematic Review of the Impact of Heatwaves on Health Service Demand in Australia'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

¹⁵¹ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

¹⁵² Elise M. Hindle and J. D. Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature: Effects on Patients, Staff and Equipment', *Journal of the Royal Army Medical Corps* 160, no. 4 (December 2014): 279–85, <https://doi.org/10.1136/jramc-2013-000076>; Grace Kelly et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Asthma and Allergic-Immunologic Disease', *Current Allergy and Asthma Reports* 23, no. 8 (August 2023): 453–61, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11882-023-01093-y>; L Schaefer et al., 'Pharmacological Properties of Emergency Drugs under Extreme Conditions', *Notfall Und Rettungsmedizin* 23, no. 4 (2020): 270–75, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10049-019-00646-x>.

¹⁵³ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

¹⁵⁴ Hindle and Henning; Schaefer et al., 'Pharmacological Properties of Emergency Drugs under Extreme Conditions'.

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Service utilisation - A rise in ambulance callouts ¹⁵⁵ and dispatch ¹⁵⁶ occurs during and after heatwaves (lag time: 1-2 days). The metanalysis from Oberai et al. (2024) found a 3% increase in the pooled RR of ambulance dispatch during heatwave days as compared to non-heatwave days; similarly, Xu et al. (2023) confirmed increases in ambulance dispatch during heatwaves, with estimates ranging from 2% to 7%, depending on the chosen heatwave definition. In particular, this increase happens for cardiovascular conditions (e.g., cardiac problems, heat

¹⁵⁵ Fadly Syah Arsad et al., 'The Impact of Heatwaves on Mortality and Morbidity and the Associated Vulnerability Factors: A Systematic Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 23 (6 December 2022): 16356, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph192316356>; Manoj Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia: A Rapid Review', *Climate* 11, no. 12 (December 2023): 1–18, <https://doi.org/10.3390/cli11120246>; Jian Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Global Epidemiological Evidence', *Environmental Research* 177 (October 2019): 108610, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108610>; Grace W. Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia: A Rapid Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, no. 13 (3 July 2023): 6285, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20136285>; Li M et al., 'Heat Waves and Morbidity: Current Knowledge and Further Direction-a Comprehensive Literature Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 12, no. 5 (18 May 2015), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph120505256>; Cristina Linares et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on the Public Health of the Mediterranean Basin Population - Current Situation, Projections, Preparedness and Adaptation', *Environmental Research* 182 (March 2020): 109107, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.109107>; Jingwen Liu et al., 'Heat Exposure and Cardiovascular Health Outcomes: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *The Lancet Planetary Health* 6, no. 6 (1 June 2022): e484–95, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00117-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00117-6); Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes? A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *Environment International* 153 (August 2021), <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envint.2021.106533>; Mason et al., 'Systematic Review of the Impact of Heatwaves on Health Service Demand in Australia'; Mehak Oberai et al., 'Preparing for a Hotter Climate: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Heatwaves and Ambulance Callouts in Australia', *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Public Health* 48, no. 1 (February 2024): 100115, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.anzjph.2023.100115>; Elen O'Donnell et al., 'The Effect of Heat Events on Prehospital and Retrieval Service Utilization in Rural and Remote Areas: A Scoping Review', *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 36, no. 6 (December 2021): 782–87, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X21001163>; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

¹⁵⁶ Mohammed Sarfaraz Gani Adnan et al., 'Vulnerability of Australia to Heatwaves: A Systematic Review on Influencing Factors, Impacts, and Mitigation Options', *Environmental Research* 213 (1 October 2022): 113703, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2022.113703>; Harvey G, Bain-Donohue S, and Dewi Sp, 'The Impact of Extreme Heat on Older Regional and Rural Australians: A Systematic Review', *The Australian Journal of Rural Health* 32, no. 2 (April 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1111/ajr.13094>; Oberai et al., 'Preparing for a Hotter Climate'; Rhea J. Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change: An Overview of Systematic Reviews', *BMJ Open* 11, no. 6 (1 June 2021): e046333, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2020-046333>; Zhiwei Xu et al., 'The Impact of Heat Waves on Children's Health: A Systematic Review', *International Journal of Biometeorology* 58, no. 2 (March 2014): 239–47, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-013-0655-x>; Zhiwei Xu et al., 'Heat, Heatwaves, and Ambulance Service Use: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis of Epidemiological Evidence', *International Journal of Biometeorology* 67, no. 10 (1 October 2023): 1523–42, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-023-02525-0>.

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stroke), cerebrovascular issues, and respiratory and renal diseases ¹⁵⁷, as well as neurological complaints ¹⁵⁸ and suicide attempts ¹⁵⁹.

Surge capacity - The impacts on surge capacity concern the *Stuff*. In particular, evidence shows that delays and logistical challenges may occur in obtaining additional resources on-site in a timely manner ¹⁶⁰.

Resources - It has been reported that rescuer equipment suffers under extreme heat conditions; for instance, electronic screens shut down ¹⁶¹, and polyvinyl chloride components, such as endotracheal tubes, oxygen face masks, and tubing, become malleable ¹⁶². This is also true under extremely cold temperatures, when materials easily break, drugs and food spoil, batteries drain, and crystals in screens freeze ¹⁶³. Thermal fluctuations and temperature variations generally pose a risk of damaging electronic equipment ¹⁶⁴. For human resources, there is an increased risk of heat-related illnesses and physiological stress during heatwaves ¹⁶⁵, as well as a potential decrease in fine motor control and cognitive function during cold spells ¹⁶⁶.

Wildfires

The only reported impacts of wildfires on the pre-hospital system concern health service utilisation and surge capacity.

¹⁵⁷ Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves'; Andrea Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves: A Systematic Review of Reviews', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 10 (January 2022): 5887, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19105887>; Linares et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on the Public Health of the Mediterranean Basin Population - Current Situation, Projections, Preparedness and Adaptation'; Y. T. Eunice Lo et al., 'Heat Impacts on Human Health in the Western Pacific Region: An Umbrella Review', *The Lancet Regional Health. Western Pacific* 42 (January 2024): 100952, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100952>; Oberai et al., 'Preparing for a Hotter Climate'.

¹⁵⁸ Oberai et al., 'Preparing for a Hotter Climate'.

¹⁵⁹ Julia Feriato Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, no. 2 (9 January 2023): 1190, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20021190>.

¹⁶⁰ Abigail Bainbridge, A. Wolfe, and M. Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management', *BMJ Mil Health* 168, no. 6 (1 December 2022): 462–66, <https://doi.org/10.1136/military-2022-002131>.

¹⁶¹ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

¹⁶² Hindle and Henning.

¹⁶³ Bainbridge, Wolfe, and Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management'; Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

¹⁶⁴ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

¹⁶⁵ Bainbridge, Wolfe, and Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management'.

¹⁶⁶ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

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Service utilisation - An increase in ambulance dispatch related to PM concentrations has been reported for asthma/COPD and diabetic problems ¹⁶⁷. In particular, the meta-analysis from Barros et al. (2023) analysed studies in Canada, showing a 1% increase in the OR of ambulance dispatch for asthma and COPD per 10 µg/m³ rise in 1 h-PM_{2.5}, and a 7.5-10.4% increase in ambulance dispatch and paramedic assessment for diabetic complications 24 hours after wildfire exposure.

Surge capacity - Impacts on surge capacity concern the System, as evidence shows that when populations are displaced in the aftermath of wildfires, they place a significant strain on the health system in the host community ¹⁶⁸.

¹⁶⁷ Bela Barros, Marta Oliveira, and Simone Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions', *Journal of Toxicology and Environmental Health. Part B, Critical Reviews* 26, no. 7 (3 October 2023): 387–415, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10937404.2023.2236548>.

¹⁶⁸ Jesse E. Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health', *Journal of the Air & Waste Management Association (1995)* 68, no. 4 (April 2018): 265–87, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10962247.2017.1401017>.

Figure 2. Visual representation of the main impacts on Pre-Hospital Care System

Box 1. Pre-hospital care system: considerations for mountain areas

In mountain areas, EWEs significantly hinder pre-hospital responders by delaying access to affected locations and timely patient care. This is partly due to the region's unique geographic and climatic conditions (e.g., rockfalls, avalanches, sudden weather changes, or poor visibility)¹⁶⁹, often necessitating rapid extrication and evacuation over immediate medical treatment¹⁷⁰. To facilitate patient prioritisation during incidents in mountain areas, the adoption of specialised triage tools tailored to mountain-specific conditions has been proposed to optimise the management of health emergencies in these settings¹⁷¹.

Air transport via helicopter is essential in mountain areas for reaching otherwise inaccessible locations. However, it becomes challenging in high winds or adverse weather conditions that reduce visibility (e.g., fog, heavy snow, storms). Strong wind can make aircraft manoeuvring difficult, increasing the risk of collisions with mountains, and this is critical given the limited availability of public transport, which may be inaccessible during EWEs (e.g., small railways being the only access point to some areas). Consequently, out-of-hospital times for injured patients in mountain areas are longer than in urban or suburban ones, leading to higher Injury Severity Scores¹⁷².

Extreme cold during cold waves in mountain areas can impact the quality of pre-hospital care. Cold-induced vasoconstriction and shock can hinder the establishment of intravenous access, while IV fluids may freeze, complicating fluid administration. Additionally, rural mountainous areas often lack sufficient Automated External Defibrillators (AEDs), delaying timely shock delivery during emergencies¹⁷³. Cross-border communication challenges can also arise during EWEs, complicating the pre-hospital management of critical patients, such as those with hypothermia¹⁷⁴.

Surge capacity impacts arise when responding to patients in valleys that become isolated due to landslides or avalanches, necessitating helicopter transport of an emergency physician

¹⁶⁹ M. Pittore et al., 'Border-Independent Multi-Functional, Multi-Hazard Exposure Modelling in Alpine Regions', *Natural Hazards* 119, no. 2 (1 November 2023): 837–58, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-023-06134-3>.

¹⁷⁰ Marc Blancher et al., 'Management of Multi-Casualty Incidents in Mountain Rescue: Evidence-Based Guidelines of the International Commission for Mountain Emergency Medicine (ICAR MEDCOM)', *High Altitude Medicine & Biology* 19, no. 2 (June 2018): 131–40, <https://doi.org/10.1089/ham.2017.0143>.

¹⁷¹ Blancher et al.

¹⁷² Simon Rauch et al., 'Pre-Hospital Times and Clinical Characteristics of Severe Trauma Patients: A Comparison between Mountain and Urban/Suburban Areas', *The American Journal of Emergency Medicine* 36, no. 10 (October 2018): 1749–53, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajem.2018.01.068>.

¹⁷³ Philip Fischer et al., 'Automated External Defibrillator Delivery by Drone in Mountainous Regions to Support Basic Life Support – A Simulation Study', *Resuscitation Plus* 14 (1 June 2023): 100384, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resplu.2023.100384>.

¹⁷⁴ Anders Wetting Carlsen et al., 'Swedish-Norwegian Co-Operation in the Treatment of Three Hypothermia Victims: A Case Report', *Scandinavian Journal of Trauma, Resuscitation and Emergency Medicine* 25 (17 July 2017): 73, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13049-017-0418-5>.

(anaesthesiologist/intensivist or emergency medicine doctor) and a nurse. Typically, local medical guards or, when available, professionals working in trauma clinics active during the winter ski season are mobilised. The evacuation of isolated individuals can also be logistically challenging, as many evacuees are tourists without access to their vehicles. This situation requires arrangements for their return home using public transport or accommodation in facilities such as hotels or residences.

A notable aspect of mountainous areas is the impact of EWEs on mental health services utilisation. These regions exhibit a high suicide rate, attributed to isolation, lack of external stimuli, and insufficient sunlight. During EWEs, these factors, combined with worsening environmental conditions, fear, and PTSD, can further elevate suicide rates, increasing the workload for the pre-hospital system (ambulance callouts and dispatch).

Box 2. Mass Casualty Incidents (MCI) in mountain areas

MCI in mountain areas present unique challenges to rescue teams, including geographical isolation, exposure to extreme weather conditions, navigation of treacherous terrain, communication difficulties (including limited or absent mobile network or radio connections), limited human resources and equipment, specific injuries and illnesses¹⁷⁵. The long distance from major health facilities represents an additional challenge.

It has been reported that incidents such as avalanches, ski lift accidents, sudden floods, groups of people lost in a harsh environment, multiple lightning victims and people struck by sudden storms have each resulted in multiple MCIs in mountain areas¹⁷⁶. The remoteness of these locations means that the initial response is likely to be made by first responders with basic training or by personnel without rescue training, such as bystanders¹⁷⁷. It is also known that total out-of-hospital time is longer in individuals injured in mountainous areas, compared to urban/suburban areas¹⁷⁸. This could result in delays in the evacuation of injured and uninjured people; moreover, the latter may become casualties if they are unable to protect themselves from extreme climatic conditions¹⁷⁹.

In order to address the issue of prolonged out-of-hospital times for injuries sustained in mountainous regions, the sequential conveyance method has proven to be an efficient approach for emergency transportation. This method allows for the evacuation of all casualties from the harsh environment first¹⁸⁰. The deployment of helicopters with

¹⁷⁵ Blancher et al., 'Management of Multi-Casualty Incidents in Mountain Rescue'.

¹⁷⁶ Blancher et al.

¹⁷⁷ Blancher et al.

¹⁷⁸ Rauch et al., 'Pre-Hospital Times and Clinical Characteristics of Severe Trauma Patients'.

¹⁷⁹ Blancher et al., 'Management of Multi-Casualty Incidents in Mountain Rescue'.

¹⁸⁰ Chih-Long Pan, Chun-Wen Chiu, and Jet-Chau Wen, 'Adaptation and Promotion of Emergency Medical Service Transportation for Climate Change', *Medicine* 93, no. 27 (December 2014): e186, <https://doi.org/10.1097/MD.000000000000186>.

enhanced mountain rescue capabilities could facilitate more effective response strategies¹⁸¹. Additionally, the utilisation of small remotely piloted aircraft (drones) could enhance scene management¹⁸².

3.2. Hospital system – Emergency pathway

Floods and storms

Evidence shows how floods and storms affect all aspects of the in-hospital emergency pathway, namely infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, surge capacity, and resources.

Infrastructure - Hospital buildings hosting the Emergency Department (ED) may be damaged and flooded¹⁸³ causing water and power outages¹⁸⁴. This results in the disruption of natural gas pipelines, utilities, temperature control, sewage disposal, essential storage, life support, medical and communication technologies, air and water quality systems, sanitation processes, lifts, and critical freezers, especially when located in ground floors¹⁸⁵. Reviews

¹⁸¹ Blancher et al., 'Management of Multi-Casualty Incidents in Mountain Rescue'.

¹⁸² Blancher et al.

¹⁸³ Dennis G. Barten et al., 'When Disasters Strike the Emergency Department: A Case Series and Narrative Review', *International Journal of Emergency Medicine* 14, no. 1 (9 September 2021): 49, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12245-021-00372-7>; Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Daniel Aiham Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects: An International Perspective', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 15, no. 7 (1 July 2018): 1379, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph15071379>; Sandie Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 9 (1 June 2022), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-022-00345-9>; Ralph Xiu-Gee Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care: A Systematic Review', *The Lancet Oncology* 19, no. 9 (1 September 2018): e482–99, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(18\)30412-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(18)30412-1); Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

¹⁸⁴ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

¹⁸⁵ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health'; Chaamala Klinger, Owen Landeg, and Virginia Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health: A Systematic Review of the Literature from 2011-2012', *PLoS Currents* 6 (2 January 2014): ecurrents.dis.04eb1dc5e73dd1377e05a10e9edde673, <https://doi.org/10.1371/currents.dis.04eb1dc5e73dd1377e05a10e9edde673>; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'; Tener Goodwin Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health', *Journal of Nursing Scholarship: An Official Publication of Sigma*

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also report the loss of clinical records in chapter format, drug protocols, clinical trials and research documents during floods ¹⁸⁶. It is also reported that power outages may interrupt radiology services in the ED ¹⁸⁷.

Access to care - Different aspects of access to ED care are impacted by floods and storms. As for their ability to perceive care quality, power outages diminish patients' perception of care quality in the ED and cause them to delay seeking treatment ¹⁸⁸. A study included in the review from Yates et al. highlights the problem of delayed care after a storm, where patients presented to the ED for trauma care more than 50 days after the event ¹⁸⁹. When it comes to the ability to seek care, it was reported that the loss of phone line hindered dialling the emergency number ¹⁹⁰. The collapse of roads and the lack of functioning lifts and hoists in case of power outages is an obstacle to reaching care, especially for the elderly and those with limited mobility ¹⁹¹. Last, obstacles also affect the ability to engage with ED services: damages to hospital infrastructures disrupt the provision of emergency care services ¹⁹² and power outages hamper the provision of Extracorporeal Life Support (ECLS) treatment for those in need ¹⁹³.

Quality of care - Power outages compromise the storage of refrigerated medications, requiring their transfer to other facilities ¹⁹⁴. Interruptions in power and access to potable water affect hygiene and sanitation ¹⁹⁵. Access to clinical records becomes problematic,

Theta Tau International Honor Society of Nursing 49, no. 6 (November 2017): 625–34, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12328>.

¹⁸⁶ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

¹⁸⁷ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

¹⁸⁸ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health: A Narrative Review', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 7, no. 4 (December 2020), <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-020-00295-0>; Elizabeth F Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care: A Systematic Review of the Bellwether Procedures', *The Journal of Climate Change and Health* 14 (1 November 2023): 100274, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joclim.2023.100274>.

¹⁸⁹ Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

¹⁹⁰ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

¹⁹¹ Barten et al., 'When Disasters Strike the Emergency Department'; Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'; Veenema et al.

¹⁹² Hasan Bayram et al., 'Impact of Global Climate Change on Pulmonary Health: Susceptible and Vulnerable Populations', *Annals of the American Thoracic Society* 20, no. 8 (August 2023): 1088–95, <https://doi.org/10.1513/AnnalsATS.202212-996CME>; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

¹⁹³ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

¹⁹⁴ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

¹⁹⁵ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

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making it difficult to track patients' results ¹⁹⁶. Furthermore, staff may have limited experience in treating hypothermic patients ¹⁹⁷.

Service utilisation - Floods result in an increase in ED visits ¹⁹⁸, in particular for hypothermia, with most patients accessing the ED within 24 hours from the event ¹⁹⁹, injuries, (e.g., contusions, open wounds, sprains, fractures, burns, head injuries, abrasions, concussions) ²⁰⁰, lower extremity cellulitis, dermatological conditions, gastrointestinal complaints ²⁰¹, diabetes-related complications (eg., diabetic foot), renal failure, hemodialysis, respiratory conditions (eg., allergic rhinitis) ²⁰², CO and gasoline poisonings ²⁰³, oxygen/medication refills²⁰⁴, vaccination ²⁰⁵, mental health problems among pregnant women (with a peak reached 8 months after the event) ²⁰⁶, pregnancy complications (up until 1 month after the

¹⁹⁶ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

¹⁹⁷ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

¹⁹⁸ Arnab K. Ghosh et al., 'Impact of Hurricanes and Associated Extreme Weather Events on Cardiovascular Health: A Scoping Review', *Environmental Health Perspectives* 130, no. 11 (November 2022): 116003, <https://doi.org/10.1289/EHP11252>; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

¹⁹⁹ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'; Dell D. Saulnier, Kim Brolin Ribacke, and Johan von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm: A Systematic Review of Human Health Following Flood and Storm Disasters', *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 32, no. 5 (October 2017): 568–79, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X17006574>.

²⁰⁰ Alique G. Berberian, David J. X. Gonzalez, and Lara J. Cushing, 'Racial Disparities in Climate Change-Related Health Effects in the United States', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 9, no. 3 (September 2022): 451–64, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-022-00360-w>; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'; Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²⁰¹ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²⁰² Kyle T. Aune, Meghan F. Davis, and Genee S. Smith, 'Extreme Precipitation Events and Infectious Disease Risk: A Scoping Review and Framework for Infectious Respiratory Viruses', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 1 (24 December 2021): 165, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19010165>; Sue Anne Bell, Jennifer Horowitz, and Theodore J Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease: A Systematic Review', *The Gerontologist* 60, no. 7 (1 October 2020): e535–47, <https://doi.org/10.1093/geront/gnz123>; Norbert Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters: Strategies for Renal Rescue', *Seminars in Nephrology* 40, no. 4 (July 2020): 393–407, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semnephrol.2020.06.007>; Emma Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes: A Scoping Review', *Clinical Diabetology* 12, no. 3 (2023): 186–200, <https://doi.org/10.5603/DK.a2023.0012>; Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²⁰³ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

²⁰⁴ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Sae Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss: A Systematic Literature Review', *PLoS Currents* 6 (18 July 2014): ecurrents.dis.fa417630b566a0c7dfdbf945910edd96, <https://doi.org/10.1371/currents.dis.fa417630b566a0c7dfdbf945910edd96>.

²⁰⁵ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²⁰⁶ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

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event)²⁰⁷, in case of power outages, failure of electricity-dependent medical devices²⁰⁸. Increases are also noted for paediatric ED visits (with young children being more at risk²⁰⁹ for hydrocarbon and/or bleach poisoning²¹⁰, diarrheal illness²¹¹ and, in case of power outages, failure of electricity-dependent medical devices²¹². Conversely, some reviews reported decreases in ED visits for orthopaedic trauma, genitourinary complaints and abdominal pain²¹³, and pediatric ED visits for soft tissue wounds and influenza²¹⁴.

Surge capacity - Different surge capacity aspects are impacted by floods/storms. First, these events lead to health needs exceeding available human resources, particularly for first aid and injury care²¹⁵ this is compounded by a shortage of ED staff and results in difficulties in long-term staff retention after disasters²¹⁶. Second, in case of many people injured, a shortage of analgesics can occur²¹⁷ and there may be a lack of equipment, medication and supplies in the affected areas, due to an increased demand, damage to existing equipment and supplies, and the obstacles affecting transportation and the supply chain²¹⁸. Overall, if there is an influx of patients in the ED during floods, this risks overwhelming the whole system and patient flow²¹⁹.

Resources - The impact on the resources concerns the ED staff, who suffer from PTSD after responding to medical emergencies during floods and storms²²⁰, mainly because of the strain on health service provision.

²⁰⁷ Berberian, Gonzalez, and Cushing, 'Racial Disparities in Climate Change-Related Health Effects in the United States'; Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health'.

²⁰⁸ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

²⁰⁹ Bruce Bekkar et al., 'Pregnancy and Newborn Health - Heat Impacts and Emerging Solutions', *Seminars in Perinatology* 47, no. 8 (December 2023): 151837, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.semperi.2023.151837>.

²¹⁰ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²¹¹ Harpreet Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States: A Scoping Review', *Journal of Primary Care & Community Health* 14 (11 July 2023): 21501319231186497, <https://doi.org/10.1177/21501319231186497>.

²¹² Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

²¹³ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²¹⁴ Aune, Davis, and Smith, 'Extreme Precipitation Events and Infectious Disease Risk'; Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

²¹⁵ Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

²¹⁶ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²¹⁷ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²¹⁸ Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions: A Scoping Review', *Disability and Rehabilitation* 45, no. 25 (December 2023), <https://doi.org/10.1080/09638288.2022.2150328>; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

²¹⁹ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'.

²²⁰ Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

Heatwaves and cold spells

All aspects of the in-hospital emergency pathway, except surge capacity and resources, are reportedly impacted by heatwaves and cold spells.

Infrastructure - As for the impact on infrastructure, evidence shows that heatwaves impact the functioning of water supply systems and medical equipment ²²¹, hampering ED service delivery.

Access to care - Heatwaves impact access to care; it has been reported that extremely high temperatures hamper emergency care seeking during pregnancy ²²². Furthermore, extreme heat influences the ability to reach care, as difficulties in reaching hospitals are worsened at the expense of sparsely populated and remote communities²²³.

Service utilisation - The majority of the impacts of heatwaves on the ED concern an increase in visits ²²⁴, with a higher risk for older and younger individuals ²²⁵, and in transition months (e.g., May) ²²⁶, specifically for direct heat illness and dehydration, headache, hyper/hypotension, and disorders of fluid and electrolyte balance ²²⁷ – Faurie et al. (2022),

²²¹ Bainbridge, Wolfe, and Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management'; Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

²²² Matthew F. Chersich et al., 'Increasing Global Temperatures Threaten Gains in Maternal and Newborn Health in Africa: A Review of Impacts and an Adaptation Framework', *International Journal of Gynaecology and Obstetrics: The Official Organ of the International Federation of Gynaecology and Obstetrics* 160, no. 2 (February 2023): 421–29, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ijgo.14381>.

²²³ Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'.

²²⁴ Adnan et al., 'Vulnerability of Australia to Heatwaves'; Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'; Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves'; Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Harvey G, Bain-Donohue S, and Dewi Sp, 'The Impact of Extreme Heat on Older Regional and Rural Australians'; Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia'; Li M et al., 'Heat Waves and Morbidity'; Liu et al., 'Heat Exposure and Cardiovascular Health Outcomes'; Mason et al., 'Systematic Review of the Impact of Heatwaves on Health Service Demand in Australia'; N. Nidens et al., 'Klimawandel ganz nah: Hitzewellen', *Die Nephrologie* 18, no. 4 (1 July 2023): 203–12, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11560-023-00659-1>; Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'; Melanie Strathearn, Nicholas J. Osborne, and Linda A. Selvey, 'Impact of Low-Intensity Heat Events on Mortality and Morbidity in Regions with Hot, Humid Summers: A Scoping Literature Review', *International Journal of Biometeorology* 66, no. 5 (May 2022): 1013–29, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00484-022-02243-z>; Wendy Jingyi Wu et al., 'Review Article: Scoping Review of the Characteristics and Outcomes of Adults Presenting to the Emergency Department during Heatwaves', *Emergency Medicine Australasia: EMA* 35, no. 6 (December 2023): 903–20, <https://doi.org/10.1111/1742-6723.14317>; Xu et al., 'The Impact of Heat Waves on Children's Health'.

²²⁵ Michelle Brennan, Paula M O'Shea, and Eamon C Mulkerrin, 'Preventative Strategies and Interventions to Improve Outcomes during Heatwaves', *Age and Ageing* 49, no. 5 (24 August 2020): 729–32, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ageing/afaa125>; Xu et al., 'The Impact of Heat Waves on Children's Health'.

²²⁶ Nidens et al., 'Klimawandel ganz nah'.

²²⁷ Brennan, O'Shea, and Mulkerrin, 'Preventative Strategies and Interventions to Improve Outcomes during Heatwaves'; Kendra R. Cicci et al., 'High Temperatures and Cardiovascular-Related Morbidity: A Scoping Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19, no. 18 (7 September 2022):

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for example, reported a RR of 1.06 (0.00-1.14) for ED presentations due to heat illness and dehydration in Georgia (US) – multiple sclerosis exacerbation ²²⁸, cardiovascular conditions (e.g., stroke, ischemic heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, cardiac dysrhythmias, heart failure), respiratory (e.g., asthma) and renal diseases (e.g., acute kidney injury and acute renal failure) ²²⁹, occupational injuries, diabetes ²³⁰, emergency cesarean sections and preterm contractions related to fatigue and dehydration ²³¹. An increase in ED access for mental health disorders has also been reported ²³², in particular for organic disorders, substance misuse, schizophrenia and schizotypal disorders, mood disorders, behaviour disorders, neurotic disorders, disorders with onset in childhood/adolescence, and suicide ²³³. For instance, Liu et al. (2021) reported an RR for mental health morbidity of 1.064 (1.006-1.123), with heatwave defined as three or more consecutive days with daily mean temperatures higher than 95th percentiles (to note: their definition of morbidity encompassed both hospital admissions and ED visits). For cold spells, the reviews reported an increase in ED visits for cardiovascular diseases ²³⁴ and injuries from falls on ice and snow ²³⁵. Increases

11243, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph191811243>; Clare Faurie et al., 'Association between High Temperature and Heatwaves with Heat-Related Illnesses: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *The Science of the Total Environment* 852 (15 December 2022): 158332, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2022.158332>; Shreya Louis et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change and Air Pollution on Neurologic Health, Disease, and Practice: A Scoping Review', *Neurology* 100, no. 10 (7 March 2023): 474–83, <https://doi.org/10.1212/WNL.0000000000201630>.

²²⁸ Louis et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change and Air Pollution on Neurologic Health, Disease, and Practice'.

²²⁹ Arsad et al., 'The Impact of Heatwaves on Mortality and Morbidity and the Associated Vulnerability Factors'; Bayram et al., 'Impact of Global Climate Change on Pulmonary Health'; Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'; Bhatta et al.; Brennan, O'Shea, and Mulkerrin, 'Preventative Strategies and Interventions to Improve Outcomes during Heatwaves'; Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves'; Ciccì et al., 'High Temperatures and Cardiovascular-Related Morbidity'; Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'; Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'; Lo et al., 'Heat Impacts on Human Health in the Western Pacific Region'; Sarah E. Young, Laveen J. Khoshnaw, and Richard J. Johnson, 'Climate and the Nephrologist: The Intersection of Climate Change, Kidney Disease, and Clinical Care', *Clinical Journal of the American Society of Nephrology: CJASN* 18, no. 3 (1 March 2023): 411–17, <https://doi.org/10.2215/CJN.08530722>.

²³⁰ Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'.

²³¹ Chersich et al., 'Increasing Global Temperatures Threaten Gains in Maternal and Newborn Health in Africa'; Schaefer et al., 'Pharmacological Properties of Emergency Drugs under Extreme Conditions'.

²³² Paolo Cianconi, Sophia Betrò, and Luigi Janiri, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health: A Systematic Descriptive Review', *Frontiers in Psychiatry* 11 (2020): 74, <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsy.2020.00074>; Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'; Linares et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on the Public Health of the Mediterranean Basin Population - Current Situation, Projections, Preparedness and Adaptation'; Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'

²³³ Cianconi, Betrò, and Janiri, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health'; Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

²³⁴ Andrew Y. Chang et al., 'Aging Hearts in a Hotter, More Turbulent World: The Impacts of Climate Change on the Cardiovascular Health of Older Adults', *Current Cardiology Reports* 24, no. 6 (1 June 2022): 749–60, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11886-022-01693-6>.

²³⁵ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

were also noted for paediatric ED visits during heatwaves for asthma ²³⁶ and during cold spells for respiratory diseases ²³⁷.

Wildfires

The reported impacts of wildfires on the hospital's emergency care pathway concern access to care, service utilisation and resources

Access to care - One review reports of general access to care barriers when it comes to wildfires ²³⁸, also affecting the ED.

Service utilisation - Evidence shows an increase in ED visits during wildfires, related to PM concentrations ²³⁹, for cardiovascular conditions (e.g., myocardial infarction, ischemic heart disease, hypertension, dysrhythmia, ischemic stroke, heart failure, cerebrovascular disease), and respiratory diseases (e.g., asthma, COPD, bronchitis, dyspnea, upper respiratory infections, pneumonia, shortness of breath, bronchiolitis, upper respiratory tract illness including laryngitis, sinusitis and rhinitis, cardiopulmonary symptoms, cough and wheeze) ²⁴⁰. Notably, the metaanalysis by Gould et al. (2024) identified a 0.36% (0.19-0.53%)

²³⁶ Lewis J. Z. Weeda et al., 'How Climate Change Degrades Child Health: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *The Science of the Total Environment* 920 (10 April 2024): 170944, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.170944>.

²³⁷ Weeda et al.

²³⁸ Michael B. Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke', *Circulation* 146, no. 10 (6 September 2022): 788–801, <https://doi.org/10.1161/CIRCULATIONAHA.121.058058>.

²³⁹ Nicolas Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes: Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *Environmental Research* 179, no. Pt A (December 2019): 108777, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2019.108777>; Anqi Jiao et al., 'Associations between Short-Term Exposure to Wildfire Particulate Matter and Respiratory Outcomes: A Systematic Review', *Science of the Total Environment* 907 (1 January 2024): 168134, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.168134>; Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia'; Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'; Richard Skinner et al., 'A Literature Review on the Impact of Wildfires on Emergency Departments: Enhancing Disaster Preparedness', *Prehospital and Disaster Medicine* 37, no. 5 (October 2022): 657–64, <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1049023X22001054>; Hassani Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 11, no. 11 (14 November 2014): 11772–804, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph111111772>.

²⁴⁰ Olorunfemi Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public', *Inhalation Toxicology* 28, no. 3 (23 February 2016): 95–139, <https://doi.org/10.3109/08958378.2016.1145771>; Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'; Carolyn Black et al., 'Wildfire Smoke Exposure and Human Health: Significant Gaps in Research for a Growing Public Health Issue', *Environmental Toxicology and Pharmacology* 55 (1 October 2017): 186–95, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.etap.2017.08.022>; Erlina Burhan and Ummul Mukminin, 'A Systematic Review of

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increase in respiratory ED visits per additional 1- $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ increase in PM_{2.5}. Increases were also reported for pediatric ED visits, specifically for asthma and other respiratory conditions²⁴¹. In turn, a review reported of decreases in ED visits from people with COPD and congestive heart failure²⁴².

Resources - As for the impacts on resources, challenges in accessing medications, supplies and equipment have been reported²⁴³.

General EWEs

Some reviews refer to the impacts of EWEs on the hospital's emergency pathway, without specification of the type of event. These general impacts concern infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, surge capacity and resources.

Respiratory Infection Due to Air Pollution during Natural Disasters', *Medical Journal of Indonesia* 29, no. 1 (20 March 2020): 11–18, <https://doi.org/10.13181/mji.oa.204390>; Wayne E. Cascio, 'Wildland Fire Smoke and Human Health', *Science of The Total Environment* 624 (15 May 2018): 586–95, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2017.12.086>; Chang et al., 'Aging Hearts in a Hotter, More Turbulent World'; Carlos F. Gould et al., 'Health Effects of Wildfire Smoke Exposure', *Annual Review of Medicine* 75, no. 1 (29 January 2024): 277–92, <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-med-052422-020909>; Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'; Kelly et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Asthma and Allergic-Immunologic Disease'; Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia'; Nazgol Naserinejad et al., 'Wildland Fire, Air Pollution and Cardiovascular Health: Is It Time to Focus on the Microvasculature as a Risk Assessment Tool?', *Frontiers in Physiology* 14 (19 July 2023), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2023.1225195>; Michael R. Rossiello and Anthony Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves', *Cureus* 11, no. 5 (28 May 2019): e4771, <https://doi.org/10.7759/cureus.4771>; Skinner et al., 'A Literature Review on the Impact of Wildfires on Emergency Departments'; Lauren Stawovy and Bathmapriya Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications: A Narrative Review', *Current Pulmonology Reports* 11 (7 September 2022): 1–7, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s13665-022-00293-7>; Marilyn Urrutia-Pereira et al., 'Impact of Exposure to Smoke from Biomass Burning in the Amazon Rain Forest on Human Health', *Jornal Brasileiro De Pneumologia: Publicacao Oficial Da Sociedade Brasileira De Pneumologia E Tisiologia* 47, no. 5 (2021): e20210219, <https://doi.org/10.36416/1806-3756/e20210219>; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

²⁴¹ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Shelby Henry et al., 'Assessing the Risk of Respiratory-Related Healthcare Visits Associated with Wildfire Smoke Exposure in Children 0-18 Years Old: A Systematic Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, no. 16 (20 August 2021): 8799, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18168799>; Stephanie M. Holm, Mark D. Miller, and John R. Balmes, 'Health Effects of Wildfire Smoke in Children and Public Health Tools: A Narrative Review', *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology* 31, no. 1 (February 2021): 1–20, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41370-020-00267-4>.

²⁴² Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'.

²⁴³ Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'.

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Infrastructure - Regarding the infrastructure, some reviews reported damages to hospital buildings after EWEs, with consequent failure of electricity, water and sewage systems ²⁴⁴.

Access to care - Reviews reported that EWEs disrupt roads and transportation systems and that emergency care services are slowed down because of the impact of EWEs ²⁴⁵.

Quality of care - Overall, the quality of emergency health services is compromised during EWEs ²⁴⁶ also due to system breakdown²⁴⁷. Moreover, power outages and lack of access to potable water compromise hygiene and sanitation ²⁴⁸.

Service utilisation - In general, EWEs lead to increases in ED visits, specifically for mood disorders ²⁴⁹ and asthma ²⁵⁰. For instance, the meta-analysis by Makrufardi et al. (2023) found that EWEs increased the risk of asthma-related ED visits by 1.25 times (1.14-1.37).

Surge capacity - Impacts have been identified for System-level surge capacity of emergency care services during EWEs, including the effect of the increasing number of patients accessing the ED on the overall capacity of the system and patients' flows ²⁵¹, and the burden of displaced people on the health system in host communities ²⁵².

Resources - When it comes to the impact on resources, all the impacts refer to the staff and concern the unsafe conditions experienced by health personnel during EWEs ²⁵³, the consequent stress and burnout suffered by the health staff ²⁵⁴ and staff absenteeism ²⁵⁵.

²⁴⁴ Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events: A Review of the Evidence on Workforce Planning, Upskilling, and Capacity Building', *The International Journal of Health Planning and Management* 39, no. 3 (May 2024), <https://doi.org/10.1002/hpm.3769>.

²⁴⁵ Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'.

²⁴⁶ Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'.

²⁴⁷ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

²⁴⁸ Zurynski Y et al.

²⁴⁹ Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

²⁵⁰ Firdian Makrufardi et al., 'Extreme Weather and Asthma: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *European Respiratory Review: An Official Journal of the European Respiratory Society* 32, no. 168 (30 June 2023): 230019, <https://doi.org/10.1183/16000617.0019-2023>.

²⁵¹ Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'.

²⁵² Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna.

²⁵³ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

²⁵⁴ Zurynski Y et al.

²⁵⁵ Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

Figure 3. Visual representation of the main impacts on Hospital Emergency Pathway

Box 3. Hospital Emergency pathway: considerations for mountain areas

EWEs have particularly negative consequences on hospital EDs located in mountain areas. Firstly, heatwaves can cause issues with air conditioning systems, complicating emergency care delivery by the facility. Regarding infrastructure, freeze-thaw cycles affect buildings, especially in high mountain areas and cold regions, potentially leading to compound disasters²⁵⁶. To preserve supplies and equipment, scholars recommended the storage of provisions in areas that are less likely to be affected by EWEs like floods or avalanches, such as above ground level²⁵⁷.

In the event of avalanches, there could be an increase in the influx of hypothermic patients to hospitals in mountain areas, as hospital staff in these regions are generally better prepared to handle these health issues. This, however, may clash with staff shortages, especially in more rural areas, as staff may commute long distances and facilities may have limited options for backup staffing²⁵⁸. Recommendations provided to enhance nursing response in disasters within hospitals are the prioritisation of investments in training, the provision of adequate human, material, and technological resources, the offering of psychological support for staff post-disaster, and the strengthening of nursing competencies for DRM. Furthermore, each location and healthcare institution should compile an inventory of all available employees to assist teams during a disaster²⁵⁹.

The danger posed by EWEs in mountain areas can lead to public fear, causing individuals to avoid leaving their homes to seek emergency care or preventing travel to the ED. As a result, certain health conditions may worsen, and patients often seek ED care only when it is too late for effective intervention.

²⁵⁶ Alcántara-Ayala, Cui, and Pasuto, 'Disaster Risk Reduction in Mountain Areas'.

²⁵⁷ TRACIE, 'Critical Access Hospital Requirements CMS Emergency Preparedness Final Rule', 6 April 2019, <https://lhattrustfunds.com/assets/uploads/documents/aspr-tracie-cah.pdf>.

²⁵⁸ Tiffany A. Radcliff et al., 'Long-Term Care Planning, Preparedness, and Response Among Rural Long-Term Care Providers', *Disaster Medicine and Public Health Preparedness* 16, no. 1 (February 2022): 12–15, <https://doi.org/10.1017/dmp.2020.211>.

²⁵⁹ Mayra Wilbert Rocha et al., 'Safe Intra-Hospital Care in Context of Vulnerability to Socio-Environmental Disasters: Implications for Nursing', *Revista Brasileira de Enfermagem* 74 (5 February 2021): e20190223, <https://doi.org/10.1590/0034-7167-2019-0223>.

3.3. Hospital system - Medical and Surgical pathway

Floods and storms

Medical and surgical pathways are impacted by floods and storms at several levels, including infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, surge capacity and resources.

Infrastructure - Water and power outages impact the functionality of medical equipment and the overall continuity of care ²⁶⁰. Critical infrastructure—including natural gas pipelines, temperature control systems, sewage disposal, essential storage, life support systems, and communication technologies—is vulnerable to disruption, especially when located in flood-prone basements ²⁶¹. The loss of medical records, drug protocols, and research documents hampers clinical operations and research activities ²⁶². Additionally, power outages can interrupt the operations of the blood bank ²⁶³.

Access to care - Power outages reduce the odds of delivering at the hospital versus at home ²⁶⁴ as well as the perception of quality of care in hospitals, leading patients to delay care seeking ²⁶⁵. Floods can cause significant disruptions to transportation infrastructure, including roads and public transport systems, as well as the malfunctioning of lifts and hoists, which hinders access to healthcare services ²⁶⁶. Damage to major hospitals with specialised units affects care provision, requiring patients to travel long distances to receive necessary treatments ²⁶⁷. Power outages hinder the ability to provide essential treatments ²⁶⁸ and the interruption of care delivery due to damaged infrastructure significantly impacts healthcare

²⁶⁰ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

²⁶¹ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

²⁶² Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁶³ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

²⁶⁴ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

²⁶⁵ Casey Ja et al.; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

²⁶⁶ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

²⁶⁷ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁶⁸ Man et al.; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

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services during floods ²⁶⁹. Additionally, elective surgical procedures are often postponed in the aftermath of such events ²⁷⁰.

Quality of care - Power outages during floods compromise the quality and storage of refrigerated medications, necessitating their transfer to maintain efficacy ²⁷¹. The inability to access clinical records due to power failures impedes tracking patients and their results ²⁷². Additionally, power outages and lack of access to potable water compromise hygiene and sanitation practices ²⁷³. Furthermore, staff often have little experience in treating hypothermic patients, affecting patient outcomes during such events ²⁷⁴.

Service utilisation - Floods and storms have been linked to an increase in hospitalizations ²⁷⁵, particularly due to cardiovascular conditions such as acute myocardial infarctions and strokes, respiratory ailments including COPD, and renal diseases arising from missed dialysis sessions ²⁷⁶. An increase in hospital admissions for schizophrenia has also been observed ²⁷⁷. Intensive care unit (ICU) admissions rise due to worsened heart failure ²⁷⁸. Paediatric hospitalisations see a surge during flood events ²⁷⁹. Conversely, there is a decrease in the utilisation of kidney transplant services ²⁸⁰ and oncology visits ²⁸¹.

²⁶⁹ Bayram et al., 'Impact of Global Climate Change on Pulmonary Health'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

²⁷⁰ Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'.

²⁷¹ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁷² Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

²⁷³ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

²⁷⁴ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

²⁷⁵ Nu Quy Linh Tran et al., 'Climate Change and Human Health in Vietnam: A Systematic Review and Additional Analyses on Current Impacts, Future Risk, and Adaptation', *The Lancet Regional Health. Western Pacific* 40 (November 2023): 100943, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.lanwpc.2023.100943>; Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'.

²⁷⁶ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'; Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'; Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'; Ghosh et al., 'Impact of Hurricanes and Associated Extreme Weather Events on Cardiovascular Health'; Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'; Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'; Wu et al., 'Review Article'; Young, Khoshnaw, and Johnson, 'Climate and the Nephrologist'; Young, Khoshnaw, and Johnson.

²⁷⁷ Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'

²⁷⁸ Ghosh et al., 'Impact of Hurricanes and Associated Extreme Weather Events on Cardiovascular Health'.

²⁷⁹ Bekkar et al., 'Pregnancy and Newborn Health - Heat Impacts and Emerging Solutions'; Linh Tran et al., 'Climate Change and Human Health in Vietnam'.

²⁸⁰ Young, Khoshnaw, and Johnson, 'Climate and the Nephrologist'.

²⁸¹ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

Surge capacity - At the surge capacity level, there is a shortage of personnel and staff long-term retention difficulties ²⁸². In situations with many injured individuals, there may be a shortage of analgesics ²⁸³. Other essential medications and equipment experience shortages due to difficulty in transportation, such as electricity-dependent equipment and supplies for patients on ventilation and equipment for vulnerable groups such as cancer patients and paediatric immunosuppressed individuals ²⁸⁴. Structure-related surge capacity issues include relocation of ICU ventilated patients to other wards to leave space for new patients ²⁸⁵.

Resources - Floods can severely disrupt the use of essential respiratory equipment, including nebulizers, oxygen, and bilevel-positive airway pressure machines ²⁸⁶, as well as ventilators ²⁸⁷, compromising care for patients with respiratory conditions. Additionally, healthcare staff may suffer from PTSD²⁸⁸.

Heatwaves and cold spells

Heatwaves and cold spells impact medical and surgical pathways at the levels of infrastructure, access to care, quality of care and service utilisation.

Infrastructure - Extremely high temperatures may impact the functioning of water supply systems and medical equipment ²⁸⁹.

Access to care - Challenges have been reported in reaching hospitals for sparsely populated and very remote communities during heatwaves ²⁹⁰.

Quality of care - During heatwaves, oxytocin storage temperature may exceed the recommended threshold ²⁹¹.

²⁸² Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁸³ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁸⁴ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

²⁸⁵ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

²⁸⁶ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

²⁸⁷ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

²⁸⁸ Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

²⁸⁹ Bainbridge, Wolfe, and Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management'; Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

²⁹⁰ Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'.

²⁹¹ Chersich et al., 'Increasing Global Temperatures Threaten Gains in Maternal and Newborn Health in Africa'.

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Service utilisation - Heatwaves have been associated with an increase in hospitalisations²⁹². This increase is due to conditions such as direct heat illnesses, dehydration, and fluid and electrolyte disorders²⁹³. Cardiovascular diseases—including heat stroke, heat exhaustion, myocardial infarction, heart disease, ischemic heart disease, hypertension, and cardiac dysrhythmias—as well as respiratory and renal diseases like acute kidney injury and kidney

²⁹² Adnan et al., 'Vulnerability of Australia to Heatwaves'; Katherine G. Arbuthnott and Shakoor Hajat, 'The Health Effects of Hotter Summers and Heat Waves in the Population of the United Kingdom: A Review of the Evidence', *Environmental Health* 16, no. 1 (5 December 2017): 119, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12940-017-0322-5>; Yuval Baharav et al., 'The Impact of Extreme Heat Exposure on Pregnant People and Neonates: A State of the Science Review', *Journal of Midwifery & Women's Health* 68, no. 3 (2023): 324–32, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jmwh.13502>; Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'; Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves'; Meghnath Dhimal et al., 'Impact of Climate Change on Health and Well-Being of People in Hindu Kush Himalayan Region: A Narrative Review', *Frontiers in Physiology* 12 (6 August 2021), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fphys.2021.651189>; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Erwin William A. Leyva, Adam Beaman, and Patricia M. Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People: An Integrative Review and Implications for Nursing', *Journal of Nursing Scholarship: An Official Publication of Sigma Theta Tau International Honor Society of Nursing* 49, no. 6 (November 2017): 670–78, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jnu.12346>; Li M et al., 'Heat Waves and Morbidity'; Linh Tran et al., 'Climate Change and Human Health in Vietnam'; Liu et al., 'Heat Exposure and Cardiovascular Health Outcomes'; Mason et al., 'Systematic Review of the Impact of Heatwaves on Health Service Demand in Australia'; Jinyoung Moon, 'The Effect of the Heatwave on the Morbidity and Mortality of Diabetes Patients; a Meta-Analysis for the Era of the Climate Crisis', *Environmental Research* 195 (1 April 2021): 110762, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envres.2021.110762>; Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Strathearn, Osborne, and Selvey, 'Impact of Low-Intensity Heat Events on Mortality and Morbidity in Regions with Hot, Humid Summers'.

²⁹³ Faurie et al., 'Association between High Temperature and Heatwaves with Heat-Related Illnesses'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Leyva, Beaman, and Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People'; Cuiqing Liu, Zubin Yavar, and Qinghua Sun, 'Cardiovascular Response to Thermoregulatory Challenges', *American Journal of Physiology. Heart and Circulatory Physiology* 309, no. 11 (1 December 2015): H1793-1812, <https://doi.org/10.1152/ajpheart.00199.2015>; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Strathearn, Osborne, and Selvey, 'Impact of Low-Intensity Heat Events on Mortality and Morbidity in Regions with Hot, Humid Summers'.

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dysfunction raise hospitalisations during heatwaves²⁹⁴. Hospitalisations for diabetes²⁹⁵, Alzheimer's disease²⁹⁶, non-cholera diarrhea²⁹⁷, and infectious diseases in the elderly over 75 years old²⁹⁸ also increase. Pregnant women face higher risks of antepartum hemorrhage and hypertensive pregnancy complications during heatwaves²⁹⁹. Additionally, there are rises in rheumatic heart disease, endocrine, genitourinary, and skin-related disorders³⁰⁰. Mental health-related hospitalisations increase during heatwaves as well³⁰¹, specifically for

²⁹⁴ Arsad et al., 'The Impact of Heatwaves on Mortality and Morbidity and the Associated Vulnerability Factors'; Bayram et al., 'Impact of Global Climate Change on Pulmonary Health'; Berberian, Gonzalez, and Cushing, 'Racial Disparities in Climate Change-Related Health Effects in the United States'; Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'; Georgia K. Chaseling, Nathan B. Morris, and Nicholas Ravanelli, 'Extreme Heat and Adverse Cardiovascular Outcomes in Australia and New Zealand: What Do We Know?', *Heart, Lung and Circulation* 32, no. 1 (1 January 2023): 43–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.hlc.2022.10.010>; Cheng et al., 'Cardiorespiratory Effects of Heatwaves'; Cicci et al., 'High Temperatures and Cardiovascular-Related Morbidity'; Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'; Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Carina J. Gronlund et al., 'Climate Change and Temperature Extremes: A Review of Heat- and Cold-Related Morbidity and Mortality Concerns of Municipalities', *Maturitas* 114 (1 August 2018): 54–59, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.maturitas.2018.06.002>; Leyva, Beaman, and Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People'; Linares et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on the Public Health of the Mediterranean Basin Population - Current Situation, Projections, Preparedness and Adaptation'; Liu, Yavar, and Sun, 'Cardiovascular Response to Thermoregulatory Challenges'; Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'; Lo et al., 'Heat Impacts on Human Health in the Western Pacific Region'; Nidens et al., 'Klimawandel ganz nah'; Israel Ropo Orimoloye et al., 'Implications of Climate Variability and Change on Urban and Human Health: A Review', *Cities* 91 (1 August 2019): 213–23, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cities.2019.01.009>; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'; Dung Phung et al., 'Ambient Temperature and Risk of Cardiovascular Hospitalization: An Updated Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *The Science of the Total Environment* 550 (15 April 2016): 1084–1102, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2016.01.154>; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'; Wu et al., 'Review Article'; Young, Khoshnaw, and Johnson, 'Climate and the Nephrologist'.

²⁹⁵ Arsad et al., 'The Impact of Heatwaves on Mortality and Morbidity and the Associated Vulnerability Factors'; Donghong Gao et al., 'Association between Extreme Ambient Heat Exposure and Diabetes-Related Hospital Admissions and Emergency Department Visits: A Systematic Review', *Hygiene and Environmental Health Advances* 4 (December 2022): 100031, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.heha.2022.100031>; Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes'.

²⁹⁶ Anthony R. White, 'The Firestorm within: A Narrative Review of Extreme Heat and Wildfire Smoke Effects on Brain Health', *Science of The Total Environment* 922 (20 April 2024): 171239, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2024.171239>.

²⁹⁷ Orimoloye et al., 'Implications of Climate Variability and Change on Urban and Human Health'.

²⁹⁸ Leyva, Beaman, and Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People'.

²⁹⁹ Baharav et al., 'The Impact of Extreme Heat Exposure on Pregnant People and Neonates'; Wu et al., 'Review Article'.

³⁰⁰ Arsad et al., 'The Impact of Heatwaves on Mortality and Morbidity and the Associated Vulnerability Factors'; Strathearn, Osborne, and Selvey, 'Impact of Low-Intensity Heat Events on Mortality and Morbidity in Regions with Hot, Humid Summers'.

³⁰¹ Cianconi, Betrò, and Janiri, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Mental Health'; Conti et al., 'Knowledge Gaps and Research Priorities on the Health Effects of Heatwaves'; Kam S, Hwang Bj, and Parker Er, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Atopic Dermatitis and Mental Health Comorbidities: A Review of the Literature and Examination of Intersectionality', *International Journal of Dermatology* 62, no. 4 (April 2023),

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conditions such as organic disorders, substance misuse, schizophrenia, psychoses, mood disorders, neurotic disorders, disorders of psychological development, disorders with onset in childhood or adolescence, suicide, dementia, and other somatoform disorders ³⁰². Longer and more intense heatwaves (seven days or more) increase the risk of hospital admissions for mental health disorders more than shorter heatwaves of one to three days ³⁰³. Moreover, heatwaves are associated with longer lengths of hospital stay ³⁰⁴. Pediatric hospitalizations also rise during heatwaves due to respiratory and renal diseases ³⁰⁵, increased neonatal intensive care unit admissions ³⁰⁶, and cases of acute bronchiolitis in children under two years old ³⁰⁷. Conversely, another review points to a decrease in hospitalisations for heart failure during heatwaves ³⁰⁸. During cold spells, hospitalisations increase as well ³⁰⁹, particularly due to dementia ³¹⁰, cardiovascular conditions like myocardial infarction, heart disease, hypertension, cerebrovascular disease, ischemic heart diseases, and stroke ³¹¹. There is also an uptick in fall-related injuries on days with snow and ice ³¹², and hospitalisations for diabetes increase during these periods ³¹³.

Wildfires

<https://doi.org/10.1111/ijd.16557>; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Thompson R et al., 'Associations between High Ambient Temperatures and Heat Waves with Mental Health Outcomes: A Systematic Review', *Public Health* 161 (August 2018),

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.puhe.2018.06.008>; White, 'The Firestorm Within'; Wu et al., 'Review Article'.

³⁰² Fiona Charlson et al., 'Climate Change and Mental Health: A Scoping Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 18, no. 9 (January 2021): 4486,

<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18094486>; Kam S, Hwang Bj, and Parker Er, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Atopic Dermatitis and Mental Health Comorbidities'; Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'; Strathearn, Osborne, and Selvey, 'Impact of Low-Intensity Heat Events on Mortality and Morbidity in Regions with Hot, Humid Summers'; Thompson R et al., 'Associations between High Ambient Temperatures and Heat Waves with Mental Health Outcomes'; White, 'The Firestorm Within'.

³⁰³ Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

³⁰⁴ Adnan et al., 'Vulnerability of Australia to Heatwaves'.

³⁰⁵ Weeda et al., 'How Climate Change Degrades Child Health'; Xu et al., 'The Impact of Heat Waves on Children's Health'.

³⁰⁶ Baharav et al., 'The Impact of Extreme Heat Exposure on Pregnant People and Neonates'.

³⁰⁷ Lo et al., 'Heat Impacts on Human Health in the Western Pacific Region'.

³⁰⁸ Harvey G, Bain-Donohue S, and Dewi Sp, 'The Impact of Extreme Heat on Older Regional and Rural Australians'.

³⁰⁹ Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes'.

³¹⁰ Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'; Thompson R et al., 'Associations between High Ambient Temperatures and Heat Waves with Mental Health Outcomes'.

³¹¹ Leyva, Beaman, and Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People'; Liu, Yavar, and Sun, 'Cardiovascular Response to Thermoregulatory Challenges'; Louis et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change and Air Pollution on Neurologic Health, Disease, and Practice'.

³¹² Gronlund et al., 'Climate Change and Temperature Extremes'.

³¹³ Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes'.

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Wildfires impact medical and surgical pathways at the levels of infrastructure, access to care, service utilisation, surge capacity and resources.

Infrastructure - Evidence shows that there may be the closure of hospital wards because of fire and smoke compromising hospital safety ³¹⁴.

Access to care - One review reports of general access to care barriers when it comes to wildfires ³¹⁵.

Service utilisation - Wildfires have been linked to an increase in hospitalizations, largely due to elevated PM concentrations in the air ³¹⁶. Respiratory conditions see a significant rise, including asthma ³¹⁷ and other ailments like COPD, bronchitis, bronchiolitis, pneumonia, and general pulmonary complaints ³¹⁸. Hospitalizations for cardiovascular diseases—including congestive heart failure, ischemic heart disease, acute myocardial infarction, cerebrovascular diseases, hypertension, and stroke—also increase during wildfire events ³¹⁹. Elderly patients previously hospitalized for cardiorespiratory conditions and COPD experience higher rates of rehospitalization in the follow-up period after wildfires ³²⁰. ICU admissions for cardiovascular diseases see an uptick as well ³²¹. Pediatric hospitalizations rise due to

³¹⁴ Barten et al., 'When Disasters Strike the Emergency Department'.

³¹⁵ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

³¹⁶ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'; Skinner et al., 'A Literature Review on the Impact of Wildfires on Emergency Departments'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'; Yiwen Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis', *Current Environmental Health Reports* 11, no. 1 (March 2024): 46–60, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40572-023-00420-9>.

³¹⁷ Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'; Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'; Cascio, 'Wildland Fire Smoke and Human Health'; Jiao et al., 'Associations between Short-Term Exposure to Wildfire Particulate Matter and Respiratory Outcomes'; Kelly et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Asthma and Allergic-Immunologic Disease'; Skinner et al., 'A Literature Review on the Impact of Wildfires on Emergency Departments'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

³¹⁸ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'; Black et al., 'Wildfire Smoke Exposure and Human Health'; Burhan and Mukminin, 'A Systematic Review of Respiratory Infection Due to Air Pollution during Natural Disasters'; Gould et al., 'Health Effects of Wildfire Smoke Exposure'; Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'.

³¹⁹ Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'; Cascio, 'Wildland Fire Smoke and Human Health'; Naserinejad et al., 'Wildland Fire, Air Pollution and Cardiovascular Health'; Skinner et al., 'A Literature Review on the Impact of Wildfires on Emergency Departments'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

³²⁰ Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

³²¹ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

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respiratory conditions ³²² and dermatitis in children under 15 years old ³²³. Interestingly, some studies report a decrease in hospitalisations for individuals with COPD and congestive heart failure during wildfire periods ³²⁴. Moreover, wildfires are associated with an increase in hospitalisations for mood disorders ³²⁵ and asthma exacerbations ³²⁶. An increase in hospitalisations for diabetes has also been observed ³²⁷.

Surge capacity - Regarding the Structure component of surge capacity, wildfires may cause the exceeding of hospital's ICU capacity ³²⁸.

Resources - In general, wildfires challenge the access to medications, medical supplies or equipment in hospital settings³²⁹.

General EWEs

Infrastructure - EWEs can cause significant damage to hospital buildings, leading to cascading failures in critical systems such as electricity, water, and sewage services ³³⁰. This infrastructural damage severely impacts healthcare delivery, especially in specialised units ³³¹.

Access to care - The ability to reach healthcare facilities is compromised due to disrupted roads and damaged health infrastructure ³³². Furthermore, the delivery of health services is slowed down, affecting the overall capacity to engage with and treat patients ³³³. These challenges lead to significant interruptions in access to life-saving treatments, such as cancer care, exacerbating health outcomes during and after EWEs ³³⁴.

Quality of care - EWEs significantly compromise the overall quality of care in health facilities ³³⁵. Power outages and lack of access to potable water further deteriorate hygiene and

³²² Henry et al., 'Assessing the Risk of Respiratory-Related Healthcare Visits Associated with Wildfire Smoke Exposure in Children 0-18 Years Old'.

³²³ Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents'.

³²⁴ Bell, Horowitz, and Iwashyna, 'Health Outcomes After Disaster for Older Adults With Chronic Disease'.

³²⁵ Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

³²⁶ Makrufardi et al., 'Extreme Weather and Asthma'.

³²⁷ Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes'.

³²⁸ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

³²⁹ Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'.

³³⁰ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

³³¹ Chang et al., 'Aging Hearts in a Hotter, More Turbulent World'; Ana Patricia Ortiz et al., 'Protecting Caribbean Patients Diagnosed with Cancer from Compounding Disasters', *The Lancet. Oncology* 25, no. 5 (May 2024): e217–24, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045\(24\)00071-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1470-2045(24)00071-8).

³³² Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

³³³ Bell et al.

³³⁴ Ortiz et al., 'Protecting Caribbean Patients Diagnosed with Cancer from Compounding Disasters'.

³³⁵ Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'.

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sanitation standards, creating additional risks for both patients and healthcare providers ³³⁶. These disruptions severely affect service delivery and patient outcomes during such events ³³⁷.

Service utilisation - EWEs are associated with an increase in hospitalizations for mood disorders ³³⁸ and asthma ³³⁹.

Surge capacity - At the System level, displaced people overburden the health system of host communities ³⁴⁰.

Resources - EWEs create unsafe working conditions for human resources ³⁴¹. Health workers also experience high levels of stress and burnout during these events ³⁴². Additionally, staff absenteeism tends to increase ³⁴³.

³³⁶ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

³³⁷ Zurynski Y et al.

³³⁸ Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

³³⁹ Makrufardi et al., 'Extreme Weather and Asthma'.

³⁴⁰ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

³⁴¹ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

³⁴² Zurynski Y et al.

³⁴³ Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

Figure 4. Visual representation of the main impacts on Hospital Medical and Surgical Pathway

3.4. Hospital system – Outpatient care pathway and Day Hospital

Floods and storms

The outpatient care pathway and Day Hospital are impacted at several levels, including infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, surge capacity and resources.

Infrastructure - Floods and storms cause significant damage to dialysis units and mental health facilities, disrupting essential healthcare services³⁴⁴. Water and power outages further exacerbate these challenges, impacting the functionality of medical equipment and continuity of care³⁴⁵. Critical infrastructure—including natural gas pipelines, temperature control systems, sewage disposal, essential storage, life support systems, and communication technologies—is vulnerable to disruption, especially when located in flood-prone basements³⁴⁶. The loss of medical records, drug protocols, and research documents hampers clinical operations and research activities³⁴⁷. Additionally, power outages can interrupt vital services like radiology operations³⁴⁸.

Access to care - Power outages decrease patients' perception of the quality of care, leading them to delay seeking treatment³⁴⁹. Moreover, patients experience difficulties in reaching the facilities due to road disruptions, lack of public transportation and potential haywire of lifts and hoists³⁵⁰. Hospitals experienced shortages of rehabilitation services and

³⁴⁴ Barten et al., 'When Disasters Strike the Emergency Department'; Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

³⁴⁵ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

³⁴⁶ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Ha, 'The Changing Climate and Pregnancy Health'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

³⁴⁷ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁴⁸ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

³⁴⁹ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

³⁵⁰ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related

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radiotherapy³⁵¹ and patients may experience interruptions in care delivery at the outpatient level due to infrastructural damage³⁵².

Quality of care - Power outages during floods and storms significantly affect healthcare services. Refrigerated medications may become compromised in quality and storage, requiring immediate transfer to maintain their efficacy³⁵³. Additionally, power outages and lack of access to potable water compromise hygiene and sanitation practices, posing health risks³⁵⁴. The inability to access clinical records due to power failures impedes tracking patients and their test results³⁵⁵. Furthermore, dialysis sessions are often shortened from four hours to three hours, impacting patient care³⁵⁶.

Service utilisation - Floods lead to an increase in outpatient visits due to injuries such as lacerations, corneal abrasions, open and infected wounds, puncture wounds, and injuries from bites and stings³⁵⁷. There is also a rise in outpatient visits for infectious diseases, including gastrointestinal illnesses, leptospirosis, skin or soft tissue infections, diarrhoea, intestinal infections, impetigo, conjunctivitis, cellulitis, and unspecified febrile illnesses³⁵⁸. Cardiovascular complaints see an uptick as well³⁵⁹. Mental healthcare outpatient consultations increase following such events³⁶⁰. During floods, dialysis sessions often decrease, especially among those evacuated³⁶¹, followed by a peak in dialysis visits during the first week after the event³⁶².

Surge capacity - Evidence suggests that floods and storms impact all aspects of surge capacity in the outpatient pathway and Day Hospital. Health needs often exceed the

Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'; Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

³⁵¹ Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁵² Bayram et al., 'Impact of Global Climate Change on Pulmonary Health'; Ghazali et al., 'Climate Change Impacts on Disaster and Emergency Medicine Focusing on Mitigation Disruptive Effects'; Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'; Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

³⁵³ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁵⁴ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

³⁵⁵ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁵⁶ Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'.

³⁵⁷ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

³⁵⁸ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb.

³⁵⁹ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb.

³⁶⁰ Lisa Woodland et al., 'Investigating the Health Impacts of Climate Change among People with Pre-Existing Mental Health Problems: A Scoping Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 20, no. 8 (18 April 2023): 5563, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph20085563>.

³⁶¹ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Young, Khoshnaw, and Johnson, 'Climate and the Nephrologist'.

³⁶² Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'.

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available staff capacities, especially technicians and nurses for services like radiotherapy³⁶³ and dialysis³⁶⁴. This is compounded by a general difficulty in retaining the staff³⁶⁵. Regarding the Staff, outpatient services and Day Hospital experience shortages of analgesics when there are many injured individuals³⁶⁶. Insufficient supplies, difficulties in transporting them to affected areas, and challenges in accessing medications and equipment further complicate the situation³⁶⁷. Regarding Structure, the influx of patients can overwhelm ambulatory capacities³⁶⁸, and the lack of operating dialysis centres leads to the relocation of dialysis patients³⁶⁹. At the System level, an influx of AKI (Acute Kidney Injury) patients overwhelms the maintenance dialysis capacity³⁷⁰.

Resources - Floods and storms also impact physical and human resources. Floods can interrupt the use of essential medical equipment such as nebulisers, oxygen, bilevel-positive airway pressure machines³⁷¹, as well as ventilators³⁷². Delivery problems of disposable dialysis items and damage to dialysis hardware further hinder patient care³⁷³. Additionally, staff may suffer from PTSD following such events³⁷⁴.

³⁶³ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁶⁴ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁶⁵ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁶⁶ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

³⁶⁷ Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

³⁶⁸ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

³⁶⁹ Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'.

³⁷⁰ Lameire et al.

³⁷¹ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

³⁷² Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

³⁷³ Lameire et al., 'Role of the International and National Renal Organizations in Natural Disasters'.

³⁷⁴ Veenema et al., 'Climate Change-Related Water Disasters' Impact on Population Health'.

Heatwaves and cold spells

Heatwaves and cold spells impact the outpatient care pathway and Day Hospital at the levels of infrastructure, access to care, quality of care and service utilisation.

Infrastructure - When it comes to infrastructure, extremely high temperatures impact the functioning of water supply systems and medical equipment ³⁷⁵.

Access to care - Heatwaves hinder the ability to reach, by challenging remote communities and sparsely populated areas in reaching hospitals ³⁷⁶.

Service utilisation - Evidence shows an increase in outpatient visits during heatwaves, due to kidney diseases ³⁷⁷ and pneumonia ³⁷⁸.

Wildfires

The outpatient care and Day Hospital pathways are impacted by wildfires at the levels of infrastructure, access to care, service utilisation and surge capacity.

Infrastructure - At the infrastructural level, wildfires may cause hospitals to close due to fire or smoke ³⁷⁹.

Access to care - Wildfires are reportedly causing challenges in accessing care ³⁸⁰.

Service utilisation - Outpatient visits increase for conditions that are related to smoke and PM concentrations ³⁸¹. Furthermore, accesses for dermatological conditions increase, including those for atopic dermatitis ³⁸², psoriasis ³⁸³ and itch ³⁸⁴. Also, complaints related to cardiovascular conditions ³⁸⁵ and mental healthcare ³⁸⁶ experienced a surge. Paediatric

³⁷⁵ Bainbridge, Wolfe, and Hartley, 'Complications with Hot, Cold and Altitude Environments in Disaster Management'; Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

³⁷⁶ Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'.

³⁷⁷ Liu J et al., 'Is There an Association between Hot Weather and Poor Mental Health Outcomes?'

³⁷⁸ Makrufardi et al., 'Extreme Weather and Asthma'.

³⁷⁹ Barten et al., 'When Disasters Strike the Emergency Department'.

³⁸⁰ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

³⁸¹ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Jiao et al., 'Associations between Short-Term Exposure to Wildfire Particulate Matter and Respiratory Outcomes'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

³⁸² Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents'.

³⁸³ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

³⁸⁴ Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents'.

³⁸⁵ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

³⁸⁶ Woodland et al., 'Investigating the Health Impacts of Climate Change among People with Pre-Existing Mental Health Problems'.

patients at the outpatient level experience respiratory problems (incl. bronchiolitis)³⁸⁷, pruritus³⁸⁸ and conjunctivitis (in those aged <15)³⁸⁹.

Surge capacity - The surge capacity is impacted at the Stuff level because of insufficient supplies and general challenges in accessing medication and equipment, also due to limitations in transport³⁹⁰. At the Structure level, patients overwhelm the capacity of ambulatories³⁹¹.

General EWEs

The outpatient care and Day Hospital pathways are impacted by general EWEs at the levels of infrastructure, access to care, quality of care, service utilisation, surge capacity and resources.

Infrastructure - The infrastructures experience multiple effects of the EWEs, with damage to buildings, and failure of water and electricity supply, and sewage systems³⁹².

Access to care - EWEs disrupt roads and infrastructures, thus limiting the ability to reach the facilities. Also, the delivery of services is slowed down, thus limiting the ability to engage with services³⁹³.

Quality of care - Quality of care is overall compromised³⁹⁴, including because of reduced hygiene and sanitation and system's breakdown³⁹⁵.

Service utilisation - Evidence shows an increase in health services utilisation and demand after EWEs³⁹⁶ for major depressive disorder, neurotic disorder, PTSD, insomnia³⁹⁷ and asthma³⁹⁸.

³⁸⁷ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Henry et al., 'Assessing the Risk of Respiratory-Related Healthcare Visits Associated with Wildfire Smoke Exposure in Children 0-18 Years Old'.

³⁸⁸ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

³⁸⁹ Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents'.

³⁹⁰ Lindsay S et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change Related Extreme Weather Events on People with Pre-Existing Disabilities and Chronic Conditions'; Yates et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on Surgical Care'.

³⁹¹ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

³⁹² Bell et al.; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

³⁹³ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

³⁹⁴ Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'.

³⁹⁵ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

³⁹⁶ Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'.

³⁹⁷ Corvetto et al., 'A Systematic Literature Review of the Impact of Climate Change on the Global Demand for Psychiatric Services'.

³⁹⁸ Makrufardi et al., 'Extreme Weather and Asthma'.

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Surge capacity - Overall, it has been shown that the presence of displaced people overburden the health system of the host country ³⁹⁹.

Resources - Human resources are at risk due to unsafe health conditions from compromised working environments ⁴⁰⁰. Human resources also experience stress and burnout ⁴⁰¹, and can be affected by absenteeism ⁴⁰².

³⁹⁹ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

⁴⁰⁰ Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

⁴⁰¹ Zurynski Y et al.

⁴⁰² Paavola, 'Health Impacts of Climate Change and Health and Social Inequalities in the UK'; Zurynski Y et al., 'Bolstering Health Systems to Cope with the Impacts of Climate Change Events'.

Figure 5. Visual representation of the main impacts on Outpatient Care Pathway and Day Hospital

3.5. Primary care and elderly care system

Floods and storms

All aspects of primary care and elderly care systems are reportedly affected by floods and storms.

Infrastructure - Among the impacts on primary care and elderly care infrastructures caused by floods and storms are: damage to primary care facilities⁴⁰³, failure of medical equipment and damage to generators, if located in flood-vulnerable places⁴⁰⁴.

Access to care - The ability to reach primary care was found to be negatively affected by a lack of transportation or bad infrastructure⁴⁰⁵, leading to a disruption of access to primary care facilities and social services, particularly for those with limited mobility⁴⁰⁶, and to the interruption of home nursing for elderly patients⁴⁰⁷. The impact on carers (e.g., need to move away from the flood-impacted areas), was another cause for the disruption of access to care for people with disabilities⁴⁰⁸. The ability to engage with primary care services and elderly care services is impacted in case of power outages, as the elderly lack access to communication technologies and means of transportation⁴⁰⁹ and those in long-term care facilities lack access to power for their electronic devices⁴¹⁰.

Quality of care - Overall, the increased needs after the event make post-flood and post-storm care at the primary care level inadequate⁴¹¹. Understaffing and lack of specific skills lead to a suboptimal level of healthcare provision during disasters⁴¹². In the case of Vietnam, the primary care system in rural areas could not provide effective care - especially at the provincial and territorial level - in response to storm and flood-related health issues, mainly due to health workers' inadequate knowledge of climate change impacts on health⁴¹³. Another issue negatively impacting the quality of primary care and elderly care is the disruption of medical records and consequent inadequate knowledge of patients'

⁴⁰³ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

⁴⁰⁴ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

⁴⁰⁵ Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'.

⁴⁰⁶ Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia'.

⁴⁰⁷ Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'.

⁴⁰⁸ Lee et al., 'Impacts of Climate Change on Health and Health Services in Northern New South Wales, Australia'.

⁴⁰⁹ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

⁴¹⁰ Lane K et al.

⁴¹¹ Linh Tran et al., 'Climate Change and Human Health in Vietnam'.

⁴¹² Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'.

⁴¹³ Naser, Haq, and Naughton.

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medications (e.g., name, dosage) ⁴¹⁴. Another aspect related to medication is the hardship in maintaining medication regimes for evacuated elderly ⁴¹⁵. Considering that 48.4% of those who are taken to shelter lack medication - because they either left them at home or soon ran out - this treatment interruption can lead to an increase in uncontrolled hypertension cases ⁴¹⁶.

Service utilisation - Several reviews reported impacts caused by floods and storms on primary care and elderly care service utilisation ⁴¹⁷. Evidence has been found on increased primary care visits up to 12 months after the flood/storm ⁴¹⁸, the main reasons being vaccinations and routine care ⁴¹⁹, prescription refills ⁴²⁰, cardiovascular diseases ⁴²¹ and patients in shelters experiencing chest pain ⁴²². Evidence also shows that the temporary reduction in access to primary care leads to a decrease in the number of patients referring to primary care after the reopening of the centres ⁴²³.

Surge capacity - The evidence related to the impact of floods and storms on primary care and elderly care capacities was only related to understaffing and insufficient emergency provisions ⁴²⁴, the need for the distribution of blankets ⁴²⁵ and the need for an increased provision of PTSD care for the elderly after floods, which entails a greater need of personnel, equipment and supplies, spaces, and coordination mechanisms ⁴²⁶.

Resources - One review ⁴²⁷ highlighted how floods and storms impact primary care and elderly care resources such as supportive tools (wheelchairs, hearing aids, canes, walkers,

⁴¹⁴ Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss'.

⁴¹⁵ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

⁴¹⁶ Javad Babaie et al., 'Cardiovascular Diseases in Natural Disasters; a Systematic Review', *Archives of Academic Emergency Medicine* 9, no. 1 (2021): e36, <https://doi.org/10.22037/aaem.v9i1.1208>.

⁴¹⁷ Babaie et al.; Cruz J et al., 'Effect of Extreme Weather Events on Mental Health: A Narrative Synthesis and Meta-Analysis for the UK', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 17, no. 22 (19 November 2020), <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph17228581>; Ghosh et al., 'Impact of Hurricanes and Associated Extreme Weather Events on Cardiovascular Health'; Klinger, Landeg, and Murray, 'Power Outages, Extreme Events and Health'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'; Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

⁴¹⁸ Cruz J et al., 'Effect of Extreme Weather Events on Mental Health'.

⁴¹⁹ Saulnier, Brolin Ribacke, and von Schreeb, 'No Calm After the Storm'.

⁴²⁰ Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴²¹ Ghosh et al., 'Impact of Hurricanes and Associated Extreme Weather Events on Cardiovascular Health'.

⁴²² Babaie et al., 'Cardiovascular Diseases in Natural Disasters; a Systematic Review'.

⁴²³ Babaie et al.

⁴²⁴ Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

⁴²⁵ Oshiro et al., 'Prevention of Hypothermia in the Aftermath of Natural Disasters in Areas at Risk of Avalanches, Earthquakes, Tsunamis and Floods'.

⁴²⁶ Leyva, Beaman, and Davidson, 'Health Impact of Climate Change in Older People'.

⁴²⁷ Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss'.

dentures, glasses, extra batteries for wheelchairs and other assistive devices, and incontinence briefs), which are lost during evacuation.

Heatwaves and cold spells

Evidence related to heatwaves' and cold spells' impacts on primary care and elderly care was only found concerning access to care and service utilisation.

Access to care - One review reported that snow and ice disrupt transportation systems, and hinder homecare and community care services, thus impacting the quality of care during cold spells ⁴²⁸.

Service utilisation - Heatwaves were found to increase primary care services usage ⁴²⁹ and demand ⁴³⁰; a meta-analysis ⁴³¹ found an increase in general practitioner consultations during heatwaves with an RR of 1.38 (1.31–1.46) for diabetics consultations ⁴³². Yet, a decrease in primary care visits for myocardial infarction was also found ⁴³³. An increase in primary care visits during cold spells was found for respiratory conditions ⁴³⁴.

Wildfires

Evidence related to wildfires' impact on primary care and elderly care was only found concerning access to care and service utilisation.

Access to care - Access to primary care facilities was found to be disrupted during wildfires ⁴³⁵ and continuity of care was found to be a major concern during natural disasters, especially for patients with chronic diseases, such as diabetes ⁴³⁶.

Service utilisation - The impacts of wildfires on primary care service utilisation were found in several of the analysed reviews ⁴³⁷. Increased respiratory physician visits were found to

⁴²⁸ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

⁴²⁹ Wu et al., 'Review Article'.

⁴³⁰ Bhatta et al., 'Examining the Heat Health Burden in Australia'.

⁴³¹ Moon, 'The Effect of the Heatwave on the Morbidity and Mortality of Diabetes Patients; a Meta-Analysis for the Era of the Climate Crisis'.

⁴³² Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

⁴³³ Arbuthnott and Hajat, 'The Health Effects of Hotter Summers and Heat Waves in the Population of the United Kingdom'.

⁴³⁴ Curtis et al., 'Impact of Extreme Weather Events and Climate Change for Health and Social Care Systems'.

⁴³⁵ Hadley et al., 'Protecting Cardiovascular Health From Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴³⁶ Ospelt et al., 'The Impact of Climate Change on People Living with Diabetes'.

⁴³⁷ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'; Black et al., 'Wildfire Smoke Exposure and Human Health'; Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'; Naserinejad et al., 'Wildland Fire, Air Pollution and Cardiovascular Health'; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate

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be positively associated (OR = 1.05, 95% CI: 1.03–1.06) with a 30 µg/m³ increase in total PM₁₀ based on TEOM (Tampered Element Oscillating Microbalance) ⁴³⁸. Evidence also shows that a 30 µg/m³ increase in total PM₁₀ based on TEOM was positively associated with asthma-related physician visits (OR = 1.16, 95% CI: 1.09– 1.23) ⁴³⁹. A statistically significant association was found between LFS PM and asthma-related physician visits (RRs for all ages and all sexes showed a positive association and ranged from 1.01 (95% CI, 1.01–1.02) to 1.11 (95% CI, 1.06–1.15)) ⁴⁴⁰. A meta-analysis reports that significant estimates were observed for incidence rate ratios for asthma physician visits per 10 µg/m³ rise in PM_{2.5} (6% increase; 2003–2010) ⁴⁴¹. A significant increase in the probability of physician visits was also found in visits for otitis media, for each 1hr exposure to 10µg/m³ elevation in PM_{2.5} ⁴⁴², and in visits for pulmonary symptoms ⁴⁴³. An increase in visits for elderly patients (> 65) was found for congestive heart failure and ischemic heart disease ⁴⁴⁴.

Surge capacity - It was reported that, when populations are displaced in the aftermath of wildfires, they place a significant strain on the whole health system in the host country ⁴⁴⁵.

Box 4. Primary care and elderly care systems: considerations for mountain areas

EWEs exert a significant impact on primary care systems and elderly care in mountain areas. Given their geographical characteristics, these regions frequently establish effective community-based healthcare systems designed to provide home-based care services to the population. Due to the higher average age of residents in mountain areas ⁴⁴⁶, these regions

Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'; Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'; Zhang et al., 'Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke on Children and Adolescents'.

⁴³⁸ Adetona et al., 'Review of the Health Effects of Wildland Fire Smoke on Wildland Firefighters and the Public'; Black et al., 'Wildfire Smoke Exposure and Human Health'; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴³⁹ Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'; Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴⁴⁰ Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'.

⁴⁴¹ Barros, Oliveira, and Morais, 'Continent-Based Systematic Review of the Short-Term Health Impacts of Wildfire Emissions'.

⁴⁴² Barros, Oliveira, and Morais.

⁴⁴³ Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'.

⁴⁴⁴ Naserinejad et al., 'Wildland Fire, Air Pollution and Cardiovascular Health'.

⁴⁴⁵ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

⁴⁴⁶ 'L'indice di vecchiaia è più alto nelle aree montane e interne', Openpolis, 23 December 2022, <https://www.openpolis.it/numeri/lindice-di-vecchiaia-e-piu-alto-nelle-aree-montane-e-interne/>.

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also exhibit a greater concentration of nursing homes, which may encounter specific challenges during EWEs.

The elderly population in rural areas is typically located at considerable distances from major urban centres and well-equipped hospitals, often relying on community clinics that are limited in staff and operate only during daytime hours. During EWEs, many older and vulnerable individuals may become isolated, complicating efforts to reach and evacuate them.

Experts recommend considering the use of telemedicine in response to demographic changes and the growing demand for mobile nursing and care services for the elderly. Key prerequisites for successful implementation include patient awareness, a robust communication infrastructure (such as broadband and fibre internet), and close collaboration between the telecommunications and healthcare sectors.

Figure 6. Visual representation of the main impacts on Primary Care and Elderly Care System

3.6. Pharmacies

Floods and storms

All aspects related to pharmacies are reportedly affected by floods and storms.

Infrastructure - Structural damage and power outages are among the impacts found on pharmacies' infrastructure caused by floods and storms - especially for those in low-income areas ⁴⁴⁷. As highlighted by a review⁴⁴⁸, after Hurricane Sandy, 74% of the pharmacies suffered from structural damage, 71% were able to reopen within one month and, after the storm, some had to replace medications, others had to replace equipment or renovate their stores completely.

Access to care - The ability to seek pharmacy services was found to be negatively affected by the inability to contact prescribers and insurance challenges. A review reports evidence about the aftermath of Hurricane Maria in Puerto Rico, where the majority (77%) of patients of community pharmacies reported problems related to their medications and 48% reported having trouble either contacting or reaching their pharmacy ⁴⁴⁹. The ability to reach pharmacy services was found to be negatively affected by damages and closures ⁴⁵⁰. Further, floods and storms negatively impact access to medication, leading to interruption of therapy ⁴⁵¹. A review ⁴⁵² reports that 10% of a cluster sample of 210 people had problems obtaining medication one week following Hurricane Ivan; after Hurricane Wilma, 4% of 150 households surveyed reported that a household member had been unable to obtain the needed medical care; treatment disruption was found for patients with musculoskeletal conditions (3.0%) and those with oncological conditions (15.3%); within 48 hours from the New York blackout, the Montefiore Medical Center's ED reported that 56 out of 65 visits were related to respiratory device failure and that medication-related problems were due to people unable to find or reach medications or were unable to obtain tests needed to adjust medications such as warfarin.

⁴⁴⁷ Ahmer Raza M et al., 'Role of Pharmacist in Disaster Management: A Quantitative Content Analysis Approach', *Innovations in Pharmacy* 12, no. 4 (22 September 2021), <https://doi.org/10.24926/iip.v12i4.4359>; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴⁴⁸ Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴⁴⁹ Sahota et al.

⁴⁵⁰ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴⁵¹ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'; Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss'.

⁴⁵² Ochi et al., 'Disaster-Driven Evacuation and Medication Loss'.

Service utilisation - Several reviews reported impacts caused by floods on pharmacy service utilisation ⁴⁵³. Evidence has been found on a decrease in e-prescribing and medication dispensation - even though return to normal volumes in the days immediately after the event was reported. This is the case for pharmacies in Texas and Florida, after Hurricanes Harvey and Irma, but is not the case for those in Puerto Rico, where pharmacies recovered their routine operations only after an extended time after Hurricane Maira's impact ⁴⁵⁴. Conversely, other reviews report increased demand for medication prescriptions during the event, especially from people with cardiovascular diseases ⁴⁵⁵. Furthermore, an increased dispensation was found for antidiarrheal medication ⁴⁵⁶, electrolyte sales ⁴⁵⁷, pulmonary reliever medication ⁴⁵⁸ and oral steroids⁴⁵⁹.

Surge capacity - The evidence related to the impact of floods on pharmacies' capacities was related to the need for task-shifting (Staff), and the lack of medical supplies (Stuff) (e.g., oxygen tanks, vaccines) ⁴⁶⁰. Evidence has been found on pharmacists performing non-traditional roles beyond their traditional scope of practice (eg., health needs assessments in shelters, triaging patients to healthcare services, treating minor injuries with over-the-counter products, serving as a contact for medication-related issues, toxicology consultations, and taking the role of poison specialists) ⁴⁶¹. Another result of the impact of floods on pharmacies' capacities is the need for implementing agile coordination mechanisms and procedures (System). A review ⁴⁶² highlighted that in the aftermath of natural disasters, pharmacies received the allowance to dispense up to 30 days of medication supply without prescription.

Heatwaves and cold spells

Evidence related to heatwaves' and cold spells' impacts on pharmacies was only found concerning access to care and service utilisation.

⁴⁵³ Ahmer Raza M et al., 'Role of Pharmacist in Disaster Management'; Babaie et al., 'Cardiovascular Diseases in Natural Disasters; a Systematic Review'; Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Casey Ja et al.; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'; Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'.

⁴⁵⁴ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴⁵⁵ Babaie et al., 'Cardiovascular Diseases in Natural Disasters; a Systematic Review'.

⁴⁵⁶ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

⁴⁵⁷ Casey Ja et al.

⁴⁵⁸ Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'.

⁴⁵⁹ Stawovy and Balakrishnan.

⁴⁶⁰ Ahmer Raza M et al., 'Role of Pharmacist in Disaster Management'; Lane K et al., 'Health Effects of Coastal Storms and Flooding in Urban Areas'.

⁴⁶¹ Ahmer Raza M et al., 'Role of Pharmacist in Disaster Management'.

⁴⁶² Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

Access to care - The ability to reach pharmacy services was found to be negatively affected by snowstorms, as reported to be happening in the Washington area, where pharmacists had to use snowmobile teams to deliver medication to homebound residents during cold spells ⁴⁶³.

Service utilisation - One review reported impacts caused by heatwaves on pharmacy service utilisation ⁴⁶⁴, and, in particular, an increased dispensation of psychotropic drugs, including antidepressants, antipsychotics, anxiolytics, tricyclics, mood stabilisers, drugs for addiction and diuretics.

Wildfires

Evidence related to wildfires' impact on pharmacies was only found concerning access to care, service utilisation and surge capacity.

Access to care - One review ⁴⁶⁵ reports the results of a study carried out in California, where wildfires were found to be associated with disrupted access to prescription of opioids for patients receiving long-term medications ⁴⁶⁶.

Service utilisation - Several reviews reported impacts caused by wildfires on pharmacy service utilisation ⁴⁶⁷. Evidence has been found of increased consumption of drugs for obstructive airway diseases in the months following the wildfire for pensioners ⁴⁶⁸. In particular, a study in Spain found that the daily doses increased by 17.69 doses per 1000 inhabitants per day (95%CI: 0.86–34.51) for male pensioners (10.29% increase) in comparison to the same population in unaffected municipalities; for the female pensioners of the affected municipality, the increase was 12.9% of daily doses per 1000 inhabitants per day ⁴⁶⁹. An increase was also observed in the dispensation of respiratory medications ⁴⁷⁰ -

⁴⁶³ Ahmer Raza M et al., 'Role of Pharmacist in Disaster Management'.

⁴⁶⁴ Wu et al., 'Review Article'.

⁴⁶⁵ Sahota et al., 'Pharmacy Deserts and Pharmacies' Roles Post-Extreme Weather and Climate Events in the United States'.

⁴⁶⁶ Iraklis E. Tseregounis et al., 'The Impact of California Wildfires on Patient Access to Prescription Opioids', *Journal of the American Pharmacists Association* 62, no. 6 (1 November 2022): 1769–77, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.japh.2022.05.012>.

⁴⁶⁷ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'; Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'; Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'; Jiao et al., 'Associations between Short-Term Exposure to Wildfire Particulate Matter and Respiratory Outcomes'; Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'; Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'; Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴⁶⁸ Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴⁶⁹ Francisco Caamano-Isorna et al., 'Respiratory and Mental Health Effects of Wildfires: An Ecological Study in Galician Municipalities (North-West Spain)', *Environmental Health* 10, no. 1 (21 May 2011): 48, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1476-069X-10-48>.

⁴⁷⁰ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

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including pulmonary reliever medication and oral steroids ⁴⁷¹, and medicines to treat asthma (short-acting beta-2-agonist, SABA, fills) ⁴⁷²; anxiolytics-hypnotics - with a significant increase found in the daily doses per 1000 inhabitants per day among men (pensioners and no pensioners) in affected municipalities (15.88% vs. 12.2%) ⁴⁷³; salbutamol ⁴⁷⁴; systemic medications⁴⁷⁵; nitroglycerin (for cardiovascular treatment) ⁴⁷⁶; reliever medications and oral steroids ⁴⁷⁷; short-acting beta-agonists for children with asthma ⁴⁷⁸.

Surge capacity - When populations are displaced in the aftermath of wildfires, they place a significant strain on the whole health system in the host country ⁴⁷⁹.

Box 5. Pharmacies: considerations for mountain areas

EWEs impact pharmacies in mountain areas, as there are few small facilities in rural regions that are highly susceptible to structural damage and increased demands for medication dispensing. Damage to infrastructure and transportation disruptions pose significant obstacles for the population attempting to access pharmacies, as well as for healthcare professionals who need to replenish supplies.

⁴⁷¹ Stawovy and Balakrishnan, 'The Threat of Wildfires and Pulmonary Complications'.

⁴⁷² Jiao et al., 'Associations between Short-Term Exposure to Wildfire Particulate Matter and Respiratory Outcomes'.

⁴⁷³ Youssouf et al., 'Non-Accidental Health Impacts of Wildfire Smoke'.

⁴⁷⁴ Borchers Arriagada et al., 'Association between Fire Smoke Fine Particulate Matter and Asthma-Related Outcomes'.

⁴⁷⁵ Belzer A and Parker Er, 'Climate Change, Skin Health, and Dermatologic Disease'.

⁴⁷⁶ Hindle and Henning, 'Critical Care at Extremes of Temperature'.

⁴⁷⁷ Rossiello and Szema, 'Health Effects of Climate Change-Induced Wildfires and Heatwaves'.

⁴⁷⁸ Rossiello and Szema.

⁴⁷⁹ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

Figure 7. Visual representation of the main impacts on Pharmacies

3.7. Public Health System

The evidence retrieved related to EWEs' impact on public health was scarce and solely concerning service utilisation and resources.

Floods and storms

Service utilisation - Several reviews reported impacts caused by floods and storms on public health services ⁴⁸⁰. Evidence has been found on the impact of power outages (resulting from floods and storms) on food refrigeration, water supply systems and disinfection, which increases public health services provision in terms of monitoring the water supply system and food security ⁴⁸¹. One review ⁴⁸² highlighted the potential water contamination from radioactive materials released in flood water after the inundation of nuclear medicine facilities. Other impacts reported are related to the increased need to track cases of Tuberculosis (TB) to confirm the continuation of treatment ⁴⁸³, the increased poison control calls for gastrointestinal illnesses following power outages ⁴⁸⁴, and the increased need to monitor and treat infections (Acinetobacter baumannii, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Aeromonas, Vibrio species, and Legionella, Mould spores, including Aspergillus and Penicillium species) ⁴⁸⁵.

Resources - One review ⁴⁸⁶ highlights how floods and storms can impact public health research when research specimens are disrupted, leading to substantial financial burdens.

⁴⁸⁰ Anucha Apisarntharak, David K. Warren, and Clovus Glen Mayhall, 'Healthcare-Associated Infections and Their Prevention after Extensive Flooding', *Current Opinion in Infectious Diseases* 26, no. 4 (August 2013): 359, <https://doi.org/10.1097/QCO.0b013e3283630b1d>; Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'; Stephen Y. Liang and Nicole Messenger, 'Infectious Diseases After Hydrologic Disasters', *Emergency Medicine Clinics of North America* 36, no. 4 (November 2018): 835–51, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.emc.2018.07.002>; Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

⁴⁸¹ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

⁴⁸² Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

⁴⁸³ Liang and Messenger, 'Infectious Diseases After Hydrologic Disasters'.

⁴⁸⁴ Casey Ja et al., 'Power Outages and Community Health'.

⁴⁸⁵ Apisarntharak, Warren, and Glen Mayhall, 'Healthcare-Associated Infections and Their Prevention after Extensive Flooding'.

⁴⁸⁶ Man et al., 'The Effect of Natural Disasters on Cancer Care'.

Wildfires

Surge capacity - When populations are displaced in the aftermath of wildfires, they place a significant strain on the whole health system in the host country ⁴⁸⁷.

General EWEs

Resources - Several reviews ⁴⁸⁸ reported an overall increase in public health expenditure due to an increased demand for public health services during floods, storms, heatwaves, cold spells, and wildfires.

Box 6. Public health system: considerations for mountain areas

The public health system in mountain areas is affected by EWEs. For instance, the municipality's water system can be impacted by floods and heavy rains, which can lead to water contamination with debris and mud, ultimately resulting in non-potability. Limited health care and public health infrastructures are critical weaknesses in rural communities; thus, in case of urban to rural evacuation due to exposure to radiation, chemical, biological or other types of hazards, the amount of evacuees is likely to overwhelm the health system of small communities ⁴⁸⁹.

Another challenge in public health management during EWEs arises from the significant population increase in mountain areas during tourist seasons, requiring substantial surge efforts to handle numbers that typically exceed the healthcare capacity of the catchment area. For example, in the northern Italian region of Valle d'Aosta, the population can increase by up to 170% during peak tourist seasons ⁴⁹⁰. In

⁴⁸⁷ Bell et al., 'Changes in Extreme Events and the Potential Impacts on Human Health'.

⁴⁸⁸ Adnan et al., 'Vulnerability of Australia to Heatwaves'; Naser, Haq, and Naughton, 'The Impact of Climate Change on Health Services in Low- and Middle-Income Countries'; Rocque et al., 'Health Effects of Climate Change'; Laetitia H. M. Schmitt, Hilary M. Graham, and Piran C. L. White, 'Economic Evaluations of the Health Impacts of Weather-Related Extreme Events: A Scoping Review', *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 13, no. 11 (8 November 2016): 1105, <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph13111105>.

⁴⁸⁹ Michael Meit, Alene Kennedy, and Thomas Briggs, 'Publication Details: Urban-to-Rural Evacuation: Planning for Rural Population Surge (Final Report) - Rural Health Research Gateway', August 2008, <https://www.ruralhealthresearch.org/publications/653>.

⁴⁹⁰ Raffaele Brustia et al., 'Results of a Prospective Observational Study on Mountaineering Emergencies in Western Alps: Mind Your Head', *High Altitude Medicine & Biology* 17, no. 2 (June 2016): 116–21, <https://doi.org/10.1089/ham.2015.0110>.

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Switzerland, winter sports regions exhibit a distinct seasonal variation in admission rates, primarily from nonlocal residents⁴⁹¹.

In mountain regions, many hazards are transboundary in nature, both in terms of impact and management, potentially leading to cumulative, multi-level effects on the region and complicating risk management and disaster response⁴⁹². This phenomenon also complicates the establishment of evacuation routes in disaster-prone areas, necessitating cross-border planning for transportation infrastructure⁴⁹³.

4. Conclusion

In conclusion, mountain regions across Europe face escalating risks from extreme weather events (EWEs) due to climate change, remoteness, and ecological sensitivity, with significant implications for health systems. Despite increasing disaster frequency—evidenced by a 26% rise in events in the European Alps over four decades—disaster risk reduction strategies and health system adaptations tailored to these vulnerable areas remain insufficient. The persistent knowledge gap underscores the urgent need for targeted research and policy action. This systematic review of reviews addresses that gap by synthesizing evidence on EWE impacts on health systems, offering critical insights to strengthen resilience and inform the Mountadapt project's preparatory efforts. Enhancing health system preparedness in mountain areas is not only a public health imperative but a vital step toward achieving equitable and effective disaster risk reduction in the face of a changing climate.

Extreme weather events (EWEs) profoundly disrupt health systems across all levels—pre-hospital care, hospital pathways (emergency, medical/surgical, outpatient), primary and elderly care, pharmacies, and public health—compromising infrastructure, access, quality, service utilization, surge capacity, and human and material resources. Floods and storms severely impair pre-hospital systems by blocking access via damaged roads and limiting air/boat transport, increasing demand for emergency services, and straining staff and supplies. Rescuers face psychological trauma, while critical medical equipment and medications are compromised by power outages and environmental damage.

⁴⁹¹ Klazien Matter-Walstra, Marcel Widmer, and André Busato, 'Seasonal Variation in Orthopedic Health Services Utilization in Switzerland: The Impact of Winter Sport Tourism', *BMC Health Services Research* 6, no. 1 (1 December 2006): 25, <https://doi.org/10.1186/1472-6963-6-25>.

⁴⁹² Kate Williamson, Rosie Witton, and Estelle Lorang, 'Adapting to Transboundary Risks in Mountain Regions | PreventionWeb', 3 May 2024, <https://www.preventionweb.net/publication/adapting-transboundary-risks-mountain-regions>.

⁴⁹³ Efendhi P. Raharjo, Sri Sarjana, and Mega Safitri, 'Transportation Infrastructure Planning in Supporting Disaster Mitigation: Case Study in Mount Gamalama', *Jàmbá: Journal of Disaster Risk Studies* 14, no. 1 (31 March 2022): 11, <https://doi.org/10.4102/jamba.v14i1.1123>.

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In hospitals, EWEs disrupt emergency and medical pathways through infrastructure failures, power and water outages, and supply chain breakdowns, leading to increased ED visits and hospitalizations for cardiovascular, respiratory, renal, and mental health conditions. Surge capacity is overwhelmed by patient influxes, staff shortages, and logistical challenges, particularly in remote or flood-prone areas. Outpatient and primary care systems suffer from interrupted services, especially for vulnerable populations, with delayed care, medication shortages, and loss of assistive devices. Pharmacies face closures, supply disruptions, and increased demand for respiratory, cardiovascular, and psychotropic medications, while staff often assume expanded roles under crisis conditions. Public health systems experience heightened surveillance needs due to water contamination, infectious disease risks, and increased expenditures.

Heatwaves and cold spells similarly strain health systems, with rising demand for care due to heat-related illnesses, cardiovascular strain, and mental health crises, while extreme temperatures degrade medication stability and equipment functionality. Wildfires exacerbate respiratory and cardiovascular morbidity, disrupt access to care, and place immense pressure on host communities through population displacement. Across all EWEs, a consistent pattern emerges in which health systems are increasingly challenged by cascading failures, reduced resilience, and inadequate preparedness—particularly in vulnerable and remote regions. This review underscores the urgent need for integrated, climate-resilient health system planning, targeted investment in infrastructure and workforce capacity, and coordinated multi-sectoral responses to safeguard health services and protect populations in the face of escalating climate risks.

Chapter 3: Observed and expected impact of climate change on human health in the Pyrenees Mountain range

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The Working Community of the Pyrenees (CTP)

1. Introduction

All European regions are vulnerable to Climate Change (CC) impacts, although its magnitude and intensity differs depending on the geographic, economic and social characteristics of the region of the planet. According to the main climate projections for Europe ^{494,495}, both the South and Southwest areas of Europe, where the Pyrenees are located, will be the most critical areas affected by CC and particularly by the frequency and intensity of extreme events. The international scientific community agrees that mountain areas such as the Pyrenees are among the most sensitive to the negative impacts of CC ^{496,497}. In fact, several studies have shown that in recent decades most of the mountain areas over the world have experienced greater temperature increases than lowland areas ^{498,499}. In the Pyrenees, CC is negatively impacting both socioeconomic and biophysical systems namely biodiversity, ecosystems, quality of life of citizens, territory and the economy ⁵⁰⁰.

The synergetic effects of higher temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns and increasing frequency and intensity of extreme events (i.e., heat waves, heavy rain, droughts) is creating new challenging scenarios for more sustainable development of this territory and particularly on the human health of the inhabitants of this transboundary mountain bioregion. Specifically, CC influences human health both directly and indirectly. The direct impacts are linked to changes in temperature and precipitation weather patterns, including those related to extreme events, which in the Pyrenees typically manifest themselves in the form of floods and extreme precipitation, directly affecting mortality and morbidity. On the other hand, the most common indirect health impacts in mountain areas are linked to interactions between climate (temperature, precipitation and extreme events), the environment, food production, water use and synergies with other risks. Indirect impacts include changes in the

⁴⁹⁴ ENSEMBLES project: <https://ensembles-eu.metoffice.gov.uk/>

⁴⁹⁵ EURO-CORDEX projects: <https://www.euro-cordex.net/>

⁴⁹⁶ EEA, 2016: Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2016. An indicator-based report

⁴⁹⁷ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos

⁴⁹⁸ Minder, J. R., Letcher, T. W., & Liu, C. (2018). The character and causes of elevation-dependent warming in high-resolution simulations of Rocky Mountain climate change. *Journal of Climate*, 31(6), 2093-2113.

⁴⁹⁹ Palazzi, E., Mortarini, L., Terzago, S., & Von Hardenberg, J. (2019). Elevation-dependent warming in global climate model simulations at high spatial resolution. *Climate Dynamics*, 52(5), 2685-2702.

⁵⁰⁰ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos

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geographical and temporal distribution of vector disease; changes in the quality and quantity of water and food; mental health and other synergistic effects such as air pollution and some meteorological events that enhance the formation of and exposure to certain atmospheric pollutants. Other possible impacts may be related to the frequency and intensity of forest fires as a consequence of droughts and high temperatures, with release of suspended particles and other atmospheric pollutants^{501, 502}.

Plant growth, favoured by CO₂ together with increased temperature, may lead to an increase in pollen production and the amount of allergens in pollen grains, extending the duration of pollen seasons. On the other hand, chemical pollutants in the atmosphere may be affected by CC, such as tropospheric ozone, whose levels are increased by higher temperatures and other atmospheric and orographic conditions typical of mountain areas that may increase their occurrence due to CC. In addition to having direct impacts on health, extreme weather events such as floods, storms, floods, droughts, etc., can generate very diverse risks for health, such as water pollution for human consumption or the alteration of agricultural and livestock systems due to the transmission of pathogens and vectors. Changes in temperature and climatic conditions may alter geographical distribution of vectors and their adaptation to different habitats, with the risk of creating the necessary conditions for the transmission of vector-borne diseases of subtropical origin to this Mediterranean mountain area.

This chapter aims to present the state of the art on the observed and expected impacts of CC on human health in the Pyrenees. However, this is a mountainous bi-region for which there is little specific bibliography on the target geographical scale, and where studies on the effects of CC focus particularly on biophysical systems, with special attention to sensitive high mountain ecosystems. In this sense, much of the literature reviewed about climate related risks on health refers to larger spatial scales, mainly the Mediterranean basin.

2. Direct impacts of CC in the Pyrenees.

2.1 Extreme temperatures

⁵⁰¹ Dasgupta, S., & Robinson, E. J. (2022). Attributing changes in food insecurity to a changing climate. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 4709.

⁵⁰² van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

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In general, a heat wave is a period of time in which maximum and minimum temperatures are above climatologically 'normal' values and are maintained for several days. However, the temperature considered as 'normal' in an area with a warm climate may be abnormal in an area with a cold climate, as is the case in the Pyrenees. There is no agreed definition of heat waves in the literature ⁵⁰³. According to the State Meteorological Agency AEMET, which operates in the southern half of the Pyrenees, a heat wave is 'a period of at least three consecutive days in which at least 10% of the weather stations considered record ambient temperatures above the 95% percentile of their daily maximum temperature series for the months of July and August of the reference period 1971- 2000'.

As defined by Météo-France, the reference agency in the northern Pyrenees, the heat indicator must be 23.4°C or higher for at least 3 days. The heatwave ends when the national heat indicator falls below 23.4°C for 2 consecutive days, or when it falls below 22.4°C for even one day. Both definitions specify a threshold from a 'climatological' point of view based on temperature. However, there is evidence that the impact on health may depend on other meteorological parameters, such as humidity or wind. This has led to the definition of apparent temperature. As an example, in the EuroHEAT project ⁵⁰⁴, a heat wave was defined as a period in which the apparent temperature (usually considered as the equivalent human-perceived temperature that is caused by combined effects of air temperature, relative humidity and wind speed) maximum and minimum exceed the 90th percentile of the monthly distribution for at least two days ⁵⁰⁵. Other studies use thresholds defined with 'epidemiological' criteria that are based on the analysis of meteorological, demographic and mortality variables. In this way, they make it possible to relate the temperature threshold to an observed impact on health ⁵⁰⁶. Correctly defining this threshold is crucial to launch effective heatwave warnings.

On the other hand, cold spells referring to temperatures below the Minimum Mortality Temperature (MMT) which means the mean daily temperature at which the lowest

⁵⁰³ <https://wmo.int/topics/heatwave>

⁵⁰⁴ D'Ippoliti, D., Michelozzi, P., Marino, C., de'Donato, F., Menne, B., Katsouyanni, K., ... & Perucci, C. A. (2010). The impact of heat waves on mortality in 9 European cities: results from the EuroHEAT project. *Environmental Health*, 9, 1-9.

⁵⁰⁵ World Health Organization. (2009). Improving public health responses to extreme weather/heat-waves: EuroHEAT: technical summary. In *Improving public health responses to extreme weather/heat-waves: EuroHEAT: technical summary*.

⁵⁰⁶ Kapwata, T., Gebreslasie, M. T., & Wright, C. Y. (2022). An analysis of past and future heatwaves based on a heat-associated mortality threshold: towards a heat health warning system. *Environmental health*, 21(1), 112.

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mortality occurs, although with a lesser impact than heat waves, also have direct impacts on human health. Some of the most common health impacts are arterial thrombosis, cardiovascular, cerebrovascular, circulatory and respiratory disease, influenza epidemics and premature mortality ⁵⁰⁷.

Observed impacts

Heat waves have associated impacts on human health, mainly an increase in cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, such as asthma and rhinitis, and increased mortality ⁵⁰⁸. Other effects include heat stroke, heat stress, fatigue, exhaustion and heat stress, which in severe cases can also be fatal ⁵⁰⁹. Although there are no specific studies on the Pyrenean region, it is estimated that in the decade 2010-2019 the exposure to heat waves has grown 64.4% (1.07 billion person-days/year compared to the previous decade (0.65 billion person-days/year) in relation to the most vulnerable population (adults above 65 years, children under one year old ⁵¹⁰. During the summer heatwave of 2022 alone, excess mortality associated with extreme temperatures is estimated at 60,000 people, with France and Spain among the 4 European countries with the worst figures ⁵¹¹. It has been shown that people living in cities are generally more exposed to extreme heat than people living in rural and mountain areas. This difference, which derives from the lower amplitude of temperature extremes in rural and mountain areas compared to cities, is particularly marked at night ⁵¹². In a study carried out in Spain, it was shown that mean daily minimum temperatures, i.e. night-time temperatures, during heat waves have been up to 4.1 °C higher in urban

⁵⁰⁷ Vicedo-Cabrera, A. M., Guo, Y., Sera, F., Huber, V., Schleussner, C. F., Mitchell, D., ... & Gasparrini, A. (2018). Temperature-related mortality impacts under and beyond Paris Agreement climate change scenarios. *Climatic change*, 150, 391-402.

⁵⁰⁸ D'Amato, G., Tedeschini, E., Frenguelli, G., & D'Amato, M. (2019). Allergens as trigger factors for allergic respiratory diseases and severe asthma during thunderstorms in pollen season. *Aerobiologia*, 35, 379-382.

⁵⁰⁹ van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

⁵¹⁰ van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965

⁵¹¹ Ballester, J., Quijal-Zamorano, M., Méndez Turrubiates, R. F., Pegenaute, F., Herrmann, F. R., Robine, J. M., ... & Achebak, H. (2023). Heat-related mortality in Europe during the summer of 2022. *Nature medicine*, 29(7), 1857-1866.

⁵¹² Fastl, C., Arnberger, A., Gallistl, V., Stein, V. K., & Dorner, T. E. (2024). Heat vulnerability: health impacts of heat on older people in urban and rural areas in Europe. *Wiener klinische Wochenschrift*, 1-8.

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observatories than in non-urban observatories in the five analyzed cities ⁵¹³. However, older adults residing in more rural territories are also affected by heat and face specific challenges in coping with extreme heat events. Compared to the plains and surrounding cities, mountain areas such as the Pyrenees often have less infrastructure to cope with extreme heat, as well as fewer cooling centres and accessible emergency services. In addition, older people in rural settings may have limited access to health facilities and services, which can delay treatment of heat-related illnesses ⁵¹⁴. The physical environment of mountain areas, although cooler due to higher altitude, vegetation and lower heat island effect, may also pose significant risks, particularly for older adults who are still engaged in agricultural or forestry activities and who may be exposed to high temperatures without adequate prevention or hydration ⁵¹⁵. Furthermore, although the number of people living in rural areas in Europe is decreasing, the relative proportion of people aged 65 and over is higher in rural regions than in urban areas in most European countries ⁵¹⁶.

On the other hand, extreme temperatures seem to be influencing the percentage of fatal accidents occurring in high mountains. A study carried out in the Austrian Alps to study the influence of meteorological variables on mountain accidents and the possible influence of CC has shown a direct correlation between rising temperatures and the likelihood of accidents occurring during typical mountain activities. Specifically, a 1°C increase in temperature was associated with a 13% increase in the likelihood of a mountain bike accident in summer and an 8% increase in the likelihood of suicide in the mountains in winter. Furthermore, in the same statistical analysis, including the study of 3285 accidents, it was concluded that an increase of 1 kWh/m² in global radiation was associated with a rain-on-snow contributions increase of between 11% and 28% in the odds of fatal accidents in summer mountaineering and winter cycle touring respectively ⁵¹⁷. However, these results should be interpreted with caution,

⁵¹³ Mentaschi, L., Duveiller, G., Zulian, G., Corbane, C., Pesaresi, M., Maes, J., ... & Feyen, L. (2022). Global long-term mapping of surface temperature shows intensified intra-city urban heat island extremes. *Global Environmental Change*, 72, 102441.

⁵¹⁴ van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

⁵¹⁵ Fastl, C., Arnberger, A., Gallistl, V., Stein, V. K., & Dorner, T. E. (2024). Heat vulnerability: health impacts of heat on older people in urban and rural areas in Europe. *Wiener klinische Wochenschrift*, 136(17), 507-514.

⁵¹⁶ <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/population-demography/demography-population-stock-balance/database>

⁵¹⁷ Neumair, M., Estrella, N., Menzel, A., & Ankerst, D. P. (2022). The influence of weather on fatal accidents in Austrian mountains. *Weather, climate, and society*, 14(1), 303-310.

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taking into account the wide range of factors that interact with each other in triggering an accident in mountain environments.

According to data published by the study “The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and CC: towards a climate resilient future”⁵¹⁸, Spain in general and in particular the southern slopes of the central Pyrenees have suffered a considerable increase in the number of heat-related deaths in the last 20 years. According to this study, in the southern central mountain range the number of heat-related deaths had increased by about 45 ± 5 deaths per year per million inhabitants per decade.

On the northern slopes of the Pyrenees, this trend seems to have been much less pronounced, with values of around 10 ± 5 deaths per million inhabitants per decade.

Figure 1: Trends in heat related mortality incidence (annual death per million per decade) in Europe for the general population (2000–2021). Source: van Daalen et al., 2022.

⁵¹⁸ van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

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Box 1. Meteosalud: a new health alert system for extreme temperatures in Spain, representing real heat exposure also in mountain areas.

In summer 2024, the Spanish government launched a new heatwave warning system with several new elements. This new system divides the Iberian Peninsula into 182 'Meteosalud' zones, instead of the 52 provinces used until now. These are the same areas used by AEMET (Agencia Estatal de Meteorología) to issue its weather warnings, which group together all the municipalities that share similar climatic characteristics within each province.

This new system allows a better representation of the real exposure to heat, avoiding the generalization of the provincial risk threshold used until now, and includes other key factors of vulnerability to heatwaves such as social, demographic and geographical factors in the equation that calculates the temperature from which the statistics of heat-related deaths are triggered. At the same time, some conditioning factors have been incorporated that influence the capacity to adapt to heat, such as the structure of the population, the level of income, how prepared the homes are or the response capacity of the health system in each territory. The result is a system that is between 1.6 and 7.6 °C away on average from AEMET's meteorological thresholds. In general, the temperatures that trigger a health alert are now lower than those that will activate the weather warnings. With these new thresholds, the aim is to better manage the risks associated with heat in order to avoid greater impacts on the health of the population thanks to a more selective and specific warning system.

With this new system, areas such as the Pyrenees have seen a considerable increase in the number of days per year on which the new updated thresholds are exceeded. If, for example, this system had been active during the heatwave of 2023, the health alert threshold temperature for heat would have been reached on 52 days in the Lleida Pyrenees, in contrast to 49 days on the southern coast of Alicante.

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Meteosalud zones in the Autonomous Community of Catalonia, with the respective maximum temperature thresholds of impact on health according to provinces. Source: Spanish Health Ministry, within the National Plan of preventive actions against the effects of excess temperature on health, 2024.

According to the climate index calculated from the homogenized climate database generated in the cross-border project under the INTERREG POCTEFA programme ⁵¹⁹, the number of warm days per year has increased by between 0.5 and 1.2 days per decade since 1961. However, this increase shows a high spatial variability, being more marked on the southern slopes of the Mediterranean Pyrenees. Small valley and low mountain areas of the Huesca Pyrenees even show a slight tendency towards a decrease in the number of warm days, but with low statistical significance.

Figure 3: Trend value (%/decade) of the 'warm days' indicator (percentage of days in a year with maximum T above the 90th percentile of the reference period 1961-1990) for the period 2000-2020. This indicator has been calculated with the Mann-Kendall test from the database created in the OPCC for the entire perimeter of the Pyrenees and at a resolution of 1 km x 1 km. OPCC geoportal, with data from POCTEFA ADAPYR project 2019-2022.

Although the vast majority of excess mortality in Europe associated with temperature extremes is correlated with heat waves, cold waves also generate excess mortality ⁵²⁰. In this sense, changes in winter maximum and minimum temperatures and changes in the intensity and severity of cold spells could also have some positive effect on health. For example, milder winters appear to be contributing to a reduction in peak winter

⁵¹⁹ <https://www.opcc-ctp.org/en/climpy>

⁵²⁰ Arbuthnott, K., Hajat, S., Heaviside, C., & Vardoulakis, S. (2018). What is cold-related mortality? A multi-disciplinary perspective to inform climate change impact assessments. *Environment international*, 121, 119-129.

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mortality, partially offsetting the increased risk during summer seasons ⁵²¹. In the Pyrenees, a statistically significant decrease in the number of cold days of about -15 cold days per decade has been observed since 1981.

Figure 4: Trend value (%/decade) of the indicator 'cold days': percentage of days in a year with maximum T below the 10th percentile of the reference period 1981-2020) for the period 1981-2020. This indicator has been calculated with the Mann-Kendall test from the database created in the OPCC for the entire perimeter of the Pyrenees and at a resolution of 1 km x 1 km. Source: OPCC geoportal, with data from POCTEFA ADAPYR project 2019-2022.

Expected impacts:

Regarding the future situation, there is a broad consensus in the scientific literature on the projected increase in the frequency, intensity and amplitude of extremely hot periods over the next century in the Mediterranean basin ^{522,523}. Projections based on an ensemble of several climate models agree on an increase in the frequency and magnitude of heat waves in most European regions during the 21st century under all socio-economic scenarios (RCPs) considered ⁵²⁴. According to an analysis carried out in 2020 by the PESETA IV project, by the end of this century, with a global warming of

⁵²¹ Cuervo-Vilches, T., Díaz, J., López-Bueno, J. A., Luna, M. Y., Navas, M. A., Mirón, I. J., & Linares, C. (2023). Impact of urban heat islands on morbidity and mortality in heat waves: Observational time series analysis of Spain's five cities. *Science of the Total Environment*, 890, 164412.

⁵²² Russo, A., Gouveia, C. M., Dutra, E., Soares, P. M. M., & Trigo, R. M. (2019). The synergy between drought and extremely hot summers in the Mediterranean. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(1), 014011.

⁵²³ Naumann, G., Russo, S., Formetta, G., Ibarreta, D., Forzieri, G., Girardello, M., & Feyen, L. (2020). Global warming and human impacts of heat and cold extremes in the EU. *Crop Pasture Sci*, 10, 47878.

⁵²⁴ Fischer, E. M., Sippel, S., & Knutti, R. (2021). Increasing probability of record-shattering climate extremes. *Nature Climate Change*, 11(8), 689-695.

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3°C, the number of EU citizens (including the UK) exposed annually to heatwave would increase from an average of 10 million in the period 1981-2010 to 300 million. If these projections are confirmed, more than half of the European population would be annually exposed to health risks from extreme temperatures ⁵²⁵. In the same study, without further adaptation, this could result in an excess of 96.000 excess heat-related deaths per year, compared to an average of 2.750 in the reference period (1981-2010). This means that, for example, in northern Spain and southern France, and under scenarios of rising temperatures of 3°C, heat waves with a current return period of 50 years could occur every summer on the southern slopes of the Pyrenees, and every 3 years on the northern slopes.

Figure 5: Top panels: mean number of summer heatwave days (HWDs) for the baseline (1986-2005) and future (2041-2060) conditions under two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) (ensemble median). Bottom panels: vulnerability index in Europe for the baseline socio-economic conditions (2015) and for the year 2050 under the two Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). The vulnerability index measures socio-economic vulnerability to

⁵²⁵ Naumann, G., Russo, S., Formetta, G., Ibarreta, D., Forzieri, G., Girardello, M., & Feyen, L. (2020). Global warming and human impacts of heat and cold extremes in the EU. *Crop Pasture Sci*, 10, 47878.

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heat stress determined by income, education, age, artificial surfaces, social isolation and pre-existing medical conditions. Source: EEA 2024 adapted from Rohat et al., 2019.

Simulations from EURO-CORDEX ⁵²⁶ suggest that between 2021-2050 there will be an increase in intensity, frequency, duration, and spatial coverage of health waves in the Iberian Peninsula by 104%. Indeed, the most significant changes will probably occur in the eastern-central region, rising to 150% in the mediterranean and the Pyrenean region ⁵²⁷.

An opposite trend is expected for cold waves within the ongoing century. Specifically, Moderate cold waves (2-year return period) will be observed only every 20 years in many areas of Europe including the Pyrenees region under 3°C of warming. According to the PESETA IV project ⁵²⁸, the trend of people exposed to cold waves will gradually decrease as the century progresses. This negative trend would be more pronounced depending on the climate scenarios considered.

Figure 6: Return period (in years) of baseline 20-year heatwave and a 2-year cold wave for 1.5°C, 2°C and 3°C global warming. Source: adapted from Naumann et.al 2020 ⁵²⁹.

Consequently, it is expected that during this century there will be a prominent decrease in the number of people exposed to health risks due to cold waves, reflected in a substantial decrease in the annual excess of deaths due to extreme cold in Europe. Specifically, for the area corresponding to the Pyrenean mountain range, the number of people exposed to cold waves per year could be reduced by 30±10% on the

⁵²⁶ <https://www.euro-cordex.net/>

⁵²⁷ Lorenzo, M. N., & Alvarez, I. (2022). Future changes of hot extremes in Spain: towards warmer conditions. *Natural Hazards*, 113(1), 383-402.

⁵²⁸ Naumann, G., Russo, S., Formetta, G., Ibarreta, D., Forzieri, G., Girardello, M., & Feyen, L. (2020). Global warming and human impacts of heat and cold extremes in the EU. *Crop Pasture Sci*, 10, 47878.

⁵²⁹ Naumann, G., Russo, S., Formetta, G., Ibarreta, D., Forzieri, G., Girardello, M., & Feyen, L. (2020). Global warming and human impacts of heat and cold extremes in the EU. *Crop Pasture Sci*, 10, 47878.

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southern slope and 20±10% on the northern slope with respect to the current exposure value, considering the 1.5°C scenario.

2.2 Extreme storms and rainfall

Extreme rainfall in mountain areas can generate floods or flash floods with potential impacts on both the physical and mental health of people. Flash floods are the most frequent in the Pyrenees, associated with very heavy rains with a short duration⁵³⁰. The direct effects of floods or flash floods include drowning, injuries caused by contact with objects carried by water flows, hypothermia and electrical injuries⁵³¹. On the other hand, floods often cause sewage overflows leading to an increased risk of incidence of infectious and viral diseases such as norovirus, hepatitis A and rotavirus, as well as other bacterial infections due to *Campylobacter spp*, Pathogenic *E. coli* and *Salmonella enterica* and, to a lesser extent⁵³², flood events can also cause heart attacks in susceptible people, respiratory problems due to anxiety and complications in pregnant women may increase⁵³³. Indirect effects of flooding include health problems caused by interrupted medical treatment; physical workload associated with clean-up and reconstruction; shortages of medical aid, electricity or drinking water; and problems with food, electricity or sanitation supply chains⁵³⁴. Living in flood-damaged housing can lead to pulmonary and systemic fungal infections and exposure to mycotoxins. It has been estimated that around 75 % of people affected by floods suffer from mental health problems: trauma, short-term mental distress or post-traumatic stress disorder, anxiety, insomnia, psychosis and depression⁵³⁵.

Observed and projected impacts

At the European level, the number of major continental floods (catastrophic floods) has been increasing since the 1980s, although the multitude of factors interacting in

⁵³⁰ Llasat, M. C., Marcos, R., Turco, M., Gilibert, J., & Llasat-Botija, M. (2016). Trends in flash flood events versus convective precipitation in the Mediterranean region: The case of Catalonia. *Journal of Hydrology*, 541, 24-37.

⁵³¹ EEA, 2016: Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2016: An indicator-based report

⁵³² <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/RRA-20210720-1799.pdf>

⁵³³ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/RRA-20210720-1799.pdf>

⁵³⁴ Paterson, D. L., Wright, H., & Harris, P. N. (2018). Health risks of flood disasters. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*, 67(9), 1450-1454.

⁵³⁵ World Health Organization. (2009). Improving public health responses to extreme weather/heat-waves: EuroHEAT: technical summary.

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concomitance make it difficult to correlate such a trend to CC ^{536, 537}. In addition to CC, which is significantly influencing the seasonal rainfall and snowmelt regime, changes in land use over the last 50 years, such as urbanisation, altered agricultural practices, progressive reforestation due to the abandonment of extensive livestock farming and the narrowing of riverbeds, are factors that act synergistically, influencing the behavior of flash floods ⁵³⁸.

In the Pyrenees, floods occur mainly as a result of high intensity rainfall, such as rapid-response 'flash floods'. Only rarely does snowmelt play an important role. The only reported case was due to the 2013 Garonne river episode, where sudden snowmelt coupled with heavy rainfall caused catastrophic floods affecting Catalonia, Aragon, Andorra, and Central Pyrenees ^{539, 540}.

In the Pyrenean mountain range, the evolution of the number of days with heavy rainfall (rainfall greater than 20 mm) shows much spatial heterogeneity. In general terms, a positive and statistically significant trend is observed in a large part of all the territories of the Pyrenees, with values of $+1 \pm 0.2$ days per decade. On the other hand, there is a decreasing trend in the number of days with heavy rainfall of -1 ± 0.2 days per decade in the upper central Pyrenees, between the Aragonese and Catalan Pyrenees.

⁵³⁶ Hov, Ø., Cubasch, U., Fischer, E., Höppe, P., Iversen, T., Gunnar Kvamstø, N., ... & Ulbrich, U. (2013). Extreme weather events in Europe: preparing for climate change adaptation. Norwegian Meteorological Institute.

⁵³⁷ Aerts, J. C., Botzen, W. J., Clarke, K. C., Cutter, S. L., Hall, J. W., Merz, B., ... & Kunreuther, H. (2018). Integrating human behaviour dynamics into flood disaster risk assessment. *Nature Climate Change*, 8(3), 193-199.

⁵³⁸ Sabelli, C. (2023). Examining the role of climate change in the Emilia-Romagna floods. *Nature Italy*, d43978-023.

⁵³⁹ <https://www.eaufrance.fr/node/6632>

⁵⁴⁰ Queralt, A., Llasat, M. D. C., Serena, J. M., & Pont, I. (2017, April). The 3rd Report on Climate Change in Catalonia: a joint initiative to bridge the gap between Science and Decision-Making. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (p. 14658).

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Figure 7: Trend value (days/decade) of the annual number of days with precipitation equal to or greater than 20 mm for the period 1981-2015. This indicator has been calculated with the Mann-Kendall test from the database created at the OPCC for the entire perimeter of the Pyrenees and at a resolution of 1 km x 1 km.

Floods in the Pyrenees have occurred most frequently in late summer and early autumn, with exceptional floods in October 1940 (more than 860 mm of rain) and November 1982 (more than 600 mm of rain) ⁵⁴¹, as well as in November 1999 and October 2018 (mainly in Northern Catalonia), accounting for the highest number of victims, in recent years, in the French Pyrenean regions ⁵⁴².

According to a recent study specific to the Pyrenean transboundary area, which has generated the first transboundary database on flooding in the Pyrenees, the total number of flooding events has been progressively increasing in the mountain range since 1980⁵⁴³.

One of the key aspects in the triggering of flash floods are rain-on-snow situations ⁵⁴⁴. These situations occur when, following a sudden increase in temperature, rainfall occurs directly on the snowpack between 1500 and 2400 m altitude.

⁵⁴¹ Queralt, A., Llasat, M. D. C., Serena, J. M., & Pont, I. (2017, April). The 3rd Report on Climate Change in Catalonia: a joint initiative to bridge the gap between Science and Decision-Making. In EGU General Assembly Conference Abstracts (p. 14658).

⁵⁴² Boudou, M., Danière, B., & Lang, M. (2016). Assessing changes in urban flood vulnerability through mapping land use from historical information. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences*, 20(1), 161-173.

⁵⁴³ Llasat, M. C., Llasat-Botija, M., Pardo, E., Marcos-Matamoros, R., & Lemus-Canovas, M. (2024). Floods in the Pyrenees: A global view through a regional database. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 2024, 1-29.

⁵⁴⁴ Bonsoms, J., López-Moreno, J. I., Alonso-González, E., Deschamps-Berger, C., & Oliva, M. (2023). Rain-on-snow response to a warmer Pyrenees. *EGU sphere*, 2023, 1-29.

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Figure 8: Monthly distribution of the total number of flood cases for the different regions. The solid line 330 shows the entire Pyrenees- POCTEFA region, and the dashed line shows the number of significant events (period 1981-2015). Source: Llasat et al., 2024 ⁽⁵⁴⁵⁾

A recent study has investigated the evolution of this type of conditions during the last decades in the Pyrenees ⁵⁴⁶. According to this research, the highest frequency of rain-on-snow for the historical climatic period (1980-2019) is found in the high altitudes (2400m) of the southwest Pyrenees (17 days/year). The maximum amount of rain-on-

⁵⁴⁵ Llasat, M. C., Llasat-Botija, M., Pardo, E., Marcos-Matamoros, R., & Lemus-Canovas, M. (2024). Floods in the Pyrenees: A global view through a regional database. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 2024, 1-29.

⁵⁴⁶ Bonsoms, J., López-Moreno, J. I., Alonso-González, E., Deschamps-Berger, C., & Oliva, M. (2024). Rain-on-snow responses to warmer Pyrenees: a sensitivity analysis using a physically based snow hydrological model. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 24(1), 245-264.

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snow is detected in the 1800 m areas of the south-eastern Pyrenees (45 mm/day, in autumn), while the highest rain-on-snow ablation is found in the 2400 m areas of the north-western Pyrenees (-10 cm/day, in summer). When air temperature increases by 1 to 4 °C compared to the historical mean, the amount and frequency of rain-on-snow precipitation increases at a constant rate during winter and early spring for all studied areas. This trend could explain the higher frequency of flash floods in the Pyrenees, coinciding also with the underlined spatial and temporal patterns found by Llasat et al⁵⁴⁷.

Figure 9: Evolution of the total number of flood events (including ordinary and non-repeated events in the different regions) for the period 1981-2015. Source: Llasat et al., 2024 ⁽⁵⁴⁸⁾.

Considering now the spatial distribution of catastrophic and extraordinary events between 1980 and 2015, we observe a higher concentration of these events in the central area of the Aragonese Pyrenees and the coastal areas of the southern Spanish and French Pyrenees, Catalonia and Nouvelle-Aquitaine respectively (see figure 10).

With regard to the number of direct fatalities associated with these events, a total of 154 victims have been recorded throughout the Pyrenees Mountain range from 1980 to 2015. The flooding of the municipality of Biescas (Aragonese Pyrenees) in 1996 was

⁵⁴⁷ Llasat, M. C., Llasat-Botija, M., Pardo, E., Marcos-Matamoros, R., & Lemus-Canovas, M. (2024). Floods in the Pyrenees: A global view through a regional database. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 2024, 1-29.

⁵⁴⁸ Llasat, M. C., Llasat-Botija, M., Pardo, E., Marcos-Matamoros, R., & Lemus-Canovas, M. (2024). Floods in the Pyrenees: A global view through a regional database. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences Discussions*, 2024, 1-29.

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the catastrophic event with the highest number of fatalities, amounting to 97 victims
549 .

Figure 10: Number of events of catastrophic and extraordinary floods (non-ordinary episodes) that affected each municipality in the Pyrenees.

2.3 Air quality and CC

CC can affect air quality and, as a consequence, impact human health through several pathways. On the one hand, CC can affect the frequency and intensity of certain atmospheric conditions that influence the processes of ventilation and dilution of atmospheric pollutants, through the increased frequency or duration of episodes of atmospheric stability or thermal inversion in the valleys^{550, 551}. On the other hand, it can also influence the speed and regime of winds by influencing the processes that determine

⁵⁴⁹ Ayala Carcedo, F.J.: La inundación torrencial catastrófica del camping Las Nieves del 7 de agosto de 1996 en el cono de deyección del Arás (Biescas Pirineo Aragonés), in: *Riesgos Naturales*, coord. by Ayala Carcedo, 480 F.J. and Olcina Cantos, J., Ariel, ISBN 84-344-8034-4, 889-912, 2002

⁵⁵⁰ Linares, C., Díaz, J., Negev, M., Martínez, G. S., Debono, R., & Paz, S. (2020). Impacts of climate change on the public health of the Mediterranean Basin population-current situation, projections, preparedness and adaptation. *Environmental research*, 182, 109107.

⁵⁵¹ Badia, A., Vidal, V., Ventura, S., Curcoll, R., Segura, R., & Villalba, G. (2023). Modelling the impacts of emission changes on O₃ sensitivity, atmospheric oxidation capacity, and pollution transport over the Catalonia region. *Atmospheric chemistry and physics*, 23(18), 10751-10774.

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their deposition and transport. In addition, CC can influence the generation and exchange conditions of secondary pollutants such as tropospheric ozone (O₃) or particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₅ and PM₁₀) both because of the greater frequency of atmospheric conditions that favor their formation and the emission of their precursors^{552,553}, and because of the greater frequency and intensity of forest fires^{554,555,556}. In fact, the gradual increase in fire risk due to the increased frequency of favourable conditions such as droughts and heat waves^{557,558,559}, could determine the punctual worsening of air quality at certain periods of the year due to suspended particulate matter from combustion^{560,561,562}. It is important to note that 60% of the surface of the Pyrenees is covered by forest, increasingly stressed by droughts, heat waves and ultimately by

⁵⁵² Doherty, J. U., Gluckman, T. J., Hucker, W. J., Januzzi, J. L., Ortel, T. L., Saxonhouse, S. J., & Spinler, S. A. (2017). 2017 ACC expert consensus decision pathway for periprocedural management of anticoagulation in patients with nonvalvular atrial fibrillation: a report of the American College of Cardiology Clinical Expert Consensus Document Task Force. *Journal of the American College of Cardiology*, 69(7), 871-898.

⁵⁵³ Guion, A., Turquety, S., Cholakian, A., Polcher, J., Ehret, A., & Lathièrè, J. (2022). Interactions between the terrestrial biosphere and atmosphere during droughts and heatwaves: impact on surface ozone over Southwestern Europe. *EGUsphere*, 2022, 1-39.

⁵⁵⁴ Monks, P.S., et al., 2015, Tropospheric ozone and its precursors from the urban to the global scale from air quality to short-lived climate forcer, *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 15, 8889-8973. <https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-15-8889-2015>

⁵⁵⁵ Gimeno, L., Nieto, R., Vázquez, M., & Lavers, D. A. (2014). Atmospheric rivers: A mini-review. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 2, 2.

⁵⁵⁶ de Dios, V. R., Hedo, J., Camprubí, À. C., Thapa, P., Del Castillo, E. M., de Aragón, J. M., ... & Boer, M. M. (2021). Climate change induced declines in fuel moisture may turn currently fire-free Pyrenean mountain forests into fire-prone ecosystems. *Science of the Total Environment*, 797, 149104.

⁵⁵⁷ Dupire, S., Curt, T., & Bigot, S. (2017). Spatio-temporal trends in fire weather in the French Alps. *Science of the total environment*, 595, 801-817.

⁵⁵⁸ De Rigo, D., Libertà, G., Durrant, T. H., Vivancos, T. A., & San-Miguel-Ayanz, J. (2017). Forest fire danger extremes in Europe under climate change: variability and uncertainty (Doctoral dissertation, Publications Office of the European Union).

⁵⁵⁹ de Dios, V. R., Hedo, J., Camprubí, À. C., Thapa, P., Del Castillo, E. M., de Aragón, J. M., ... & Boer, M. M. (2021). Climate change induced declines in fuel moisture may turn currently fire-free Pyrenean mountain forests into fire-prone ecosystems. *Science of the Total Environment*, 797, 149104.

⁵⁶⁰ Von Schneidemesser, E., Monks, P. S., Allan, J. D., Bruhwiler, L., Forster, P., Fowler, D., ... & Sutton, M. A. (2015). Chemistry and the linkages between air quality and climate change. *Chemical reviews*, 115(10), 3856-3897.

⁵⁶¹ Kinney, P. L. (2018). Interactions of climate change, air pollution, and human health. *Current environmental health reports*, 5, 179-186.

⁵⁶² Guion, A. (2022). Droughts and heatwaves in the Western Mediterranean, impact on ozone pollution (Doctoral dissertation, Sorbonne Université).

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the increased water demand by the atmosphere that decreases fuel moisture ⁵⁶³. These abiotic stress conditions caused by climatic extremes, together with the progressive increase in average temperatures, induce abiotic stress in plants, which often respond by generating volatile organic compounds (VOC), mostly isoprenes, which are the main natural precursor of tropospheric O₃ ⁵⁶⁴.

Another natural source of suspended particulate matter comes from the so-called Saharan dust: this is particulate matter suspended in the atmosphere from the Sahara desert and transported by the wind to other regions. African Dust Outbreak (ADO) is generally generated by the resuspension of soil particles and forest fires, and in the Pyrenees particles can be transported from other areas. Some studies point to ADOs as one of the main contributors of the increase in regional-level background levels of PM₁₀ in southern Europe ⁵⁶⁵. Using thermodynamic parameters, a positive trend of increasing ADOs has been seen as well as an increase in the probability of their occurrence in the period 1941-2020 ^{566,567}, probably due to changes in the general atmospheric circulation and patterns of the Atmospheric rivers (ARs). The ARs are elongated and narrow bands of clouds and high water vapor content which advect low-latitude air poleward ⁵⁶⁸ that are believed to account for most of the annual moisture transport from the tropics into mid and high latitudes ⁵⁶⁹.

In addition, it is important to highlight that in many occasions tropospheric O₃ generated in urban and industrial areas or formed in rural areas close to them can be transported to mountain areas, such as the Pyrenees, through local or mesoscale

⁵⁶³ de Dios, V. R., Hedo, J., Camprubí, À. C., Thapa, P., Del Castillo, E. M., de Aragón, J. M., ... & Boer, M. M. (2021). Climate change induced declines in fuel moisture may turn currently fire-free Pyrenean mountain forests into fire-prone ecosystems. *Science of the Total Environment*, 797, 149104.

⁵⁶⁴ Strada, S., Pozzer, A., Giuliani, G., Coppola, E., Solmon, F., Jiang, X., ... & Giorgi, F. (2023). Assessment of isoprene and near-surface ozone sensitivities to water stress over the Euro-Mediterranean region. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 23(20), 13301-13327.

⁵⁶⁵ Querol, X., Pérez, N., Reche, C., Ealo, M., Ripoll, A., Tur, J., ... & Alastuey, A. (2019). African dust and air quality over Spain: is it only dust that matters?. *Science of the total environment*, 686, 737-752.

⁵⁶⁶ Salvador, P., Pey, J., Pérez, N., Querol, X., & Artíñano, B. (2022). Increasing atmospheric dust transport towards the western Mediterranean over 1948–2020. *NPJ Climate and Atmospheric Science*, 5(1), 34.

⁵⁶⁷ Salvador, P., Pey, J., Pérez, N., Alastuey, A., Querol, X., & Artíñano, B. (2024). Estimating the probability of occurrence of African dust outbreaks over regions of the western Mediterranean basin from thermodynamic atmospheric parameters. *Science of the Total Environment*, 922, 171307.

⁵⁶⁸ Gimeno, L., Nieto, R., Vázquez, M., & Lavers, D. A. (2014). Atmospheric rivers: A mini-review. *Frontiers in Earth Science*, 2, 2.

⁵⁶⁹ Francis, D., Fonseca, R., Nelli, N., Bozkurt, D., Picard, G., & Guan, B. (2022). Atmospheric rivers drive exceptional Saharan dust transport towards Europe. *Atmospheric Research*, 266, 105959.

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circulations ⁵⁷⁰. It has been shown that an important part of the tropospheric O₃ in the Iberian Peninsula is due to regional transport from other European regions during the maximum summer events ⁵⁷¹. Moreover, it is common in the Mediterranean basin for higher surface tropospheric O₃ concentrations to be recorded in rural areas than in urban areas because tropospheric O₃ levels are higher downwind of its precursor sources at distances of hundreds or even thousands of kilometres ⁵⁷². Another consequence of tropospheric O₃ episodes is its linked with high levels of particles ⁵⁷³, ⁵⁷⁴, especially ultra-fine particles (PM_{2.5}). In fact, particular meteorological conditions, such as thermal inversions typical of mountain valleys, can hinder the dilution and transport of pollutants emitted locally by the various anthropogenic sources, often even from transnational sources ⁵⁷⁵, significantly increasing the vulnerability of some local populations to atmospheric pollution due to increased exposure.

From the literature reviewed in this chapter, it can be assumed that CC negatively affects air quality in terms of tropospheric O₃ and PM_x, even in the absence of changes in precursor emissions from anthropogenic activities. This penalty has important implications at the human health level, but its quantification involves complex meteorological, chemical and biological processes and feedback whose operation is very complex and difficult to quantify ⁵⁷⁶.

⁵⁷⁰ Li, S., Gilbert, L., Vanwambeke, S. O., Yu, J., Purse, B. V., & Harrison, P. A. (2019). Lyme disease risks in Europe under multiple uncertain drivers of change. *Environmental health perspectives*, 127(6), 067010.

⁵⁷¹ Pay, M. T., Gangoiti, G., Guevara, M., Napelenok, S., Querol, X., Jorba, O., & Pérez García-Pando, C. (2019). Ozone source apportionment during peak summer events over southwestern Europe. *Atmospheric chemistry and physics*, 19(8), 5467-5494.

⁵⁷² Vivanco, M. G., Garrido, J. L., Martín, F., Theobald, M. R., Gil, V., Santiago, J. L., ... & Bailador, A. (2021). Assessment of the effects of the spanish national air pollution control programme on air quality. *Atmosphere*, 12(2), 158.

⁵⁷³ Carnerero, C., Pérez, N., Petäjä, T., Laurila, T. M., Ahonen, L. R., Kontkanen, J., ... & Querol, X. (2019). Relating high ozone, ultrafine particles, and new particle formation episodes using cluster analysis. *Atmospheric Environment: X*, 4, 100051.

⁵⁷⁴ Carnerero, C., Rivas, I., Reche, C., Pérez, N., Alastuey, A., & Querol, X. (2021). Trends in primary and secondary particle number concentrations in urban and regional environments in NE Spain. *Atmospheric Environment*, 244, 117982.

⁵⁷⁵ Garatachea, R., Pay, M. T., Achebak, H., Jorba, O., Bowdalo, D., Guevara, M., ... & Pérez García-Pando, C. (2024). National and transboundary contributions to surface ozone concentration across European countries. *Communications Earth & Environment*, 5(1), 588.

⁵⁷⁶ Fu, T.-M. and Tian, H. (2019) Climate Change Penalty to Ozone Air Quality: Review of Current Understandings and Knowledge Gaps. *Curr. Pollut. Reports* 2019 53 5, 159–171. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S40726-019-00115-6>

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Figure 11: Correlations between O₃ and PM10 concentrations and key weather variables determining its concentration. Source: Jacob and Winner, 2009 ⁽⁵⁷⁷⁾

Variable	Ozone	PM
Temperature	++	-
Regional stagnation	++	++
Wind speed	-	-
Mixing depth	=	--
Humidity	=	+
Cloud cover	-	-
Precipitation	=	--

Observed impacts

Although emissions of air pollutants have decreased in Europe in recent decades, exposure to air pollution is considered the most important environmental risk to human health of the European population ⁵⁷⁸. According to WHO ⁵⁷⁹ the most relevant air pollutants in terms of harm to human health are particulate matter (PM), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and tropospheric ozone (O₃). Exposure to air pollutants causes a large number of diseases, such as lung disease, strokes, tracheal, bronchial and lung cancers, aggravated asthma and respiratory infections and rhinitis. Although air pollution affects the entire population, some groups are more likely to suffer from it such as children, the elderly, pregnant women and people with pre-existing health problems ⁵⁸⁰. According to data from the European Environment Agency ⁵⁸¹, in 2019 alone, approximately 307.000 premature deaths attributable to long-term exposure to particulate matter with a diameter of 2.5 µm or less (PM_{2.5}), 40.400 premature deaths attributable to exposure to nitrogen dioxide (NO₂) and 16.800 premature deaths attributable to exposure to tropospheric ozone (O₃) were counted in Europe, coinciding

⁵⁷⁷ Jacob, D. J., & Winner, D. A. (2009). Effect of climate change on air quality. *Atmospheric environment*, 43(1), 51-63.

⁵⁷⁸ EEA, 2024: Report 01/2024, European Climate Risk Assessment

⁵⁷⁹ <https://iris.who.int/bitstream/handle/10665/255336/9789241565486-eng.pdf>

⁵⁸⁰ EEA, 2016: Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2016 An indicator-based report

⁵⁸¹ EEA (2021) Health impacts of air pollution in Europe, 2021

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in order of magnitude with recent studies on the topic ^{582, 583, 584} that corroborate comparable order of magnitude statistics. In recent years, the proportion of the European population exposed to air pollutant concentrations above EU limit values, and the consequent health impact, has decreased for PM_{2.5} and NO₂.

However, regarding tropospheric ozone, its concentration in the Mediterranean basin is increasing, even though global maximum values are decreasing ^{585, 586}. While emissions of primary pollutants (many of them precursors of tropospheric ozone such as NO_x and Volatile Organic Compounds), have been considerably reduced at the European level, tropospheric O₃ concentrations have slightly increased or at least have presented a large interannual variability not linear with the evolution of its main anthropogenic, NO_x from hydrocarbon combustion and industrial activity (figure 12).

⁵⁸² Viegi, G., Baldacci, S., Maio, S., Fasola, S., Annesi-Maesano, I., Pistelli, F., ... & Forastiere, F. (2020). Health effects of air pollution: a Southern European perspective. *Chinese medical journal*, 133(13), 1568-1574.

⁵⁸³ Juginović, A., Vuković, M., Aranza, I., & Biloš, V. (2021). Health impacts of air pollution exposure from 1990 to 2019 in 43 European countries. *Scientific Reports*, 11(1), 22516.

⁵⁸⁴ Khomenko, S., Cirach, M., Pereira-Barboza, E., Mueller, N., Barrera-Gómez, J., Rojas-Rueda, D., ... & Nieuwenhuijsen, M. (2021). Premature mortality due to air pollution in European cities: a health impact assessment. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 5(3), e121-e134.

⁵⁸⁵ Orru, H., Åström, C., Andersson, C., Tamm, T., Ebi, K. L., & Forsberg, B. (2019). Ozone and heat-related mortality in Europe in 2050 significantly affected by changes in climate, population and greenhouse gas emission. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(7), 074013.

⁵⁸⁶ EEA (2021) Health impacts of air pollution in Europe, 2021

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Figure 12: evolution of NO_x (a), PM_{2.5} (b), PM₁₀(c) and tropospheric O₃ (d) concentrations from 2012 to 2023 in the EU27. Source: EEA, 2024 ⁵⁸⁷

Analyzing the evolution of the indicators of cumulative exposure to O₃ (the SOMO₃₅ for humans) in the Iberian Peninsula, it is clear that the improvement in air quality (and, therefore, the consequent decrease in risk to humans) is extremely slow, much slower than the decrease in atmospheric emissions of its precursors. At the measurement stations closest to the southern slopes of the Pyrenees, Masagué et al ⁵⁸⁸ confirm an upward trend in this indicator equivalent to +73 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$ in the period between 2015 and 2019.

Figure 13: (a, b) Present-day SOMO₃₅ concentrations ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}$) for 2015-2019 from the 364 stations with valid data. (a) Spatial variation. (b) Box-plot by station type. Upper numbers--number of stations of each type. (c, d) Statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) trends in SOMO₃₅ (2008-2019) ($\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}\cdot\text{year}^{-1}$) from the 303 stations with valid data. (c) Spatial variation of the trends. (d) Annual variation by station type. Circles--trends from individual stations; black squares--averages; black lines--standard deviations. Upper numbers (top to bottom)--number of stations; trends; percentage of stations recording upward/downward trends. (e-h) Same captions as for (a-d), respectively, but for the percentile 93.2 of the daily maximum 8-hour average (MDA8), P93.2. (b, f) Horizontal lines in SOMO₃₅ and P93.2 --critical level of 6,000 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}\cdot\text{day}$ (Ellingsen et al., 2008); the Directive's Target Value (120 $\mu\text{g}\cdot\text{m}^{-3}$). Abbreviations for stations are: UT/UI/UB--urban

⁵⁸⁷ <https://www.eea.europa.eu/data-and-maps/data/external/air-quality-e-reporting>

⁵⁸⁸ Masagué, J., Escudero, M., Alastuey, A., Mantilla, E., Monfort, E., Gangoiti, G., ... & Querol, X. (2023). Spatiotemporal variations of tropospheric ozone in Spain (2008–2019). *Environment international*, 176, 107961.

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(traffic/industrial/background); ST/SI/SB--suburban (traffic/industrial/background); and RB/RI/RBREM--rural (background/industrial/regional background). Source: Masagué et al., 2023 ⁵⁸⁹.

Box 2: heat waves and atmospheric pollution in the autonomous community of Navarre

Heatwaves and air pollution are closely linked, with each factor amplifying the negative effects of the other, creating a hazardous environment for human health. The Autonomous Community of Navarra, through an integrated LIFE project called LIFE NADAPTA, has carried out a study to assess the impact of air pollution and the increase in ambient temperature on the population's health. Partly thanks to this project, Navarre incorporated the Spanish Ministry's Framework Plan for short-term action in case of ambient air pollution episodes. Among other elements, the new plan arising from this transposition sets the threshold values and actions for all the Administrations in this territory, so that both the administrations and the population have official information on the exceeding of the pollution thresholds contemplated in this Framework Plan and on what actions should be implemented at each of the levels of action, regardless of the geographical area in which they are located.

CÓMO AFECTA LA CONTAMINACIÓN DEL AIRE A LA SALUD

Irritación ocular y de las vías respiratorias (molestias en nariz y garganta, tos, picor de ojos, etc.).

Mayor riesgo de enfermedades cardíacas y respiratorias, así como algunos tipos de cánceres.

Dificultad respiratoria, sobre todo con el esfuerzo físico.

Palpitaciones, opresión en el pecho, fatiga.

GRUPOS DE POBLACIÓN MÁS SENSIBLES

- Personas con enfermedades crónicas. Especialmente trastornos respiratorios crónicos (EPOC, asma), enfermedades cardiovasculares y/o diabetes.
- Niños y niñas
- Personas mayores
- Mujeres embarazadas

ADEMÁS, AUMENTA EL RIESGO

- Si esfuerzo físico intenso (ejercicio, trabajo al aire libre).
- El vivir en zonas urbanas especialmente contaminadas.
- En situaciones de exclusión social.

LIFE NADAPTA

Gobierno de Navarra Nafarroako Gobernua

ACORDA 2030

⁵⁸⁹ Massagué, J., Escudero, M., Alastuey, A., Mantilla, E., Monfort, E., Gangoiti, G., ... & Querol, X. (2023). Spatiotemporal variations of tropospheric ozone in Spain (2008–2019). *Environment international*, 176, 107961.

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During the summer of 2024, this Plan has been integrated into the region's High Temperature Plan, due to the fact that high temperatures have a direct impact on the concentration and dispersion of certain pollutants such as, for example, contributing to the formation of ozone or increasing the concentration of suspended particles, due to the fact that heat waves usually bring with them an increase in the risk of fires, one of the natural causes of PM formation. In addition, the second action programme of this plan includes the integration of air pollution into the information system on extreme temperatures in order to consider the synergic effect of extreme temperatures and air quality on the health of the population of Navarre.

The same phenomenon has been observed throughout the Mediterranean basin. Several studies suggest that CC may be contributing significantly to the increase in population exposure to tropospheric O₃ over the last decades ^{590, 591, 592, 593}.

⁵⁹⁰ Andersson, C., Langner, J., & Bergstroumm, R. (2007). Interannual variation and trends in air pollution over Europe due to climate variability during 1958–2001 simulated with a regional CTM coupled to the ERA40 reanalysis. *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology*, 59(1), 77-98.

⁵⁹¹ Ellingsen, K., Gauss, M., Van Dingenen, R., Dentener, F. J., Emberson, L., Fiore, A. M., ... & Wild, O. (2008). Global ozone and air quality: a multi-model assessment of risks to human health and crops. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics Discussions*, 8(1), 2163-2223.

⁵⁹² Hedegaard, G. B., Brandt, J., Christensen, J. H., Frohn, L. M., Geels, C., Hansen, K. M., & Stendel, M. (2008). Impacts of climate change on air pollution levels in the Northern Hemisphere with special focus on Europe and the Arctic. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 8(12), 3337-3367.

⁵⁹³ Colette, A., Granier, C., Hodnebrog, Ø., Jakobs, H., Maurizi, A., Nyiri, A., ... & Vrac, M. (2012). Future air quality in Europe: a multi-model assessment of projected exposure to ozone. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 12(21), 10613-10630.

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Figure 14: estimated increase in tropospheric O₃ concentration in Europe attributed to natural climate variability and CC for the period 1958-2001 (left) and 1978-2001 (right). Source: EEA 2012 ⁽⁵⁹⁴⁾

In this sense, there is a study that found greater potential health impacts from O₃ exposure associated with forest fires than from PM_{2.5}. Since the relative risk of O₃ exposure is actually lower than that of PM_{2.5} exposure. The reason is attributed to the more widespread impact of wildfires on O₃ due to a longer atmospheric lifetime of O₃ (about 280 months) in contrast to PM_{2.5} (days to weeks) ⁽⁵⁹⁵⁾.

Expected impacts:

Despite efforts to reduce major air pollutants at European level, CC is already influencing ozone concentrations due to changes in meteorological conditions, increased methane concentration, as well as increased emissions of specific ozone precursors (e.g. Increased isoprene from vegetation under higher temperatures and/or

⁵⁹⁴ EEA Report No 12/2012. Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2012. An indicator-based report

⁵⁹⁵ Tian, C., Yue, X., Zhu, J., Liao, H., Yang, Y., Chen, L., ... & Cao, Y. (2023). Projections of fire emissions and the consequent impacts on air quality under 1.5° C and 2° C global warming. *Environmental Pollution*, 323, 121311.

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emissions) from forest fires ⁵⁹⁶). According to an specific study on mortality and hospital admissions associated with future trends in tropospheric O₃ concentrations in Europe, the value of the SOMO₃₅ indicator could increase by 2000±500 µg·m⁻³·day⁻¹ in the period 2041-2060 compared to the average of the 1961-1990 reference period in the Pyrenees mountain range area. There is, however, some regional variability in the projections, depending on which global climate model it is used (ECHAM4 or HadCM3) and CO₂ emission scenario (A2 or A1B) is assumed.

Figure 15: Change in the sum of SOMO₃₅ (ozone daily 8-h maximum means .35 ppb(volume) values in the calendar year) due to CC-induced ozone exposure variations considering the A2 scenario. MATCH: model of atmospheric transport and chemistry. Source: from Orru et al., 2019 ⁵⁹⁷.

In fact, the same study concludes that respiratory hospital admissions and associated excess mortality could increase considerably in Europe compared to current values, although with considerable spatial variability between areas. On a large scale, Orru et al ⁵⁹⁸ suggests that there would be an increase in ozone-related mortality in southern Europe, and central Europe and a slight decrease in northern Europe. For the area corresponding to the transboundary Pyrenean territory, according to the HadCM3 model and using the A2 emissions scenario, deaths associated with O₃ exposure could

⁵⁹⁶ Tian, C., Yue, X., Zhu, J., Liao, H., Yang, Y., Chen, L., ... & Cao, Y. (2023). Projections of fire emissions and the consequent impacts on air quality under 1.5° C and 2° C global warming. *Environmental Pollution*, 323, 121311.

⁵⁹⁷ Orru, H., Åström, C., Andersson, C., Tamm, T., Ebi, K. L., & Forsberg, B. (2019). Ozone and heat-related mortality in Europe in 2050 significantly affected by changes in climate, population and greenhouse gas emission. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(7), 074013.

⁵⁹⁸ Orru, H., Åström, C., Andersson, C., Tamm, T., Ebi, K. L., & Forsberg, B. (2019). Ozone and heat-related mortality in Europe in 2050 significantly affected by changes in climate, population and greenhouse gas emission. *Environmental Research Letters*, 14(7), 074013.

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experience a certain decrease in the central Pyrenees (between 0 and + 0.025% compared to the 1990-2009 reference period). However, there would be a proportionally larger increase in the western and eastern Pyrenees, somewhat more marked in the southern than in the northern Pyrenees (between +0.1 and 0.2% compared to the 1990-2009 reference period). Some authors claim that this penalty effect of CC on atmospheric pollution (mainly O₃ and PM secondary pollutants) could even cancel out the beneficial effects on human health of reducing emissions of major precursors over the course of this century ^{599, 600, 601}

For particulate matter (PM_x), several studies agree that air particle concentrations are expected to increase slightly in the future ^{602, 603}. One of the main causes seems to be that CC could further alter the behaviour of key meteorological variables in the production of the precursors of the secondary fraction of particulate matter. Another key factor could be linked to the increased frequency and intensity of forest fires in the coming decades. While this phenomenon has so far not been a particularly serious public health problem in the Pyrenees compared to the rest of the Mediterranean basin, it could become so in the coming decades ^{604, 605}. According to Bento et al ⁶⁰⁶, under the most pessimistic change scenarios, the southern slopes of the Pyrenees

⁵⁹⁹ Fortems-Cheiney, A., Foret, G., Siour, G., Vautard, R., Szopa, S., Dufour, G., ... & Beekmann, M. (2017). A 3° C global RCP8.5 emission trajectory cancels benefits of European emission reductions on air quality. *Nature Communications*, 8(1), 89.

⁶⁰⁰ Park, S. et al. (2020) A likely increase in fine particulate matter and premature mortality under future climate change. *Air Qual. Atmos. Heal.* 2020 132 13, 143–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11869-019-00785-7>

⁶⁰¹ Zanis, P., Akritidis, D., Turnock, S., Naik, V., Szopa, S., Georgoulas, A. K., ... & van Noije, T. (2022). Climate change penalty and benefit on surface ozone: a global perspective based on CMIP6 earth system models. *Environmental Research Letters*, 17(2), 024014.

⁶⁰² Pienkosz, B. D., Saari, R. K., Monier, E., & Garcia-Menendez, F. (2019). Natural variability in projections of climate change impacts on fine particulate matter pollution. *Earth's Future*, 7(7), 762-770.

⁶⁰³ Park, S. et al. (2020) A likely increase in fine particulate matter and premature mortality under future climate change. *Air Qual. Atmos. Heal.* 2020 132 13, 143–151. <https://doi.org/10.1007/S11869-019-00785-7>

⁶⁰⁴ de Dios, V. R., Hedou, J., Camprubí, À. C., Thapa, P., Del Castillo, E. M., de Aragón, J. M., ... & Boer, M. M. (2021). Climate change induced declines in fuel moisture may turn currently fire-free Pyrenean mountain forests into fire-prone ecosystems. *Science of the Total Environment*, 797, 149104.

⁶⁰⁵ Pimont, F., Ruffault, J., Opitz, T., Fargeon, H., Barbero, R., Castel-Clavera, J., ... & Dupuy, J. L. (2022). Future expansion, seasonal lengthening and intensification of fire activity under climate change in southeastern France. *International journal of wildland fire*, 32(1), 4-14.

⁶⁰⁶ Bento, V. A., Lima, D. C., Santos, L. C., Lima, M. M., Russo, A., Nunes, S. A., ... & Soares, P. M. (2023). The future of extreme meteorological fire danger under climate change scenarios for Iberia. *Weather and Climate Extremes*, 42, 100623.

could experience an increase of more than 100 % of days with extreme fire danger in 2071 compared to the average of the reference period 1971-2000.

2.3.1 Pollen and allergies

Aeroallergens, such as pollen and fungal spores, are the two main allergic conditions associated with allergic rhinitis and asthma⁶⁰⁷. Pollen proteins can exacerbate allergic rhinoconjunctivitis (pollinosis) and allergic asthma by acting as antigens for the immune system. The impacts of CC on respiratory allergic diseases through pollen and fungal spores could be one of the main indirect effects of CC on public health. Rising global temperatures are extending the growing season of many plants, leading to earlier blooming in spring and delayed die-off in fall. As a result, the pollen season lasts longer, increasing exposure time for allergy sufferers⁶⁰⁸. At the same time, plants are beginning to release pollen earlier in the year⁶⁰⁹. For example, trees like birch and alder can start pollinating weeks earlier than usual, affecting individuals sensitive to tree pollen⁶¹⁰. Beside this, CC can increase pollen production⁶¹¹. Higher CO₂ Levels enhance plant growth and increase pollen production. Plants like ragweed, a common allergen, produce more pollen when exposed to higher CO₂ concentrations^{612,613}. In addition, CC may also be influencing the allergy-generating capacity of the main pollen types since the increased CO₂ not only boosts the quantity of pollen but also enhances its allergenic potential by increasing the amount of allergenic proteins of the pollen

⁶⁰⁷ Averbeck M, Gebhardt C, Emmrich F et al (2007) Immunologic principles of allergic disease. *J Dtsch Dermatol Ges* 5:1015–1028 Barber D, de la Torre F, Feo F et al (2008)

⁶⁰⁸ Dirr, L., Bastl, K., Bastl, M., Berger, M., & Berger, U. E. (2023). Prolonging the period of allergenic burden: late-flowering grasses and local peculiarities. *Allergo Journal International*, 32(6), 157-161.

⁶⁰⁹ Damialis, A., Fotiou, C., Halley, J. M., & Vokou, D. (2011). Effects of environmental factors on pollen production in anemophilous woody species. *Trees*, 25, 253-264.

⁶¹⁰ Biedermann, T., Winther, L., Till, S. J., Panzner, P., Knulst, A., & Valovirta, E. (2019). Birch pollen allergy in Europe. *Allergy*, 74(7), 1237-1248.

⁶¹¹ Mousavi, F., Oteros, J., Shahali, Y., & Carinanos, P. (2024). Impacts of climate change on allergenic pollen production: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Agricultural and Forest Meteorology*, 349, 109948.

⁶¹² Hamaoui-Laguel, L., Vautard, R., Liu, L. I., Solmon, F., Viovy, N., Khvorostyanov, D., ... & Epstein, M. M. (2015). Effects of climate change and seed dispersal on airborne ragweed pollen loads in Europe. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(8), 766-771.

⁶¹³ Rauer, D., Gilles, S., Wimmer, M., Frank, U., Mueller, C., Musiol, S., ... & Alessandrini, F. (2021). Ragweed plants grown under elevated CO₂ levels produce pollen which elicit stronger allergic lung inflammation. *Allergy*, 76(6), 1718-1730.

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⁶¹⁴, ⁶¹⁵. Pollen grains can become more potent, meaning each grain contains higher levels of allergens, intensifying allergic reactions. Beside this, CC is causing shifts in plant distribution, with some species moving to new areas where they previously did not thrive. This means people may be exposed to new types of pollen they haven't encountered before, increasing the likelihood of developing allergies. At the same time, Plants like ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) well known for its highly allergenic pollen, are progressively expanding their area of distribution in the Pyrenees expanding into new areas ⁶¹⁶, ⁶¹⁷, increasing the risk of seasonal allergies in populations that were not previously affected. In addition, during dry periods, plants release more pollen as a stress response that in synergy with air pollution can exacerbate respiratory symptoms, making allergies worse.

Figure 16: Monthly current (baseline) and future (2041-2060) ragweed pollen counts (grains per cubic meter) across Europe. Data are the average of the CHIMERE and WRF/RegCM model suites for RCP4.5 and a reference plant invasion scenario. © EuroGeographics for the administrative boundaries. Source: Lake et al., 2017 ⁶¹⁸

⁶¹⁴ Zhao F, Elkelish A, Durner J et al (2016) Common ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.): allergenicity and molecular characterization of pollen after plant exposure to elevated NO₂. *Plant Cell Environ* 39:147–164

⁶¹⁵ Zhao F, Durner J, Winkler JB et al (2017) Pollen of common ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.): illumina-based de novo sequencing and differential transcript expression upon elevated NO₂/O₃. *Environ Pollut* 224:503–514

⁶¹⁶ Cunze, S., Leiblein, M. C., & Tackenberg, O. (2013). Range expansion of *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* in Europe is promoted by climate change. *International Scholarly Research Notices*, 2013(1), 610126.

⁶¹⁷ Hamaoui-Laguel, L., Vautard, R., Liu, L. I., Solmon, F., Viovy, N., Khvorostyanov, D., ... & Epstein, M. M. (2015). Effects of climate change and seed dispersal on airborne ragweed pollen loads in Europe. *Nature Climate Change*, 5(8), 766-771.

⁶¹⁸ Lake, I. R., Jones, N. R., Agnew, M., Goodess, C. M., Giorgi, F., Hamaoui-Laguel, L., ... & Epstein, M. M. (2017). Climate change and future pollen allergy in Europe. *Environmental health perspectives*, 125(3), 385-391.

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Longer and more intense pollen seasons, combined with higher pollen counts, can lead to worse symptoms for allergy sufferers, including sneezing, runny nose, itchy eyes, and exacerbated asthma. With more exposure to potent pollen, there is an increased risk of developing asthma, particularly in children. People with asthma may experience more severe and frequent attacks during high pollen days.

Observed impacts:

In the Pyrenees, in the last fifty years, the average annual air temperature has increased by +0.1,9 °C/decade, and the local warming has been slightly higher than the one on a global scale ⁶¹⁹. Hence, warmer temperatures and altered precipitation patterns are leading to longer and more intense pollen seasons, higher pollen concentrations, and increased allergenicity ⁶²⁰. These changes are contributing to a rise in respiratory allergies and impacting the health and quality of life for local residents and tourists. Monitoring these trends is crucial for developing effective adaptation strategies to mitigate the health impacts of CC in the region.

In a study evaluating the correlation between pollen concentrations and different meteorological variables at 6 measuring stations in Catalonia, 2 of them in the Catalan pre-Pyrenees, the trend of the 22 main allergenic species common in the rest of the mountain range was analyzed. In this study, in which data from 1996 to 2011 were analyzed, statistically significant correlations were recorded between the variations of the main allergenic species pollen concentration with precipitation (negative), insolation (positive) and temperature (positive). Temperature was the meteorological variable that showed a greater influence in the pollen production and the timing of the pollen season, being insolation the least one. The Start of the Main Pollen Season was the pollen parameter more correlated with the meteorological variables, especially with winter temperatures (Husam et al., 2018).

According to ⁶²¹, the onset date of the clinically relevant pollen season for public health has been considerably advanced for both olive and birch pollen in the Pyrenees.

⁶¹⁹ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos ISBN: 978-84-09-06268-3

⁶²⁰ Alarcón, M., del Carmen Casas-Castillo, M., Rodríguez-Solà, R., Periago, C., & Belmonte, J. (2024). Projections of the start of the airborne pollen season in Barcelona (NE Iberian Peninsula) over the 21st century. *Science of the total environment*, 173363.

⁶²¹ van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

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Specifically, birch has anticipated the onset of the pollen season by 20 ± 5 days (in the decade 2011-2020 with respect to the average of the decade 1981-1990) in the whole cross-border Pyrenean area except in the central Aragonese Pyrenees, where no statistically significant trends have been detected. Regarding olive trees, the advance of the pollen season for the Pyrenees as a whole was 15 ± 5 days (in the decade 2011-2020 with respect to the average of the decade 1981-1990), except for the Atlantic Pyrenees of both slopes, where no statistically significant difference was found between the two periods analyzed.

Figure 17: Difference of decadal medians (days) in the start of clinically relevant pollen seasons in Europe Change of decadal medians in start of clinically relevant pollen season (days) for (A) birch and (B) olive in Europe at NUTS level 2, comparing 2011–20 with 1981–90. Dot-shaded areas have statistically insignificant trends (p value >0.1). White areas (without shade) had clinically relevant seasons that occurred less than 5 times between 1981 and 1990 or 2011 and 2020. Source: van Daalen et al., 2024⁽⁶²²⁾.

Expected impacts:

The Pyrenees are expected to face significant impacts from CC on pollen and allergies, with longer and more intense pollen seasons, higher pollen concentrations, and increased allergenic potency. These changes pose a growing public health challenge, particularly for individuals with respiratory conditions. Monitoring, public awareness, and adaptive strategies will be crucial to mitigate the effects and protect the health and well-being of both residents and visitors to the region.

⁶²² van Daalen, K. R., Romanello, M., Rocklöv, J., Semenza, J. C., Tonne, C., Markandya, A., ... & Lowe, R. (2022). The 2022 Europe report of the Lancet Countdown on health and climate change: towards a climate resilient future. *The Lancet Public Health*, 7(11), e942-e965.

2.4 Mountain gravitational hazards (landslides, avalanches, rock fall and other gravitational hazards).

Climate warming is changing the magnitude, timing, and spatial patterns of mountain snowpacks and precipitation. The warmer atmosphere is leading to precipitation phase shifts, with decreased snowfall fraction ⁶²³. The combination of snowfall fraction and snowpack decrease directly affects the frequency and intensity of rain-on-snow events, which is a common cause of flash-flood events and slope instability in snow dominated regions. The sudden saturation of soil during these events triggers landslides, especially on steep and unstable slopes with permafrost (^{624,625}). Although at present the presence of permafrost in the Pyrenees is not very important in extension ⁶²⁶, seasonal permafrost is degrading, destabilizing rocky slopes and increasing the likelihood of rockfalls and landslides particularly increasing the exposure of mountaineers and climbers to such risk ⁶²⁷. On the other hand, CC also affects snow dynamics and, as a consequence, avalanche behavior. Indeed, warmer winter temperatures are increasing the occurrence of freeze-thaw cycles, leading to the formation of unstable snowpacks. This instability can result in more frequent and dangerous avalanches, particularly in high-altitude areas popular for winter sports and sky resorts related infrastructures ⁶²⁸.

Increased geological instability, increased mass movements, debris flows and avalanches of different types can lead to the destabilization of the foundations of high mountain tourist infrastructures (e.g. cable cars, hotels and restaurants) as well as result in a direct threat to tourists carrying out their activities in high altitude environments

⁶²³ Bonsoms, J., López-Moreno, J. I., Alonso-González, E., Deschamps-Berger, C., & Oliva, M. (2023). Rain-on-snow response to a warmer Pyrenees. *EGU sphere*, 2023, 1-29.

⁶²⁴ Rennert, K. J., Roe, G., Putkonen, J., and Bitz, C. M.: Soil thermal and ecological impacts of rain on snow 800 events in the circumpolar arctic, *J Clim*, 22, 2302–2315, <https://doi.org/10.1175/2008JCLI2117.1>, 2009.

⁶²⁵ Westermann, S., Boike, J., Langer, M., Schuler, T. v., and Etzelmüller, B.: Modeling the impact of wintertime rain events on the thermal regime of permafrost, *Cryosphere*, 5, 945–959, <https://doi.org/10.5194/tc-5-945-2011>, 2011.

⁶²⁶ Serrano, E., Morales, C., González-Trueba, J., & Martín, R. (2009). Cartografía del permafrost de montaña en los Pirineos españoles. *Finisterra*, 44(87).

⁶²⁷ Rico, I., Magnin, F., Lopez Moreno, J. I., Serrano, E., Alonso-González, E., Revuelto, J., ... & Gómez-Lende, M. (2021). First evidence of rock wall permafrost in the Pyrenees (Vignemale peak, 3,298 m asl, 42° 46' 16 "N/0° 08' 33 "W). *Permafrost and Periglacial Processes*, 32(4), 673-680.

⁶²⁸ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos ISBN: 978-84-09-06268-3

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⁶²⁹. The existing danger is heightened by the expansion of settlements and new tourist infrastructures in areas already at risk, which will become even more unstable due to CC.

However, the correlation between gravitational events and CC is complex and influenced by a multitude of factors such as land use changes, making it extremely difficult to associate certain trends with climate alone.

Observed and expected impacts.

At the scale of the Pyrenees, climatic and geomorphological conditions have been analyzed to explain the occurrence of landslides ⁶³⁰, but little has been done to date on the question of the future evolution of these phenomena in relation to CC. Rodríguez et al ⁶³¹ studied the effect of CC on slope stability in the Catalan Pyrenees during the century. The results of the study show that for the period 2041-2070 there could be an increase in instability events and a decrease in return periods for the three types of soils considered in the numerical modelling.

On the other hand, the risk of wildfires, due to higher average temperatures and more frequent extreme events, could result in an increase in gravity-controlled processes such as erosion, debris flows and landslides. In addition, rising temperatures and changing groundwater flows could also destabilize soils. In the Pyrenees, the increase in landslides is associated with torrential rains and the degradation of vegetation during infrastructure construction, or the replacement of native vegetation by less well-rooted vegetation ⁶³². Another study suggests that changes in land use projected for the coming decades could have a beneficial effect on the frequency and intensity of

⁶²⁹ Eckert, N., Corona, C., Giacona, F., Gaume, J., Mayer, S., van Herwijnen, A., ... & Stoffel, M. (2024). Climate change impacts on snow avalanche activity and related risks. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 1-21.

⁶³⁰ Beguería, S., & Lorente, A. (2002). Landslide hazard mapping by multivariate statistics: comparison of methods and case study in the Spanish Pyrenees.

⁶³¹ Rodríguez, S., Puig i Polo, C., Lloret Morancho, A., Vaunat, J., & Hurlimann Ziegler, M. (2021). Effect of climate change on slope stability: a numerical analysis using predictions of the Catalan Pyrenees. In *International Society for Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering Online Library: 13th International Symposium on Landslides (XIII ISL)* (pp. 1-8). International Society for Soil Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering (ISSMGE).

⁶³² Bernardie, S., Vandromme, R., Thiery, Y., Houet, T., Grémont, M., Masson, F., ... & Bouroullec, I. (2021). Modelling landslide hazards under global changes: the case of a Pyrenean valley. *Natural Hazards and Earth System Sciences*, 21(1), 147-169.

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landslides. Specifically, Shu et al. ⁶³³ demonstrated that on the northern slope of the central Pyrenees, the progressive expansion of forested areas driven by changes in land use could considerably improve slope stability, even counteracting the effect of climatic extremes. This is in particular because the process of progressive reforestation, and especially as forests become more mature involves root development which has the capacity to reduce the occurrence of shallow landslides ⁶³⁴, with forests having a particularly significant effect due to their deeper roots. However, there are many uncertainties regarding the beneficial effect that land use changes could have on slope stability.

Avalanches range from small slides that barely affect skiers, to catastrophic phenomena that endanger communities or mountain circulation circuits. Avalanche formation results from complex interactions between terrain, snowpack, and weather conditions, which can lead to dry or wet snow sliding ⁶³⁵. Most avalanche fatalities occurred in uncontrolled territory (mostly recreational accidents); few fatalities are reported in controlled territory (developments and transportation corridors) (EEA, 2017a). In the Catalan Pyrenees, an average of 1 to 2 fatal cases per year has been reported since 1987, evidencing a downward trend that may be the result of the increasing use of basic personal safety equipment for mountain activities (Martin-Vide, 2016).

From 1975 to 2001, 92 people have died in Spain due to avalanches. In the central Aragonese Pyrenees, between the years 1980 and 2000, there have been 42 deaths due to avalanches, approximately half of the deaths registered in Spain due to this phenomenon (Heraldo de Aragón, 2018). In the Pyrenees, the main causes of death because of avalanches are asphyxia (72-75% of cases), severe trauma (19-24% of cases) and the association of hypothermia, hypoxia and hypercapnia or triple H phenomenon (2% of cases) ⁶³⁶. In the Pyrenean Mountain range, wind-plate avalanches predominate: conditions are characterized by the usual presence of dense and compact snow, with thinner snowpack thicknesses compared to other mountainous areas ⁶³⁷. Through dendrogeomorphology studies for avalanche dating and reconstruction, it has

⁶³³ Shu, H., Hürlimann, M., Molowny-Horas, R., González, M., Pinyol, J., Abancó, C., & Ma, J. (2019). Relation between land cover and landslide susceptibility in Val d'Aran, Pyrenees (Spain): Historical aspects, present situation and forward prediction. *Science of the total environment*, 693, 133557.

⁶³⁴ Beguería, S. (2006). Changes in land cover and shallow landslide activity: a case study in the Spanish Pyrenees. *Geomorphology*, 74(1-4), 196-206.

⁶³⁵ EEA, 2016: Climate change, impacts and vulnerability in Europe 2016
An indicator-based report

⁶³⁶ <https://revistaemergencias.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/483-485.pdf>

⁶³⁷ García i Sellés, C. (2017). Variabilidad espacio-temporal de grandes aludes en el Pirineo Oriental según la estructura del manto nivoso y la circulación atmosférica.

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been shown that the winter of 1995-1996 was the most extraordinary in terms of occurrence of large avalanches in the Eastern Pyrenees. A statistical increase of the latter was reported by García-Sellés et al. ⁶³⁸ and especially of wet snow events ⁶³⁹ in the same region. Future evolution will depend on possible changes in the characteristics of the snowpack and its correlation with avalanches. In general, it is assumed that possible changes in avalanche frequency and magnitude are correlated with changes in the snow pack, with a probable reduction of avalanche risks at low and medium altitudes (due to increased winter temperatures), although a higher frequency of heavy precipitation events may counteract this trend ⁶⁴⁰. According to García-Hernández et al. ⁶⁴¹, avalanche episodes in the Pyrenees will probably be less frequent in the future. The determining factors in this evolution is linked to the land marginalization phenomenon, because of the decrease of stocking rate, and grazing focused on flat environments located closer to the villages. This will probably lead to a vegetation colonization process which the last stage is the passive reforestation of formerly grazed areas, generating greater stability in the snow layers and greater protection in case of occurrence of the phenomenon.

According to a recent meta-analysis on the observed evolution and future projections on the impact of CC on avalanches in mountain areas ⁶⁴², in general terms it is likely to observe a decrease in avalanche number, size, seasonality and active paths at low elevations, and an increase in the proportion of wet avalanches relative to dry avalanches. Increased snowfall at high elevations can lead to peaks in avalanche activity and an increase in the number of wet and slush-like avalanches. Activity patterns gradually shift from low to high elevations under continued warming. However, uncertainty about future CC requires active risk management, along with a combination of permanent and temporary protective measures

⁶³⁸ García-Sellés, C., Peña, J. C., Martí, G., Oller, P., & Martínez, P. (2010). WeMOI and NAOi influence on major avalanche activity in the Eastern Pyrenees. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 64(2), 137-145.

⁶³⁹ Oller, P., Muntan, E., García-Sellés, C., Furdada, G., Baeza, C., & Angulo, C. (2015). Characterizing major avalanche episodes in space and time in the twentieth and early twenty-first centuries in the Catalan Pyrenees. *Cold Regions Science and Technology*, 110, 129-148.

⁶⁴⁰<https://www.alpconv.org/en/home/news-publications/publications-multimedia/detail/rsa7-natural-hazard-risk-governance/>

⁶⁴¹ García-Hernández, C., Ruiz-Fernández, J., Sánchez-Posada, C., Pereira, S., Oliva, M., & Vieira, G. (2017). Reforestation and land use change as drivers for a decrease of avalanche damage in mid-latitude mountains (NW Spain). *Global and Planetary Change*, 153, 35-50.

⁶⁴² Eckert, N., Corona, C., Giacona, F., Gaume, J., Mayer, S., van Herwijnen, A., ... & Stoffel, M. (2024). Climate change impacts on snow avalanche activity and related risks. *Nature Reviews Earth & Environment*, 1-21.

3. Indirect impacts of CC in the Pyrenees.

3.1 Vector borne disease

CC is significantly impacting the transmission and spread of vector-borne diseases in the Pyrenees Mountain range. The increase in temperature, changes in precipitation, and altered ecosystems are creating favourable conditions for the proliferation of disease-carrying vectors such as mosquitoes and ticks. CC has been implicated in the observed shift of ticks to elevated altitudes and latitudes, including the *Ixodes ricinus* tick species which is the vector for Lyme borreliosis and tick-borne encephalitis ⁶⁴³. CC has also been a factor in the expansion of other relevant disease vectors in Europe such as *Aedes albopictus* (the Asian tiger mosquito), which transmits diseases like Zika, dengue and chikungunya ^{644, 645, 646}. Also, Phlebotomus sandfly species, which transmits diseases including Leishmaniasis, has been reported to be expanding its distribution area in part because of CC ⁶⁴⁷. Future climate-sensitive impacts on health are challenging to project quantitatively, in part due to the intricate interplay between non-climatic and climatic drivers, weather-sensitive pathogens and climate-change adaptation ⁶⁴⁸. Acting synergically, globalization and international air travel and international transport of goods contribute to pathogen and vector dispersion internationally but the phenomena involved are complex and it can be difficult to isolate climatic factors separately ⁶⁴⁹.

⁶⁴³ Rizzoli, A.; Hauffe, H.C.; Carpi, G.; Vourc'h, G.I.; Neteler, M.; Rosà, R. Lyme borreliosis in Europe. *Eurosurveillance* 2011, 16, 19906.

⁶⁴⁴ Ryan, S. J., Carlson, C. J., Mordecai, E. A., & Johnson, L. R. (2019). Global expansion and redistribution of Aedes-borne virus transmission risk with climate change. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 13(3), e0007213.

⁶⁴⁵ Semenza, J. C., & Paz, S. (2021). Climate change and infectious disease in Europe: Impact, projection and adaptation. *The Lancet Regional Health–Europe*, 9.

⁶⁴⁶ Semenza, J. C., Rocklöv, J., & Ebi, K. L. (2022). Climate change and cascading risks from infectious disease. *Infectious diseases and therapy*, 11(4), 1371-1390.

⁶⁴⁷ Trájer, A. J., Bede-Fazekas, Á., Hufnagel, L., Horváth, L., & Bobvos, J. (2013). The effect of climate change on the potential distribution of the European Phlebotomus species. *Applied Ecology and Environmental Research*, 11(2), 189-208.

⁶⁴⁸ Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

⁶⁴⁹ Semenza, J. C., et al., 2016, 'Determinants and Drivers of Infectious Disease Threat Events in Europe', *Emerging Infectious Diseases* 22(4), pp. 581–589 (DOI: 10.3201/eid2204).

3.1.1 Tick-borne diseases: tick-borne encephalitis (TBE) and Lyme borreliosis (Lyme disease) by *Ixodes Ricinus*.

In the Pyrenees there is no systematic sampling of ticks or the pathogens they transmit, making it impossible to know the risk they pose to the inhabitants and tourists in the Pyrenees. However, like many temperate mountainous regions, are likely to be experiencing shifts in tick populations due to CC, among other factors associated with global changes ⁶⁵⁰. *Ixodes ricinus*, a primary vector for TBE and Lyme borreliosis, is expanding its range to higher altitudes, leading to increased incidences of these diseases. Effective monitoring and adaptation strategies are essential to mitigate the risks posed by this growing public health threat.

Observed and expected impacts:

Increasingly warmer temperatures in the Pyrenees are causing changes in the habitat and distribution of several species of ticks ⁶⁵¹.

On the one hand, the increasingly mild temperatures are extending the geographical range of *Ixodes ricinus*. This tick species prefers humid, temperate climates, and warmer temperatures allow it to survive and reproduce at higher altitudes, previously unsuitable for its survival. The main determinants affecting the spatiotemporal abundance of the different stages are related to humidity and temperature ⁶⁵². For adults and larvae, summer seems to be the most influential period for their abundance, while for nymphs, winter conditions and those of the preceding months seem to be

⁶⁵⁰ Li, S., Gilbert, L., Vanwambeke, S. O., Yu, J., Purse, B. V., & Harrison, P. A. (2019). Lyme disease risks in Europe under multiple uncertain drivers of change. *Environmental health perspectives*, 127(6), 067010.

⁶⁵¹ Wongnak, P., Bord, S., Jacquot, M., Agoulon, A., Beugnet, F., Bournez, L., ... & Chalvet-Monfray, K. (2022). Meteorological and climatic variables predict the phenology of *Ixodes ricinus* nymph activity in France, accounting for habitat heterogeneity. *Scientific Reports*, 12(1), 7833.

⁶⁵² Peralbo-Moreno, A., Espí, A., Barandika, J. F., García-Pérez, A. L., Acevedo, P., & Ruiz-Fons, F. (2024). Spatiotemporal dynamics of *Ixodes ricinus* abundance in northern Spain. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 15(6), 102373.

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determining factors ⁶⁵³. Surveys have detected higher tick abundance in areas where they were historically rare, particularly at higher altitudes where climate conditions have become more favourable ⁶⁵⁴. On the other hand, the decrease in seasonal minimum temperatures could be causing an extension of the tick's activity season ⁶⁵⁵. Traditionally, *Ixodes ricinus* ticks are active during spring and autumn. However, milder winters and longer warm seasons have increased their activity period, resulting in a prolonged risk of tick bites and infection. As a result, In the Pyrenees, ticks are being found at increasingly higher elevations as warmer temperatures and reduced snow cover allow their habitats to extend. Ticks have been reported at altitudes up to 1,500 meters, where they were once rare ⁶⁵⁶. Akl et al. ⁶⁵⁷ analysed the prevalence of pathogens in more than 1900 samples of *Ixodes ricinus* from a peak in the French Pyrenees of Nouvelle-Aquitaine (Pic de Bazès, 1804 m). In this study, *B. burgdorferi* s.l., *Babesia* spp., *Rickettsia* spp. and *Anaplasma phagocytophilum* were detected in *Ixodes ricinus* ticks collected in 2009, 2011, 2013 and 2015. Among the sequenced pathogens, researchers detected in this population of ticks the presence of *Babesia* sp. EU1 and *Rickettsia helvetica*, as well as *Rickettsia monacensis* for the first time in France. In fact, the incidence rate of human Lyme borreliosis in French Pyrenees was found to be between 20 and 59 per 100,000 inhabitants in a study conducted from 2009 to 2012 ⁶⁵⁸.

Secondly, CC could be altering the phenology of these arthropods. Warmer temperatures accelerate the development rate of ticks, speeding up the tick's life cycle,

⁶⁵³ Moreno, A., Espí, A., Barandika, J. F., García-Pérez, A. L., Acevedo, P., & Ruiz-Fons, F. (2024). Spatiotemporal dynamics of *Ixodes ricinus* abundance in northern Spain. *Ticks and Tick-borne Diseases*, 15(6),

⁶⁵⁴ Akl, T., Bourgoïn, G., Souq, M. L., Appolinaire, J., Poirel, M. T., Gibert, P., ... & Zenner, L. (2019). Detection of tick-borne pathogens in questing *Ixodes ricinus* in the French Pyrenees and first identification of *Rickettsia monacensis* in France. *Parasite*, 26.

⁶⁵⁵ Estrada-Peña, A., Ayllón, N., & De La Fuente, J. (2012). Impact of climate trends on tick-borne pathogen transmission. *Frontiers in physiology*, 3, 64.

⁶⁵⁶ Hoch, T., Madouasse, A., Jacquot, M., Wongnak, P., Beugnet, F., Bournez, L., ... & Agoulon, A. (2024). Seasonality of host-seeking *Ixodes ricinus* nymph abundance in relation to climate. *Peer Community Journal*, 4.

⁶⁵⁷ Akl, T., Bourgoïn, G., Souq, M. L., Appolinaire, J., Poirel, M. T., Gibert, P., ... & Zenner, L. (2019). Detection of tick-borne pathogens in questing *Ixodes ricinus* in the French Pyrenees and first identification of *Rickettsia monacensis* in France. *Parasite*, 26.

⁶⁵⁸ Vandenesch A, Turbelin C, Couturier E, Arena C, Jaulhac B, Ferquel E, Choumet V, Saugeon C, Coffinieres E. 2014. Incidence and hospitalisation rates of Lyme borreliosis, France, 2004 to 2012. *Eurosurveillance*, 19, 34.

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leading to faster transitions between larval, nymphal, and adult stages ⁶⁵⁹. This could result in more frequent tick bites and an increased risk of transmitting pathogens ⁶⁶⁰. At the same time, the absence of the limiting factor linked to low temperatures could enhance the reproductive success of *Ixodes ricinus*, potentially increasing tick population densities in affected areas ⁶⁶¹.

Thirdly, CC, together with changes in land use, are at the basis of changes in the hosts availability and behaviour. CC is leading to shifts in distribution of key tick hosts (e.g., rodents, deer and birds) induced by shifts in vegetation in the habitats upon which these animals depend, hence influencing where ticks can find their hosts ⁶⁶². These changes can drive both humans and animals into higher elevations and forested areas for cooler environments, increasing the likelihood of human-tick contact and thus the risk of disease transmission ⁶⁶³.

On the other hand, CC may also influence the prevalence of different tick-borne pathogens. Higher tick densities and longer active seasons increase the potential for ticks to acquire and transmit pathogens such as the *Borrelia burgdorferi* complex (causing Lyme disease) and the TBE virus (causing Tick-Borne Encephalitis). On the other hand, cellular replication rates of the TBE virus in ticks may also be influenced by warmer temperatures, potentially enhancing the virus's capacity to spread among tick populations ⁶⁶⁴.

According to a recent study, TBE cases increased between 2012 and 2020 in Europe, and there was a north-west bound spread in continental Europe.

⁶⁵⁹ Akl, T., Bourgoïn, G., Souq, M. L., Appolinaire, J., Poirel, M. T., Gibert, P., ... & Zenner, L. (2019). Detection of tick-borne pathogens in questing *Ixodes ricinus* in the French Pyrenees and first identification of *Rickettsia monacensis* in France. *Parasite*, 26.

⁶⁶⁰ Estrada-Peña, A., Ayllón, N., & De La Fuente, J. (2012). Impact of climate trends on tick-borne pathogen transmission. *Frontiers in physiology*, 3, 64.

⁶⁶¹ Semenza, J. C., & Paz, S. (2021). Climate change and infectious disease in Europe: Impact, projection and adaptation. *The Lancet Regional Health–Europe*, 9.

⁶⁶² Rizzoli A, Tagliapietra V, Cagnacci F, Marini G, Arnoldi D, Rosso F, Rosa R (2019) Parasites and wildlife in a changing world: The vector-host- pathogen interaction as a learning case. *International Journal for Parasitology-Parasites and Wildlife*, 9, 394-401. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijppaw.2019.05.011>

⁶⁶³ Habib, J., Zenner, L., Garel, M., Mercier, A., Poirel, M. T., Itty, C., ... & Bourgoïn, G. (2024). Prevalence of tick-borne pathogens in ticks collected from the wild mountain ungulates mouflon and chamois in 4 regions of France. *Parasite*, 31.

⁶⁶⁴ Gray JS, Dautel H, Estrada-Peña A, Kahl O, Lindgren E. Effects of climate change on ticks and tick-borne diseases in europe. *Interdiscip Perspect Infect Dis*. 2009;2009:593232. doi: 10.1155/2009/593232. Epub 2009 Jan 4. PMID: 19277106; PMCID: PMC2648658

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Figure 18: Number of autochthonous tick-borne encephalitis cases reported by week for EU/EEA countries with complete reporting, 2012–2020 (n = 24,629). Source: Van Heuverswyn et al., 2023 ⁽⁶⁶⁵⁾

However, according to the few studies on future projections of TBE incidence, the increase in TBE incidence is likely to occur mainly in north-eastern Europe (especially Scandinavia) while in westernmost and Mediterranean Europe including the Pyrenees (especially the southern slopes) it might even decrease.

According to this study, this could be due to the expected increase in arable land to the detriment of forest area, caused by the gradual decrease in crop yields due to CC. However, this dynamic seems to be reversed in the Pyrenees, where the lack of generational replacement is leading to the abandonment of traditional agricultural activities, leading to the natural reforestation of a large part of the cross-border Pyrenean territory ⁶⁶⁶.

⁶⁶⁵ Van Heuverswyn, J., Hallmaier-Wacker, L. K., Beauté, J., Dias, J. G., Haussig, J. M., Busch, K., ... & Gossner, C. M. (2023). Spatiotemporal spread of tick-borne encephalitis in the EU/EEA, 2012 to 2020. *Eurosurveillance*, 28(11), 2200543.

⁶⁶⁶ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos ISBN: 978-84-09-06268-3

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Figure 19: Projected baseline and future Lyme disease risk ranges under SSP1×RCP2.6 and SSP4×RCP4.5 scenarios. The projected distribution of risk indicator, DIN (infected nymphal ticks per ha), at the baseline of 2010 in (A) winter and (B) peak season are classified into five levels: null (DIN=0), negligible (DIN<82), low (82≤DIN<698), moderate (698≤DIN<1,608), and high (DIN≥1,608). Among the six combined scenarios considered, the SSP1×RCP2.6 represents the least risky future in which the low emissions scenario (RCP2.6) is combined with a sustainability socio economic scenario (SSP1). Both the (C) winter low-risk range and (D) peak season high-risk range were projected to likely decrease by the 2050s. The Blue/red colour gradients indicate agreement among projections under different climate models, with darker meaning higher agreement. The patterned blue/red area refers to the baseline projections for comparison. The SSP4×RCP4.5 is the most risky future in which the intermediate emissions scenario (RCP4.5) is combined with an unequal future of increased socioeconomic disparities (SSP4), under which an overall increase and geographical changes in both (E) winter low-risk range and (F) peak season high-risk range by the 2050s were projected. Source: Li et al., 2019 ⁶⁶⁷

⁶⁶⁷ Li, S., Gilbert, L., Vanwambeke, S. O., Yu, J., Purse, B. V., & Harrison, P. A. (2019). Lyme disease risks in Europe under multiple uncertain drivers of change. *Environmental health perspectives*, 127(6), 067010.

3.1.2 Mosquito-borne diseases

CC is increasingly influencing the dynamics of mosquito-borne diseases (MBS) in Europe, including the Pyrenees Mountain range. Rising temperatures, altered precipitation patterns, and changes in land use are creating favourable conditions for mosquitoes and the pathogens they carry ⁶⁶⁸. The Pyrenees bioregion, is now witnessing increased risks from several mosquito-borne diseases, such as West Nile virus (WNV), Dengue and Chikungunya. However, It should be noted that the transmission of vector-borne diseases requires an introduced and/or established vector population, a pathogen and suitable environmental and climatic conditions across the full cycle of vector-borne disease transmission in humans ⁶⁶⁹.

Observed and expected impacts:

Mosquitos habitats are influenced by temperature, humidity and precipitation levels ⁶⁷⁰. Warmer temperatures have allowed mosquitoes, particularly invasive species like *Aedes albopictus* (Asian tiger mosquito) and *Aedes aegypti* (yellow fever mosquito), to expand their range into new areas, including the Pyrenees ⁶⁷¹. These species are primary vectors for diseases like Dengue, Chikungunya, and Zika virus ^{672, 673}.

CC seems to be contributing to the extension of the activity season of these vectors, due to milder winters and longer summers ⁶⁷⁴. On the other hand, the warmer temperatures are leading to an altitude shift of its distribution: traditionally, colder

⁶⁶⁸ Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

⁶⁶⁹ Randolph SE, Rogers DJ. The arrival, establishment and spread of exotic diseases: patterns and predictions. *Nat Rev Microbiol* 2010;8:361–71.

⁶⁷⁰ Brown JJ, Pascual M, Wimberly MC, Johnson LR, Murdock CC. 2023 Humidity: the overlooked variable in the thermal biology of mosquito-borne disease. *Ecol. Lett.* 26, 1029–1049. (doi:10.1111/ele.14228)

⁶⁷¹ Pardo-Araujo, M., Eritja, R., Alonso, D., & Bartumeus, F. (2024). Present and future suitability of invasive and urban vectors through an environmentally driven mosquito reproduction number. *Proceedings B*, 291(2034), 20241960.

⁶⁷² Roiz, D., Neteler, M., Castellani, C., Arnoldi, D., & Rizzoli, A. (2011). Climatic factors driving invasion of the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*) into new areas of Trentino, northern Italy. *PloS one*, 6(4), e14800.

⁶⁷³ Delisle, E., Rousseau, C., Broche, B., Leparac-Goffart, I., L'ambert, G., Cochet, A., ... & Golliot, F. (2015). Chikungunya outbreak in Montpellier, France, september to october 2014. *Eurosurveillance*, 20(17).

⁶⁷⁴ Estrada-Peña, A., Ayllón, N., & De La Fuente, J. (2012). Impact of climate trends on tick-borne pathogen transmission. *Frontiers in physiology*, 3, 64.

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temperatures limited mosquito presence at higher altitudes ⁶⁷⁵, ⁶⁷⁶. However, as temperatures rise, mosquitoes are now found at increasing elevations in the Pyrenees, reaching altitudes where they previously could not survive ⁶⁷⁷.

CC may also alter the life cycle of mosquitoes, increasing their presence and distribution. Higher temperatures accelerate the development rate of mosquito larvae and shorten the time required for eggs to hatch ⁶⁷⁸. This results in higher reproduction rates and larger mosquito populations ⁶⁷⁹.

On the other side, warmer conditions can increase the biting rate and the capacity of mosquitoes to transmit viruses. Pathogen development within mosquitoes (e.g., the extrinsic incubation period for viruses like Dengue and West Nile) is also shortened in warmer temperatures, enhancing transmission efficiency.

The first record of its establishment was in Italy in 1990, and *Aedes albopictus* is now present in several EU Member States, predominantly present in the southernmost and central parts of the European continent ⁶⁸⁰. Southern France and northern Spain have reported sporadic cases of autochthonous Dengue and West Nile virus, indicating local transmission rather than imported cases ⁶⁸¹. According to the European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDC), between 2017 and 2024, new establishment of *Aedes albopictus* has been confirmed in 7 Pyrenean territories, including Lleida, Huesca, Navarra, Guipúzcoa and Álava on the southern slope, and Ariège and Hautes-Pyrénées on the northern slope. In the case of the Basque Country region, the presence

⁶⁷⁵ Cunze, S., Kochmann, J., Koch, L. K., & Klimpel, S. (2016). *Aedes albopictus* and its environmental limits in Europe. *PLoS One*, 11(9), e0162116.

⁶⁷⁶ Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

⁶⁷⁷ Balaji, B. N. Insects in a changing climate: A review of distribution patterns, ecological roles and future challenges.

⁶⁷⁸ Roiz, D., Neteler, M., Castellani, C., Arnoldi, D., & Rizzoli, A. (2011). Climatic factors driving invasion of the tiger mosquito (*Aedes albopictus*) into new areas of Trentino, northern Italy. *PloS one*, 6(4), e14800.

⁶⁷⁹ Reinhold, J. M., Lazzari, C. R., & Lahondère, C. (2018). Effects of the environmental temperature on *Aedes aegypti* and *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes: a review. *Insects*, 9(4), 158.

⁶⁸⁰ Caminade, C., Medlock, J. M., Ducheyne, E., McIntyre, K. M., Leach, S., Baylis, M., & Morse, A. P. (2012). Suitability of European climate for the Asian tiger mosquito *Aedes albopictus*: recent trends and future scenarios. *Journal of the Royal Society Interface*, 9(75), 2708-2717.

⁶⁸¹ ECDC, 2019. Autochthonous cases of dengue in Spain and France, 1 October 2019

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of *Aedes albopictus* was confirmed for the first time in 2012, coming from an outbreak in the French region of Nouvelle-Aquitaine ⁶⁸².

Figure 20: The map shows the current known distribution of *Aedes albopictus* in Europe at 'regional' administrative level, as of July 2024. EFSA, 2024 ⁶⁸³.

A study by Goiri et al ⁶⁸⁴ demonstrates the increasing presence of *Aedes albopictus* in the municipalities of Álava and Guipúzcoa, starting with the first outbreak detected in Alava. During the period studied by the authors (2013-2018), the number of eggs counted in the different traps used in the study generally increased over the years, with a particularly pronounced peak in 2018. Regarding the future expected situation, several authors agree on a progressive expansion of the suitability of the Pyrenean

⁶⁸² Goiri, F., González, M. A., Goikolea, J., Oribe, M., de Castro, V., Delacour, S., ... & García-Pérez, A. L. (2020). Progressive invasion of *Aedes albopictus* in Northern Spain in the period 2013–2018 and a possible association with the increase in insect bites. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(5), 1678.

⁶⁸³ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/en/publications-data/aedes-albopictus-current-known-distribution-july-2024>

⁶⁸⁴ Goiri, F., González, M. A., Goikolea, J., Oribe, M., de Castro, V., Delacour, S., ... & García-Pérez, A. L. (2020). Progressive invasion of *Aedes albopictus* in Northern Spain in the period 2013–2018 and a possible association with the increase in insect bites. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 17(5), 1678.

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territory for the establishment of this mosquito ^{685,686}. Specifically, in the case of the Pyrenees, Pardo Araujo et al ⁶⁸⁷ project a consistent increase in the number of months in which the mosquito would be active in the coming decades. Compared to the current period, the number of months suitable for the development of *Aedes albopictus* could be extended by 4 ± 1 month in the whole cross-border Pyrenean territory, especially in the bordering areas. Oliveira et al. ⁶⁸⁸ estimated an expansion of the suitable Pyrenean territory for the development of this vector. In particular, a large part of the mountain range that is currently classified as unsuitable or uncertain, would become suitable or highly suitable for this vector during the course of this century.

Figure 21: Patterns of consensus among published predictions of current habitat suitability for *Aedes albopictus* in Europe. Suitable and unsuitable areas result from the agreement of 5 or more predictions (left). Future trajectories of suitability for *Aedes albopictus* in Europe. Each trajectory represents a different combination of predicted status (suitable, uncertain, unsuitable) in the two timeframes (present and future). Source: Oliveira et al., 2021 ⁶⁸⁹.

This expansion could lead to an increased likelihood of Chikungunya spread, as models have generally projected that moderate climatic suitability for Chikungunya

⁶⁸⁵ Oliveira, S., Rocha, J., Sousa, C. A., & Capinha, C. (2021). Wide and increasing suitability for *Aedes albopictus* in Europe is congruent across distribution models. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 9916.

⁶⁸⁶ Pardo-Araujo, M., Eritja, R., Alonso, D., & Bartumeus, F. (2024). Present and future suitability of invasive and urban vectors through an environmentally driven mosquito reproduction number. *Proceedings B*, 291(2034), 20241960.

⁶⁸⁷ Pardo-Araujo, M., Eritja, R., Alonso, D., & Bartumeus, F. (2024). Present and future suitability of invasive and urban vectors through an environmentally driven mosquito reproduction number. *Proceedings B*, 291(2034), 20241960.

⁶⁸⁸ Oliveira, S., Rocha, J., Sousa, C. A., & Capinha, C. (2021). Wide and increasing suitability for *Aedes albopictus* in Europe is congruent across distribution models. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 9916.

⁶⁸⁹ Oliveira, S., Rocha, J., Sousa, C. A., & Capinha, C. (2021). Wide and increasing suitability for *Aedes albopictus* in Europe is congruent across distribution models. *Scientific reports*, 11(1), 9916.

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transmission is expected, especially in France, Spain, Germany and Italy ⁶⁹⁰, ⁶⁹¹. The risk of dengue in Europe could increase due to climate-related proliferation in the density or seasonal activity of *Aedes albopictus*.

Strengthening surveillance, enhancing vector control, and implementing climate adaptation strategies are essential steps to mitigate the growing public health threat in the region.

3.1.3 Sandfly-borne diseases (*Leishmania infantum*, causing visceral leishmaniasis, and *Leishmania tropica*, by sandfly flebotomine)

In Europe, leishmaniasis is the most prevalent disease transmitted by phlebotomine sandflies, which is caused by two parasites: *Leishmania infantum*, responsible for visceral leishmaniasis, and *Leishmania tropica*, responsible for cutaneous leishmaniasis ⁶⁹². The Pyrenees is experiencing climate-induced changes that are altering the dynamics of *Phlebotomus* sandfly populations, thereby increasing the risk of leishmaniasis in this region.

Observed and expected impacts

Like the mosquitoes, a milder climate in the Pyrenees could lead to an expansion of the sandfly distribution area: *Phlebotomus perniciosus* and *Phlebotomus ariasi* (key vectors of *L. infantum*), are sensitive to temperature. Rising temperatures in the Pyrenees are enabling these vectors to expand northward and to higher altitudes, where they were

⁶⁹⁰ Nsoesie, E. O., Kraemer, M. U., Golding, N., Pigott, D. M., Brady, O. J., Moyes, C. L., ... & Brownstein, J. S. (2016). Global distribution and environmental suitability for chikungunya virus, 1952 to 2015. *Eurosurveillance*, 21(20), 30234.

⁶⁹¹ Tjaden, N. B., Suk, J. E., Fischer, D., Thomas, S. M., Beierkuhnlein, C., & Semenza, J. C. (2017). Modelling the effects of global climate change on Chikungunya transmission in the 21st century. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 3813.

⁶⁹² Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

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previously absent ^{693,694}. Furthermore, modifications of landscapes and habitats due to human activities, as well as an increase in the movement of reservoirs and new species of competent vectors, are contributing to the spread of *Leishmania infantum* ⁶⁹⁵. Leishmaniasis is a climate-sensitive zoonotic disease caused by Leishmania parasites and transmitted by female Phlebotomine sandflies. Cutaneous (most common and causes skin sores) and visceral (rarer, systemic, and with high fatality) leishmaniasis, caused by *Leishmania infantum*, are endemic in parts of Europe, with the estimated number of cutaneous and visceral leishmaniasis cases amounting to 1100–1900 per 100.000 in south-eastern Europe and 10 000–17 000 in western Europe ⁶⁹⁶.

CC is extending the active season of sandflies, traditionally limited to warmer months (e.g., May–October). Mild winters and earlier springs allow sandflies to emerge sooner and remain active longer, increasing the risk of disease transmission. This trend has been detected especially in the western French Pyrenees where *Phlebotomus ariasi* and *Phlebotomus perniciosus* are found to be the most common vectors ⁶⁹⁷. Specifically, *Phlebotomus ariasi* has been reported at higher elevations and further north in recent years ⁶⁹⁸.

In the central Pyrenees, already in 2012 Ballart et al ⁶⁹⁹ identified a wider geographical and altitudinal distribution of *Phlebotomus ariasi* in Andorra (central Pyrenees), where it was located between 800 and 2200 m asl. The study also identified for the first time *Phlebotomus perniciosus* in Andorra, with captures below 1000 m asl. The finding of these species, both proven vectors of human and canine leishmaniasis in bordering

⁶⁹³ Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

⁶⁹⁴ Díaz-Sáez, V., Corpas-López, V., Merino-Espinosa, G., Morillas-Mancilla, M. J., Abattouy, N., & Martín-Sánchez, J. (2021). Seasonal dynamics of phlebotomine sand flies and autochthonous transmission of *Leishmania infantum* in high-altitude ecosystems in southern Spain. *Acta Tropica*, 213, 105749.

⁶⁹⁵ Montoya-Alonso, J. A., Morchón, R., Costa-Rodríguez, N., Matos, J. I., Falcón-Cordón, Y., & Carretón, E. (2020). Current distribution of selected vector-borne diseases in dogs in Spain. *Frontiers in Veterinary Science*, 7, 564429.

⁶⁹⁶ <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/Spatial-relationship-presence-absence-Leishmania-march2023.pdf>

⁶⁹⁷ Alten, B., Maia, C., Afonso, M. O., Campino, L., Jimenez, M., González, E., ... & Gradoni, L. (2016). Seasonal dynamics of phlebotomine sand fly species proven vectors of Mediterranean leishmaniasis caused by *Leishmania infantum*. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 10(2), e0004458.

⁶⁹⁸ Jourdain, F., & Paty, M. C. (2019). The impact of climate change on vectors and vector-borne diseases in France. *Les Tribunes de la sante*, 61(3), 41-51.

⁶⁹⁹ Ballart, C., Barón, S., Alcover, M. M., Portús, M., & Gállego, M. (2012). Distribution of phlebotomine sand flies (Diptera: Psychodidae) in Andorra: first finding of *P. perniciosus* and wide distribution of *P. ariasi*. *Acta tropica*, 122(1), 155-159.

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areas of France and Spain, was considered in terms of a possible emergence of leishmaniasis in Andorra. Other sentinel focuses have been observed in the French Ariège Pyrenees, which is being monitored to prevent the possible spread of this disease to higher altitudes ⁷⁰⁰.

Temperature and relative humidity affect the survival and reproduction rate of phlebotomine sandflies and parasite development ⁷⁰¹, so CC could shift the range of leishmaniasis in the future ⁷⁰². Some modelling studies indicate that mountainous areas such as the Pyrenees could become increasingly suitable for *Phlebotomus* species in the coming decades, as it has been projected in the Alps ⁷⁰³. In a study on the future expansion of Leishmaniasis vectors in the Mediterranean basin, it was found that all species considered have prospects of gaining new suitable areas for vectors ⁷⁰⁴. More specifically, *Phlebotomus papatasi* and *Phlebotomus tobi* are the ones that could experience the greatest expansion of potential suitable range during this century in the Pyrenees ⁷⁰⁵.

Expanded climatic suitability for sandflies could extend leishmaniasis risk, although expansion may be contained by the somewhat restricted movement ability of sandflies ⁷⁰⁶.

⁷⁰⁰ Dereure, J., Vanwambeke, S. O., Malé, P., Martinez, S., Pratlong, F., Balard, Y., & Dedet, J. P. (2009). The potential effects of global warming on changes in canine leishmaniasis in a focus outside the classical area of the disease in southern France. *Vector-Borne and Zoonotic Diseases*, 9(6), 687-694.

⁷⁰¹ Negev, M., Paz, S., Clermont, A., Pri-Or, N. G., Shalom, U., Yeger, T., & Green, M. S. (2015). Impacts of climate change on vector borne diseases in the Mediterranean Basin—implications for preparedness and adaptation policy. *International journal of environmental research and public health*, 12(6), 6745-6770.

⁷⁰² Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

⁷⁰³ Fischer, D., Moeller, P., Thomas, S. M., Naucke, T. J., & Beierkuhnlein, C. (2011). Combining climatic projections and dispersal ability: a method for estimating the responses of sandfly vector species to climate change. *PLoS neglected tropical diseases*, 5(11), e1407.

⁷⁰⁴ Chalhaf, B., Chemkhi, J., Mayala, B., Harrabi, M., Benie, G. B., Michael, E., & Ben Salah, A. (2018). Ecological niche modeling predicting the potential distribution of *Leishmania* vectors in the Mediterranean basin: impact of climate change. *Parasites & vectors*, 11, 1-9.

⁷⁰⁵ Koch, L. K., Kochmann, J., Klimpel, S., & Cunze, S. (2017). Modeling the climatic suitability of leishmaniasis vector species in Europe. *Scientific reports*, 7(1), 13325.

⁷⁰⁶ Semenza, J. C., & Suk, J. E. (2018). Vector-borne diseases and climate change: a European perspective. *FEMS microbiology letters*, 365(2), fnx244.

3.2 Water and food-borne diseases

Health can be affected in different ways by exposure to changes in rainfall and water availability and quality, increased water pollution, proliferation of toxic microorganisms, ecosystem imbalances and changes in biodiversity ⁷⁰⁷. Foodborne diseases can be caused by biological agents, which consist of infectious microorganisms such as bacteria, viruses and parasites, or the toxins produced by these organisms that remain active in food. Climate modifies the dispersal and transmission patterns of these biological agents increasing the risks to food safety, including those posed by toxigenic fungi and from increased use of chemicals ⁷⁰⁸.

Observed and expected impacts

It is not possible to assess whether past CC has already affected water- and food-borne diseases in the Pyrenees, but the sensitivity of pathogens to climate factors suggest that CC could be having effects on these diseases.

Due to CC in the Pyrenees, it is expected that the intensification of alterations to the hydrological cycle could have a strong impact on water quality ⁷⁰⁹ and, therefore, on human health, for those who do not have access to or do not have adequate treatment systems. It must be considered that many mountain municipalities do not yet have wastewater treatment plants, or they are not properly sized for the floating population they receive during the high summer and winter tourism season. This could mean that during critical periods of the year, the concentration of pollutants in the water can be so high that even bathing could be a health risk in some rivers. This problem could be particularly relevant during the increasingly severe low water levels caused by the change in precipitation regime in synergy with the progressive increase in river water temperature ⁷¹⁰. In fact, several waterborne and foodborne diseases demonstrate seasonal peaks during the warmer season, such as salmonellosis, non-cholera *Vibrio*

⁷⁰⁷ Loopstra, R., Reeves, A., & Stuckler, D. (2015). Rising food insecurity in Europe. *Lancet*, 385(9982), 2041.

⁷⁰⁸ Bezner Kerr, R., Liebert, J., Kansanga, M., & Kpienbaareh, D. (2022). Human and social values in agroecology: A review. *Elem Sci Anth*, 10(1), 00090.

⁷⁰⁹ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos ISBN: 978-84-09-06268-3

⁷¹⁰ OPCC-CTP (2018). El cambio climático en los Pirineos: impactos, vulnerabilidades y adaptación Bases de conocimiento para la futura estrategia de adaptación al cambio climático en los Pirineos ISBN: 978-84-09-06268-3

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infections, campylobacteriosis and giardiasis ^{711,712}. On the other hand, it should be noted that an increase in temperature combined with extreme precipitation leads to cascading phenomena with negative impacts on drinking water quality ⁷¹³. Precipitation can mobilise faecal pathogens from pastures, transferring them to rivers and lakes downstream, where they can enter water treatment plants and distribution systems, leading to possible outbreaks of waterborne diseases ⁷¹⁴.

Beside this, higher temperatures and altered moisture conditions increase the risk of infections by several climate-sensitive foodborne pathogens, such as *Salmonella* spp., *Campylobacter* spp. and toxin-producing *Escherichia coli* strains ⁷¹⁵.

According to Watkiss et al. ⁷¹⁶, *Salmonella* cases increase by 5-10% for each degree increase in weekly temperatures above a threshold of around 5 °C (with key factors being inadequate food preparation and storage prior to consumption). Campylobacteriosis, mainly caused by *Campylobacter* bacteria, is one of the main gastroenteritis-associated diseases, mainly related to the consumption of chicken meat. In the future, major outbreaks of *Salmonella* will probably be linked to the consumption of leafy vegetables; a 1°C increase in ambient temperature above 5°C may cause a 5-10% increase in *Salmonella* infections ⁷¹⁷. By 2100, 50% of the additional *Salmonella* infections in Europe are projected to be caused by increased temperature and not by a population increase ⁷¹⁸.

⁷¹¹ EEA, 2024: Report 01/2024, European Climate Risk Assessment

⁷¹² Semenza, J. C., & Paz, S. (2021). Climate change and infectious disease in Europe: Impact, projection and adaptation. *The Lancet Regional Health–Europe*, 9.

⁷¹³ Semenza, J. C., Rocklöv, J., & Ebi, K. L. (2022). Climate change and cascading risks from infectious disease. *Infectious diseases and therapy*, 11(4), 1371-1390.

⁷¹⁴ Semenza, J. C. (2021). CLIMATE CHANGE IMPACTS ON THE HYDROLOGIC CYCLE AND WATERBORNE DISEASES. *Global Climate Change and Human Health: From Science to Practice*, 67.

⁷¹⁵ EEA, 2024: Report 01/2024, European Climate Risk Assessment

⁷¹⁶ Watkiss, P., Horrocks, L., Pye, S., Searl, A., & Hunt, A. (2009). Impacts of climate change in human health in Europe. PESETA-Human health study. European Commission, Institute for Prospective Technological Studies.

⁷¹⁷ Semenza, J. C., & Menne, B. (2009). Climate change and infectious diseases in Europe. *The Lancet infectious diseases*, 9(6), 365-375.

⁷¹⁸ Rupasinghe, R., Chomel, B. B., & Martínez-López, B. (2022). Climate change and zoonoses: A review of the current status, knowledge gaps, and future trends. *Acta Tropica*, 226, 106225.

4. Conclusion

Climate change (CC) is profoundly transforming the health and environmental landscape of the Pyrenees, with direct and indirect impacts already evident and projected to intensify in the coming decades. Direct impacts include rising extreme temperatures, with heatwaves becoming more frequent, intense, and longer-lasting—particularly on the southern slopes, where heat-related mortality has increased by 45 deaths per million inhabitants per decade. Older adults in rural and mountainous areas face heightened vulnerability due to limited access to cooling infrastructure, healthcare, and emergency services, despite cooler ambient temperatures. Heatwaves also increase the risk of fatal accidents in mountain environments, with a 13% rise in mountain biking incidents per 1°C temperature increase. Cold spells, though less impactful, still contribute to cardiovascular and respiratory morbidity and mortality.

Extreme rainfall and flash floods—driven by intensified precipitation and rain-on-snow events—are increasing in frequency, especially in the central and southern Pyrenees, with significant risks of drowning, injuries, infectious disease outbreaks (e.g., hepatitis A, rotavirus), and mental health crises. The 1996 Biescas flood, which claimed 97 lives, exemplifies the deadly potential of these events. Climate-driven changes in snowpack dynamics and permafrost degradation are also increasing the risk of landslides, rockfalls, and debris flows, threatening both infrastructure and human safety, particularly in high-altitude tourist zones.

Air quality is deteriorating due to CC, with rising levels of tropospheric ozone and particulate matter (PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀). Warmer temperatures enhance natural emissions of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) from forests and increase the frequency of Saharan dust outbreaks and wildfires, all contributing to higher pollution levels. These pollutants are linked to respiratory and cardiovascular diseases, with ozone concentrations in the Pyrenees projected to rise significantly by mid-century, posing a growing public health burden.

Allergies are escalating due to longer, more intense pollen seasons driven by earlier spring blooms, extended growing periods, and increased pollen production under higher CO₂ levels. Species like ragweed are expanding into new areas, exposing previously unaffected populations to new allergens. This trend is already altering the timing and severity of allergic rhinitis and asthma in the region.

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Indirect impacts are equally concerning. Climate change is facilitating the northward and upward expansion of disease vectors: *Ixodes Ricinus* ticks, *Aedes albopictus* mosquitoes, and *Phlebotomus* sandflies are now found at higher altitudes and latitudes, increasing the risk of Lyme disease, tick-borne encephalitis, dengue, chikungunya, and leishmaniasis. These diseases, once rare in the Pyrenees, are now emerging in new areas, including Andorra and the French and Spanish Pyrenean slopes.

Water and food safety are also under threat. Altered hydrological cycles, reduced water availability, and extreme rainfall events compromise water quality, increasing the risk of waterborne diseases like giardiasis and salmonellosis. Warmer temperatures accelerate the growth of pathogens such as *Salmonella* and *Campylobacter*, with projections indicating a 5–10% rise in infections per 1°C temperature increase. Foodborne outbreaks may become more frequent, especially linked to leafy vegetables and poultry.

In summary, the Pyrenees are experiencing a multi-faceted health crisis driven by climate change. The convergence of extreme weather, deteriorating air and water quality, expanding vector-borne diseases, and worsening allergies demands urgent, integrated adaptation strategies. Strengthening early warning systems, improving health infrastructure in remote areas, enhancing surveillance of emerging diseases, and promoting climate-resilient land use and public awareness are critical to safeguarding the health and well-being of both residents and visitors in this vulnerable mountain region.

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1. Introduction

The impacts of climate change on human health have gained increasing attention as the frequency and intensity of extreme weather events (EWEs) and natural disasters continue to rise ⁷¹⁹. Events such as heatwaves, floods or storms pose significant threats to public health, influencing a wide range of non-communicable diseases (NCDs) ⁷²⁰. The NCDs include respiratory conditions (e.g., chronic bronchitis, asthma), cardiovascular diseases, and mental health disorders ⁷²¹. Understanding the interplay between these health outcomes due to climatic changes is critical for designing effective public health strategies and enhancing resilience.

A recent literature review indicates that heatwaves are the most extensively studied extreme weather events (EWEs) ⁷²². The review underscores that the majority of existing studies are conducted at localized or regional scales, focusing on specific resident populations exposed to particular EWEs. In contrast, relatively few studies have examined the broader impacts of EWEs at the national or supranational level. Furthermore, the review finds that research has predominantly been conducted in developing and warmer countries, where inadequate public health systems and insufficient climate-resilient infrastructure exacerbate the effects of climate change on non-communicable diseases (NCDs).

Additionally, the review highlights a research gap in mountainous and colder regions, particularly regarding the effects of heatwaves. Within the European context, the review identifies a limited number of studies, with the majority focusing on Spain, followed by France, Switzerland, and a few other countries. Based on the gathered literature, we could not find any study conducted at the pan-European level. There are also considerable heterogeneity in methodological approaches, with studies employing different measures of temperature and precipitation across varying spatial and temporal scales, depending on the research hypothesis related to EWEs and their impact on NCDs. Moreover, findings from these studies are often contingent upon

⁷¹⁹ Berlemann and Steinhardt, “Climate Change, Natural Disasters, and Migration—a Survey of the Empirical Evidence.”

⁷²⁰ Baccini et al., “Heat Effects on Mortality in 15 European Cities”; Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France”; Charlson et al., “Climate Change and Mental Health”; Rataj, Kunzweiler, and Garthus-Niegel, “Extreme Weather Events in Developing Countries and Related Injuries and Mental Health Disorders - a Systematic Review.”

⁷²¹ World Health Organization, “Noncommunicable Diseases.”

⁷²² Lea Bernhardt and Prasanta Kumar Roy, “Empirical Evidence of the Effects of Climate Change on NCDs: A Literature Review,” *Review of Economics* 75, no. 2 (August 27, 2024): 71–108, <https://doi.org/10.1515/roe-2024-0058>.

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demographic factors such as age, gender, income level, occupation, and pre-existing health conditions.

Building on these insights, our study aims to examine the influence of EWEs on the prevalence and progression of NCDs across Europe by integrating health and climate data from multiple sources. Utilizing pan-European health datasets, such as the European Social Survey (ESS), this analysis employs regression techniques to explore the relationship between climatic variables and health outcomes. Climate data are sourced from the European Copernicus Programme, ensuring comprehensive and standardized coverage across diverse geographic regions. Given the heightened vulnerability of cardiovascular and respiratory conditions to extreme weather events—including heatwaves and deteriorating air quality—our analysis focuses on these specific NCD categories.

To examine the impact of temperature and precipitation on health outcomes, we collected various health datasets, which are presented in Table A2. To ensure robust results, we tested several models, incorporating variations in the temperature threshold (e.g., 25°C, 30°C, 35°C) and the duration of these temperature conditions (e.g., 2 consecutive days, 3 consecutive days, etc.). Additionally, we explored different time frames for the occurrence of high-temperature days (e.g., the past 28 days, 90 days, etc.). In this report, we present both OLS and probit models for each of our three dependent health variables, regressed on three distinct climate variables, resulting in a total of 18 estimations.

The findings show that high temperatures have a positive and significant impact on the prevalence of high blood pressure. If at least one day in the past 28 days had a mean temperature above 30°C, the likelihood of experiencing high blood pressure increases by 10%. If there were two consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C, this likelihood rises by 20%. For respiratory problems, we also find a positive and significant effect of high temperatures. The likelihood of experiencing respiratory issues increases by 16% if there was at least one day with a mean temperature above 30°C and by 10% if there were two consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C. Furthermore, our results do not indicate any significant health effects of high precipitation rates, except for high blood pressure, where the precipitation coefficient shows a significant negative impact on its prevalence. However, the significance levels are lower compared to those of the heat coefficients.

Our model is well specified from the aspect of omitted variable bias (OVB) as most of our control variables exhibit the expected effects on health outcomes. Based on the

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literature review⁷²³ discussed earlier, we deploy a very limited number but specific number of controls to ensure minimum OVB on one hand and to avoid overfitting on the other hand. We observe a significant relationship for age, income, education level, and smoking with all our dependent variables. The prevalence of health issues increases with age and decreases with higher income and education levels. Smoking is found to increase the prevalence of health issues, with positive and significant coefficients.

In the following section, we provide a concise overview of the existing literature and establish the theoretical foundation for our variable selection. Section 3 outlines the datasets collected, the data processing steps, and the methodology employed for empirical analysis. Section 4 presents the results and discusses their implications. Finally, section 5 offers concluding remarks.

2. Related Literature

The body of literature examining the impact of climate change—and consequently EWEs—on NCDs has expanded significantly in recent years, highlighting the growing relevance of this research field⁷²⁴. The literature suggests that EWEs - including heatwaves, wildfires, flooding, droughts, and storms - may exacerbate existing NCDs like cardiovascular diseases (e.g. stroke, ischaemic heart disease), respiratory diseases (e.g. asthma, COPD) and mental health disorders (e.g. anxiety, depression)⁷²⁵. The increasing frequency and intensity of climate-related disasters seem to significantly impact the prevalence and severity of NCDs⁷²⁶.

⁷²³ Bernhardt and Roy.

⁷²⁴ Schulte, Rössli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland”; Charlson et al., “Climate Change and Mental Health”; Salvador et al., “Public Health Implications of Drought in a Climate Change Context”; Walinski et al., “The Effects of Climate Change on Mental Health”; Agache et al., “Climate Change and Global Health”; Sullenbarger, Schutzenhofer, and Haase, “Climate Change: Implications for Community Mental Health.”

⁷²⁵ Agache et al., “Climate Change and Global Health”; Chen et al., “Influence of Heat Wave Definitions to the Added Effect of Heat Waves on Daily Mortality in Nanjing, China.”; Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health”; Liu et al., “A Systematic Review of the Physical Health Impacts from Non-Occupational Exposure to Wildfire Smoke”; Salvador et al., “Public Health Implications of Drought in a Climate Change Context”; Turner, Connell, and Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia”; Walinski et al., “The Effects of Climate Change on Mental Health”; Zeng et al., “The Effect of Heat Waves on Mortality and Effect Modifiers in Four Communities of Guangdong Province, China.”

⁷²⁶ Liu, Yongqiang, Stanturf, John, and Goodrick, Scott, “Trends in Global Wildfire Potential in a Changing Climate”; Peduzzi et al., “Global Trends in Tropical Cyclone Risk”; Perkins-Kirkpatrick and Lewis, “Increasing Trends in Regional Heatwaves”; Tellman et al., “Satellite Imaging Reveals Increased Proportion of Population Exposed to Floods”; Trenberth et al., “Global Warming and Changes in

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Extreme temperatures and heatwaves significantly impact both the mortality and morbidity of NCDs. Studies find an increase in all-cause mortality associated with heatwaves, as well as heightened cardiovascular mortality and adverse respiratory outcomes ⁷²⁷. While the evidence on higher cardiovascular mortality is mostly conclusive, some studies report inconclusive or insignificant results for respiratory mortality ⁷²⁸. Regarding morbidity, research shows significant increases in all-cause morbidity, respiratory morbidity and cardiovascular morbidity due to heat exposure ⁷²⁹. However, findings on cardiovascular morbidity remain mixed with some studies finding a decrease in morbidity or inconclusive results ⁷³⁰, whereas the pattern for respiratory outcomes appears more consistent. Additionally, heat-related conditions such as heat exhaustion and heat fatigue have been shown to exacerbate NCDs ⁷³¹.

Regarding the psychological dimension, the existing literature demonstrates a significant relationship between EWEs and mental health outcomes. Most studies report considerable negative effects of EWEs on psychological well-being, with the exception of heatwaves, where findings remain inconclusive due to contradictory results across studies ⁷³². Research on wildfires predominantly focuses on physiological health impacts, although evidence suggests that wildfires also negatively affect mental

Drought”; Weilhammer et al., “Extreme Weather Events in Europe and Their Health Consequences – A Systematic Review.”

⁷²⁷ Baccini et al., “Heat Effects on Mortality in 15 European Cities”; Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France”; Monteiro et al., “Excess Mortality and Morbidity during the July 2006 Heat Wave in Porto, Portugal.”

⁷²⁸ Nicholas J Arisco et al., “The Effect of Extreme Temperature and Precipitation on Cause-Specific Deaths in Rural Burkina Faso: A Longitudinal Study,” *The Lancet Planetary Health* 7, no. 6 (June 2023): e478–89, [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(23\)00027-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(23)00027-X); Hualiang Lin et al., “Temperature Changes between Neighboring Days and Mortality in Summer: A Distributed Lag Non-Linear Time Series Analysis,” *PLOS ONE* 8, no. 6 (2013), <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0066403>.

⁷²⁹ Gronlund et al., “Heat, Heat Waves, and Hospital Admissions among the Elderly in the United States, 1992–2006”; Knowlton et al., “The 2006 California Heat Wave: Impacts on Hospitalizations and Emergency Department Visits”; Turner, Connell, and Tong, “The Effect of Heat Waves on Ambulance Attendances in Brisbane, Australia.”

⁷³⁰ Pham Ngan Giang et al., “The Effect of Temperature on Cardiovascular Disease Hospital Admissions among Elderly People in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam,” *Global Health Action* 7, no. 1 (December 2014): 23649, <https://doi.org/10.3402/gha.v7.23649>; Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland.”

⁷³¹ Guirguis et al., “Heat, Disparities, and Health Outcomes in San Diego County’s Diverse Climate Zones”; Stephanie Hopp, Francesca Dominici, and Jennifer F. Bobb, “Medical Diagnoses of Heat Wave-Related Hospital Admissions in Older Adults,” *Preventive Medicine* 110 (May 2018): 81–85, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ypmed.2018.02.001>.

⁷³² Bundo et al., “Ambient Temperature and Mental Health Hospitalizations in Bern, Switzerland”; Guirguis et al., “Heat, Disparities, and Health Outcomes in San Diego County’s Diverse Climate Zones.”

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health, with outcomes varying across different population groups ⁷³³. Storms and droughts have been shown to contribute to various mental health problems, including emotional distress, increased rates of depression ⁷³⁴. In the context of floods, studies indicate that mental stress persists over extended periods, highlighting a significant and long-lasting psychological burden ⁷³⁵. Studies report that common mental health outcomes of flooding include symptoms of post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), anxiety, flashbacks, sleeplessness and depression ⁷³⁶. These psychological effects often extend beyond the immediate trauma, as depression, anxiety and PTSD levels have been shown to remain elevated for years after flooding events compared to pre-flood levels ⁷³⁷.

Overall, the literature underscores the substantial negative impact of EWEs on NCDs. However, a noticeable research gap remains, as the majority of studies continue to prioritize physiological health impacts over psychological outcomes. This imbalance highlights the need for more comprehensive research into the mental health consequences of EWEs to better inform public health strategies and resilience measures.

Comparing our results with the findings in the literature, we observe some similarities. For respiratory problems, both our study and the broader literature identify a significant and positive impact of high temperatures. Regarding cardiovascular outcomes, our findings indicate a positive impact on high blood pressure but a negative impact on heart or circulation problems. Here, the findings in the literature are not entirely consistent. While most studies report a positive and significant effect of high temperatures on cardiovascular outcomes, some also identify a significant negative impact for example on myocardial infarction and cardiac failure ⁷³⁸, both of which fall under the category of heart and circulation problems. However, we must be cautious when comparing our results to findings in the literature. While most studies in the

⁷³³ Schwarz et al., “Wildfire Smoke Knows No Borders: Differential Vulnerability to Smoke Effects on Cardio-Respiratory Health in the San Diego-Tijuana Region”; Wettstein and Vaidyanathan, “Psychotropic Medication Prescriptions and Large California Wildfires”; Wollschlaeger et al., “Investigation of Climate Change Impacts on Long-Term Care Facility Occupants.”

⁷³⁴ Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health”; Walinski et al., “The Effects of Climate Change on Mental Health.”

⁷³⁵ Charlson et al., “Climate Change and Mental Health.”

⁷³⁶ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households.”

⁷³⁷ Dai et al., “Long-Term Psychological Outcomes of Flood Survivors of Hard-Hit Areas of the 1998 Dongting Lake Flood in China”; Mulchandani et al., “The English National Cohort Study of Flooding & Health.”

⁷³⁸ Schulte, Rösli, and Ragetti, “Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland”; Monteiro et al., “Excess Mortality and Morbidity during the July 2006 Heat Wave in Porto, Portugal.”

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literature focus on actual hospital admission data, which provides detailed information about specific diagnoses, our survey data is based on individuals from a random sample of the general population, regardless of whether they have experienced health issues. These individuals were asked if they had encountered any health problems in the past, without a narrowly defined scope. This distinction introduces several issues, which are discussed later.

To further empirically investigate the impact of EWEs on NCDs, we use pan-European health data with local climate information. This approach aims to address and narrow the existing research gap in this area. In the next chapter, we explain the collected datasets and the methodology in more detail.

3. Data and Methodology

3.1 Climate data

Our primary climate data is from the publicly hosted European climate service “Copernicus Climate Data Store”⁷³⁹. It offers high-resolution gridded meteorological and climatological data for Europe. This dataset is derived from a network of ground-based observations and is used for climate monitoring, research, and policy development. The dataset provides daily values for key climate variables, which enables us to analyse trends and variations in weather patterns over time.

We use the variables maximum temperature, mean temperature, minimum temperature, precipitation and relative humidity from this dataset. These variables are on a daily temporal resolution and spatial resolution of 0.1° x 0.1° resolution which corresponds to approximately 11.1 km x 11.1 km at the equator. Since the actual distance covered by one degree of latitude remains fairly constant (~111 km), but longitude varies with latitude, the exact kilometre value depends on the location. For the European region, this corresponds to approximately 10–11 km x 10–11 km. For more details on the variable description, see Table 5. These spatially gridded climate variables are extracted on regional grids based on the NUTS regions in health data.

⁷³⁹ Copernicus Climate Change Service, “E-OBS Daily Gridded Meteorological Data for Europe from 1950 to Present Derived from in-Situ Observations” ([object Object], 2020), <https://doi.org/10.24381/CDS.151D3EC6>.

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Variable	Unit	Definition	Mean	Min.	Max.	SD
Mean temperature	°C	Daily mean air temperature measured near the surface, usually at height of 2 meters.	7.7	-6.96	20.58	7.64
Minimum temperature	°C	Daily minimum air temperature measured near the surface, usually at height of 2 meters.	4.26	-9.34	15.88	6.89
Maximum temperature	°C	Daily maximum air temperature measured near the surface, usually at height of 2 meters.	11.11	-4.62	24.99	8.32
Mean Precipitation	mm/day	Total daily amount of rain, snow and hail measured as the height of the equivalent liquid water in a square meter	69.38	39.14	97.87	11.35

Table 5. Primary climate variables: Units, definitions and summary statistics.

Using the primary climate variables as seen in Table , we derive binary (1,0) indicators that are shown in Table . The procedure to develop these indicators is as follows. We assume a period of 28 days (n) past the day before interview day for our analysis. This includes the series of days from lag 1, lag 2, till lag 28. We develop an index for heatwave as 1, when on any two consecutive days in a rolling window of 2 days within a 28-day period mean temperature has exceeded 30°C and 0 otherwise. We develop another index for hot days as 1, when on any day within a 28-day period mean temperature has exceeded 30°C, else 0. Similarly, we define high precipitation days as 1 when any day within a 28-day period has more than 90 millimeters of precipitation, else 0. For details on a sample of such indicators, refer to Table .

Variable	Definition	Interpretation
temp_mean_consec2	It has value 1, when on any two consecutive days in a rolling window of 2 days within past 28 days has exceeded mean temperature 30°C, else 0.	Indicates exposure to heatwave
temp_mean_count	It has value 1, when on any day within past 28 days has exceeded minimum temperature 30°C, else 0.	Indicates exposure to hot days
precip_mean_count_90mm	It has value 1 when on at least one day within past 28 days daily mean precipitation is greater than equal to 90 millimetres.	Indicates exposure to heavy precipitation days

Table 6. Derived climate variable structure and interpretation.

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The following plots provide an overview on the trends in the climate variables on a monthly resolution for entire Europe. These plots are based on the same source, namely the Copernicus Climate Data Store, ⁷⁴⁰.

Data is available on monthly, seasonal and yearly temporal resolutions. We select the monthly resolution and the spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. At the equator, this corresponds to approximately 27.8 km x 27.8 km grid area. However, at mid-latitudes in Europe, this corresponds to approximately 25–28 km x 25–28 km. These spatially gridded monthly climate variables are extracted on the regional grid for entire Europe.

Figure 3. Mean monthly temperatures from 1940 until 2023 (°C).

As seen in The following plots provide an overview on the trends in the climate variables on a monthly resolution for entire Europe. These plots are based on the same source, namely the Copernicus Climate Data Store, .

Data is available on monthly, seasonal and yearly temporal resolutions. We select the monthly resolution and the spatial resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$. At the equator, this corresponds to approximately 27.8 km x 27.8 km grid area. However, at mid-latitudes in Europe, this corresponds to approximately 25–28 km x 25–28 km. These spatially gridded monthly climate variables are extracted on the regional grid for entire Europe.

⁷⁴⁰ "Climate Indicators for Europe from 1940 to 2100 Derived from Reanalysis and Climate Projections," accessed February 6, 2025, <https://cds.climate.copernicus.eu/datasets/sis-ecde-climate-indicators?tab=overview>.

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Figure 3, the mean monthly temperature varies slightly over time and a slight upward trend is visible, which aligns well with scientific findings on global warming. Notably, in the earlier years, especially between 1940 and 1956, there were frequent extreme dips in the lowest temperatures, indicating particularly cold winters. Minimum temperatures of -10°C or lower occurred multiple times during this period (e.g., January 1940: -10.4°C , January 1942: -11.4°C , January 1956: -10.7°C). After 1987 (January 1987: -9.99°C), however, there have been no years where the average temperatures dropped to -7°C or below. At the same time, average summer temperatures of 20°C were never reached until 2010, but since then, this threshold has been exceeded twice (July 2010: 20.6°C , July 2018: 20°C). Monthly average temperatures of 19°C or more were recorded 10 times since 2000, whereas this only occurred twice before the turn of the millennium (1972 and 1999). In 2023, the mean monthly temperature is 8.34°C (for more details on the mean temperatures from 2000 on see figure A1 in the appendix).

A particularly notable year is 2010, which is characterized by strong contrasts. In January 2010, the average temperature was -7°C , while the summer saw an average of 20.6°C . The annual average temperature for 2010 was 7.9°C , which, after 13 consecutive warm years, was the first time it fell below the long-term average of 8.2°C . However, despite this cooler annual temperature, a major heatwave occurred for three weeks during the summer ⁷⁴¹.

⁷⁴¹ Uwe Kirsche and Gerhard Lux, "Jahresrückblick: Deutschlandwetter Im Jahr 2010 Viel Abwechslung – Alles in Allem Etwas Zu Kalt Und Zu Nass," Presse-Info (Offenbach am Main: Deutscher Wetterdienst, December 29, 2010), https://www.dwd.de/DE/presse/pressemitteilungen/DE/2010/20101229_deutschlandwetter_jahr.pdf?__blob=publicationFile&v=3.

Figure 4. Mean monthly precipitation from 1940 until 2023 in mm.

As shown in Figure 2, the mean monthly precipitation has displayed an upward trend over the last 80 years. It increased significantly until the 1970s, then stagnated for a period before rising again in the 2010s (for mor details on precipitation from 2000 on see figure A2 in the appendix).

3.2. Health data

We utilize two health datasets for our analysis. They are from the publicly available European Social Survey (ESS) ⁷⁴² datasets. The ESS surveys are academically driven cross-national surveys that have been conducted across Europe since its inception in 2001. Every two years, newly selected cross-sectional samples participate in face-to-face interviews. They collect data on attitudes, beliefs, and behavioural patterns across diverse populations in more than thirty countries.

⁷⁴² ESS Data Portal, "European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ESS ERIC)," Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research., 2024, <https://ess.sikt.no/en/>.

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We select the 7th survey ⁷⁴³ and the 11th ⁷⁴⁴, survey due to the availability of health-related questions. For more details on these three datasets refer to Table 3. Overview of the analysed health survey datasets. Other health survey datasets which we acquired but could not utilize for our analysis due to inadequate spatiotemporal resolutions with respect to the survey respondents are in the Appendix.

Name	Period	Respondents	Respondent's age	NCD category
European Social Survey (ESS), wave 11	2023-2024	22190	15 years & above	Respiratory, Cardiovascular
European Social Survey (ESS), wave 7	2014-2015	40185	14 years & above	Respiratory, Cardiovascular

Table 7. Overview of the analysed health survey datasets.

From the ESS datasets, we select the three most suitable health variables and other relevant sociodemographic variables that are common across both waves to ensure a larger sample availability. A sample health variable “hltprhb” asks “Which of the health problems on this card have you had or experienced in the last 12 months, that is since [MONTH, YEAR]? High blood pressure” with value (0, 1) for the category (no, yes). For more details on these variables, please refer Table 8. The control variables include age, gender, income level, education, smoking habits, alcohol habits etc. For more details, refer to Table 5. Overview health and control variables.

Variable	Description	Values	Source
High Blood Pressure	Health problems, last 12 months: high blood pressure	0 = not marked 1 = marked	ESS7, ESS11
Heart or Circulation Problems	Health problems, last 12 months: heart or circulation problems	0 = not marked 1 = marked	ESS7, ESS11
Breathing Problems	Health problems, last 12 months: breathing problems	0 = not marked 1 = marked	ESS7, ESS11

Table 8. Overview of health variables in our analysis.

⁷⁴³ European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC), “ESS7 - Integrated File, Edition 2.3 [Data Set],” Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research., 2023, <https://ess.sikt.no/en/datafile/9c96a1b2-b027-43c1-8c74-e883f892d0bb>.

⁷⁴⁴ European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure (ESS ERIC), “ESS11 - Integrated File, Edition 2.0 [Data Set],” Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in Education and Research., 2024, <https://ess.sikt.no/en/datafile/242aaa39-3bbb-40f5-98bf-bfb1ce53d8ef>.

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Note: There was a follow up question for people with health problems: “And which of the health problems that you had or experienced in the last 12 months hampered you in your daily activities in any way?”. However, since this lacks objectivity, we focus solely on the mere existence of the health problem and not on the question of whether its presence hampers the person.

For the empirical analysis, the original categorization of the control variables requires adjustments. For example, the education variable typically includes around 20 categories, which vary across countries due to differences in education systems. In addition to standard levels such as basic school, high school, college, and university, some classifications include certificate programs, vocational training, and apprenticeships. While other control variables do not exhibit the same structural differences, they also contain multiple categories. To facilitate calculation and interpretation of results, we transform the raw variables from the ESS datasets as follows: All categorical variables, such as region, gender, and household income level, are converted into factors.

Gender is treated as a binary variable, with 1 representing female and 0 representing male. We include gender in our analysis because health impacts can differ significantly between males and females, making gender-sensitive analysis essential ⁷⁴⁵.

Income levels, originally reported in deciles, are grouped into three categories: the 1st to 3rd decile as low income, the 4th to 7th decile as middle income, and the remaining deciles as high income. The literature indicates that socioeconomic status can influence health outcomes, particularly due to differences in access to healthcare institutions ⁷⁴⁶. Consequently, we expect individuals in higher income groups to have a lower risk of the health outcomes examined.

Alcohol consumption, previously categorized by frequency (daily/weekly/monthly), is recoded as 1 if the respondent drinks alcohol at least occasionally, and 0 otherwise. We expect alcohol to have a positive impact on our dependent health variables, as alcohol consumption is known as a risk factor for various health outcomes ⁷⁴⁷.

Smoking habits remain categorized based on smoking frequency and cessation status, but the category labels differ across ESS waves. Respondents are classified as 1 if they currently smoke or have smoked in the past, and 0 otherwise. Similar to alcohol

⁷⁴⁵ Fouillet et al., “Excess Mortality Related to the August 2003 Heat Wave in France.”

⁷⁴⁶ Lamond, Joseph, and Proverbs, “An Exploration of Factors Affecting the Long Term Psychological Impact and Deterioration of Mental Health in Flooded Households.”

⁷⁴⁷ Graham et al., “Flood- and Weather-Damaged Homes and Mental Health.”

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consumption, we consider smoking a risk factor for NCDs and anticipate a positive impact on our dependent variable.

The **education** variable consists of multiple categories, ranging from primary school to PhD, including separate categories for dropouts and completed degrees. It also includes additional qualifications such as certificates, vocational training, and apprenticeships. For simplification, we classify primary school and below as category 1, high school, apprenticeships, vocational training, and certificate courses as category 2, and diploma, college, and university degrees as category 3. We include education as a control because higher education levels are associated with better knowledge of health risks and better health outcomes ⁷⁴⁸. Consequently, we expect that higher levels of education will reduce the risk of the health outcomes examined in our study.

However, some residual bias remains due to differences in category definitions and the number of categories across countries and survey waves. This may lead to a degree of misclassification, potentially introducing correlation between the three final education categories. While this represents a common clustering challenge, it is unlikely to introduce bias in the estimate of the main health variable, as education is not directly correlated with the weather variables.

⁷⁴⁸ Graham et al.

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Figure 5. Reported health problems by age, education and income group.

Figure 5 illustrates the percentage of respondents experiencing health problems across different age, education and income groups. Consistent with our expectations regarding the control variables, the data indicates that the prevalence of health issues increases with age, with all health problems being more common in older age groups. However, this trend appears to be slightly less pronounced for breathing problems compared to the other two health outcomes. Additionally, the health issues decrease with increasing income and education and again, this trend is less pronounced for breathing problems.

Table 5 shows the distribution of health and control variables across the different survey waves. The last column presents the data used for our estimations, which consists of two separate ESS waves. ESS7 had more respondents from 21 different countries, while in ESS11 13 countries participated. So, our merged dataset represents a total of 23 countries which are distributed relatively equally. Germany has the most respondents with 8.76% followed by Austria and the United Kingdom (for further information about the country distribution see Table A1 in the appendix). Table 6 indicates that the sample in both original waves is very balanced, with the distribution of gender being nearly identical. The age structure, income distribution and education show only minor variations with more respondents in the high-income group and less in the low-income group in wave 11 and less people in education group 1, more in group 2 and less in group 3 in wave 11. Additionally, alcohol consumption differs

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slightly with approximately two percentage points more respondents in Wave 11 reporting complete abstinence from alcohol and similarly slightly less people report to smoke in wave 11. Health issues appear to be consistently distributed across the different waves. Among the reported health conditions, high blood pressure emerges as the most prevalent issue, affecting approximately 20% of respondents. Overall, both waves show a highly similar distribution of variables, making them well-suited for merging.

Table 5. Overview health and control variables.

Variable	ESS Wave 7	ESS Wave 11	Both Waves merged
Respondents in total	40185	22190	62375
Male respondents	18871 (46.99%)	10271 (46.29%)	29142 (46.74%)
Female respondents	21292 (53.01%)	11919 (53.71%)	33211 (53.26%)
Age Mean/ Median/ SD (Minimum / Maximum)	49.28 /49 /18.74 14/114	51.88 / 53 / 18.73 15 / 90	50.2 / 51 /18.78 14 / 114
Alcohol consumption No / Yes	9687 / 30498 (24.11% / 75.89%)	5897 / 16293 (26.58% / 73.42%)	15584 / 46791 (24.98% / 75.02%)
Smoking No / Yes	18005 / 22180 (44.81% / 55.19%)	10226 / 11964 (46.08% / 53.92%)	28231 / 34144 (45.26% / 54.74%)
Income group Low / Medium / High	18190 / 13583 / 8412 (45.27% / 33.8% / 20.93%)	9199 / 7696 / 5295 (41.46% / 34.68% / 23.86%)	27389 / 21279 / 13707 (43.91% / 34.11% / 21.98%)
Education level 1/2/3	19628 /10499/ 10058 (48.84% / 26.13% / 25.03%)	9825/ 7624/ 4741 (44.28% / 34.36% / 21.37%)	29453/ 18123/ 14799 (47.22% / 29.05% / 23.73%)
Breathing problems No/Yes	34920 / 3214 (91.57% / 8.43%)	20251 / 1939 (91.26% /8.74%)	55171 / 5153 (91.46% / 8.54%)
Heart or circulation problems No/Yes	34160 / 3974 (89.58% / 10.42%)	19656/ 2534 (88.58% / 11.42%)	53816 / 6508 (89.21% / 10.89%)
High blood pressure No/Yes	31118 / 7016 (81.6% / 18.4%)	17358 / 4832 (78.22% / 21.78%)	48476 / 11848 (80.36% / 19.64%)
Wave time	August 2014 - December 2015	March 2023 - January 2024	

3.4 Methodology

In our analysis, we employ an empirical regression approach using the data sources described above. First, we conduct an Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression to estimate the effect of climate variables on health outcomes such as blood pressure, heart circulation, and breathing problems. In this baseline model, we include a set of control variables—namely age, gender, income, education, alcohol consumption, and smoking—to account for other factors that may influence health outcomes. Second, we estimate a Probit model. Although the OLS model serves as a useful starting point, it has limitations when modelling binary outcomes, as it can yield predicted probabilities outside the [0, 1] interval. The Probit model addresses this issue by incorporating the

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bounded nature of the dependent variable, thereby providing more consistent and interpretable estimates of the underlying probabilities. By comparing the results from both approaches, we perform a robustness test to ensure that our findings are valid and reliable across different modelling techniques. For the estimation, we use the software R ⁷⁴⁹.

OLS works by minimizing the sum of squared differences between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable, thereby providing the best linear unbiased estimates under standard assumptions ⁷⁵⁰.

The base model is specified as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ClimateVar}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

where Y_{it} is the health outcome for individual i at time t , ClimateVar_{it} represents the climate variable (e.g., temperature or precipitation), β_0 is the intercept, β_1 measures the effect of the climate variable on the health outcome, and ε_{it} is the error term. We expect the sign and significance of β_1 to reflect the hypothesized relationship; for instance, a positive and significant coefficient would indicate that an increase in the climate variable is associated with worsening health outcomes.

To account for potential confounders, we extend our model by adding control variables, which include both continuous variables (e.g., age, income level) and dummy variables (e.g., gender, alcohol consumption status). The augmented model is expressed as:

$$Y_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{ClimateVar}_{it} + \beta_2 X_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

where X_{it} is a vector of control variables. Furthermore, we explore various model specifications, including the inclusion of a squared term (e.g. ClimateVar_{it}^2) to capture potential nonlinear effects.

The R^2 statistic in our models indicates the proportion of the variance in the health outcomes that is explained by the independent variables. A higher R^2 suggests that the

⁷⁴⁹ R Core Team, "A Language and Environment for Statistical Computing" (Vienna, Austria: R Foundation for Statistical Computing, 2022), <https://www.r-project.org/>.

⁷⁵⁰ James Stock and Mark Watson, *Introduction to Econometrics : Global Edition*, 4th ed. (Pearson Deutschland, 2020), <https://elibrary.pearson.de/book/99.150005/9781292264523>.

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model has a better fit, though it should be interpreted in conjunction with the significance and theoretical plausibility of the coefficients.

As our dependent variables are binary, taking a value of 1 if the individual has health problems and 0 otherwise, we also employ a probit model to estimate the probability that an individual experiences health problems related to blood pressure, heart circulation, or breathing issues. The assumes that the error term follows a standard normal distribution, thereby ensuring that the predicted probabilities lie between 0 and 1.

The standard assumption of the Probit model is that there exists an unobserved latent variable Y_i^* , which is linearly related to the explanatory variables and a normally distributed error term ε_i :

$$Y_i^* = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki} + \varepsilon_{it}, \quad (3)$$

where $\varepsilon_i \sim N(0, \cdot)$. The observed binary outcome Y_i is then defined as:

$$Y_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } Y_i^* > 0, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

The probability of observing $Y_i = 1$ is given by:

$$P(Y_i = 1 | X_i) = \varphi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \dots + \beta_k X_{ki}), \quad (5)$$

where $\varphi(\cdot)$ denotes the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution.

Once the parameters are estimated, we examine the marginal effects, which provide insights into the change in the predicted probability of the outcome (i.e., experiencing health problems) associated with a one-unit change in the explanatory variables. Marginal effects are particularly useful in a non-linear model like the Probit model, as they help in interpreting the impact of each variable on the probability of the outcome.

4. Results and Discussion

The following section is organized as follows. We present three regression tables as figures. For the ease of readability, we provide explanatory notes at the bottom of each figure. Each figure contains two regression models each from regression of three health

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variables on one climate variable along with a set of control variables. We split our discussion of results based on these figures into four sub-sections. In the first section, we discuss results on impact of the climate variables on high blood pressure, which draws inferences from three figures. The second sub-section focusses on impact of climate variables on respiratory problems, third sub-section on heart and circulatory problems and the final sub-section on the control variables and overall limitations.

4.1 High blood pressure

For our dependent variable related to high blood pressure, we find that the temperature variables in both regressions have positive and highly significant coefficients across all specifications. For easier interpretation, we focus on the marginal effects of the estimations. In both heat regressions, the values from the OLS and probit model are very similar with 0.096 and 0.097 for the count variable (Figure 6) and 0.187 and 0.222 for the consecutive 2 days variable (Figure 7). Based on these results, we interpret that if, within the last 28 days, there was at least one day with a mean temperature above 30°C, the likelihood of experiencing high blood pressure increases by approximately 10%. Furthermore, if there were two consecutive days with a mean temperature above 30°C, the likelihood of high blood pressure increases by 20%. This shows that while moderate decreases in temperature increases the prevalence of high blood pressure⁷⁵¹, heat with mean temperatures above 30°C can also increase the prevalence of high blood pressure.

⁷⁵¹ Frederic Bauer et al., "Impact of Weather Changes on Hospital Admissions for Hypertension," *Scientific Reports* 12, no. 1 (April 5, 2022): 5716, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-022-09644-5>.

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Figure 6. Regression results for at least one day with mean temperature $\geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$.

	breathing		blood_pressure		heart_circulation	
	(1) OLS	(2) Probit	(3) OLS	(4) Probit	(5) OLS	(6) Probit
temp_mean_count	0.162*** (0.017)	0.731*** (0.123)	0.096*** (0.023)	0.383*** (0.093)	-0.193*** (0.014)	-1.057*** (0.106)
age	0.001*** (0.000)	0.007*** (0.001)	0.008*** (0.000)	0.034*** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.027*** (0.001)
gender	0.014*** (0.003)	0.094*** (0.017)	-0.007* (0.004)	-0.025 (0.017)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.010 (0.021)
income	-0.016*** (0.002)	-0.104*** (0.014)	-0.006** (0.003)	0.020 (0.013)	-0.017*** (0.002)	-0.085*** (0.012)
education	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.064*** (0.014)	-0.032*** (0.003)	-0.106*** (0.014)	-0.015*** (0.002)	-0.058*** (0.015)
smoking	0.027*** (0.003)	0.179*** (0.020)	0.007* (0.004)	0.074*** (0.016)	0.010*** (0.004)	0.117*** (0.021)
alcohol	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.068*** (0.021)	-0.008 (0.005)	-0.007 (0.021)	-0.035*** (0.004)	-0.163*** (0.021)
Observations	49,040	47,540	49,040	48,716	49,040	48,137
Squared Correlation	0.04295	0.04285	0.16765	0.17424	0.11006	0.13105
Pseudo R ²	0.13665	0.06653	0.18412	0.18437	0.23640	0.16123
BIC	24,165.5	35,912.2	50,439.9	49,150.2	29,033.5	36,886.1
Marginal Effect	0.162*** (0.017)	0.167*** (0.038)	0.096*** (0.023)	0.097*** (0.026)	-0.193*** (0.014)	-0.093*** (0.011)
date fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
region fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: The independent variable `temp_mean_count` is the simplified name of `temp_mean_count_threshold30_horizon28` for all columns. It has value 1 when on at least one day within past 28 days daily mean temperature is greater than equal to 30°C . The dependent variables are binary (1,0) health variables with columns 1 and 2 for breathing problem, columns 3 and 4 for blood pressure and columns 5 and 6 for heart/circulatory problems. Columns 1, 3, 5 correspond to OLS regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively. Columns 2,4, 6 correspond to Probit regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively. Age, gender, income, education, smoking and income are control variables. Standard errors are clustered at the region-date level and reported in parentheses and significance codes are * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. The reported marginal effects for each model reflect the direct elasticity of independent variable on dependent variable.

We performed a third regression to analyse the impact of high precipitation rates on our health outcomes (Figure 8). However, since most studies examining flooding events and high precipitation focus primarily on mental health effects, we did not expect to find significant impacts on physical health outcomes. Moreover, one study that analysed the effect of precipitation on high blood pressure found no significant impact⁷⁵², while another study reported a significant but very modest effect, suggesting that increased rainfall slightly raises the prevalence of high blood pressure⁷⁵³. Surprisingly, the high precipitation coefficient in our regression is both significant and negative for high blood pressure, but for one out of two estimations only on the 5% significance level. Interpreting the marginal effects (-0.068 for OLS and -0.063 for probit), our results suggest that if at least one day in the past 28 days

⁷⁵² Bauer et al.

⁷⁵³ Louise Aubinière-Robb et al., "Blood Pressure Response to Patterns of Weather Fluctuations and Effect on Mortality," *Hypertension* 62, no. 1 (July 2013): 190–96, <https://doi.org/10.1161/HYPERTENSIONAHA.111.00686>.

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experienced precipitation exceeding 90 mm, the prevalence of high blood pressure decreases by approximately 6.5%. We conclude that the results could be comprehensive, if the data would have more than 1 day of high precipitation, so at least 2 consecutive days above 90mm, as more consecutive days of high precipitation could eventually lead to a flood event, providing the right variation in precipitation level on the health parameter. As this is not possible with our data, we could not explore the underlying mechanism. Finally, this mechanism might require medical expertise and microdata at respondent level, which is outside the scope of this research.

Figure 7. Regression results for 2 consecutive days with mean temperature $\geq 30^{\circ}\text{C}$.

	breathing		blood_pressure		heart_circulation	
	(1) OLS	(2) Probit	(3) OLS	(4) Probit	(5) OLS	(6) Probit
temp_mean_consec2	0.109*** (0.016)	0.516*** (0.123)	0.187*** (0.023)	0.801*** (0.096)	-0.142*** (0.014)	-0.696*** (0.108)
age	0.001*** (0.000)	0.007*** (0.001)	0.008*** (0.000)	0.034*** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.027*** (0.001)
gender	0.014*** (0.003)	0.093*** (0.017)	-0.007* (0.004)	-0.025 (0.017)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.010 (0.021)
income	-0.016*** (0.002)	-0.104*** (0.014)	-0.006** (0.003)	0.020 (0.013)	-0.017*** (0.002)	-0.085*** (0.012)
education	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.064*** (0.014)	-0.032*** (0.003)	-0.106*** (0.014)	-0.015*** (0.002)	-0.058*** (0.015)
smoking	0.027*** (0.003)	0.179*** (0.020)	0.007* (0.004)	0.074*** (0.016)	0.010*** (0.004)	0.116*** (0.021)
alcohol	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.068*** (0.021)	-0.008 (0.005)	-0.007 (0.021)	-0.035*** (0.004)	-0.163*** (0.021)
Observations	49,040	47,540	49,040	48,716	49,040	48,137
Squared Correlation	0.04291	0.04279	0.16769	0.17429	0.11002	0.13093
Pseudo R ²	0.13651	0.06649	0.18416	0.18442	0.23630	0.16116
BIC	24,167.7	35,913.5	50,438.0	49,148.2	29,035.9	36,888.2
Marginal Effect	0.109*** (0.016)	0.107** (0.033)	0.187*** (0.023)	0.222*** (0.031)	-0.142*** (0.014)	-0.075*** (0.01)
date fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
region fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: The independent variable temp_mean_consec2 is the simplified name of temp_mean_consec2_threshold30_horizon28 for all columns. It has value 1 when in a moving window of 2 days within past 28 days, daily mean temperature on both days is greater than equal to 30°C. The dependent variables are binary (1,0) health variables with columns 1 and 2 for breathing problem, columns 3 and 4 for blood pressure and columns 5 and 6 for heart/circulatory problems. Columns 1, 3, 5 correspond to OLS regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively. Columns 2,4, 6 correspond to Probit regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively. Age, gender, income, education, smoking and income are control variables. Standard errors are clustered at the region-date level and reported in parentheses and significance codes are * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. The reported marginal effects for each model reflect the direct elasticity of independent variable on dependent variable.

4.2 Respiratory problems

For our breathing problems variable, we find a positive and highly significant impact of the temperature variable across all estimations. Focusing on the marginal effects, we observe that both the probit and OLS models yield highly similar results, with values of 0.162 and 0.167 in the first regression (Figure 6) and 0.109 and 0.107 in the second (Figure 7). Interpreting these findings, we conclude that if there was at least one day within the last 28 days with a mean temperature above 30°C, the likelihood of experiencing breathing problems increases by approximately 16%. If there were two consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C, the likelihood increases by around 10%. We are surprised by this finding, as it seems counterintuitive that a higher number of days with mean temperatures above 30°C leads to a smaller percentage increase in the risk of breathing problems.

Aligning with our expectations, the precipitation regression results indicate no significant impact of high precipitation on the likelihood of breathing problems (Figure 8).

Figure 8. Regression results for at least one day with mean precipitation ≥ 90 mm.

	breathing		blood_pressure		heart_circulation	
	(1) OLS	(2) Probit	(3) OLS	(4) Probit	(5) OLS	(6) Probit
precip_mean_count90mm	0.007 (0.013)	0.067 (0.099)	-0.068** (0.033)	-0.312*** (0.113)	0.023 (0.017)	0.139 (0.151)
age	0.001*** (0.000)	0.007*** (0.001)	0.008*** (0.000)	0.034*** (0.001)	0.004*** (0.000)	0.027*** (0.001)
gender	0.014*** (0.003)	0.093*** (0.017)	-0.007* (0.004)	-0.025 (0.017)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.010 (0.021)
income	-0.016*** (0.002)	-0.104*** (0.014)	-0.006** (0.003)	0.020 (0.013)	-0.017*** (0.002)	-0.085*** (0.012)
education	-0.009*** (0.002)	-0.064*** (0.014)	-0.032*** (0.003)	-0.106*** (0.014)	-0.015*** (0.002)	-0.058*** (0.015)
smoking	0.027*** (0.003)	0.179*** (0.020)	0.007* (0.004)	0.074*** (0.016)	0.010*** (0.004)	0.117*** (0.021)
alcohol	-0.011*** (0.003)	-0.068*** (0.021)	-0.008 (0.005)	-0.007 (0.021)	-0.035*** (0.004)	-0.162*** (0.021)
Observations	49,040	47,540	49,040	48,716	49,040	48,137
Squared Correlation	0.04288	0.04272	0.16766	0.17425	0.10998	0.13089
Pseudo R ²	0.13641	0.06645	0.18412	0.18438	0.23621	0.16112
BIC	24,169.3	35,914.5	50,439.8	49,149.8	29,038.2	36,889.5
Marginal Effect	0.007 (0.013)	0.011 (0.017)	-0.068* (0.033)	-0.063** (0.02)	0.023 (0.017)	0.024 (0.028)
date fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
region fixed effects	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓

Note: The independent variable `precip_mean_count90mm` is the simplified name of `precip_mean_count_threshold90_horizon28` for all columns. It has value 1 when on at least one day within past 28 days daily mean precipitation is greater than equal to 90 millimetres. The dependent variables are binary (1,0) health variables with columns 1 and 2 for breathing problem, columns 3 and 4 for blood pressure and columns 5 and 6 for heart/circulatory problems. Columns 1, 3, 5 correspond to OLS regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively.

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Columns 2,4, 6 correspond to Probit regression for breathing, blood pressure and heart circulation respectively. Age, gender, income, education, smoking and income are control variables. Standard errors are clustered at the region-date level and reported in parentheses and significance codes are * $p < 0.10$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$. The reported marginal effects for each model reflect the direct elasticity of independent variable on dependent variable.

4.3 Heart or circulation problems

For our final dependent variable, heart or circulation problems, we find significant temperature coefficients, but with a sign contrary to our expectations. The marginal effect for the first temperature variable is -0.193 for the OLS estimation and -0.093 for the probit model (Figure 6), indicating a substantial difference between the two models. This can occur when the dependent variable in OLS has extreme probabilities (close to 0 or 1), the OLS estimates may be exaggerated due to poor model fit, whereas probit estimates could be lower due to the normal distribution assumption. Furthermore, if the independent variable has high variance or a non-normal distribution, the OLS coefficient may overstate the effect relative to the probit coefficient. Interpreting these results, it would suggest that if there was at least one day within the last 28 days with a mean temperature above 30°C, the likelihood of experiencing heart or circulation problems decreases by approximately 10% (probit) or 20% (OLS). For the second regression, the marginal effects are -0.142 (OLS) and -0.075 (probit) (Figure 7), again showing considerable divergence. This would imply that if there were two consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C, the likelihood of heart or circulation problems decreases by 14% (OLS) or 7.5% (probit).

However, these results could be influenced by the nature of the variable itself. While the reviewed literature primarily focuses on specific cardiovascular health outcomes, such as stroke, heart failure, or myocardial infarction (Schulte, Röösl, and Ragetti 2021), the ESS variable for heart or circulation problems is based on a general question about whether respondents experienced any such issues within the last 12 months. Since this question does not target specific diseases but rather encompasses all potential issues in this broad category, respondents might not report a heart or circulation problem if they do not recognize that one of their health issues falls under this category. Additionally, people may not recall general heart or circulation problems as accurately as they would if asked about specific conditions.

Moreover, most studies that identify significant effects of heat on cardiovascular health focus on mortality. In contrast, the ESS survey only captures morbidity, as it interviews living respondents, thereby excluding individuals who may have died from heat-related cardiovascular issues. As highlighted in the literature review, findings on heat-related morbidity are less consistent compared to those on mortality, with studies

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reporting insignificant results for cardiovascular outcomes associated with heat exposure or even a decrease in cardiovascular outcomes just like we found in our data⁷⁵⁴.

For the precipitation regression, we do not find any significant impact of high precipitation on heart or circulation problems, which is in line with our expectations (Figure 8).

4.4 Control variables

Our model is well specified from the aspect of control variables, as they exhibit the expected effects on health outcomes. Based on the literature review⁷⁵⁵ discussed earlier, we deploy a very limited number but specific number of controls to ensure minimum omitted variable bias on one hand and to avoid overfitting on the other hand. The regression results indicate that most controls exhibit the expected signs and significance levels. The coefficient for age is positive and highly significant across all specifications, suggesting that with increasing age, the prevalence of health issues rises. This outcome aligns with expectations and is consistent with the findings presented in Figure 3.

Similarly, the negative and significant coefficients for education and income are consistent with Figure 3, indicating that higher levels of education or income are associated with a lower probability of experiencing health issues. The coefficient for income switches signs only once, in the fourth specification in all regressions; however, this change can be disregarded, as it is not statistically significant.

The gender coefficient is highly significant and positive for the breathing variable, indicating that being female increases the likelihood of breathing problems. For the blood pressure variable, the gender coefficient is negative, however it is only statistically significant at the 10% level in one of the two specifications. For heart or circulation issues the gender variable does not show any significant effects.

⁷⁵⁴ Youn-Hee Lim, Yun-Chul Hong, and Ho Kim, "Effects of Diurnal Temperature Range on Cardiovascular and Respiratory Hospital Admissions in Korea," *Science of The Total Environment* 417–418 (2012): 55–60, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2011.12.048>; Schulte, Rössli, and Ragetti, "Heat-Related Cardiovascular Morbidity and Mortality in Switzerland"; Giang et al., "The Effect of Temperature on Cardiovascular Disease Hospital Admissions among Elderly People in Thai Nguyen Province, Vietnam"; Kovats, Hajat, and Wilkinson, "Contrasting Patterns of Mortality and Hospital Admissions during Hot Weather and Heat Waves in Greater London, UK."

⁷⁵⁵ Bernhardt and Roy, "Empirical Evidence of the Effects of Climate Change on NCDs."

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The smoking coefficient is positive and highly significant in five out of the six specifications, which supports the expected finding that smoking increases the prevalence of health issues.

Surprisingly, the alcohol coefficient is only significant for the breathing and heart or circulation specifications and exhibits a negative sign, contrary to expectations, suggesting that alcohol consumption reduces the risk of these health problems. However, this unexpected result may stem from the transformation of the alcohol variable into a binary format, whereas the original variable contained seven distinct categories ranging from daily consumption to never. Figure A3 illustrates the original distribution of health problems across different frequencies of alcohol consumption, showing that individuals who consume alcohol daily tend to have a higher prevalence of health issues.

4.5 Limitations

This study has several limitations that warrant acknowledgment. First, the reliance on self-reported health data introduces the possibility of response bias, as respondents may not provide entirely accurate or honest answers to health-related questions. Furthermore, survey data are inherently subjective, as they reflect individuals' perceptions and interpretations of their own health status. As previously discussed in the context of cardiovascular and circulatory conditions, the survey questions are relatively broad. More specific questions targeting distinct types of cardiovascular and respiratory diseases would enhance the ability to precisely assess the impact of extreme weather events (EWEs) on non-communicable diseases (NCDs).

Second, the survey question on health issues requires respondents to recall their experiences over the past 12 months, which may lead to recall bias and the inclusion of health problems unrelated to EWEs, potentially distorting the findings. While it may be possible to control for such confounding factors with additional information, the survey dataset lacks the necessary variables to address this issue. Additionally, the survey is conducted over a relatively short time frame, with each respondent participating only once. Consequently, the data structure constitutes a repeated cross-section rather than a panel dataset, limiting the ability to track within-individual variation over time. A panel dataset, in which the same individuals are surveyed repeatedly, would provide a more robust framework for analysing the long-term effects of EWEs on health outcomes.

Another limitation pertains to the relatively low pseudo- R^2 values in our models (ranging between 0.066 and 0.184), which may indicate omitted variable bias or the

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presence of unobserved confounding factors. Including additional control variables could improve the precision of the estimates; however, correlations between key factors such as education and income may introduce multicollinearity, affecting the reliability of the results.

Moreover, despite compiling multiple datasets related to NCDs, such as EHIS (Eurostat) and EQLS, we encountered significant data constraints. A larger sample size with greater spatiotemporal coverage would enhance both the internal and external validity of the study, as it would provide a more representative picture of the population under investigation. Additionally, the lack of precise geolocation data for survey respondents prevented us from directly linking their residential locations to local temperature and precipitation conditions, further constraining the analysis.

Given these limitations, we emphasize the need for broader access to disaggregated health data to facilitate more comprehensive research on the relationship between EWEs and NCDs. Future studies would benefit from improved data availability at finer spatial and temporal scales, enabling more precise assessments of climate-health interactions across diverse regions.

5. Conclusion

This study investigates the impact of elevated temperatures and high precipitation levels on the prevalence of non-communicable diseases (NCDs), specifically hypertension, respiratory disorders, and cardiovascular conditions. To achieve this, we integrated pan-European health data with local climate information, utilizing climate records from the European Copernicus Programme and health survey data from two waves of the European Social Survey (ESS), which were merged to construct the final dataset. Climate data were sourced from multiple providers, including Copernicus Climate Data Store (CDS) and NASA. The selection of a specific climate dataset was guided by the structural characteristics of the health data. Although we examined multiple health datasets, we ultimately relied solely on ESS data due to various limitations and inconsistencies in other sources (see Table A2). The analysis also incorporated several control variables—such as age, gender, income, education, smoking habits, and alcohol consumption—which were adjusted to align with the study's methodological framework.

The empirical strategy involved estimating three regression models, each corresponding to a distinct dependent variable: respiratory problems, hypertension, and cardiovascular disorders. The key independent variables included three extreme weather indicators: (1) daily mean temperature exceeding 30°C, (2) at least two

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consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C, and (3) precipitation levels equal to or exceeding 90mm. The models also controlled for demographic and socioeconomic factors, such as age, gender, and income. Both ordinary least squares (OLS) and probit regression techniques were applied, yielding a total of 18 different estimations.

The findings suggest that elevated temperatures significantly increase the prevalence of hypertension and respiratory problems. Specifically, experiencing at least two consecutive days with mean temperatures above 30°C within the past 28 days is associated with approximately a 20% increase in hypertension prevalence and a 10% increase in respiratory issues. However, in contrast to expectations, higher temperatures appear to be associated with a significant reduction in the prevalence of cardiovascular conditions. Meanwhile, high precipitation levels did not exhibit a significant effect on respiratory or cardiovascular health but were found to have a negative association with hypertension, suggesting that increased precipitation may lower the prevalence of high blood pressure.

The majority of control variables demonstrated expected relationships with health outcomes. Age was positively correlated with all three health conditions, while higher income and educational attainment were associated with lower prevalence rates. Smoking, as anticipated, was positively and significantly correlated with adverse health outcomes.

As outlined in the limitations section, the study underscores the necessity for improved and more detailed data in this research domain. Health surveys should be designed with greater specificity regarding medical conditions and should be conducted at regular intervals to mitigate the methodological challenges discussed earlier. Finally, future research should extend the analysis to examine the effects of extreme weather events on mental health outcomes, aiming to identify systematic patterns between climatic conditions and specific psychological disorders.

Appendix

Figure A1. Mean monthly Temperature (°C) 2000-2023.

Figure A2. Mean monthly Precipitation (mm) 2000-2023.

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Table A1. Country distribution.

Country	Respondent Count ESS 7	Respondent Count ESS 11	Respondent Count ESS merged
AT - Austria	1795 (4.47%)	2354 (10.61%)	4149 (6.65%)
BE - Belgium	1769 (4.4%)	0	1769 (2.84%)
CH - Switzerland	1532 (3.81%)	1384 (6.24%)	2916 (4.67%)
CZ - Czechia	2148 (5.35%)	0	2148 (3.44%)
DE - Germany	3045 (7.58%)	2420 (10.91%)	5465 (8.76%)
DK - Denmark	1502 (3.74%)	0	1502 (2.41%)
EE - Estonia	2051 (5.1%)	0	2051 (3.29%)
ES - Spain	1925 (4.79%)	0	1925 (3.01%)
FI - Finland	2087 (5.19%)	1563 (7.04%)	3650 (5.85%)
FR - France	1917 (4.77%)	0	1917 (3.07%)
GB - United Kingdom	2264 (5.63%)	1684 (7.59%)	3948 (6.33%)
HR - Croatia	0	1563 (7.04%)	1563 (2.51%)
HU - Hungary	1698 (4.23%)	2118 (9.54%)	3816 (6.12%)
IE -Ireland	2390 (5.95%)	2017 (9.09%)	4407 (7.07%)
IL - Israel	2562 (6.38%)	0	2562 (4.11%)
LT - Lithuania	2250 (5.6%)	1365 (6.15%)	3615 (5.8%)
NL - Netherlands	1919 (4.78%)	1695 (7.64%)	3614 (5.79%)
NO - Norway	1436 (3.57%)	1337 (6.03%)	2773 (4.45%)
PL - Poland	1615 (4.02%)	0	1615 (2.59%)
PT - Portugal	1265 (3.15%)	0	1265 (2.03%)
SE - Sweden	1791 (4.46%)	0	1791 (2.87%)
SI - Slovenia	1224 (3.05%)	1248 (5.62%)	2472 (3.96%)
SK - Slovakia	0	1442 (6.5%)	1442 (2.31%)

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Table A2. Additional Health Survey datasets.

Name	Period	Respondents	Respondent's age	NCD category
European Health Interview Survey (EHIS) ⁷⁵⁶	2006-2009, 2013-2015, 2018-2020	311385	15 years & above	Respiratory, Cardiovascular, Mental health
European Quality of Life Survey (EQLS) ⁷⁵⁷	2003, 2007, 2011-2012, 2016	142435	18 years & above	Respiratory, Cardiovascular, Mental health
Flash Eurobarometer 246 (Parents' views on the mental health of their child) ⁷⁵⁸	09.10.2008 - 17.10.2008	12783	6-17 years	Mental health
Flash Eurobarometer 530 (Mental Health) ⁷⁵⁹	14.06.2023 - 21.06.2023	26492	15 years & above	Mental health
Eurobarometer 73.2 ⁷⁶⁰	26.02.2010 - 17.03.2010	27304	15 years & above	Mental health
Eurobarometer 64.4 ⁷⁶¹	07.12.2005 - 11.01.2006	29248	15 years & above	Mental health
Eurobarometer 58.2 ⁷⁶²	2002	16230	15 years & above	Mental health
European Social Survey (ESS) ⁷⁶³	2002, 2004, 2006, 2008, 2010, 2012, 2016, 2018, 2020	457745 approximately	15 years & above	Physical health

⁷⁵⁶ "European Health Interview Survey - Microdata - Eurostat," accessed February 14, 2025, <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/web/microdata/european-health-interview-survey>.

⁷⁵⁷ "European Quality of Life Survey | European Foundation for the Improvement of Living and Working Conditions," accessed March 18, 2024, <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/data-catalogue/european-quality-life-survey>.

⁷⁵⁸ European Commission, "Flash Eurobarometer 246 (Parents' Views on the Mental Health of Their Child)Flash Eurobarometer 246 (Parents' Views on the Mental Health of Their Child)" ([object Object], 2009), <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.4882>.

⁷⁵⁹ European Commission, Brussels, "Flash Eurobarometer 530 (Mental Health)Flash Eurobarometer 530 (Mental Health)" ([object Object], 2023), <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.14204>.

⁷⁶⁰ European Commission, "Eurobarometer 73.2 (Feb-Mar 2010)Eurobarometer 73.2 (Feb-Mar 2010): Humanitarian Aid, Domestic Violence Against Women,and Mental Well-Being: Humanitarian Aid, Domestic Violence Against Women,and Mental Well-Being" ([object Object], 2012), <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.11429>.

⁷⁶¹ European Commission, "Eurobarometer 64.4 (Nov 2005- Jan 2006)Eurobarometer 64.4 (Nov 2005- Jan 2006): Mental Well-Being, Telecommunications, Harmful Internet Content, and Farm Animal's Welfare: Mental Well-Being, Telecommunications, Harmful Internet Content, and Farm Animal's Welfare" ([object Object], 2012), <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.10972>.

⁷⁶² European Commission, "Eurobarometer 58.2 (Oct-Dec 2002)Eurobarometer 58.2 (Oct-Dec 2002): Health and Developing Countries: Health and Developing Countries" ([object Object], 2012), <https://doi.org/10.4232/1.10954>.

⁷⁶³ ESS Data Portal, "European Social Survey European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ESS ERIC)."

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Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE) ⁷⁶⁴	2004, 2006/07, 2008/09, 2011, 2013, 2015, 2017, 2019/2020, 2021/2022		50 years & above	Mental health, physical health
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⁷⁶⁴ Axel Börsch-Supan et al., “Data Resource Profile: The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe (SHARE),” *International Journal of Epidemiology* 42, no. 4 (August 1, 2013): 992–1001, <https://doi.org/10.1093/ije/dyt088>.

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Figure A3. Health Problems by age group and alcohol consumption in both ESS waves.

Note: alcohol consumption levels include 1= every day, 2=several times a week, 3=once a week, 4=2-3 times a month, 5=once a month, 6=less than once a month, 7=never.

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1. Introduction

Climate change has become one of the greatest global threats to public health, with complex effects on both the environment and the human body. Rising global temperatures, changes in precipitation patterns, increased frequency of extreme weather events, and higher atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) levels directly and indirectly influence human health. Climate change also has an impact on allergic diseases and asthma, increasing the prevalence and severity of allergic reactions. Climate change is responsible for changing several pollen characteristics, such as geographical distribution, concentration, season length, and allergenicity; for rapid biodiversity loss; and for increasing the levels and toxicity of air pollutants, such as particulate matter (PM), greenhouse gasses (GHGs) ⁷⁶⁵.

Numerous studies have shown that rising atmospheric CO₂ levels and increased temperatures influence the allergenicity of pollen and fungal spores. For example, the pollen of ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) grown under elevated CO₂ conditions triggers stronger allergic reactions, both in vitro and vivo ⁷⁶⁶. Similarly, temperature has been identified as a factor that enhances pollen allergenicity, with higher temperatures leading to more potent allergens ⁷⁶⁷. Additional research has explored the combined effects of elevated CO₂ and other environmental stressors, such as ozone pollution and drought. Findings suggest that while ozone may reduce allergen content, the overall increase in pollen production due to higher CO₂ levels, particularly in *Phleum pratense* (timothy grass), leads to greater allergen exposure ⁷⁶⁸. Moreover, conditions such as drought, when combined with increased CO₂, can amplify the allergenic potential of certain pollens, such as ragweed pollen. These results highlight the complex

⁷⁶⁵ Agache, Ioana, et al. "Climate change and allergic diseases: A scoping review." *The Journal of Climate Change and Health* (2024): 100350; Paudel, Bibek, et al. "Increased duration of pollen and mold exposure are linked to climate change." *Scientific reports* 11.1 (2021): 12816; Anderegg, William RL, et al. "Anthropogenic climate change is worsening North American pollen seasons." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 118.7 (2021): e2013284118; Nadeau, Kari C., et al. "Climate change: a call to action for the United Nations." *Allergy* 77.4 (2022): 1087-1090; Luschkova, Daria, Claudia Traidl-Hoffmann, and Alika Ludwig. "Climate change and allergies." *Allergo journal international* 31.4 (2022): 114-120.

⁷⁶⁶ Rauer, Denise, et al. "Ragweed plants grown under elevated CO₂ levels produce pollen which elicit stronger allergic lung inflammation." *Allergy*. 2021;76(6):1718–30.

⁷⁶⁷ Gentili, Rodolfo, et al. "Ambrosia artemisiifolia L. temperature-responsive traits influencing the prevalence and severity of pollinosis: a study in controlled conditions." *BMC Plant Biology* 19 (2019): 1-9.

⁷⁶⁸ Albertine, Jennifer M., et al. "Projected carbon dioxide to increase grass pollen and allergen exposure despite higher ozone levels." *PLoS One* 9.11 (2014): e111712.

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interactions between climate change and allergenicity, indicating a growing risk of allergic diseases as environmental conditions continue to shift.

Climate change has significantly impacted the seasonality of airborne allergens, with observable shifts in pollen patterns ⁷⁶⁹. Rising temperatures have led to earlier starts and longer durations for the pollen seasons of certain species, such as oak and grasses, while the peak of pollination has also shifted earlier. However, the effects are not uniform across all species—some, like birch, have not shown significant changes in their pollen seasonality. These changes in the timing and length of pollen release underscore the complex and region-specific nature of climate change's impact on allergenic plants, with important implications for public health and allergy management ⁷⁷⁰.

It is important to mention that one of the major allergen sources in Europe is ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*) ⁷⁷¹, an invasive plant native to North America ⁷⁷². Climate change is significantly influencing the distribution and allergenicity of ragweed, a potent aeroallergen responsible for causing allergic reactions such as rhinitis and asthma ⁷⁷³. Ragweed is expanding in Europe due to warmer temperatures and increased CO₂ levels, which enhance pollen production and allergenicity ⁷⁷⁴. The expansion of ragweed into new regions will increase the number of people exposed to its allergenic pollen, potentially leading to new sensitizations and worsening symptoms in already sensitized individuals. Lake and collaborators assessed the future impact of

⁷⁶⁹ Pfaar, Oliver, et al. "Defining pollen exposure times for clinical trials of allergen immunotherapy for pollen-induced rhinoconjunctivitis—an EAACI position paper." *Allergy* 72.5 (2017): 713-722.

⁷⁷⁰ Paudel, Bibek, et al. "Increased duration of pollen and mold exposure are linked to climate change." *Scientific reports* 11.1 (2021): 12816; Adams-Groom B, Selby K, Derrett S, Frisk CA, Pashley CH, Satchwell J, et al. Pollen season trends as markers of climate change impact: *Betula*, *Quercus* and *Poaceae*. *Sci Total Environ.* 2022;831:154882; Velasco-Jiménez, María José, et al. "Pollen season trends in winter flowering trees in South Spain." *Aerobiologia* 36 (2020): 213-224; Manangan, Arie, et al. "Long-term pollen trends and associations between pollen phenology and seasonal climate in Atlanta, Georgia (1992-2018)." *Annals of Allergy, Asthma & Immunology* 127.4 (2021): 471-480; Ziska, Lewis H., et al. "Temperature-related changes in airborne allergenic pollen abundance and seasonality across the northern hemisphere: a retrospective data analysis." *The Lancet Planetary Health* 3.3 (2019): e124-e131.

⁷⁷¹ Schaffner, Urs, et al. "Biological weed control to relieve millions from *Ambrosia* allergies in Europe." *Nature Communications* 11.1 (2020): 1745.

⁷⁷² Chen, Kuan-Wei, et al. "Ragweed pollen allergy: burden, characteristics, and management of an imported allergen source in Europe." *International Archives of Allergy and Immunology* 176.3-4 (2018): 163-180.

⁷⁷³ Rasmussen, Karen, et al. "Climate-change-induced range shifts of three allergenic ragweeds (*Ambrosia* L.) in Europe and their potential impact on human health." *PeerJ* 5 (2017): e3104.

⁷⁷⁴ Rauer, Denise, et al. "Ragweed plants grown under elevated CO₂ levels produce pollen which elicit stronger allergic lung inflammation." *Allergy* 76.6 (2021): 1718-1730; Ziska, Lewis H., et al. "Temperature-related changes in airborne allergenic pollen abundance and seasonality across the northern hemisphere: a retrospective data analysis." *The Lancet Planetary Health* 3.3 (2019): e124-e131.

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climate change on ragweed distribution in Europe, pollen production and dispersion, as well as its effect on sensitization rates. Projections indicate that within the next 15–30 years (2041–2060), the number of individuals sensitized to ragweed pollen will double. Moreover, nearly all European countries are expected to experience ragweed exposure in the future ⁷⁷⁵.

Figure 2.1. Ragweed pollen concentration in Europe and ragweed spread in Romania. (A) Ragweed pollen concentrations (grains/m³ of air) across Europe, after Schaffner et al. ⁷⁷⁶; (B) Ragweed spread in Romania (1908 – 2012) associated with mean annual temperatures, after Leru et al. ⁷⁷⁷;

Note: The images are distributed under CC BY 4.0 International License from <https://www.nature.com/articles/s41467-020-15586-1#Fig1> (A) and <https://www.mdpi.com/1660-4601/19/17/10613> (B)

Romania is among the European countries most impacted by the spread of ragweed (Figure 2.1A). The distribution of ragweed is closely linked to the average temperature, with a concentration in areas with higher temperatures (Figure 2.1B) ⁷⁷⁸. Ragweed is considered an important allergy source in Romania, among other common allergens from trees, grasses and weeds with representative species such as birch, timothy grass

⁷⁷⁵ Lake, Iain R., et al. "Climate change and future pollen allergy in Europe." *Environmental health perspectives* 125.3 (2017): 385-391.

⁷⁷⁶ Schaffner, Urs, et al. "Biological weed control to relieve millions from Ambrosia allergies in Europe." *Nature Communications* 11.1 (2020): 1745.

⁷⁷⁷ Leru, Polliana Mihaela, et al. "Biologic pollution due to Ambrosia (Ragweed) pollen in urban environment of Bucharest." *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health* 19.17 (2022): 10613.

⁷⁷⁸ Leru, Polliana, et al. (2022)

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and mugwort ⁷⁷⁹. All these species are considered important aeroallergens regarded as common causes of seasonal respiratory allergy. These sources are listed among 20 allergen sources detected in the western Romania region (Timisoara) area with high counts of pollen detected in spring, late summer and fall ⁷⁸⁰. Although previous studies conducted in western Romania at the beginning of 2000 showed grass pollen to be the most common aeroallergen ⁷⁸¹, subsequent studies showed changes in the airborne concentrations of pollen in late summer and autumn due to ragweed invasion.

Objectives of the study

The first objective of the study was to evaluate the air quality in western Romania, to identify the most abundant bioparticles in this region which can affect the human health, especially respiratory allergens.

Secondly, the study aimed to evaluate the allergenic sensitization patterns of the population in Western Romania, thereby determining the main elicitors of respiratory allergy in the last 17 years.

And lastly, the third objective of the study was to assess the effects of climate change on the elicitors of respiratory allergy and to predict the incidence of allergy to the main respiratory allergen sources based on the detected levels of airborne allergens.

2. Data and Methodology

2.1 Pollen data

Data of airborne particles between 2007-2009

Between 2007 and 2009, airborne particle monitoring was performed using the volumetric sampling method with the VPPS 2000 Lanzoni sampler, installed on a building near the Timisoara city center, for collection, identification, and quantification from February to October.

⁷⁷⁹ Ianovici, Nicoleta, Carmen Bunu Panaitescu, and Ileana Brudiu. "Analysis of airborne allergenic pollen spectrum for 2009 in Timișoara, Romania." *Aerobiologia* 29 (2013): 95-111.

⁷⁸⁰ Ianovici, N et. al. (2013)

⁷⁸¹ N. Ianovici and A. Faur. "Quantitative and qualitative study of the atmospheric pollen in 2001." *Annals of West University of Timișoara, ser. Biology* 7 (2005): 35-44; Ianovici N, Sirbu C. Analysis of airborne ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.) pollen in Timișoara, 2004. *Analele Univ din Oradea, Fasc Biol.* 2007;14:101-8.

Data of airborne particles during 2024

Since 2024, data on airborne particles in the Timișoara Metropolitan Area have been collected using real-time bio-particle analyzers, model Lumbara Edge. Each analyzer is equipped with an environmental module (including sensors, GPS, WLAN, BLE, intrusion detection, and an independent battery), a soil module, and a bio-particle monitoring module powered by a 60W solar panel. Additionally, each unit has an energy module with a 60Ah battery and an enclosure or direct connection to a 220V power source.

The equipment was installed in 4 locations in Timisoara and its metropolitan area: SCJUT (Timiș County Hospital), King Michael I University of Life Sciences (Aradului Nord), Dudeștii Noi, Dumbrăvița, forming a peri-urban monitoring network (Figure 2.2., a-d).

Figure 2.2. The locations where the installation of the equipments was completed were a) Timiș County Emergency Clinical Hospital, b) King Michael I University of Life Sciences (Aradului Nord), c) Dudeștii Noi village and d) Dumbrăvița village, city center.

Initially, the stations operated on solar panels and were later connected to a 220V power supply, with battery backup protection in case of power outages. In terms of connectivity and data acquisition, the stations are integrated into the Alergotel platform.

The module is equipped with the following sensors:

- Temperature: -40°C - 125°C (+/- 0.3)
- Humidity: 0-90 % relative humidity (+/- 3%)
- Atmospheric pressure: 300-1100 hPa (noise 0.2 Pa, Offset temperature coefficient ± 1.5 Pa/K)
- Wind speed: 0-70.0 m/ s
- Wind direction: 0-360 grade directions
- Rainfall: 0-9999.9mm
- Ultraviolet (A+B): operating class -40°C to $+85^{\circ}\text{C}$, peak sensitivity at 365 nm

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- Illuminance: operating class -40 °C to +85 °C range 1-65535 lux with high resolution

Moreover, the bio-particle analyzers operate based on a machine vision algorithm that captures and classifies airborne particles. The system draws in air, collects particulate matter (such as pollen and dust) using a specialized tape, and analyzes it in real time. The monitoring stations have been specifically configured to detect bio-particles characteristic of the local flora (see Table 2.1).

Table 2.1. Bioparticles detected by the monitoring stations

TREE POLLENS (TRE)			MOLDS		
ACE	<i>Acer</i>	Maple	ALT	<i>Alternaria</i>	Alternaria
ALN	<i>Alnus</i>	Alder	ASPGSP	<i>Aspergillus sp</i>	Aspergillus
BET	<i>Betula</i>	Birch	BOTSP	<i>Botrytis spp</i>	Botrytis
CORY	<i>Corylus</i>	Hazelnut	CLASP	<i>Cladosporium sp</i>	Cladosporium
CUP	<i>Cupressaceae</i>	Cedar	PENICI	<i>Penicillium sp</i>	Penicillium
FAG	<i>Fagus</i>	Beech			
FRA	<i>Fraxinus</i>	Ash			
MOR	<i>Morus</i>	Mulberry			
PIN	<i>Pinus</i>	Pine			
POP	<i>Populus</i>	Poplar			
QUE	<i>Quercus</i>	Oak			
SAL	<i>Salix</i>	Willow			
ULM	<i>Ulmus</i>	Elm			
GRASS POLLENS (GRA)			WEEDS		

POA	Poaceae	Grass	AMB	Ambrosia	Ragweed
			ART	Artemisia	Mugwort
			CHE	Chenopodium	Goosefoot
			PLA	Plantago	Plantain
			URT	Urtica	Nettle

2.2. Health data

Sensitization data of allergic patients were collected from the Allergy Department of SCJUT and several private allergy clinics from Timisoara, from 2008 until 2024. Sensitization evaluation was performed by skin prick testing (SPT) to various standardized cutaneous extracts of allergens: hazel (*Corylus avellana*), alder (*Alnus incana*), birch (*Betula alba*), plane (*Platanus vulgaris*), oak (*Quercus robur*), ash (*Fraxinus excelsior*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), rye (*Secale cereale*), barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), orchardgrass (*Dactylis glomerata*), lawn grass (*Lolium perenne*), timothy grass (*Phleum pratense*), grass pollen mix (orchard grass, lawn grass, red fescue, rye, timothy grass, meadow soft grass), mugwort (*Artemisia vulgaris*), ragweed (*Ambrosia artemisiifolia*), *Alternaria alternata*, *Cladosporium herbarum*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Penicillium*, *Candida albicans*, dog (*Canis familiaris*), cat (*Felis catus*), house dust mites (*Dermatophagoides pteronyssinus*, *Dermatophagoides farinae*, tested separately), cockroach (*Blattella germanica*), Histamine dihydrochloride (10 mg/ml, equivalent to 6 mg histamine) was used as the positive control and a phenolated glycerol-saline solution as the negative control. The SPT was considered positive if the wheal diameter was at least 3 mm. Alternatively, for patients who were not eligible for skin testing, allergic sensitization was assessed by measuring the allergen-specific IgE antibodies from serum using either singleplex or multiplex methods. Additionally, based on anamnesis and SPT, patients were diagnosed with various allergic diseases (allergic rhinitis, conjunctivitis, allergic asthma and skin reactions).

When analysing and displaying the data, we grouped all types of tree pollen sensitizations into a single category (tree pollen). Similarly, we combined all grass pollen sensitizations into a single category (grasses) and did the same for molds.

For the year 2024, the patient data and the bioparticle concentration data (pollen and mold) per calendar week were analysed together. Therefore, mean bioparticle

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concentration for the respective week were correlated with the number of patients sensitized to the particular allergen source seeking medical attention during that week. These data were correlated using Spearman rank correlation. A linear regression was performed using the number of patients which came to the allergology clinic as dependent variable and the pollen/mold concentration as predictor variable. Statistical analysis was performed in SPSS.

2.3. Climate data

Climate data (temperature and precipitation) from the past 45 years was obtained and analyzed from online databases, while the climate data for 2024 was collected using the environmental module of the real-time bioparticle analyzers.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Main airborne allergen sources detected in the Timisoara metropolitan area

Pollen data from 2007-2009

The provided Figure 2.3a depicts the seasonal variation of tree pollen concentrations, highlighting the spring months between March and April as the peak allergy season for tree pollen. There are noticeable differences in pollen concentrations between the years; the highest peak concentration was detected in 2009, reaching above 3500 grains/m³ in March, while in 2008, the peak was lower. Pollen concentrations are low at the beginning (January and February), and from June onwards, indicating the beginning and end of the tree pollen season (from March to May).

Figure 2.3. Detection of airborne pollen from 2007-2009: a) Tree pollen, b) Poaceae pollen, c) Ragweed pollen.

The seasonal variation of grass pollen concentrations, with the peak occurring in late spring/early summer, is illustrated in Figure 2.3b. There are some differences in pollen concentrations between the years, but they are generally quite similar, with 2008 appearing to have a slightly higher peak concentration in June. Pollen concentrations are very low at the beginning (January-March) and end (September-October) of the period, indicating the beginning and end of the grass pollen season. Compared to the tree pollen season, the grass pollen season appears to be more spread out, lasting from April to August, though peak concentrations are in May and June.

Further, Figure 2.3c illustrates the seasonal variation of ragweed pollen concentrations, with the peak ragweed pollen season occurring in late summer/early autumn, specifically in August and September. This period is marked by the highest pollen concentrations. There are noticeable differences in pollen concentrations between the years; for instance, 2008 shows the highest peak concentration (approximately 3000 grains/m³) in August, while 2007 has the lowest peak pollen concentration. Ragweed pollen concentrations are very low from January to June, indicating that the ragweed pollen season starts in July and ends in October. Compared to tree and grass pollen, the ragweed pollen season is more concentrated and shorter, with a sharp increase and decrease in pollen levels.

Pollen data from 2024

During 2024, pollen data were collected using the real-time bio-particle analyzers installed in the four locations as follows: Aradului Nord, Dumbrăvița, Dudeștii Noi and the County Hospital area (SCJUT). Data were measured as the quantity of particles per cubic meter (PPM3). Pollen grains were detected as tree, grass or weed pollen. Pollen data showed that more pollen from tree species was detected compared to weeds or grasses. The following tree pollen grains were detected, from spring to summer, with different peaks from the following species: *Acer*, *Alnus*, *Betula*, *Coryllus*, *Cupressaceae*, *Fagus*, *Fraxinus*, *Morus*, *Pine*, *Poplar*, *Quercus*, *Salix*, and *Ulmus*, among others. A variation was found between pollen data measured in different locations (Appendix Figure A2.1). The total count of tree pollen in each day was calculated, and mean pollen counts from all four locations were displayed in Figure 2.4a. Grass pollen was detected at the end of the summer (Figure 2.4b), mostly in the peri-urban areas (Appendix Figure A2.2).

Ragweed pollen was detected in higher quantities starting mid-August to mid-September, similar to previous findings, with peak concentration at the beginning of September (Figure 2.4c) (Appendix Figure A2.3).

Figure 2.4. Detection of airborne pollen in 2024: a) Tree pollen, b) Poaceae pollen, c) Ragweed pollen.

The concentrations of mold spores are depicted in Appendix Figure A2.4, while Appendix Figure A2.5 displays the concentrations of nonbiological pollutants such as dust particles, ash, plastic fibers and other inorganic particles.

3.2. Sensitization patterns to airborne allergens in patients from the Timisoara metropolitan area

Sensitization patterns

Figure 2.5 illustrates the changing landscape of allergen sensitization over time, from 2008 to 2024. In most years, ragweed pollen appears to be the most significant allergen. House dust mites are also a major allergen source throughout the years, often being the second-largest allergen source. Moreover, the proportions of patients sensitized to tree pollen, grass pollen, mold, and animal dander vary from year to year, but they generally contribute less to the overall allergen profile compared to ragweed and house dust mite allergic patients. There are noticeable fluctuations in the relative proportions of different allergens across the years; for instance, the proportion of mold and animal dander sensitization seems to vary more significantly than ragweed or house dust mites. Overall, this data highlights the consistent importance of ragweed pollen and house dust mites in allergic sensitization, while also showing the variability in other allergen sources like tree pollen, grass pollen, mold, and animal dander from year to year, suggesting that while some allergens are consistently prevalent, others may be more influenced by seasonal or environmental factors.

Figure 2.5. Sensitization patterns in allergic patients from Timisoara (2008-2024).

Association between pollen concentration and the number of allergic patients

The association between the **tree pollen concentration** and the number of patients experiencing tree pollen allergies across various weeks of 2024 is depicted in Figure 2.6. There is a notable peak in both the number of allergic patients and the pollen concentration around week 12 (mid-March), suggesting a relationship between increased pollen levels and heightened allergic reactions during that period. Overall, the graph demonstrates a seasonal pattern where an initial increase in tree pollen concentration corresponds with a rise in the number of reported tree pollen allergy cases, particularly in the earlier weeks represented.

Figure 2.6. Association between the number of tree pollen allergic patients and tree pollen concentration.

Figure 2.7 displays the relationship between **grass pollen concentration** and the number of patients experiencing grass pollen allergies in 2024. A notable increase in both the number of allergic patients and the pollen concentration occurs around week 36, suggesting a direct association between the high pollen levels and allergic reactions within the sensitized patients. Furthermore, there are smaller peaks in patient numbers that correspond with increases in pollen concentration at other times of the year, indicating a somewhat consistent link between pollen levels and allergic symptoms.

Figure 2.7. Association between the number of grass allergic patients and grass-pollen concentration.

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Figure 2.8 displays the correlation between **ragweed pollen concentration** and the number of ragweed pollen allergic patients across different weeks of the year. Notably, the highest number of allergic patients and the peak pollen concentration coincide around weeks 36 to 38, suggesting a direct relationship between increased pollen levels and heightened allergic reactions within the population. The graph demonstrates that as the pollen concentration rises, so does the number of individuals affected by ragweed pollen allergies, indicating a clear seasonal pattern of allergic response corresponding to the ragweed pollen season.

Figure 2.8. Association between the number of ragweed-allergic patients and ragweed pollen concentration.

Figure 2.9 illustrates the relationship between mold spore concentration and the number of patients sensitized to molds, across different weeks of 2024. While there isn't a perfect, consistent correlation between the two, the graph reveals some interesting trends. Notably, weeks with higher mold spore concentrations, particularly around weeks 24-40, tend to coincide with periods where there are more mold-allergic patients reported, though the patient numbers fluctuate significantly. The highest patient number is reached around week 26, while the mold concentration is high from week 34 and peaks around week 38.

Figure 2.9. Association between the number of mold-allergic patients and mold spore concentration.

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In general, the pollen concentration measurements did not correlate with the number of allergic patients which came to the clinic during that week. However, in the figures a delay of 2-3 weeks can be observed between the peak of pollen concentration and peak of sensitized patients seeking medical attention at the clinic due to symptoms induced by the culprit allergen. Only ragweed pollen concentration was found to significantly predict the number of ragweed pollen allergic patients using linear regression model ($F_{1,32}=8.43$, $p=0.007$, adjusted $R^2=0.184$).

3.3. Climate dynamics of the Timisoara Metropolitan Area

Temperature and precipitation dynamics in the last 45 years

Figure 2.10. Estimation of the mean annual temperature in Timisoara, Romania, from 1979 to 2024. The dashed blue line represents the linear climate change trend, and the warming stripes represent the average temperature for a year (blue – colder years; red - warmer years).

Note: Figure distributed from Meteo Blue under a CC-BY-ND licence (https://www.meteoblue.com/en/climate-change/timi%c8%99oara_romania_665087)

The graph above from Figure 2.10 shows an estimation of the mean annual temperature for the larger region of Timisoara. The dashed blue line indicates a positive

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temperature trend, suggesting it is getting warmer in Timisoara over time due to climate change. The warming stripes suggest a colder period from 1979 to 2006 with few yearly exceptions, whereas an increasing temperature starting in the year 2007 was observed with the highest peak in the average annual temperature found in 2024.

Regarding the precipitation data for Timisoara, over the same period, no clear trend could be observed towards a change in mean yearly precipitation amount (as shown by the horizontal blue line in Figure 2.11). There are wetter years (green stripes) and drier years (brown stripes).

Figure 2.11. Estimation of the mean total precipitation for the larger region of Timișoara, Romania, from 1979 to 2024. The dashed blue line represents the linear climate change trend. The lower part the graph shows the precipitation stripes. Each coloured stripe represents the total precipitation of a year (green – wetter years; brown - drier years).

Note: Figure distributed from Meteo Blue under a CC-BY-ND licence (https://www.meteoblue.com/en/climate-change/timi%C8%99oara_romania_665087)

Further, monthly anomalies of temperature and precipitation were evaluated (Figure 2.12). The top graph indicates more cold months from 1980 up to 2005, whereas from 2006-2025, there is a clear increase of warm months over the years, which reflects the global warming associated with climate change. Regarding the precipitation anomaly,

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the differences between the wetter and the drier months are not that remarkable, which is consistent with Figure 2.11).

Figure 2.12. Monthly anomalies of temperature and precipitation from 1979 to 2025.

Note: Figure distributed from Meteo Blue under a CC-BY-ND licence (https://www.meteoblue.com/en/climate-change/timișoara_romania_665087)

Main weather factors recorded in the Timisoara Metropolitan Area in 2024

The air temperature, relative humidity and pressure, as well as wind speed, rainfall and UV index, were registered from March to October 2024 in the Timisoara area. The average temperature value registered from the beginning of March to the end of October was 19.7 °C, with the highest temperature value being registered during July (40.8 °C) and the lowest during March (0.4 °C) (Appendix Figure A2.6a). The air relative humidity registered during the same period ranged from 23.8% to 97.6% with an average value of 65%, suggesting a great variation in the air humidity from spring to fall (Appendix Figure A2.6b), In addition, air pressure values were registered between 986 and 1022 hPa, with an average value of 1003 hPa (Appendix Figure A2.6c).

Moreover, wind speed values were registered with an average value of 0.31 m/s, ranging between 0 and 3.2 m/s, indicating a maximum wind force with a 2 Beauford number on the Beauford scale (Appendix Figure A2.7). The registered rainfall results (Appendix Figure A2.8) ranged from 0 to 40.5 mm, with an average value of 0.42 mm from March to October, indicating a slight amount of rainfall in general. Further, other

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parameters, such as the illuminance and UV index, were evaluated. The illuminance results recorded for the same period were expressed as lux and ranged between 0 and 54612 with an average value of 13494 lux (Appendix Figure A2.9a). The registered values for the UV index ranged between 0.1 and 9, with an average value of 1.3 Appendix Figure A2.9b.

Figure 2.13 illustrates the relationship between average temperature, mean precipitations and ragweed pollen concentration over August, September, and October of 2024. The average temperature fluctuates throughout the period, with a notable peak in early August. The ragweed pollen concentration shows a gradual increase starting mid-August, peaking in early September, and then gradually declining throughout October. The mean precipitations showed some sharp spikes, particularly around the end of August and mid-September. The data indicates a complex association between these factors during the ragweed pollen season. Higher temperatures in August could contribute to initial ragweed pollen growth and release, which is reflected in the mean pollen levels. Precipitation might then play a role in either suppressing or releasing pollen, depending on its intensity and timing, explaining the fluctuating pattern. The mean pollen counts appear to respond to both temperature and precipitation, and it suggests that high pollen levels may be associated with periods of lower precipitation, while spikes in precipitation might temporarily reduce airborne pollen.

Figure 2.13. Association between ragweed pollen concentrations, mean precipitations and average temperature in 2024

4. Conclusions

The present study found a clear seasonal component to allergen exposure and allergic reactions, as illustrated by the distinct peaks in pollen and spore concentrations during specific periods of the year. Ragweed pollen appears to be a dominant allergen, particularly during late summer and early autumn, leading to a important increase in new sensitizations in allergic patients during that time. Tree and grass pollen seasons, while impactful, are more defined by the spring and early summer months, respectively, and play also a considerable role in inducing respiratory allergies.

Differences in sensitization patterns towards various sources of respiratory allergens across different years highlight variation in exposure towards these allergen sources. While some allergies, such as ragweed and house dust mite allergy, maintain consistent prevalence, others, such as mold spores, show more variability, suggesting their sensitivity to seasonal or environmental changes.

Thirdly, while a general correlation exists between allergen concentrations and the number of allergic patients, the relationship is not always linear. Other factors beyond pollen concentrations, such as individual sensitivities, existing comorbidities, and environmental conditions, can also affect allergic responses. Moreover, the analysis of mold spore concentrations reveals a more nuanced connection with patient allergies, suggesting that while mold can contribute to allergic symptoms, other factors may influence the severity and occurrence of mold allergies. It seems that mold allergens are present over more weeks during the year.

The analysis of environmental factors in Timisoara reveals a clear warming trend over the years, with a noticeable shift towards higher temperatures starting in 2007 and peaking in 2024. The data shows a prolonged colder period from 1979 to 2006, followed by a steady increase in warm months from 2006 to 2025, aligning with global climate change patterns. However, precipitation data does not exhibit a significant trend, indicating that while temperature rise is evident, precipitation patterns remain variable. The observed increase in warm months highlights the impact of climate change on regional climate conditions, emphasizing the need for climate adaptation strategies.

In conclusion, the interplay between allergen exposure, environmental factors, and individual sensitivities shapes the landscape of allergic diseases, emphasizing the need for comprehensive approaches to manage and mitigate the impact of allergies on public health.

Limitations of our study

The study is limited by data availability and the complexity of interactions between meteorological and biological factors. Individual sensitivity to pollen and other environmental factors can also influence the results. Integrating genetic data and research on heat-resistant plants could offer solutions for agriculture and pollen management. Expanding the study to a larger scale to capture regional variations over time in the pollen season and the impact of climate change would be beneficial for developing targeted allergy management strategies.

Future perspectives

Future perspectives include developing more precise models that integrate additional variables, such as air pollution and climate change, to improve allergy management strategies.

Appendix

Pollen and spore data from 2024

Figure A2.1. Detection of airborne pollen from tree species a) Acer, b) Alnus, c) Betula, d) Corylus, e) Cupressaceae, f) Fagus, g) Fraxinus, h) Morus, i) Pine, j) Poplar, k) Quercus, l) Salix, m) Ulmus, n) Other trees. The number of pollen grains detected per cubic meter are shown on the y-axis.

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Figure A2.2. Detection of airborne pollen from grasses. The number of pollen grains detected per cubic meter are shown on the y-axis.

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Figure A2.3. Detection of airborne pollen from weeds a) *Plantago*, b) *Chenopodium*, c) *Ambrosia*. The number of pollen grains detected per cubic meter is shown on the y-axis.

Figure A2.4. Detection of airborne mold spores from a) *Alternaria*, b) *Botrytis*, c) *Cladosporium*, d) *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus* e) other molds. Spores detected per cubic meter are shown on the y-axis.

Nonbiological pollutants over the monitoring period in 2024

Figure A2.5. Detection of nonbiological pollutants a) dust particles, b) Ash, c) Plastic fibers and d) other inorganic particles from the Timisoara area. Particles detected per cubic meter are shown on the y-axis.

Main weather factors recorded in the Timisoara Metropolitan Area in 2024

Figure A2.6. Weather data from the Timisoara Metropolitan Area registered from March to October 2024 using the real-time bio-particle analyzers. a) Air temperature, b) Air relative humidity and c) Air pressure.

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Figure A2.7. The wind speed measured in the Timisoara Metropolitan Area from March to October 2024 using the real-time bio-particle analyzers.

Figure A2.8. Rainfall (mm) values measured in Timisoara Metropolitan Area from March to October 2024 using real-time bio-particle analyzers.

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Figure A2.9. Environmental parameters measured in Timisoara Metropolitan Area from March to October 2024 using the real-time bio-particle analyzers; a) Illuminance and b) UV index.

MOUNTADAPT is a Horizon Europe project aiming to boost the community-driven resilience of the health system in European mountain areas, mitigating the impact of climate change on public health. Leveraging the expertise of 27 partners, including healthcare facilities, public authorities, innovators, and researchers, MOUNTADAPT aims to develop solutions and strategies to enhance healthcare climate adaptation and safeguard the health and well-being of communities living in mountain regions.

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